

Evaluating the Relationship Between

Material Culture and

Social Networks in Archaeology

by

Robert Jacob Bischoff

A Dissertation Presented in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Doctor of Philosophy

Approved April 2025 by the
Graduate Supervisory Committee:

Matthew Peeples, Chair
Michelle Hegmon
C. Michael Barton

ARIZONA STATE UNIVERSITY

August 2025

ABSTRACT

This dissertation evaluates the extent to which material culture networks, constructed from similarities in artifacts, can serve as effective proxies for past social networks. While commonly assumed in archaeological network studies, this link has rarely been systematically tested. To address this, I integrate agent-based modeling, geometric morphometrics, machine learning, and multilayer network analysis with a case study from the central U.S. Southwest.

The ArchMatNet agent-based model simulates social interaction and material production among hunter-gatherers and small-scale horticulturalists. Key variables such as population size, interaction frequency, learning strategy, and trait visibility can be controlled. Results demonstrate that material culture networks align with social networks under specific conditions, particularly when traits differ between groups and are transmitted through a mix of prestige and conformism.

These findings are tested against an empirical case study. A heuristic projectile point typology was developed using geometric morphometrics and machine learning, based on over 3,000 points from 81 sites in the U.S. Southwest. This typology forms the basis for a regional network analysis, which suggests that projectile points reflect broad-scale interaction but differ in structure from ceramic networks. A multilayer analysis of ceramic, architectural, and lithic data from Tonto Basin further shows that different artifact classes produce distinct network structures. These variations likely reflect diverse social processes, including gendered patterns of production and exchange.

Overall, the results demonstrate that material culture networks can offer meaningful insights into social interaction, but their reliability depends on several factors: trait distinctiveness, transmission dynamics, trait visibility, and data quality. This work contributes to

archaeological network analysis by combining experimental and empirical methods and by emphasizing the need to critically assess assumptions behind similarity-based models.

The approaches presented here are broadly applicable, but their interpretive power depends on context. Under the right conditions, material culture can reflect social networks in analytically useful ways, but only if archaeologists remain attentive to its constraints.

DEDICATION

To my mother, Joy, who inspired my journey into archaeology, and to my wife, Emily, who has supported me throughout this journey.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I express my sincere gratitude to the many individuals who supported this research. First, I thank my committee members for their consistent support and guidance throughout this process. Dr. Matthew Peeples, my committee chair, has somehow managed to balance encouragement to finish my dissertation with reassurance that I was not taking too long. He has dedicated an impressive amount of time to refining my ideas and making them presentable and achievable. I am grateful to Dr. Michelle Hegmon and Dr. Michael Barton for their insights, critiques, and support as committee members.

This dissertation would not have been possible without collaboration with Dr. Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias and Dr. Claudine Gravel-Miguel, who coauthored the ArchMatNet agent-based model. Their contributions were critical to the theoretical and technical foundations of this research. We spent many hours on Zoom during the COVID-19 pandemic working out bugs in the code. Dr. Zach Selden, Dr. Loren Davis, Dr. Michael Shott, and Dr. Bernard Means led a geometric morphometrics workshop in my first semester at ASU, which significantly helped advance my understanding of the methods. Dr. James Allison mentored me at Brigham Young University, and I owe much to him and the BYU Department of Anthropology for setting me on my current path.

I am grateful to those who assisted with data collection, imaging, and access to collections. Dr. Barbara Mills, Dr. Charles Adams, Rich Lange, and Dr. Christopher Caseldine provided access to key collections and institutional support. I thank Wesley Bernardini, Kellam Throgmorton, Joseph Bryce, Lindsey Vogel-Teeter, and Joshua Watts for providing projectile point images and data. Kathryn MacFarland, Gwenn Gallenstein, and Signe Valentinsson facilitated work with collections at the Arizona State Museum and the Museum of Northern Arizona. Chiara Umbriano contributed to data collection and analysis, while Ronald Vasquez and Michael Brooks assisted with scanning. I deeply appreciate all

who contributed their time and expertise to this project. Dr. Caseldine deserves additional credit for accommodating time for dissertation writing.

I gratefully acknowledge financial support from multiple sources. Primary funding was provided by the National Science Foundation through the Archaeology Program's Doctoral Dissertation Research Improvement Award (DDRI; Grant - 2308629). Additional support came from the Arizona Archaeological and Historical Society, the GPSA Research Grant Program at Arizona State University, the SHESC Research Committee, and the Center for Archaeology and Society Student Research Grant. Their generous support helped fund travel, data collection, and analysis throughout this research.

I thank my family and friends for their support. My mother brought me to her college classes as a child and inspired my love of archaeology at an early age. My wife, Emily, has never wavered in her support of my academic pursuits, even as our family has grown. My children have been a source of comfort, motivation, and needed stress relief throughout my dissertation research. There are too many wonderful friends and colleagues to name, but I am grateful to all who have supported me in this process.

Research Computing at Arizona State University provided access to the Sol supercomputer for running the ArchMatNet agent-based model.

Note: I utilized OpenAI's ChatGPT (GPT-4) to assist with code debugging, script optimization, and writing refinement during this research. All research design, data analysis, and interpretations presented are my own. This usage aligns with ASU's Digital Trust Guidelines for Generative AI.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
LIST OF TABLES	x
LIST OF FIGURES	xi
CHAPTER	
1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Style, Interaction, and Material Culture	4
1.2 Research Design and Chapter Overview	9
References	11
2 BRIDGING MATERIAL CULTURE NETWORKS AND SOCIAL NET- WORKS IN ARCHAEOLOGY	18
2.1 Introduction	18
2.1.1 Networks in Archaeology	23
2.1.2 Agent Based Models	26
2.2 ArchMatNet	27
2.3 Methods	33
2.4 Results	36
2.4.1 Network Comparisons	36
2.4.2 Model Parameters	39
2.4.3 ERGMs	41
2.4.4 Network Centrality	44
2.4.5 Individual Networks	45
2.5 Conclusion	48
Acknowledgements	51
Data Availability	52

CHAPTER	Page
References	52
3 A GEOMETRIC MORPHOMETRIC AND MACHINE LEARNING AP- PROACH TO REGIONAL PROJECTILE POINT ANALYSIS IN THE SOUTHWEST UNITED STATES	62
3.1 Introduction	62
3.1.1 Study Region: Central U.S. Southwest, AD 1100–1500.	65
3.1.2 Geometric Morphometrics	67
3.2 Dataset	70
3.3 Methods	72
3.3.1 Landmark analysis	73
3.3.2 EFA	74
3.3.3 Dimensionality Reduction	75
3.3.4 Spatial Analysis	77
3.3.5 Machine Learning	78
3.4 Existing Typologies	79
3.5 Attribute-based Typology	86
3.6 Geographic Clustering	96
3.7 Discussion	101
3.8 Conclusion	103
Data Availability	105
References	105
4 INVESTIGATING MATERIAL CULTURE THROUGH MULTILAYER NETWORK ANALYSIS IN TONTO BASIN	121
4.1 Introduction	121

CHAPTER	Page
4.2 Tonto Basin	123
4.3 Data Collection	125
4.4 Network Analysis	126
4.4.1 Defining Networks	127
4.4.2 Interpreting Networks	128
4.4.3 Network Similarity	131
4.4.4 Network Analysis Methods	133
4.4.5 Spatial	136
4.4.6 Architecture	136
4.4.7 Ceramics	137
4.4.8 Projectile Points	137
4.5 Results	138
4.6 Discussion	143
4.7 Conclusion	147
Data Availability	148
References	149
5 SYNTHESIZING MATERIAL CULTURE AND NETWORK DATA	162
5.1 Multilayer Analysis	162
5.1.1 Dataset and Methods	162
5.1.2 Results	164
5.1.3 Multilayer Discussion	165
5.2 Evaluating Material Culture Networks	170
5.2.1 ArchMatNet	171
5.2.2 Central U.S. Southwest	172

CHAPTER	Page
5.3 Computational Archaeology	173
5.4 Conclusion	174
References	176
REFERENCES	178
APPENDICES	
A PERMISSIONS AND CODE FOR CHAPTER 2	212
B CODE AND ENVIRONMENTS FOR CHAPTER 3	424
C CODE FOR CHAPTER 4	528
D CODE FOR CHAPTER 5	544
E NOTICE OF COPYRIGHT PERMISSIONS	566

LIST OF TABLES

Table	Page
1.1. Definitions of Methods Used in this Dissertation.	2
2.1. Primary ArchMatNet Parameters	29
2.2. Network Comparison Results	35
2.3. Network Comparison Results	38
2.4. ERGM Results	45
3.1. Equivalent Projectile Point Types	69
3.2. Projectile Point Sources	72
3.3. Hotelling's T^2 Tests for Projectile Point Types	83
3.4. Hotelling's T^2 Tests for Attribute-Based Point Types.....	96
4.1. Project Sites and Data	132
4.2. Mean Eigenvalues for Ceramic and Point Networks by Type of Architecture ...	143

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure	Page
1.1. Example Network with Weighted Edges.	3
1.2. Abstraction and Representation of the Diffusion of Technology through Social Networks.	4
1.3. Project area and Archaeological Culture Regions.	5
1.4. Conceptual Model Demonstrating how Attribute Visibility Affects Material Culture.	9
2.1. Abstract Comparison of Social Networks Versus Material Culture Networks. . .	19
2.2. Netlogo Interface for the ArchMatNet Agent-based Model.	28
2.3. Boxplots Comparing Social and Material Culture Network Correlations from ArchMatNet.	37
2.4. ArchMatNet Variable Correlations.	42
2.5. Interaction and Material Culture Networks with and without Unique Starting Traits in ArchMatNet.	47
3.1. Geographical Boundaries of the Project Area.	67
3.2. Landmark configuration example.	74
3.3. Distortion in Base Orientation Revealed by PCA in Procrustes Analysis of Pro- jectile Points.	76
3.4. Mean Landmark Placements for Side-notched Projectile Points by Type.	82
3.5. Mean Landmark Placements for Triangular Projectile Points by Type.	83
3.6. UMAP Projection of Procrustes-aligned Landmarks for Side-notched Projectile Points.	84
3.7. Examples of Awatovi and Buck Taylor Projectile Points.	85

Figure	Page
3.8. UMAP Projection of Procrustes-aligned Landmarks for Triangular Projectile Points.	86
3.9. UMAP Projection Illustrating Continuous Morphological Variation.	87
3.10. Decision Tree for Projectile Point Classification Process.	89
3.11. Confusion Matrices for Machine Learning Models Used to Classify Projectile Point Attributes.	90
3.12. Hierarchical Clustering Dendrogram of Projectile Point Outlines Based on EFA.	91
3.13. UMAP of EFA Coefficients for All Projectile Points.	92
3.14. Histogram of Notch Ratios for Side-notched Projectile Points.	93
3.15. Heatmap Comparing Original Projectile Point Types to Attribute-based Types. .	95
3.16. Projectile Point Shapes for Newly Devised Projectile Point Types.	97
3.17. Distribution of Side-notched Projectile Point Types.	99
3.18. Distribution of Triangular Projectile Point Types.	100
3.19. Map of Projectile Point Communities.	102
4.1. Map of Archaeology Sites from the Roosevelt Platform Mounds Study in Tonto Basin.	124
4.2. Network Graph Displaying Side-Notched Points From Tonto Basin as Nodes With Ties Showing the Morphometric Distance Between Points.	139
4.3. Network Graph Displaying Triangular Points From Tonto Basin as Nodes With Ties Showing the Morphometric Distance Between Points.	140
4.4. Graphs Showing the Networks Used in this Chapter.	141
4.5. Boxplots Showing the Eigenvector Centrality for Ceramic and Point Networks. .	142
4.6. Boxplots Showing the Pearson Correlation Between Each Network in Tonto Basin.	144

Figure	Page
5.1. Site Occupations for Selected Archaeological Sites Used in this Analysis.	163
5.2. Site locations discussed in this analysis.	164
5.3. Multilayer Network Graphs Showing Relationships Among Archaeological Sites.	166
5.4. Eigenvector Centrality Scores for Each Site in the Ceramic and Projectile Point Similarity Networks.	167
5.5. Map of Louvain Communities Detected from a Multilayer Network Combining Ceramics and Projectile Points.	168
5.6. Graph Correlation Matrices Comparing Spatial, Ceramic, and Projectile Point Similarity Networks.	169

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Social network analysis (SNA) is used to study the structure and dynamics of interactions among social actors at a variety of scales. It provides a robust set of methods and theoretical expectations linking network structures and positions to different kinds of outcomes for actors within a network (M. A. Peeples 2019, p. 6), and it is growing rapidly in archaeological research (Brughmans and Brandes 2017; Collar et al. 2015).

Network approaches offer a means of understanding how social affiliations develop and change through time. Importantly, these methods can accommodate analyses across multiple scales without reifying the traditional, spatially bounded categories associated with the culture-historical paradigm (Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Holland-Lulewicz 2021). Archaeological network studies typically use characteristics of material culture—such as source, style, or technology—as proxies for social relations. However, important questions remain regarding the relationship between specific types of material evidence and the social relations that network studies aim to capture.

For example, inferences based on structural positions such as brokerage (e.g., M. A. Peeples and Haas 2013) require strong supporting evidence for the social connections they assume. Because direct relationships are difficult to document in the archaeological record, relations identified through patterns in material culture should be viewed probabilistically (M. A. Peeples 2019, p. 29). This dissertation explicitly explores the complex relationships between social networks and the material proxies archaeologists use to model them.

While network science is the primary focus, this dissertation also employs a variety of computational methods—including agent-based modeling (ABM), geographic information

Table 1.1: Definitions of Methods Used in this Dissertation.

Definitions
Agent-based model (ABM): A computational method that simulates the interactions of autonomous agents.
Geographic Information Systems (GIS): A system of software and hardware used to visualize, analyze, and interpret spatial data.
Geometric Morphometrics (GMM): A set of methods used to quantify and analyze the shape of objects.
Machine Learning (ML): A set of methods used to classify and predict patterns in data.
Network Science: A set of methods used to analyze relationships between entities.

systems (GIS), geometric morphometrics (GMM), and machine learning (ML). Definitions for these terms are provided in Table 1.1.

The term “network” (Figure 1.1) is used in two ways: as a reference to actual social relations among actors, and as a formal analytical construct (nodes and edges) used to abstract and analyze those relationships. In archaeology, networks built from material cultural patterns are not social networks in a strict sense. Rather, they represent proxies that map imperfectly onto social relationships. Clarifying the connection between these two uses of *network* is one of the primary goals of this dissertation.

To maintain clarity throughout the chapters, I refer to the patterns of social interaction as “interaction networks,” and to those built from material culture as “material culture networks” or “archaeological similarity networks” (Collar et al. 2015, p. 16). Defining and analyzing any kind of network in archaeology requires abstraction: a past phenomenon of interest must first be conceptualized in network terms and then translated into data—nodes and edges—that represent that concept (Ulrik Brandes et al. 2013; Collar et al. 2015).

Figure 1.2 illustrates this process using a stylized model of technological diffusion, where network ties represent exchange pathways. Although network approaches have

Figure 1.1: A simple network with nodes (circles) and edges (lines). Edges can have weights that represent the strength (or other quantification) of the edge, which are represented by the numbers placed on the edges.

proven useful for understanding the structure of social relations in the past, it remains unclear how material culture-derived networks relate to the social processes they are intended to reflect (M. A. Peeples, B. J. Mills, et al. 2016). Without stronger guiding assumptions, there is a risk of overinterpreting “networks” as social phenomena when they may reflect other processes.

The methods archaeologists use to construct material culture networks vary widely, including similarities in object counts, stylistic attributes, geochemical sourcing, and production techniques (e.g., J. Birch and Hart 2018; Bischoff 2018; Borck et al. 2015; Golitko, Meierhoff, et al. 2012; B. J. Mills, Jeffery J Clark, et al. 2013; B. J. Mills, J. M. Roberts J., et al. 2013; M. A. Peeples 2018). There is also growing recognition that different kinds of interaction may leave different signatures in material culture (e.g., Gosselain 2000; Hegmon 2000; Hodder 1982; Wiessner 1983). Highly visible features may reflect emulation or

Figure 1.2: Abstraction and representation of the diffusion of technology through social networks. The phenomenon of technological diffusion is conceptualized as the movement of objects and information along exchange pathways. In the abstraction (left), shared interactions between sites lead to similar technological outcomes. In the representation (right), a stylized network shows site A trading with site B (but not with C), resulting in the spread of technology X from A to B over time.

stylistic convergence, while low-visibility traits often signal more direct forms of interaction, such as shared learning environments.

Any network analysis must ask: what kind of relationship is being modeled? Is it exchange, migration, shared production techniques, aesthetics, kinship, or a combination? This dissertation evaluates the relationship between material culture and social networks using both a virtual experiment (an agent-based model) and an empirical analysis focused on the Western Pueblo region of the U.S. Southwest (see Figure 1.3).

1.1 Style, Interaction, and Material Culture

The relationship between social interaction and material culture is a broad and complex issue, but one that must be addressed before any network analysis can be undertaken. This study was built on a theoretical model described by Peebles (2018) for exploring the trajec-

Figure 1.3: Geographical boundaries of the project area, encompassing parts of the Ancestral Pueblo, Hohokam, Mogollon, and Sinagua archaeological culture regions. Project boundary is in black. The Tonto Basin boundary is in red.

ories of groups sharing collective social identities at large scales (Calhoun 1997; see also Calhoun 1995; Somers 1994; Stokke and Tjomsland 1996; Tilly 1978; Tilly 2001; Tilly 2002; Tilly 2004; Tilly 2005; H. White 1992; H. White 2008). According to this perspective, the overall process of social identification can be understood as comprising two modes, relational and categorical identification (M. A. Peeples 2018, p. 8).

Relational identification refers to the process through which individuals identify with others through direct interactions such as kinship, exchange, and other kinds of frequent, direct interactions. Categorical identification refers to the process through which individuals identify with groups based on perceived similarities with others in those groups, such as ethnicity, religion, and nationality. Importantly, categorical identification does not necessarily

involve direct interaction and thus may link many people who are unknown to each other. These modes of identification and their interplay provide a useful framework for interpreting how identities and group membership are expressed in different types and features of material culture, in part through the concept of style.

Style has been defined in several ways (e.g., Hegmon 1992, pp. 517–518; Macdonald 1990; Wiessner 1983; Wiessner 1984; Wiessner 1985). Carr (1995b, pp. 164–167) defines what he calls “material style” using several criteria, but primarily it is a material pattern with a restricted range of forms and a restricted spatio-temporal and contextual distribution. Other characteristics include the simultaneous expression of multiple styles and the existence of functionally equivalent alternatives—called isochrestic variation by Sackett (1982). Carr (1995b, p. 166) adds a few qualifications to Sackett’s original concept: functionally equivalent does not necessarily mean that the styles have identical performance characteristics, conscious choice is not necessary for different styles, and enculturation is only one of many factors involved in stylistic differences. From these definitions, it follows that patterns in the material culture in this study that are not restricted in space or time can be disregarded. Patterns that show restricted ranges can be used to infer social connections. The expression of multiple styles also indicates that evidence for both categorical and relational identities may be observed in a single artifact. These attributes should be distinguished in order to infer the types of social interaction that underlie patterns of similarity.

Technology is closely related to style, and it too has many definitions (Lechtman 1977; Lemonnier 1986; Lemonnier 1989; Lemonnier 1992; Pfaffenberger 1988, p. 41). Carr (1995b, p. 157) defines technology as “raw materials and production procedures.” The definition of technology used here includes several aspects: the processes and techniques of making or using a thing, the social and idiosyncratic context of the behavior, the material and ecological constraints, and the *chaîne opératoire* (Torres 2002) of the thing’s use-life.

Understanding the modifications made throughout the life history of an object is essential for material culture studies, as the original form of the object can be obscured by subsequent use, modification, and discard (resharpening is particularly important for projectile points). All aspects of material culture technology should be considered before social inferences can be made.

Many studies investigated relationships between material culture and social identification (e.g., Carr 1995b; Carr 1995a; Jeffery J Clark 2001; Dietler and Herbich 1998; Gosselain 1998; Gosselain 2000; Gosselain 2016; Hodder 1982; Huntley 2008; Lemonnier 1986; Lyons 2003; Neuzil 2008; Sassman and Rudolphi 2001; Stark, Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark 1998; Wiessner 1983; Wiessner 1997). Many of these studies found that variation in technological practices involved in processes such as building homes and making pottery, weapons, and other items are sometimes meaningful expressions of group social identity and sometimes are not. Meaningful variation must be identified empirically and case by case. There are some regularities, however, including that visibility is often helpful for understanding material style and social behaviors (Carr 1995a, p. 173; Wobst 1977). For example, the spread of low visibility technologies such as architectural construction techniques are interpreted as evidence of migration, while the spread of highly visible styles is more likely to represent emulation or diffusion (e.g., Jeffery J Clark 2001; Jeffery J Clark, Lyons, et al. 2008). Many of these same arguments can also be linked to the modes of identification described above. Categorical identification is not based on direct interactions among members of such groups but is often symbolized with highly visible material such as public architecture or objects used in public contexts (M. A. Peeples 2018, pp. 18–39). Relational identities, on the other hand, are formed through direct interactions and are more likely to be evidenced low-visibility attributes such as forming techniques or features found

in domestic spaces see also (Carr 1995a; Jeffery J Clark 2001, pp. 6–22; M. A. Peebles 2018, pp. 18–39).

The visibility of an attribute also affects the level of transmission. Low-visibility attributes are more difficult to observe and copy than high-visibility attributes, although a sufficient degree of skill may be required. Figure 1.4 describes how this would affect material culture. Whereas high-visibility attributes may be easily copied, low-visibility attributes usually require careful observation of the crafting process. Communities of practice generate commonalities in low-visibility attributes representative of the strong relational connections within them. Constellations of practice represent greater diversity in practice but still share relational connections through historical, kinship, geographical, or other associations (Van Oyen 2016; Wenger 1998, pp. 126–133). As discussed, sharing high-visibility attributes indicates a categorical connection but does not require frequent interaction. Thus, levels of visibility can be used to infer categorical and relational connections among communities (see Upton 2019).

Understanding how material culture reflects social interaction requires both theoretical clarity and methodological precision. As discussed above, the concepts of style, technology, and visibility provide important frameworks for interpreting the social meaning of material variation. However, translating those frameworks into network models poses significant challenges. Not all material similarities indicate interaction, and the type of attribute—whether highly visible or embedded in production techniques—can lead to different interpretations. This ambiguity highlights the need for a systematic evaluation of how different forms of material culture relate to the social processes we seek to understand.

To address this challenge, the following chapters combine computational modeling with empirical case studies to explore how interaction networks can be inferred from material culture. The research design brings together network science, geometric morphometrics,

Figure 1.4: Conceptual model demonstrating how the attribute visibility of material culture is expected to affect the level of similarity expressed in an object.

agent-based modeling, and machine learning in an effort to build, test, and interpret archaeological networks in ways that account for both theory and complexity. The chapter overview below outlines how each stage of the dissertation contributes to this broader goal.

1.2 Research Design and Chapter Overview

This dissertation follows a hybrid format in which three standalone articles (Chapters 3–5) are integrated into a cohesive framework through this introduction and the concluding chapter. Each article contributes to the overarching question of how material culture networks can be constructed, validated, and interpreted in archaeological research, although chapter 3, as will be explained, is more targeted towards generating an appropriate dataset.

To evaluate the relationship between material culture networks and interaction networks, Chapter 2 introduces the ArchMatNet agent-based model (Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias

2023; Bischoff, Padilla-Iglesias, and Gravel-Miguel 2024; Padilla-Iglesias and Bischoff 2024). The model simulates social interactions and material production using two different material culture proxies: projectile points and ceramics. These proxies are parameterized to reflect different patterns of use and transmission. The simulation allows controlled testing of how well material culture networks reflect the underlying social networks—something not possible in empirical data alone.

Chapter 3 serves as an intermediate step between the agent-based model and its application. It presents a regional analysis of over 3,000 projectile points using geometric morphometrics and machine learning, primarily to develop a dataset that can be used for empirical network construction. This chapter also evaluates existing projectile point typologies and introduces an alternative classification based on measurable attributes and shape data.

Chapter 4 integrates projectile points, ceramics, and architectural data to build multi-layer material culture networks for the Tonto Basin. It shows that different types of material culture generate different networks, likely reflecting differences in how those materials—and the knowledge to produce them—circulated in past communities. Given that pottery and projectile points are often associated with specific genders in the archaeological literature, these differences may even reflect gendered social networks.

Chapter 5 concludes the dissertation by evaluating the alignment between the empirical results and the patterns simulated by ArchMatNet. It also discusses broader implications for archaeological network analysis, particularly in light of growing interest in computational and reproducible research.

In many ways, this dissertation is an exercise in computational archaeology. As the field evolves, new methods are being adopted rapidly—but best practices for using them are still being developed. This project is an effort to combine several emerging approaches to address a core archaeological question: how do patterns in material culture relate to patterns

of social interaction? At the same time, it critically evaluates the assumptions and outcomes of those methods, with the goal of contributing to the growing body of work on networks in archaeology.

References

- Birch, Jennifer and John P Hart (Jan. 2018). “Social Networks and Northern Iroquoian Confederacy Dynamics”. In: *American Antiquity* 83 (1), pp. 13–33. ISSN: 0002-7316. DOI: 10.1017/aaq.2017.59. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0002731617000592/type/journal_article.
- Bischoff, Robert J (2018). *A Temporal and Spatial Analysis of San Juan Red Ware. Master's thesis, Department of Anthropology, Brigham Young University, Provo, Utah.* URL: <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/etd/7003/>.
- Bischoff, Robert J and Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias (July 10, 2023). “A description and sensitivity analysis of the ArchMatNet agent-based model”. en. In: *PeerJ Computer Science* 9, e1419. ISSN: 2376-5992. DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.1419. URL: <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-1419/> (visited on 07/24/2023).
- Bischoff, Robert J, Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias, and Claudine Gravel-Miguel (2024). “Evaluating the Effects of Randomness on Missing Data in Archaeological Networks”. In: *Accepted to CAA 2021 Conference: Limassol, Cyprus.* DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b>.
- Borck, Lewis et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Are Social Networks Survival Networks? An Example from the Late Pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 33–57. ISSN: 1573-7764,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5>.
- Brandes, Ulrik et al. (Apr. 2013). “What is Network Science?” In: *Network Science* 1 (1), pp. 1–15. ISSN: 2050-1242,2050-1250. DOI: 10.1017/nws.2013.2. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/network-science/article/what-is-network-science/C0794B28C613757F09C3FB315500E3A1>.

- Brughmans, T and U Brandes (2017). “Visibility Network Patterns and Methods for Studying Visual Relational Phenomena in Archeology”. In: *Frontiers in Digital Humanities* 4.
- Calhoun, Craig J (Jan. 1995). *Critical Social Theory: Culture, History, and the Challenge of Difference*. en. Blackwell. 326 pp. ISBN: 9781557861382. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_WgDnwEACAAJ.
- (1997). *Nationalism*. Concepts in social thought. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press. 120 pp. ISBN: 9780816631209.
- Carr, Christopher (1995a). “A Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Carr C. and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 171–258. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- (1995b). “Building a Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Christopher Carr and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 151–170. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- Clark, Jeffery J (2001). *Tracking Prehistoric Migrations: Pueblo Settlers Among the Tonto Basin Hohokam*. en. Vol. 65. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. 124 pp. ISBN: 9780816520879. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=27Tk3xNT-6UC>.
- Clark, Jeffery J, Patrick D Lyons, et al. (2008). “Immigrants and Population Collapse in the Southern Southwest”. In: *Archaeology Southwest* 22 (4).
- Collar, Anna et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Networks in Archaeology: Phenomena, Abstraction, Representation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 1–32. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6>.
- Dietler, Michael and Ingrid Herbich (1998). “Habitus, Techniques, Style: An Integrated Approach to the Social Understanding of Material Culture and Boundaries”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution, pp. 232–263.
- Feinman, Gary M and Jill E Neitzel (Dec. 1, 2020). “Excising Culture History from Contemporary Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 60, p. 101230.

ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101230. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416520302038>.

Golitko, Mark, James Meierhoff, et al. (June 2012). “Complexities of collapse: the evidence of Maya obsidian as revealed by social network graphical analysis”. en. In: *Antiquity* 86 (332), pp. 507–523. ISSN: 0003-598X, 1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/s0003598x00062906. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0003598X00062906/type/journal_article.

Gosselain, Olivier P (1998). “Social and Technical Identity in a Clay Cristal Ball”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam Stark. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 78–106.

— (Sept. 1, 2000). “Materializing Identities: An African Perspective”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 7 (3), pp. 187–217. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1023/A:1026558503986. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026558503986>.

— (2016). “The World is Like a Beanstalk: Historicizing Potting Practice and Social Relations in the Niger River Area”. en. In: *Knowledge in Motion: Constellations of Learning Across Time and Place*. Ed. by Andrew P Roddick and Ann B Stahl. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, pp. 36–66. ISBN: 9780816533749. URL: <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/44808> (visited on 03/11/2019).

Hegmon, Michelle (Jan. 1, 1992). “Archaeological Research on Style”. In: *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21 (1), pp. 517–536. ISSN: 0084-6570. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.anthro.21.1.517. URL: https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev.an.21.100192.002505?casa_token=6qKr2S4tTBMAAAAA:WKU4gaCaBHKmkj-Kv2CAYnC0mbdzfIXxVG7Xflho10RvGx23v8LM7uestyIFA-5JuHMqLAJcZrFFA.

— ed. (2000). *The Archaeology of Regional Interaction: Religion, Warfare, and Exchange across the American Southwest and Beyond*. English. University Press of Colorado. ISBN: 9780870819049.

Hodder, Ian (1982). *Symbols in Action: Ethnoarchaeological Studies of Material Culture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9780521241762. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-TSE9AAAAIAAJ>.

Holland-Lulewicz, Jacob (Jan. 4, 2021). “From Categories to Connections in the Archaeology of Eastern North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research* 29, pp. 537–579. ISSN: 1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w>.

- Huntley, Deborah L (2008). *Ancestral Zuni Glaze-Decorated Pottery: Viewing Pueblo IV Regional Organization through Ceramic Production and Exchange*. Vol. No. 72. Anthropological Papers. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Lechtman, Heather (1977). "Style in Technology, Some Early Thoughts". In: *Material Culture: Style, Organization, and Dynamics of Technology*. Ed. by H Lechtman and R S Merrill. New York: West Publishing, pp. 3–20.
- Lemonnier, Pierre (June 1, 1986). "The Study of Material Culture Today: Toward an Anthropology of Technical Systems". In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 5 (2), pp. 147–186. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90012-7. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416586900127>.
- (1989). "Bark Capes, Arrowheads and Concorde: On Social Representations of Technology". In: *The Meaning of Things: Material Culture and Symbolic Expressions*. Ed. by Ian Hodder. London: Hyman, Unwin, pp. 156–171.
- (1992). *Elements for an Anthropology of Technology*. Ann Arbor: Museum of Anthropology, University of Michigan. URL: <https://philpapers.org/rec/LEMEFA>.
- Lyons, Patrick D (2003). *Ancestral Hopi Migrations*. English. First Edition edition. Anthropological Paper Number 68. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816522804.
- Macdonald, W K (1990). "Investigating Style: An Exploratory Analysis of some Plains Burials". en. In: *Uses of Style in Archaeology*. Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press, pp. 52–60.
- Mills, Barbara J, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (Apr. 9, 2013). "Transformation of social networks in the late pre-Hispanic US Southwest". en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110 (15), pp. 5785–5790. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1219966110. URL: <http://www.pnas.org/content/110/15/5785>.
- Mills, Barbara J, John M Roberts Jr, et al. (2013). "The Dynamics of Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic U.S. Southwest". en. In: *Network Analysis in Archaeology: New Approaches to Regional Interaction*. Ed. by Carl Knappett. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 181–202. DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199697090.003.0008.
- Neuzil, Anna A (2008). *In the Aftermath of Migration: Renegotiating Ancient Identity in Southeastern Arizona*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona No. 73. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.

- Padilla-Iglesias, Cecilia and Robert J Bischoff (Oct. 9, 2024). “Hunter-gatherer mobility patterns influence the reconstruction of social networks from archaeological assemblages”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 59, p. 104798. ISSN: 2352-409X,2352-4103. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798>.
- Peeples, Matthew A (2018). *Connected Communities: Networks, Identity, and Social Change in the Ancient Cibola World*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816535682. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-fyw-DwAAQBAJ>.
- (Feb. 4, 2019). “Finding a Place for Networks in Archaeology”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research*, pp. 1–49. ISSN: 1059-0161,1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8>.
- Peeples, Matthew A and W Randall Haas (June 2013). “Brokerage and Social Capital in the Prehispanic U.S. Southwest”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 115 (2), pp. 232–247. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1111/aman.12006. URL: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/aman.12006/abstract>.
- Peeples, Matthew A, Barbara J Mills, et al. (2016). “Analytical Challenges for the Application of Social Network Analysis in Archaeology”. In: *The Connected Past: Challenges to Network Studies in Archaeology and History*. Ed. by Tom Brughmans, Anna Collar, and Fiona Coward. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 59–84.
- Pfaffenberger, Bryan (1988). “Fetishised Objects and Humanised Nature: Towards an Anthropology of Technology”. In: *Man* 23 (2), pp. 236–252. ISSN: 0025-1496. DOI: 10.2307/2802804. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2802804>.
- Sackett, J R (1982). “Approaches to Style in Lithic Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 1, pp. 59–112.
- Sassman, Kenneth E and Victoria Rudolphi (2001). “Communities of Practice in the Early Ceramic Traditions of the American Southeast”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Research* 57, pp. 407–425. ISSN: 0091-7710.
- Somers, Margaret R (Oct. 1994). “The narrative constitution of identity: A relational and network approach”. en. In: *Theory and society* 23 (5), pp. 605–649. ISSN: 0304-2421,1573-7853. DOI: 10.1007/bf00992905. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/BF00992905>.
- Stark, Miriam T, Mark D Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark (1998). “Social Boundaries and Technical Choices in Tonto Basin Prehistory”. en. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, D.C: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 208–231.

- Stokke, Hugo and Marit Tjomsland (1996). *Collective Identities and Social Movements*. en. Bergen, Norway: Chr. Michelsen Institute.
- Tilly, Charles (1978). *From Mobilization to Revolution*. en. Reading, Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley.
- (June 1, 2001). “Mechanisms in Political Processes”. In: *Annual Review of Political Science* 4 (1), pp. 21–41. ISSN: 1094-2939. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.polisci.4.1.21. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.4.1.21>.
- (2002). *Stories, Identities, and Political Change*. en. Lanham, Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield. 257 pp. ISBN: 9780742518810. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=x465AAAAIAAJ>.
- (2004). “Social Boundary Mechanisms”. In: *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* 34 (2), pp. 211–236. ISSN: 0048-3931. DOI: 10.1177/0048393103262551. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0048393103262551>.
- (2005). *Identities, Boundaries, and Social Ties*. en. Boulder, Colorado: Paradigm Publishers.
- Torres, Marcos Martínón (2002). “Chaîne Opératoire: The concept and its applications within the study of technology”. In: *Gallaecia* 21, pp. 29–44. URL: <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/descarga/articulo/265493.pdf>.
- Upton, Andrew James (2019). “Multilayer Network Relationships and Culture Contact in Mississippian West-central Illinois, A.D. 1200 - 1450”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Michigan State University, East Lansing.
- Van Oyen, Astrid (Mar. 1, 2016). “Historicising Material Agency: from Relations to Relational Constellations”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 23 (1), pp. 354–378. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0>.
- Wenger, Etienne (1998). *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Vol. 9. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. URL: <https://valenciacollege.edu/faculty/development/teaching-learning-academy/documents/CommunityofPractice.pdf>.
- White, Harrison (1992). *Identity and Control: A Structural Theory of Social Action*. en. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

White, Harrison (2008). *Identity and Control: How Social Formations Emerge*. en. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.

Wiessner, Polly (1983). “Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 48 (2), pp. 253–276. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280450. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-and-social-information-in-kalahari-san-projectile-points/52D6230881B0C69260ABE226BD82EC0E>.

— (1984). “Reconsidering the Behavioral Basis for Style: a Case Study among the Kalahari San”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 3 (3), pp. 190–234. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(84)90002-3. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416584900023>.

— (Jan. 1985). “Style or Isochrestic Variation? A Reply to Sackett”. In: *American Antiquity* 50 (1), pp. 160–166. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280643. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-or-isochrestic-variation-a-reply-to-sackett/206F9510A8BF0402883F6A436A9BB787> (visited on 01/14/2020).

— (1997). “Seeking Guidelines through an Evolutionary Approach: Style Revisited among the !Kung San of the 1990s”. In: *Rediscovering Darwin*. Ed. by C Michael Barton and Geoffrey A Clark. Vol. 7. Archeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association. Arlington: American Anthropological Association, pp. 157–176.

Wobst, H Martin (1977). “Stylistic Behavior and Information Exchange”. In: *For the Director: Research Essays in Honour of the Late James B. Griffin*. Ed. by C E Cleland. Vol. 61. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, pp. 317–342.

CHAPTER 2

BRIDGING MATERIAL CULTURE NETWORKS AND SOCIAL NETWORKS IN ARCHAEOLOGY

2.1 Introduction

Over the last two decades, network studies have proliferated in archaeology and the social and behavioral sciences in general. In archaeology, much of this work has focused on building empirical networks based on artifact distributions and frequencies. The underlying assumption governing much of that work is that similarities or the presence of common categories or types of materials can be used as a proxy for connections among people at various scales (see M. A. Peeples 2019). The complexities of the relationships between material similarity and relationships among people is sometimes acknowledged (M. A. Peeples, B. J. Mills, et al. 2016; M. A. Peeples, J. Roberts J. M., and Yin 2024; Sindbæk 2007), but there has been relatively little work focused explicitly on testing the underlying assumptions of such network models (but see Golitko 2023; Gravel-Miguel and Coward 2024). This leaves us with an essential question: to what degree can similarities in attributes or types of artifacts serve to represent patterns of interaction that occurred in the past and how do such patterns relate to our formal network models (Figure 2.1)? In this paper, we attempt to approach this complex relationship using a combination of Agent Based Models and statistical approaches for evaluating network processes.

Discussions about material culture in archaeology, particularly its use as a proxy for social interaction, are extensive (Gosselain 2000; Hegmon 1992; Hodder 1982; M. A. Peeples 2018; Wiessner 1983). Although the arguments about the connections between material

Figure 2.1: An abstract comparison of a social network and a material culture network, representing the core research question: to what extent do patterns in material culture reflect underlying social interactions?

patterns and social processes are diverse, there are a few commonalities that have been recognized across a broad array of contexts. For example, highly visible aspects of style (e.g., painted designs, public buildings, ceramic decoration, textile patterns, personal adornments) are widely seen and displayed thus material similarities may indicate some degree of interaction between producers or simply imitation without direct contact. On the other hand, similarities in low-visibility technological aspects of design and production (e.g., hidden foundation stones) tend to more often result from direct, frequent interactions, such as those found in shared learning environments. This essentially mirrors older debates in archaeology and the anthropology of technology focused on style vs. isochrestic variation and the relation with other social processes (J R Sackett 1982; James R Sackett 1986; Wiessner 1985; see Hegmon 1992). Numerous studies have examined the connection between material culture and social identity (Carr 1995b; Carr 1995a; Jeffery J Clark 2001; Dietler and Herbich 1998; Gosselain 2000; Hodder 1982; Huntley 2008; Lemonnier 1986; Lyons 2003; Neuzil 2008; Wiessner 1983), revealing that variation in technological practices—whether in building, pottery, or weapons—can sometimes reflect social identity, though this is not always the case. Determining the significance of such variation requires empirical analysis on a case-by-case basis. We must add that we define social identity in a broad sense recognizing that it is mutable and multiple for each person.

There are some recurring patterns in the literature on material culture and identity, such as the role visibility plays in linking material style to social behavior (Carr 1995a, p. 173; Wobst 1977). Visibility influences transmission levels: low-visibility traits are harder to observe and replicate, typically requiring more skill and closer involvement, while high-visibility traits are often more easily copied. For instance, the spread of low-visibility technologies is often interpreted as evidence of migration, while the spread of highly visible styles is more likely to signify emulation or diffusion (Jeffery J Clark 2001). This is because high-visibility traits are more likely to be copied than low-visibility traits. Communities of practice tend to exhibit commonalities in low-visibility attributes, reflecting the strong relational connections within them. By contrast, constellations of practice (groups of related communities) show greater diversity yet still share relational connections through history, kinship, geography, or other ties (Van Oyen 2016; Wenger 1998, pp. 126–133). Sharing high-visibility attributes suggests a social connection but doesn't necessitate frequent interaction.

Studies of cultural transmission suggest there are two primary mechanisms which high or low-visibility traits may be learned: prestige and conformism. Prestige-based transmission occurs when individuals preferentially imitate those who are perceived as successful or esteemed within their group, thereby acquiring skills or knowledge that are associated with high status. These traits are, presumably, more advantageous (Henrich 2004; Morgan, Cross, and Rendell 2015). In contrast, conformist transmission refers to the tendency of individuals to adopt the most common behaviors or beliefs within their social group, effectively leading to homogenization of cultural traits. This mechanism can enhance group cohesion and facilitate the maintenance of cultural boundaries, as it tends to reduce variation within groups while increasing differences between them (Henrich 2004; Muthukrishna, Morgan, and Henrich 2016). However, while conformist transmission can stabilize cultural norms,

it may also impede the spread of innovative ideas, particularly in dynamic environments where adaptability is crucial (Morgan, Cross, and Rendell 2015). Both types of transmission occur in any given society, although conformism is primarily relied on (Henrich and McElreath 2003, p. 131).

As the literature suggests, the relationship between material culture and social interaction is complex. It becomes clear that there is no universal answer to how effectively any form of material culture can act as a proxy for social interaction. Instead, we must approach the question from a broader perspective while accounting for historical contingencies that shape interpretations of specific types of material culture at different times.

Leaving aside the question of how specific types of material culture relate to social identity or relationships, how can the relationship between social interaction networks and material culture be evaluated if archaeologists cannot observe the past? How can we validate our methods and assumptions? Moreover, how do various social processes like exchange, migration, intermarriage, and cultural diffusion affect these patterns (see Padilla-Iglesias and Bischoff 2024, for additional discussion on this question)? One avenue to answer these questions would be to look at ethnoarchaeological studies of material culture, and indeed general models of the relationship between material culture patterns and identity are often deeply informed by ethnoarchaeological case studies (Jeffery J Clark 2001). In our examination of potential ethnoarchaeological studies, however, we found four major limitations: the availability of data, the scale of the study, the time depth of the study, and the lack of sufficient variables. A major exception to these limitations is the study by Golitko (2023) using ethnographic data from across New Guinea. He compared material culture networks, created from bone dagger attributes and ethnographic records of interaction, and found some evidence that material culture networks are correlated with social networks, but the correlations were not strong. Centrality scores and neighborhood detection also performed poorly.

Golitko suggests caution when applying network methods to archaeological data, although he recognizes limitations in his study and continues to support the use of network analysis as a tool for archaeologists. This study is an excellent example of how ethnographic data can be used to address the relationship between material culture and social networks. In general, ethnoarchaeological studies are often limited to a single village or a small number of villages. Data collection is time consuming and difficult even at smaller scales. The time depth of these studies is usually limited. Most studies are conducted over a few years, although some have been conducted over decades. However, the time depth of these studies is still orders of magnitude less than the time depth of archaeological studies. Finally, ethnoarchaeological studies often lack the variables needed to answer the questions we are interested in. For example, many studies do not record the social networks related to the material culture they are studying or vice versa.

What is needed is a dataset of material culture that spans several generations, encompasses a large region with sufficient material culture variability to recognize cultural boundaries, and results from the direct social interaction between individuals. If we cannot observe the past or the present to obtain the necessary data, then we are left with the virtual. This is precisely what agent-based models (ABMs) provide. ABMs have been likened to “behavioral laboratories” (Premo 2006) where experiments can be conducted under controlled conditions. ABMs are computer simulations where agents make decisions based on a set of rules. Over time these simple rules can lead to complex, emergent behaviors (Epstein 2006). We are not the first to investigate the relationship between material culture and social networks using an ABM. Work by Gravel-Miguel (2017; 2024), a co-author of the agent-based model discussed herein, found that similarities in artifact attributes can serve as adequate representations of past social interactions, particularly when cultural transmission is a key factor. She found that material culture, influenced by mechanisms like conformism

and prestige-based learning, correlates with social networks, though indirect transmission and environmental constraints may complicate the accuracy of these reconstructions, and careful consideration of external factors is necessary for accurate interpretation.

The model used in this analysis, ArchMatNet (Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias 2023; Bischoff, Padilla-Iglesias, and Gravel-Miguel 2024; Padilla-Iglesias and Bischoff 2024), is designed to replicate simple social interactions among hunter-gatherers. The model details are presented in a future section. Elsewhere we use the ArchMatNet model to shed light on how variability in the settlement patterns and mobility strategies among prehistoric societies affected the structure of the archaeological record and our ability to recover past social networks from it (Padilla-Iglesias and Bischoff 2024). Here, we investigate more broadly how social interaction networks correlate with material culture networks, investigate the correlations between specific activities and material culture, compare the generative properties of each type of network, and investigate the contributions of various parameters from the model.

2.1.1 Networks in Archaeology

Network science approaches to archaeological research continue to grow (Collar et al. 2015; Tom Brughmans and Matt Peeples 2017) for good reasons. Network methods have already proved useful as tools for exploring and formalizing complex relational patterns in archaeological data across a huge array of contexts, scales, and questions (see Peeples 2019; Brughmans, Mills, Munson and Peeples 2024). Beyond this, network theory and network thinking also have the potential to help us move beyond some of the “culture-historical baggage” (Holland-Lulewicz 2021, p. 538), and rigidly defined categories of traditional archaeological models towards an approach that better accommodates the empirical ethnographic

and archaeological evidence of variability and fluid boundaries (Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Holland-Lulewicz 2021; John Edward Terrell et al. 2023). In their critiques of the tacit continuation of culture-history methods in archaeology, Feinman and Neitzel (2020) and Holland-Lulewicz (2021) suggest relational perspectives, such as social network analysis, are key to moving beyond the rigid categorical approaches currently fundamental to archaeological practice.

The relational perspective fundamental to network approaches holds that we must consider both the nature and structure of interactions among social units as well as the attributes of individuals or groups to fully understand social phenomena (Tom Brughmans and M. A. Peeples 2023, p. 19; M. A. Peeples 2019, p. 6). Network science is concerned with all aspects of relational data (Ulrik Brandes et al. 2013, p. 19), and networks can be generated from many types of archaeological data. Common network types include material culture (B. J. Mills, Jeffery J Clark, et al. 2013), movement (Scheidel 2014), spatial proximity (John E Terrell 1977), and inter-visibility (Fraser 1980). In each of these examples, a person, group, or place is represented by a node and a relationship is created to other nodes. It is the relationship between these nodes that defines the structure of the network. Relationships are defined in many ways, but here we are interested in similarity networks in which the relationships represent commonalities in the relative frequencies material culture attributes. Similarities in material culture are seen as a proxy for the probability of a connection between a set of actors or contexts and can be treated a weighted based on the strength of such similarities (M. A. Peeples and J. M. Roberts 2013). Each network can be analyzed visually in a network graph or quantified using various formal metrics, such as centrality scores. Network centrality measures the potential influence of a node on the network and different centrality metrics can be used to characterized different kinds of flows and movements across networks (Borgatti 2005). Nodes that have a high centrality score

for a given metric may have more connections than average or may be positioned centrally in the network and thus may gain some advantage based on their position.

Despite the promise of network methods for addressing a broad range of archaeological questions pertaining to interaction, there are many challenges. Even the creation of a network representation can be difficult. In archaeological practice, a network is an abstraction of the phenomena we wish to study (Collar et al. 2015). Prignano and colleagues (2017) list three common difficulties in creating network representations: defining boundaries, nodes, and relations. None of these are easy tasks and all existing caveats to archaeological data are applicable to network datasets: missing or incomplete data, inaccurate data, taphonomic issues, taxonomic issues and others. Some work has been done on the issues mentioned by Prignano and colleagues. Re-sampling networks has shown that many large networks are robust to missing nodes (Gjesfjeld 2015; M. A. Peeples, B. J. Mills, et al. 2016), as long as the samples are random (Bischoff, Padilla-Iglesias, and Gravel-Miguel 2024). Even once a network representation has been created, there are many issues regarding its interpretation. Here we are concerned particularly with archaeological similarity networks. These networks are typically created with a site or context as a node and relations are defined based on a similarity measure based on the relative frequencies of different categories of material culture. Rather than interpreting a relation between nodes as the existence of a face-to-face interaction, such as exchange or migration, this tie should be considered a representation of the probability of a connection having existed between the sites (M. A. Peeples 2019, p. 20). As this literature demonstrates, network analysis in archaeology has not been adopted uncritically, yet there remains more to be done. If similarity networks represent only the probability of interaction, as Peeples indicates, then this leaves an important question: how well does a similarity tie that represents the probability of interaction compare to the actual interaction that took place in the past?

As mentioned, Golitko (2023) addressed this question with an ethnoarchaeological study, but he recognizes that the study has limitations. For example, the ethnographic network is composed of binary ties indicating whether a relationship existed between communities. How might the results change if the network were weighted by the frequency of interaction? Eigenvector centrality, one of the centrality measures used by Golitko, is commonly used by archaeologists and is a good way to measure the importance of a node in a network. Calculating the eigenvector centrality for the entire ethnographic network shows that all of the sites that contain bone dagger data had a centrality score of zero. How might the results be different if more central locations in the network had bone dagger data? These questions are not meant to disparage the work of Golitko, but to highlight the complexity of working with network data or any archaeological or ethnographic data. This complexity is why we turned to agent-based models to compliment the work of Golitko and others.

2.1.2 Agent Based Models

An agent-based model (ABM) is a computer simulation in which agents are programmed to make decisions based on a set of rules (see Romanowska, Wren, and Crabtree 2021, for an overview). Over time these rules can lead to complex, emergent behaviors (Epstein 2006). Characteristics of emergent behaviors include self-organization, unpredictability, and bottom-up processes. In other words, the end result of the simulation is not preprogrammed into the model but develops as the model progresses from the base set of rules. ABMs can be useful in a variety of circumstances in archaeology, although they are “not a miracle cure” or “panacea” as Rogers and Cegielski write (2017, p. 12843). These authors note there are several areas ABMs are particularly useful. One of the ways they suggest ABMs can be useful is exploring material links to social dynamics (J. D. Rogers

and Wendy H Cegielski 2017, p. 12843). That is precisely what we attempt here. While ABMs clearly cannot replicate reality or replace empirical data, they are particularly valuable in that they force researchers to explicitly state our assumptions. It is easy to overlook assumptions when crafting a narrative from archaeological data, but in an ABM, every assumption must be programmed into the model. ABMs can be more generalized (Barton and Riel-Salvatore 2014; Brantingham 2003; Creanza, Kolodny, and Feldman 2017; A. White 2013) or more specific and based on empirical data (Barton, Riel-Salvatore, et al. 2011; Tom Brughmans and Poblome 2016; Crabtree 2015; Gravel-Miguel 2017). In our case, we use a more generalized model. By eliminating data specific to any one place or time, we hope to more clearly see the relationships between material culture and social interaction networks without introducing confounding variables.

2.2 ArchMatNet

The ArchMatNet model is a generalized agent-based model (ABM) designed to represent patterns of social interaction and material culture among hunter-gatherers or small-scale horticulturalists (Figure 2.2). Agents represent individuals who are organized into hierarchically nested social groups: each agent belongs to a camp, and each band consists of three camps. Bands are spatially dispersed across a virtual landscape, and the simulation proceeds in discrete time steps representing monthly intervals.

A key feature of the model is that opportunities for interaction are hierarchically structured:

- Most interactions occur among agents in the same camp
- Fewer interactions occur among agents in different camps within the same band
- The fewest interactions occur among agents in different bands

Figure 2.2: Netlogo interface for the ArchMatNet agent-based model. Small tents represent camps. Large tents represent areas where camps aggregate as bands. The background of the model world represents different environmental areas. Various parameters can be set using the sliders or switches, and metrics can be monitored using the plots.

This pattern mimics expected real-world social behavior, where interaction is more frequent and intense within smaller social units and decreases with social distance. While this is the general pattern set out in the model, each run will differ in actual execution due to the stochasticity built into the model.

During each monthly time step, agents may engage in several activities:

- Produce pottery or projectile points using known styles
- Innovate new pot or point styles
- Visit or hunt with other agents (hunting is band-limited; visiting spans bands)
- Participate in band aggregation events where all band members temporarily co-reside
- Migrate to a different camp

Every interaction provides a chance for material exchange (trading pots/points) and social learning (adopting new styles). Learning occurs either through conformism (copying

popular styles) or prestige bias (copying successful or admired individuals). Parameters defined by the user govern the frequency of each activity and the likelihood of trade, learning, and innovation (see Table 2.1).

Pots and points are randomly dropped by agents and form the virtual archaeological record. All agent interactions are recorded, producing a dataset of social ties. Thus, the model outputs both material culture and social network data, allowing us to evaluate how well material culture proxies capture patterns of interaction.

The model assumes a one-month timestep to balance temporal resolution and computational efficiency. A typical run includes 4,000 time steps, equivalent to ~333 years, which is appropriate for simulating archaeological time scales. Although camps are dispersed, the model assumes that agents can visit any other camp and return within a month—consistent with estimated round-trip travel distances of ~540 km based on known daily mobility rates (Drennan 1984).

Each agent has a personal network of friends or allies whom they may visit. These relationships are dynamic and may include individuals from other camps or bands. However, intra-band connections dominate, reinforcing stronger cohesion at the band level, which is in line with ethnographic expectations. Because each step represents a full month, agents may participate in multiple activities per time step.

Table 2.1: Primary ArchMatNet Parameters

Parameter	Default Value	Description
aggregationDuration	1	Length of aggregation (one time step)
aggregationFreq	12	Frequency of aggregation (camps gathering together by band every n time steps)
campPopulation	15	Number of agents in each camp

(continued)

Parameter	Default Value	Description
pTrading	5	Probability (out of 100) that trading will occur
pHunting	1	Probability (out of 100) that hunting will occur
learningMethod	50	Probability of prestige learning versus conformism (0 means that all people learn from conformism while 50 is an equal mix of prestige and conformism and 100 is complete prestige learning)
nOfBands	3	Number of bands (three camps are created per band)
nTicks	4000	The number of ticks (time steps) the simulation lasts
pMigration	0.05	Probability (out of 100) that migration occurs
pLuckyLeap	1	Probability (out of 100) that a new style of artifact is invented
pNewObject	10	Probability (out of 100) that a new object is created by an agent
transmissionRate	5	Probability (out of 100) that a new object is created by an agent

(continued)

Parameter	Default Value	Description
uniqueTraits	TRUE	Determines if everyone starts with the same trait or if they start with a trait unique to their own camp
visibility	TRUE	Determines if some traits are more visible (and thus easier to transmit) than others
pVisiting	5	Probability (out of 100) that visiting occurs

Agents can learn through conformity by copying popular styles or through prestige by copying the style of the most successful hunter or most popular potter. One model parameter that affects the probability of traits being copied is called **visibility**. This parameter can be turned on or off, and, when on, randomly assigns traits as high-visibility or low-visibility. High-visibility traits have a much greater chance of being passed on than low-visibility traits.

Agents make pots and points based on styles they learn from others or innovate themselves. The model can be set to give each camp a unique starting trait for pots and points or to have a single starting trait for all agents.

The primary difference between points and pots is that prestige is assigned randomly to pots, while prestige for points is based on hunting success. Hunting success is based on the suitability of a point type to the local environment. Thus, there is a functional aspect to points not present in pots. This therefore affects prestige-based learning but not conformism.

Each interaction (visiting, trading, learning, or hunting) between agents is recorded, and pots and points are randomly dropped. The pots and points found in each camp represent the

archaeological record, and the summed counts of interaction between each camp represent the social networks.

With these data, we can investigate the relationships between these processes, that is, between the social interactions and resultant material patterns. For a further description of the model and an investigation of its parameters see Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias (2023) or see the description of the model in the supplementary material.

There is much stochasticity involved in an agent-based model (Romanowska, Crabtree, et al. 2019). This stochasticity is represented by using assigned probabilities to determine the likelihood of an event. This randomness prevents the model from being entirely deterministic and allows even unlikely scenarios to occur. To account for the stochastic nature of the model, the results of more than 30,000 simulations were used in this analysis. Arizona State University's Sol supercomputer (Jennewein et al. 2023) was used to run the simulations.

The total number of simulations is a result of numerous runs of the model exploring various permutations of parameters related to frequencies of activities, population sizes, learning, and other relevant parameters. As demonstrated in a prior analysis (Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias 2023), most parameters did not significantly affect model outcomes such as similarities between camp assemblages or the number of interactions between agents in each camp (many of the 26 total parameters control the frequency of an activity or the number of agents involved in an activity), however, parameters were again tested against the graph correlations discussed in the methods section, and the results are discussed below.

Note that hunting networks are not compared due to the limitation that hunting only takes place within a band. This restricts the network to within band only making them incomparable to other networks.

As mentioned, the primary output of the ArchMatNet model is the artifact assemblage

for each camp and the total interactions of each type between each camp. The model will export raw data for each camp, but we also created a condensed output for model experiments where parameters are tested through repetitive simulations of different combinations of values. This condensed output returns a matrix of values for each type of interaction showing the total counts of interactions between each camp (which are aggregated from the counts of each agent in the camp). It also returns a matrix of similarity values indicating the similarity of each artifact assemblage (pot and point) to each other camp. The methods of network construction are described in the next section.

2.3 Methods

The goal of this analysis is to compare networks generated based on the behaviors and activities directly modeled in the ABM to those generated based on the material assemblages that such behaviors left behind. This is a way for us to directly assess the degree to which material cultural patterns may or may not allow us to reconstruct the generative behaviors and also allow us to assess potential sources of equifinality. Numerous methods can be used to compare similarities in network graphs (M. A. Peeples and Tom Brughmans 2023, Section 12). The applicability of each method depends on the type of graphs being compared and the research questions addressed. In our case, we are comparing two types of networks. The social interaction network represents how often different camps interacted with each other, and the material culture network shows how similar the artifacts from these camps are. The social interaction network is a weighted, undirected graph where the weight of the edge represents the frequency of interaction between two camps. Undirected means that the relationships do not have a specific direction. Weighted means the edge (or relationship) between each node is represented by a value instead of a binary tie that either exists

or does not exist. The material culture network is a weighted, undirected graph where the weight of the edge represents the similarity of the material culture between two camps.

The first difficulty we encountered in comparing our networks was the incommensurability of edge weights for the material culture and interaction networks. For the material culture networks, the strength of the connections between camps was determined by how similar the artifacts found in each camp at the end of the model (accumulated through random breaking of artifacts) were to one another. Each pot or point had a type assignment in the model. Similarities between pot and point assemblages were calculated using a weighted Jaccard index (see Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias 2023, for a more detailed description). The interaction networks were created simply by aggregating the counts of each interaction of the given type (learning, trading, visiting, or hunting). Table 2.2 summarizes each network. Given that interaction intensity or similarity is the desired output, transforming the edge weights into z-scores is appropriate. Z-scores help standardize the data by showing how much each value differs from the mean, making it easier to compare different networks. Z-scores were calculated for each edge weight in the networks, which were then scaled from 0 to 1 to facilitate easier interpretation of network metrics. This method makes the edge weights more comparable and suitable for network comparison methods.

Three methods of comparing and statistically analyzing the networks are used in this study: graph correlation, the quadratic assignment procedure (QAP), and Exponential Random Graph Models (ERGMs). The graph correlation is implemented in the *sna* package (Butts 2023) in R (Team, R Core 2024). This correlation is equivalent to a Pearson's product-moment coefficient and values range from 1 (perfect correlation) to -1 (perfect negative correlation) and measures the degree of agreement in the presence/absence or weights of edges in a pair of graphs representing the same set of nodes.

A QAP test (Krackardt 1987) is related to the graph correlation measure and uses Monte

Table 2.2: Network Comparison Results

Network	Description
Learning	Count of interactions between agents engaging in cultural transmission (either learned a trait or taught a trait)
Trading	Count of interactions between agents exchanging objects (pots or points)
Visiting	Count of interactions between agents who are allies (friends) and are visiting each at a camp or central aggregation area
Point	This network is created from broken (dropped) point artifacts at each camp and similarities between camps are calculated via the weighted Jaccard index
Pot	This network is created from broken (dropped) pot artifacts at each camp and similarities between camps are calculated via the weighted Jaccard index

Carlo simulations to assess the alignment nodes and edges in a network. Essentially, the QAP method takes two similarity matrices with the same rows and columns and calculates the correlation coefficient among them and then permutes the order of the rows and columns some large number of times calculating the correlation coefficient for each permutation. QAP can then statistically assess how likely you would be to match or exceed the original correlation coefficient with a random permutation, thus helping to assess the statistical likelihood of association. This procedure is also implemented in the *sna* package and returns p-values indicating the likelihood that the networks are independent. In our analysis, a p-value tells us whether the networks are related or independent. A p-value of 1 means the networks are identical, while a p-value of 0 means they have no relationship.

The final method of comparison is the use of ERGMs as implemented in the *ergm* package (Handcock et al. 2018; Hunter et al. 2008) in R. ERGMs help us understand how different parts of a network, such as nodes and connections, form by estimating the processes that may have shaped the observed network structure. This enables us to test whether certain network features, like the connections between camps, are likely due to chance or driven by

underlying interaction patterns. Although ERGMs are not commonly used in archaeology (Amati et al. 2020; Tom Brughmans, Keay, and Earl 2014; W H Cegielski 2024; Wang and Marwick 2021), they are valuable for modeling relationships between camps in our study. By estimating parameters that describe the processes likely to have generated the network, ERGMs allow for the simulation of multiple networks, which can then be compared to the observed network to assess the likelihood that observed patterns are due to specific generative processes. These models also allow for the inclusion of various variables to predict the network structure, with different models being compared to determine the best fit.

2.4 Results

2.4.1 Network Comparisons

The first question we address is what is the overall relationship between the different networks produced from our model? These include three interaction networks (visiting, trading, and learning) as well as two types of material culture similarity networks based on pot and point types. Recall pots and points are differentiated in the model by prestige-based transmission: pot prestige is randomly assigned, while point prestige depends on hunting success. Point attributes are also adapted to specific environments, boosting hunting success. Figure 2.3 illustrates the correlations between pairs of networks (refer to Table 2.2 for network descriptions; the numerical scores are listed in Table 2.3). The visiting and trading networks are almost identical, with a correlation approaching 1.0, indicating that visiting almost always results in trade. Learning is also closely correlated with both visiting and trading, but to a lesser degree, because interaction does not always result in learning. The six correlations between types of interaction (visiting, and learning) and types of material

Figure 2.3: Graph correlation boxplot comparison of the social interaction and material culture networks for networks generated in the ArchMatNet agent-based model.

culture (points and pots) are lower than those between two types of interaction but are still fairly strong with scores greater than 0.75; the same holds for the correlation between the two types of material culture. All of these have larger ranges because each of the material culture networks exhibit considerable outliers, as is expected with the stochasticity built into the ABM and with more than 30,000 simulations. The QAP test results listed in Table 2.3 are consistent with the graph correlation results and indicate that the strong correlations are generally not due to chance and that the networks are independent. All values are close to 1.0, indicating a strong relationship between these networks.

Outliers shown in Figure 2.3 were investigated further. Some of the outliers can be attributed to runs where the probability of trading was zero. The average correlation for visiting and point networks with a zero probability of trading was 0.12, which was much

Table 2.3: Network Comparison Results

Network Comparison	Graph Correlation	QAP Test
Point_Combined	0.747	0.996
Pot_Combined	0.749	0.996
Point_Pot	0.756	0.997
Learning_Point	0.762	0.997
Learning_Pot	0.764	0.998
Visiting_Pot	0.767	0.997
Trading_Pot	0.767	0.998
Visiting_Point	0.769	0.997
Trading_Point	0.770	0.997
Trading_Learning	0.965	0.999
Visiting_Learning	0.966	0.999
Visiting_Trading	0.999	1.000

lower than any other parameter in the model. Trading being one of the three mechanisms (learning and migration are the others) for material culture to spread between camps makes it no surprise that this severely affects the material culture networks. There are, however, relatively few runs with zero probability of trading and many runs set with the default trading probability had equally low correlation values. Additionally, runs with a high probability of creating new objects also have lower correlations. Likely, this results in large numbers of objects deposited in the virtual assemblages and makes it harder to detect markers of interaction. This has relevance for interpreting large archaeological assemblages. Notably, there were no outliers for runs of the model where each parameter was set to its default value.

We expected to see some differences between how interaction networks and material culture networks correlate, but, as the boxplots in Figure 2.3 and graph correlation values in Table 2.3 show, the results indicate that the correlation values were almost the same for all types of interactions and material culture. Thus, our model does not appear to provide any insight into what types of interaction may better reflect material culture networks. This

is likely due to trading and learning co-occurring with visiting. Several parameters affected the network correlations. These effects were stronger than those discovered during the initial model testing (Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias 2023) and are discussed in the next section.

2.4.2 Model Parameters

All model parameters were tested to determine their effect on the network correlations. Parameters in an ABM are values that can be changed each simulation and affect agent behavior. The parameters discussed in this paper are listed in Table 2.1. The full parameter list can be viewed in the supplemental information online or in Appendix A Table 1 and their importance to the model are described in (Bischoff and Padilla-Iglesias 2023). Parameters related to mobility (frequency of aggregation, population size, migration rates, and frequency of visiting) were tested with additional model runs and are discussed in another analysis (see Padilla-Iglesias and Bischoff 2024). One of the key factors affecting the correlation between material culture and interaction networks is whether all agents start with the same types of pots and points or if each camp begins with its own unique set of traits. This significantly affects how well the material culture networks align with the interaction networks. In other words, does every agent make the same type of pot and point or are agents making different types of pots and points depending on the camp they belong to? The average graph correlation value between visiting interaction networks and point networks is 0.16 when the starting traits are the same versus 0.77 when the starting traits are unique per camp. The graph correlation for every agent starting with the same trait is almost nonexistent when compared to the strong correlation that exists when each camp has unique starting traits. Clearly, differences in material culture are necessary to use material culture networks as a representation of social interaction networks. For this reason, all results shown in this

analysis, including the graph correlations shown previously, only include model runs with unique traits.

Determining a single parameter's effect is challenging when multiple parameters are changed. One method for determining the effects of each parameter is to fit the model parameters and graph correlation values (the dependent variable) to a generalized additive model (GAM). GAMs can model complex, nonlinear relationships between dependent and independent variables and can also handle categorical and continuous predictors (Hastie and Tibshirani 1990). Thus, GAMs help us understand how different factors influence the strength of the relationship between social interactions and material culture. This makes a GAM a suitable tool for understanding the variables in the ArchMatNet model. There are 24 parameters that can be adjusted in ArchMatNet that impact model results. If all of these variables are included in a GAM (not including *uniqueTraits* which is set to 1—meaning bands start with different traits), the r^2 result returned by the *gam* function in the *mgcv* (S. N. Wood 2017) package in R is 0.451 (full results can be viewed in Appendix A Table 2). Nearly half of the variance is explained by these parameters (the rest being the natural stochasticity in the model), but if most of the parameters are removed, the r^2 value only drops to 0.372 with four remaining parameters: *aggregationFreq*, *learningMethod*, *nTicks*, and *visibility*. Only about 10 percent of the variance is lost by removing 19 parameters. This suggests that the model is not overly sensitive to most parameters. The variables that are highly sensitive are shown in Figure 2.4. The *aggregationFreq* variable controls how often bands come together to visit, hunt, trade, and learn. More interaction within bands appears to generate stronger correlations with the material culture networks. The *learningMethod* was ran as a factor in the gam model, as the values represent a continuum from 0 where all learning is based on conformism to 100 where all learning is based on prestige. A value of 50 indicates that learning is split between the two methods. As shown in Figure 2.4, the *learningMethod*

has a nonlinear relationship where equal learning methods have the strongest correlations, but the correlation values decrease as the learning method leans towards one method or the other. Prestige learning does result in a slightly lower correlation than conformism. The *nTicks* parameter controls the number of time steps in the model. In this case, each time step, or tick, represents a one-month period. The shortest period, 2000 ticks, would represent nearly 167 years. The longer the model ran, the smaller the correlation values became. This indicates that material culture networks are less correlated over long timespans than shorter periods. The *visibility* parameter controls the likelihood that certain traits are copied. When *visibility* is 0 the correlation between networks is stronger. Thus, the introduction of low-visibility traits introduces more variability in the network comparison, although the relationship is still strong. Other variables that may have an impact—though smaller than those discussed here according to the GAM—include population size, and probabilities of interaction and learning. Regardless of the parameters, with the major exception of *uniqueTraits*, most runs of the model have significant correlations between the interaction networks and material culture networks.

2.4.3 ERGMs

The ERGM analysis was used to determine whether the interaction and material culture networks shared the same structural properties. As described earlier, ERGMs allow us to model the generative properties that create network structures. If similar generative structures match both types of networks then we can conclude that the networks are similar in structure. Three models were used in this analysis, each incorporating an edge parameter, which is a default for ERGM analyses since a network cannot exist without edges. Each model also includes a band parameter, which assigns each node (representing a camp) to

Figure 2.4: Boxplots showing the distribution of graph correlation values for the most influential parameters in the ArchMatNet model as determined by a generalized additive model (GAM). The y-axis is the graph correlation values between a visiting interaction network and a point interaction network.

a specific band. This is important because the band each camp belongs to affects interaction frequencies. The triangle parameter captures triadic structures where three nodes are all mutually connected, a common feature in networks. Note that the triangle model was attempted with only the edge and band parameter but in most cases the model failed to converge, which is a recognized issue in the **ergm** package. In this ABM, each band consists of three camps, always forming a triad of strong interactions. Two related parameters, GWESP (geometrically weighted edgewise shared partners) and thretrail (two-paths or three trails), are used to capture specific network structures. GWESP measures the likelihood that two nodes sharing a common partner will form a triangle. This parameter reflects the tendency for camps connected to the same camp to form direct links between themselves.

The threetrail parameter, on the other hand, identifies network structures where three nodes are connected by two edges, without forming a triangle. It captures paths to triads through intermediate nodes and is used to detect strong connections between camps from different bands, helping to form a broader network structure. The three models together are:

1. edge + band
2. edge + gwesp + threetrail + band
3. edge + triangle + threetrail + band

The fit of the ERGM models were assessed using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), which is a metric used to assess the quality of a model. Lower AIC values indicate a better model fit. We used a goodness-of-fit (GOF) test to evaluate how well the ERGM replicated the structural properties of the observed network and assess the adequacy of the models in reproducing key network features. ERGMs are computationally intensive. A random sample of 100 model runs was selected and each model run was fitted to the three models for each of the five types of networks returned from ArchMatNet (visiting, trading, learning, point, and pot). Each ERGM was run for the default 1024 iterations resulting in at least 2,000,000 total simulations depending on how many iterations each ERGM requires (between 1 and 60). Unfortunately, the *ergm* function in R has a tendency to fail when trying to replicate certain network structures and some ERGMs did not return results. A final note for the ERGMs is that they require binary networks. All network weights were binarized by calculating the 75th quantile for the edge weights and retaining links above that quantile. This is an arbitrary cutoff but it can be useful in identifying the structural relationships among the strongest ties (see M. A. Peebles and J. M. Roberts 2013).

Table 2.4 shows the results of the ERGM simulations. For clarity, only point and visiting networks are shown. Other networks return similar results and can be explored in the analysis code in the supplemental material or Appendix A. The GOF test indicates that all

models performed well at capturing the structures of the network (1 equals a good fit and 0 a poor fit; GOF plots can be viewed in the supplementary material). This GOF test is useful for statistical validation of ERGM results. The AIC results indicate that both the gwesp and triangle parameters plus the threerail and the default parameters fit the model well. These results are expected based on the triadic nature of the three camps within each band that each form strong connections with each other. The most important parameter appears to be the threerail parameter. This parameter would matter in the ArchMatNet models because weaker ties between bands would be formed by some camps while other camps might lack those ties. The threerail parameter shows that camps acting as intermediaries in the network is an important part of the network structure.

With a well-fitting ERGM model, we can now generate simulated networks that replicate the key structural properties of the observed network. We can then compare the correlation between simulated networks and the original network. A total of 10,000 simulations of a random visiting network compared to the original network return an average graph correlation of only 0.15. Of the 10,000 simulated networks, the highest correlation was 0.55. This is far from the near 1 correlation between interaction networks generated from ArchMatNet. A comparison of 10,000 simulated point networks to the original visiting network yields an average correlation of only 0.05 with a max of 0.5. These tests clearly demonstrate that the network correlations discussed previously are not likely chance occurrences.

2.4.4 Network Centrality

Calculating centrality measures is often an important part of analyzing a network. We calculated the same centrality measures used by Golitko (2023): betweenness, closeness, degree, and eigenvector. The centrality results highlight a weakness of the ArchMatNet

Table 2.4: ERGM Results

network	formula	gof	aic
point	edge + band	0.98	104.43
point	edge + gwesp + threetrail + band	0.99	95.38
point	edge + triangle + threetrail + band	0.98	89.25
visiting	edge + band	0.98	106.64
visiting	edge + gwesp + threetrail + band	1.00	93.10
visiting	edge + triangle + threetrail + band	1.00	96.44

model. Because the network is fairly symmetrical (each camp has two strong connections forming a band and weak connections to camps in other bands) the centrality scores are all fairly identical. For example, the eigenvector centrality of a sample model run ranges from 0.15 to 0.24. This is a narrow range. The same network has a degree centrality range of 4.0 to 4.1. Likewise betweenness and closeness centrality have narrow ranges. Because there is so little variation, the correlation between centrality scores for interaction networks and material culture networks is poor, ranging from approximately 0.2 to -0.2. Only model runs with 4 or more bands were used in an attempt to increase variation, but the number of bands appears to make little difference or even decrease the correlation between network centrality scores for interaction and material culture networks. This is an example of a limitation of a generalized ABM where the results cannot adequately represent empirical data.

2.4.5 Individual Networks

While comparing thousands of model runs is essential for statistical validity, it is useful to carefully examine individual networks to better understand the network structure. Fig-

ure 2.5 compares networks where *uniqueTraits* are set to false (a) and true (b)—meaning that in (a) everyone starts with the same traits and in (b) everyone in different camps has a different trait. Each of the five types of networks compared in this analysis are shown. The visiting, learning, and trading networks are all comparable across both model runs. There is a significant difference between the point and pot runs. For the networks that do not have unique starting traits, the point and pot networks are a jumbled mess. The network structure in no way resembles the interaction networks and in the case of the pot network, no differentiation is possible at all, even with only the strongest 50% of links shown in the network graphs. On the other hand, the pot and point networks with unique starting traits closely resemble the interaction networks. All of the intra-band triads are represented. There are a number of differences in the weaker connections between camps and bands. Besides the necessity of having material culture networks with enough variation, the point and pot networks with unique starting traits demonstrate that these networks struggle with exact replication of weaker links. Figure 2.3 shows that the pot and point networks had the weakest correlations (although they were still high). Caution should be applied when interpreting weak connections between networks based on material culture. These weak connections can be important parts of network analysis, but material culture may not always be adequate for determining specific weak relationships between nodes. The final observation of these networks, is that the point and pot networks exhibit some differences. There are different generative processes involved while the major relationships are the same. It appears a more complete picture could be created by combining the pot and point networks, meaning interaction can be better represented by multiple types of material culture.

Figure 2.5: Networks of interaction and material culture for two runs of the ArchMatNet model. Networks (a) are from a run of the model where the parameter `uniqueTraits` is set to false, meaning each band has identical starting traits. Networks (b) include networks where `uniqueTraits` are set to true, and each band unique starting traits. Nodes are colored by band and numbered by camp. Only the strongest 50% of links are shown. The color and size of the edges represent the strength (or weight) of the relationship between each node.

2.5 Conclusion

This study has highlighted the utility of the ArchMatNet agent-based model for understanding the dynamic relationships between social interaction and material culture networks. By simulating these networks under varied conditions and analyzing the results using graph correlations, generalized additive models (GAMs), Exponential Random Graph Models (ERGMs), and other methods, we have attempted to provide a deeper understanding of how material culture can serve as a proxy for social interactions. Our most important findings can be summarized into three main points. (1) Material culture networks (i.e., network representations based on similarities in artifacts between camps) can be good representations of social interaction networks (i.e., counts of interactions between individuals from different camps), provided there is sufficient variation in the material culture given the affects of the **uniqueTraits** parameter. We have not attempted to qualify how much variation in material culture is necessary. This is a potential avenue of future research but may depend on regional and temporal contingencies. Overall, the correlations between interaction networks and material culture networks were strong and highly significant (see the graph correlation and QAP results). (2) Material culture networks are inherently fuzzier than social interaction networks (see, in particular, Figure 2.3 and Figure 2.5). The connections between material culture networks and social interaction networks were not as strong as those between different types of interaction networks, suggesting that using artifacts to map social interactions can sometimes blur or weaken the relationships we see. This is an expected result but one that network analysts should always keep in mind. Strong relationships may appear weaker when viewed through material culture, or weak or non-existent relationships may appear stronger. Viewing social networks through a material culture lens in effect has a smoothing effect on the strength of relationships. We did find that the strongest relation-

ships tended to remain relatively strong in both interaction and material culture networks. (3) Different types of material culture can produce different results. While the point and pot networks exhibited strong similarities, close comparisons (see Figure 2.5) demonstrated notable differences in which bands had the strongest inter-band ties. The use of multiple types of material culture appears to provide a more accurate representation of interaction networks.

The model results also show that despite the stochastic nature of agent-based models, certain parameters consistently had a significant impact on the correlation between social and material networks. Specifically, factors such as the frequency of aggregation, learning methods, the number of time steps, and the visibility of traits play critical roles in shaping these networks. As band members interact more frequently, their material culture networks tend to show stronger correlations with their social interaction networks. This reinforces the idea that material culture is most reflective of social ties when there is consistent and repeated interaction between groups. The sensitivity of the model to the learning method parameter also underscores the importance of how information is transmitted within the community. Gravel-Miguel (2017) found that even low rates of cultural transmission produced similarities between reconstructed and observed social networks. The non-linear relationship between the learning method (whether conformist or prestige-based) and network correlations suggests that a balance between these learning strategies produces the strongest correlations. There is an interesting correlation with ethnographic studies of cultural transmission that indicate mixed models of prestige and conformism also do best (Chudek et al. 2012; Henrich and Boyd 1998; Henrich and McElreath 2003; Henrich and Broesch 2011). There are different mechanisms in play in the ethnographic studies than the ArchMatNet model. In the ABM, low levels of prestige transmission appear to reduce the spread of traits, while high levels of prestige transmission causes too much transmission for the ma-

terial culture to adequately represent the social processes. The mechanisms are related for the ethnographic studies in that conformism helps maintain distinct cultural identities while prestige allows for the spread of advantageous traits. The visibility of cultural traits also emerges as a critical factor as enabling the differential learning of traits based on their visibility decreases the correlation between interaction and material culture networks. This suggests that the visibility of traits can introduce variability into the network, which may be important for understanding the dynamics of social and material culture networks. While the current output of the ArchMatNet model does not provide the opportunity to investigate the specifics of how high- and low-visibility traits independently affect correlations between material culture and interaction networks, future investigations will better be able to understand these interactions.

The use of ERGMs allowed us to model structural dependencies within the network, showing that triadic closure and intermediary paths play key roles in the structure of both the interaction and material culture networks. Essentially, the ERGM results demonstrate that both networks have similar generative structures. ERGMs also allow for statistical validation of the model through the use of simulated networks with the same structural properties as the actual network. This method of network validation can be used in a variety of network applications.

While the results of this study suggest that the ArchMatNet model is a powerful tool for investigating the relationship between social and material culture networks, they also highlight certain limitations. The largest limitation is the symmetry in the network structure that does not generate enough variation in network centrality to make a useful comparison between networks. Future research should prioritize the emphasis of long-distance ties. Something this model does not consider is that sometimes the avoidance of a camp can be just as important as seeking out a camp to visit. People can have many reasons to visit a

particular camp or to avoid visiting another camp. Including preferential node attachment (increasing the inter-band connections between some camps) while ensuring other nodes avoid each other will create more variation and provide a better opportunity to evaluate the structural position of nodes in the network.

In summary, the findings from the ArchMatNet model provide valuable insights into the relationships between social and material culture networks. The model demonstrates that, while material culture networks often serve as good proxies for social networks, certain factors—particularly the frequency of interaction, learning strategies, and trait visibility—play crucial roles in determining the strength of this relationship. These results emphasize the importance of carefully considering the parameters that shape these networks in both archaeological interpretations and agent-based modeling. As such, the ArchMatNet model not only contributes to our understanding of past social dynamics but also offers a methodological framework for future research in this area, highlighting the potential for ABMs to simulate complex, emergent social phenomena.

Acknowledgements

Claudine Gravel-Miguel contributed equally to the creation of ArchMatNet with the authors of this paper (see Appendix E for permissions). Matthew Peeples, Michelle Hegmon, and Michael Barton provided guidance and feedback that greatly improved the final product.

Data Availability

The ArchMatNet model is peer-reviewed and can be found here along with its ODD description: <https://doi.org/10.25937/08kx-4f24>. Supplementary material can be found in an OSF (Open Science Foundation) repository here: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/DE3VQ>.

Note: This paper was co-authored by Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias and is intended for publication in Plos ONE.

References

- Amati, Viviana et al. (June 19, 2020). “A Framework for Reconstructing Archaeological Networks Using Exponential Random Graph Models”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 27 (2), pp. 192–219. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-019-09423-z. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10816-019-09423-z>.
- Barton, C Michael and Julien Riel-Salvatore (June 1, 2014). “The Formation of Lithic Assemblages”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 46, pp. 334–352. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2014.03.031. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440314001204>.
- Barton, C Michael, Julien Riel-Salvatore, et al. (Dec. 1, 2011). “Modeling Human Ecodynamics and Biocultural Interactions in the Late Pleistocene of Western Eurasia”. In: *Human Ecology* 39 (6), pp. 705–725. ISSN: 0046-8169,1572-9915. DOI: 10.1007/s10745-011-9433-8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-011-9433-8>.
- Bischoff, Robert J and Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias (July 10, 2023). “A description and sensitivity analysis of the ArchMatNet agent-based model”. en. In: *PeerJ Computer Science* 9, e1419. ISSN: 2376-5992. DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.1419. URL: <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-1419/> (visited on 07/24/2023).
- Bischoff, Robert J, Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias, and Claudine Gravel-Miguel (2024). “Evaluating the Effects of Randomness on Missing Data in Archaeological Networks”. In: *Ac-*

cepted to CAA 2021 Conference: Limassol, Cyprus. DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b>.

Borgatti, Stephen P (2005). “Centrality and Network Flow”. In: *Social Networks* 27 (1), pp. 55–71. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2004.11.008. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873304000693>.

Brandes, Ulrik et al. (Apr. 2013). “What is Network Science?” In: *Network Science* 1 (1), pp. 1–15. ISSN: 2050-1242,2050-1250. DOI: 10.1017/nws.2013.2. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/network-science/article/what-is-network-science/C0794B28C613757F09C3FB315500E3A1>.

Brantingham, P Jeffrey (2003). “A Neutral Model of Stone Raw Material Procurement”. In: *American Anthropologist* 68 (3), pp. 487–509.

Brughmans, Tom, Simon Keay, and Graeme Earl (Sept. 2014). “Introducing exponential random graph models for visibility networks”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 49, pp. 442–454. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2014.05.027. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440314002052>.

Brughmans, Tom and Matt Peeples (Oct. 14, 2017). “Trends in Archaeological Network Research: A Bibliometric Analysis”. en. In: *Journal of Historical Network Research* 1 (1), pp. 1–24. ISSN: 2535-8863,2535-8863. DOI: 10.25517/jhnr.v1i1.10. URL: <https://jhnr.uni.lu/index.php/jhnr/article/view/10>.

Brughmans, Tom and Matthew A Peeples (2023). *Network Science in Archaeology*. Cambridge Manuals in Archaeology. Cambridge University Press.

Brughmans, Tom and Jeroen Poblome (Apr. 2016). “Roman bazaar or market economy? Explaining tableware distributions through computational modelling”. In: *Antiquity* 90 (350), pp. 393–408. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.15184/aqy.2016.35. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/roman-bazaar-or-market-economy-explaining-tableware-distributions-through-computational-modelling/6C64CA37C247869A21A6DE6CE18F55FD> (visited on 09/09/2019).

Butts, Carter T (2023). *sna: Tools for Social Network Analysis*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=sna>.

Carr, Christopher (1995a). “A Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Carr C. and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 171–258. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.

- Carr, Christopher (1995b). “Building a Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Christopher Carr and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 151–170. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- Cegielski, W H (2024). “Networks, Agent-Based Modeling, and Archaeology”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Tom Brughmans et al. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press, pp. 280–293.
- Chudek, Maciej et al. (Jan. 1, 2012). “Prestige-biased cultural learning: bystander’s differential attention to potential models influences children’s learning”. en. In: *Evolution and human behavior: official journal of the Human Behavior and Evolution Society* 33 (1), pp. 46–56. ISSN: 1090-5138,1879-0607. DOI: 10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2011.05.005. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2011.05.005> (visited on 09/16/2024).
- Clark, Jeffery J (2001). *Tracking Prehistoric Migrations: Pueblo Settlers Among the Tonto Basin Hohokam*. en. Vol. 65. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. 124 pp. ISBN: 9780816520879. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=27Tk3xNT-6UC>.
- Collar, Anna et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Networks in Archaeology: Phenomena, Abstraction, Representation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 1–32. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6>.
- Crabtree, Stefani A (Mar. 2015). “Inferring Ancestral Pueblo Social Networks from Simulation in the Central Mesa Verde”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 144–181. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9233-8. URL: <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10816-014-9233-8>.
- Creanza, Nicole, Oren Kolodny, and Marcus W Feldman (May 2017). “Greater than the Sum of Its Parts? Modelling Population Contact and Interaction of Cultural Repertoires”. en. In: *Journal of the Royal Society, Interface / the Royal Society* 14 (130), p. 20170171. ISSN: 1742-5689,1742-5662. DOI: 10.1098/rsif.2017.0171. URL: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsif.2017.0171>.
- Dietler, Michael and Ingrid Herbich (1998). “Habitus, Techniques, Style: An Integrated Approach to the Social Understanding of Material Culture and Boundaries”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution, pp. 232–263.

- Drennan, Robert D (Mar. 1984). “Long-distance transport costs in pre-Hispanic Mesoamerica”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 86 (1), pp. 105–112. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100>.
- Epstein, Joshua M (2006). *Generative Social Science: Studies in Agent-Based Computational Modeling*. en. Princeton University Press. 356 pp. ISBN: 9780691125473. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=T8_zh3F7rMIC.
- Feinman, Gary M and Jill E Neitzel (Dec. 1, 2020). “Excising Culture History from Contemporary Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 60, p. 101230. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101230. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416520302038>.
- Fraser, D (1980). “The Cutpoint Index: A Simple Measure of Point Connectivity”. In: *Area* 12 (1), pp. 301–304.
- Gjesfjeld, Erik (Mar. 1, 2015). “Network Analysis of Archaeological Data from Hunter-Gatherers: Methodological Problems and Potential Solutions”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 182–205. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9>.
- Golitko, Mark (Dec. 1, 2023). “A performance test of archaeological similarity-based network inference using New Guinean ethnographic data”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 72, p. 101550. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2023.101550. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416523000661>.
- Gosselain, Olivier P (Sept. 1, 2000). “Materializing Identities: An African Perspective”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 7 (3), pp. 187–217. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1023/A:1026558503986. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026558503986>.
- Gravel-Miguel, Claudine (2017). “The Impacts of Geography and Climate Change on Magdalenian Social Networks”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, School of Human Evolution and Social Change, Arizona State University, Tempe. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/2286/R.I.44052>.
- Gravel-Miguel, Claudine and Fiona Coward (2024). “Palaeolithic Social Networks and Behavioural Modernity”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Matthew A Peoples et al. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 443–458.
- Handcock, Mark S et al. (2018). *ergm: Fit, Simulate and Diagnose Exponential-Family Models for Networks*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ergm>.

- Hastie, T J and R J Tibshirani (1990). *Generalized additive models*. en. London: Chapman and Hall.
- Hegmon, Michelle (Jan. 1, 1992). “Archaeological Research on Style”. In: *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21 (1), pp. 517–536. ISSN: 0084-6570. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.anthro.21.1.517. URL: https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev.an.21.100192.002505?casa_token=6qKr2S4tTBMAAAAA:WKU4gaCaBHKmkj-Kv2CAYnC0mbdzfIXxVG7Xflho10RvGx23v8LM7uestyIFA-5JuHMqLAJcZrFFA.
- Henrich, Joseph (2004). “Cultural Group Selection, Coevolutionary Processes and Large-Scale Cooperation”. en. In: *Journal of theoretical biology* 220 (4), pp. 577–590. ISSN: 0022-5193,1095-8541.
- Henrich, Joseph and Robert Boyd (July 1, 1998). “The Evolution of Conformist Transmission and the Emergence of Between-Group Differences”. In: *Evolution and Human Behavior* 19 (4), pp. 215–241. ISSN: 1090-5138. DOI: 10.1016/S1090-5138(98)00018-X. URL: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S109051389800018X?casa_token=X6ZIYQeGMRgAAAAA:pgCEIAE-46nIUh7IOg3TDAeZeZNF3XcKDVomg48JAt6LTIxnWOB1oSiaDN715wOxPflYBiA3.
- Henrich, Joseph and James Broesch (Apr. 12, 2011). “On the nature of cultural transmission networks: evidence from Fijian villages for adaptive learning biases”. en. In: *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences* 366 (1567), pp. 1139–1148. ISSN: 0962-8436,1471-2970. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2010.0323. URL: https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rstb.2010.0323?casa_token=RJ9t4MK7qKoAAAAA:Yc_yW5N5VKWDOMLfbz0-4EHP-a7G_CQP4xVgjLXPQEKw8Zs52A_jdw8Y64QVW36GIq-zOzWSul&casa_token=tfIMRw4goysAAAAA:Mt44Db-HUAQHSEFywCi1Gj8qYjTPKA vV0T5RAVsW-A-OMG8Ha9-CNIy72dCBLvpR3ErGM05EliGm.
- Henrich, Joseph and Richard McElreath (Jan. 2003). “The evolution of cultural evolution”. en. In: *Evolutionary anthropology* 12 (3), pp. 123–135. ISSN: 1060-1538,1520-6505. DOI: 10.1002/evan.10110. URL: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/evan.10110?casa_token=NxPG9otvpAoAAAAA:EuT8mLXtRkSdaHAHH1AMxamjjQG-HvNXOJxoEumyulswlYA0yTFqvIWY0tG_Fw9N5te2Z7fGuq5fDQ.
- Hodder, Ian (1982). *Symbols in Action: Ethnoarchaeological Studies of Material Culture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9780521241762. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-TSE9AAAAIAAJ>.
- Holland-Lulewicz, Jacob (Jan. 4, 2021). “From Categories to Connections in the Archaeology of Eastern North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research* 29, pp. 537–

579. ISSN: 1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w>.

Hunter, David R et al. (2008). “ergm: A Package to Fit, Simulate and Diagnose Exponential-Family Models for Networks”. In: *Journal of Statistical Software* 24 (3), pp. 1–29.

Huntley, Deborah L (2008). *Ancestral Zuni Glaze-Decorated Pottery: Viewing Pueblo IV Regional Organization through Ceramic Production and Exchange*. Vol. No. 72. Anthropological Papers. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.

Jennewein, Douglas M et al. (Sept. 10, 2023). “The Sol Supercomputer at Arizona State University”. In: *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing* (Portland, OR, USA). PEARC '23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 296–301. ISBN: 9781450399852. DOI: 10.1145/3569951.3597573. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597573> (visited on 05/02/2024).

Krackardt, David (1987). “QAP Partialling as a Test of Spuriousness”. In: *Social Networks* 9 (2), pp. 171–186. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/0378-8733(87)90012-8. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378873387900128>.

Lemonnier, Pierre (June 1, 1986). “The Study of Material Culture Today: Toward an Anthropology of Technical Systems”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 5 (2), pp. 147–186. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90012-7. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416586900127>.

Lyons, Patrick D (2003). *Ancestral Hopi Migrations*. English. First Edition edition. Anthropological Paper Number 68. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816522804.

Mills, Barbara J, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (Apr. 9, 2013). “Transformation of social networks in the late pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110 (15), pp. 5785–5790. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1219966110. URL: <http://www.pnas.org/content/110/15/5785>.

Morgan, Thomas J H, Catharine P Cross, and Luke E Rendell (2015). “Nothing in human behavior makes sense except in the light of culture: Shared interests of social psychology and cultural evolution”. en. In: *Evolutionary Perspectives on Social Psychology*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 215–228. ISBN: 9783319126968. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-12697-5_17. URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-12697-5_17.

- Muthukrishna, Michael, Thomas J H Morgan, and Joseph Henrich (Jan. 2016). “The when and who of social learning and conformist transmission”. In: *Evolution and human behavior: official journal of the Human Behavior and Evolution Society* 37 (1), pp. 10–20. ISSN: 1090-5138,1879-0607. DOI: 10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2015.05.004.
- Neuzil, Anna A (2008). *In the Aftermath of Migration: Renegotiating Ancient Identity in Southeastern Arizona*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona No. 73. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Padilla-Iglesias, Cecilia and Robert J Bischoff (Oct. 9, 2024). “Hunter-gatherer mobility patterns influence the reconstruction of social networks from archaeological assemblages”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 59, p. 104798. ISSN: 2352-409X,2352-4103. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798>.
- Peeples, Matthew A (2018). *Connected Communities: Networks, Identity, and Social Change in the Ancient Cibola World*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816535682. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-fyw-DwAAQBAJ>.
- (Feb. 4, 2019). “Finding a Place for Networks in Archaeology”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research*, pp. 1–49. ISSN: 1059-0161,1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8>.
- Peeples, Matthew A and Tom Brughmans (2023). *Online Companion to Network Science in Archaeology*. URL: <https://archnetworks.ne>.
- Peeples, Matthew A, Barbara J Mills, et al. (2016). “Analytical Challenges for the Application of Social Network Analysis in Archaeology”. In: *The Connected Past: Challenges to Network Studies in Archaeology and History*. Ed. by Tom Brughmans, Anna Collar, and Fiona Coward. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 59–84.
- Peeples, Matthew A and John M Roberts (July 2013). “To Binarize or not to Binarize: Relational Data and the Construction of Archaeological Networks”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 40 (7), pp. 3001–3010. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.03.014. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440313001040>.
- Peeples, Matthew A, Jr Roberts John M, and Yi Yin (2024). “Challenges for network research in archaeology”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Matthew A Peeples et al. Oxford University Press, pp. 34–49. ISBN: 9780198854265. DOI: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198854265.013.2. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198854265.013.2>.

- Premo, Luke S (2006). “Agent-Based Models as Behavioral Laboratories for Evolutionary Anthropological Research”. In: *Arizona Anthropologist* 17, pp. 91–113.
- Prignano, Luce, Ignacio Morer, and Albert Diaz-Guilera (2017). “Wiring the Past: A Network Science Perspective on the Challenge of Archeological Similarity Networks”. In: *Frontiers in Digital Humanities* 4. ISSN: 2297-2668. DOI: 10.3389/fdigh.2017.00013. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fdigh.2017.00013>.
- Rogers, J Daniel and Wendy H Cegielski (2017). “Building a better past with the help of agent-based modeling”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 114 (49), pp. 12841–12844. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1718277114. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1718277114>.
- Romanowska, Iza, Stefani A Crabtree, et al. (May 2019). “Agent-Based Modeling for Archaeologists: Part 1 of 3”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 7 (2), pp. 178–184. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.1017/aap.2019.6. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances-in-archaeological-practice/article/agentbased-modeling-for-archaeologists-part-1-of-3/B044D059FABC3F793205C6407BF32B09>.
- Romanowska, Iza, Colin D Wren, and Stefani A Crabtree (2021). *Agent-Based Modeling for Archaeology: Simulating the Complexity of Societies*. Santa Fe: The Santa Fe Institute Press.
- Sackett, J R (1982). “Approaches to Style in Lithic Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 1, pp. 59–112.
- Sackett, James R (Sept. 1, 1986). “Isochrestism and style: A clarification”. en. In: *Journal of anthropological archaeology* 5 (3), pp. 266–277. ISSN: 0278-4165,1090-2686. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90008-5. URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0278-4165\(86\)90008-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0278-4165(86)90008-5) (visited on 02/21/2025).
- Scheidel, W (2014). “The Shape of the Roman World: Modelling Imperial Connectivity”. In: *Journal of Roman Archaeology* 27, pp. 7–32. ISSN: 1047-7594,2331-5709. DOI: 10.1017/S1047759414001147. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S1047759414001147/type/journal_article.
- Sindbæk, Søren M (Mar. 1, 2007). “Networks and nodal points: the emergence of towns in early Viking Age Scandinavia”. en. In: *Antiquity* 81 (311), pp. 119–132. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/s0003598x00094886. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00094886>.

- Team, R Core (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria. URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Terrell, John E (1977). “Human Biogeography in the Solomon Islands”. In: *Fieldiana* 68 (1), pp. 1–47. ISSN: 0071-4739.
- Terrell, John Edward et al. (Mar. 10, 2023). *Modeling the Past: Archaeology, History, and Dynamic Networks*. en. Berghahn Books. 248 pp. ISBN: 9781800738706. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=ziWBEEAAQBAJ>.
- Van Oyen, Astrid (Mar. 1, 2016). “Historicising Material Agency: from Relations to Relational Constellations”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 23 (1), pp. 354–378. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0>.
- Wang, Li-Ying and Ben Marwick (Oct. 1, 2021). “A Bayesian networks approach to infer social changes from burials in northeastern Taiwan during the European colonization period”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 134, p. 105471. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2021.105471. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440321001412>.
- Wenger, Etienne (1998). *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Vol. 9. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. URL: <https://valenciacollege.edu/faculty/development/teaching-learning-academy/documents/CommunityofPractice.pdf>.
- White, Andrew (2013). “An Abstract Model Showing That the Spatial Structure of Social Networks Affects the Outcomes of Cultural Transmission Processes”. In: *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 16 (3). ISSN: 1460-7425. DOI: 10.18564/jasss.2219. URL: <http://jasss.soc.surrey.ac.uk/16/3/9.html>.
- Wiessner, Polly (1983). “Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 48 (2), pp. 253–276. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280450. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-and-social-information-in-kalahari-san-projectile-points/52D6230881B0C69260ABE226BD82EC0E>.
- (Jan. 1985). “Style or Isochrestic Variation? A Reply to Sackett”. In: *American Antiquity* 50 (1), pp. 160–166. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280643. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-or-isochrestic-variation-a-reply-to-sackett/206F9510A8BF0402883F6A436A9BB787> (visited on 01/14/2020).

Wobst, H Martin (1977). “Stylistic Behavior and Information Exchange”. In: *For the Director: Research Essays in Honour of the Late James B. Griffin*. Ed. by C E Cleland. Vol. 61. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, pp. 317–342.

Wood, S N (2017). *Generalized Additive Models: An Introduction with R*.

CHAPTER 3

A GEOMETRIC MORPHOMETRIC AND MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH TO REGIONAL PROJECTILE POINT ANALYSIS IN THE SOUTHWEST UNITED STATES

3.1 Introduction

Projectile points, and stone tools in general, are rarely the subject of regional-scale studies in the post-archaic era of the U.S. Southwest (for some exceptions see Cameron 2001; C. M. Hoffman 1997; Justice 2002b; Chris Loendorf 2010; Paige 2022; Ryan 2017; Sedig 2014; Sliva 1999; Sliva 2006; Whittaker and Bryce 2017). One problem with a regional analysis for projectile points is that numerous type names and schemas have been devised, often ad hoc, across the Southwest. This complicates comparisons, as the number of type names likely exceeds the number of distinct styles (Sliva 2006, p. 37). A relatively new method for projectile point analysis is drawn from the field of geometric morphometrics (GMM). GMM enables us to measure shape differences more objectively, without depending on traditional classification systems. While GMM can help identify differences in morphology, the rapid development of machine learning means we can automate projectile point analyses once an appropriate procedure and training dataset has been created. Of course the problem of harmonizing or even creating regional projectile point typologies is not limited to the Southwest U.S. This article is not meant to create a new typology for general use. Rather, it is a case study on conducting regional-scale analyses of projectile points using GMM for the purposes of examining regional scale interaction.

Projectile point styles are often associated with social identity (Mason 1894, p. 655;

Waguespack et al. 2009, p. 787; Whittaker 1994, pp. 260–268). This is not always the case, though there is evidence there is some association between projectile point types and known cultural groups in the Southwest. Functional differences in projectile point types cannot, however, be ignored as a contributing factor to stylistic differences. Projectile point styles in the Southwest, particularly the type of hafting, are affected by their intended purpose. Hunting and warfare have different requirements for optimal projectile point performance which affects point morphology (Chris Loendorf, L. Simon, et al. 2015).

Ecological variation can also affect morphology. A recent study of Central African hunter-gatherers found subsistence tools, including projectiles, were less frequently exchanged than musical instruments and more adapted to local ecologies (Padilla-Iglesias, Blanco-Portillo, et al. 2024). In the Southwest there are a limited number of large game animals that inhabit most of the region, thus large game animals are not expected to form local ecological niches. Large game animals are noted because stone points were typically not used for small game (Ellis 1997; Chris Loendorf, L. Simon, et al. 2015; Waguespack et al. 2009).

Besides ecological reasons for morphology differences, resharpening and repurposing can affect the typology of projectile points (e.g., Bamforth 1991; Gardner and Verrey 1979; C. M. Hoffman 1985; Larick 1985). Fortunately, experiments with the type of small arrow points considered in this study demonstrate this is unlikely to be a significant factor (Chris Loendorf, T. A. Rogers, et al. 2019). Loendorf and colleagues found through experimental research that most small arrow points cannot be reworked when damaged while firing. Also, because the points may have been more work to reattach to the arrow than to make another, the bases are unlikely to have been commonly reworked. Azevedo and colleagues (2014) studied the morphology of points after tool modification and found that the original shape was still the primary factor in the overall variation. They also note that arrow point tips

are most affected by resharpening, echoing the work of Loendorf and colleagues. Because the base of the point is less likely to be affected by reworking in general, and the base is the primary discriminant between types in the Southwest (Justice 2002b; Sliva 1997; Sliva 2006), resharpening is not likely to be an important factor in this analysis.

Ethnographic and archaeological sources in the Southwest document the use or association of projectile points with various social and symbolic functions (Bayman 2007, pp. 78–79; Beaglehole 1936; Cushing 1883; Dittert 1959; Fewkes 1898; Justice 2002b, pp. 309–310; Kaldahl 2000; Kamp, Whittaker, and Bryce 2016; Parsons 1932; Parsons 1939; Russell 1908; Sedig 2014; Simpson 1953; J. Stevenson 1884; M. C. Stevenson 1894; M. C. Stevenson 1903; Whittaker and Kamp 2016). These factors suggest that social differences play a substantial role in projectile point style, and thus, there is some association with recognized archaeological cultures and projectile point styles. I presume that similarities in projectile point styles represent interaction, however, it is also possible that identical point styles can independently be invented in multiple areas (i.e., convergence). I assume interaction/diffusion as the default explanation because all of the areas in my study area are known to have interacted and exchanged goods.

The primary goal of this study is to examine and develop heuristics for efficiently examining regional variation in projectile points using GMM methods and machine learning. Besides difficulties with typologies, analyzing sufficient numbers of projectile points for a suitable regional analysis is an expensive process at least in time and typically also in resources. The use of GMM and machine learning can help to automate the analysis and reduce the time and resources needed to conduct a regional analysis. This study will examine the utility of these methods for a regional analysis of projectile points.

Goals:

1. **Discrimination** – Determine whether GMM can distinguish projectile point types.

2. **Method Selection** – Identify optimal GMM approaches.
3. **Automation** – Improve reproducibility and efficiency using machine learning.
4. **Regional Analysis** – Explore projectile point distributions across the Southwest.

To address these objectives, this case study focuses on a large region of the central U.S. Southwest during the late pre-Hispanic period between AD 1100 and 1500. This period and location present an opportunity to examine projectile point variation across several archaeological culture areas and during a time of marked social change. By analyzing a large collection of projectile points from this region, this study provides a methodological framework for conducting regional-scale analyses of projectile points.

3.1.1 Study Region: Central U.S. Southwest, AD 1100–1500.

The project area (Figure 3.1) includes a large portion of northern Arizona and north-west New Mexico extending from the Tonto Basin below the Mogollon Rim to areas near Monument Valley on the north and the Flagstaff area in the west to the Zuni Mountains in the east. It also includes the site of S’edav Va’aki (formerly known as Pueblo Grande), from the Phoenix Basin, which was added for an additional comparative site. This large area encompasses a diverse landscape across which archaeologists have defined multiple archaeological culture areas (Ancestral Pueblo, Mogollon, Sinagua, Hohokam) and regional traditions (Kayenta, Cibola, and others). This extent includes much of the contemporary and traditional lands of both Hopi and Zuni Pueblos. Relationships between archaeological culture area designations and groups of people with shared identities are obviously complex (Duff 2002; M. A. Peeples 2018), but the scope of the region defined here is certainly large enough to capture cultural variation that spans many distinct social boundaries and identities.

This area and time period provide an excellent context for exploring variation in projectile point design and distribution. The study's geographical and cultural scope allows for examining potential boundaries in stylistic distributions across distinct regions and culture areas. Interaction was common between these regions (e.g., E Charles Adams, Stark, and Dosh 1993; Bernardini 2005; Bischoff 2023b; Jeffery J Clark 2001; Duff 2000; Duff 2004; Gauthier 2021; B. J. Mills, Jeffery J Clark, et al. 2013; B. J. Mills, M. A. Peeples, et al. 2015; M. A. Peeples and Haas 2013; M. A. Peeples 2018; Matthew Peeples et al. 2021; Stark, Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark 1998). Between AD 1100 and 1200, populations grew throughout the study region (Bernardini et al. 2021; Dean 2010; Hill, Jeffery J Clark, et al. 2004), while major societal changes occurred after the end of the Chacoan regional system around the middle of the century (Cameron and Duff 2008). During the late AD 1200s the Hopi and Zuni regions became major population centers and outlying areas began consolidating into larger, more aggregated pueblos (Bernardini 2005; Bernardini et al. 2021; Kintigh, Glowacki, and Huntley 2004; M. A. Peeples 2018; Schachner 2012). This consolidation of population into aggregated communities and, eventually, overall population decline continued until European contact. Major social changes profoundly affected the people in these areas. These changes include the development of the Kachina cult (E C Adams 1994; Ware 2014); the appearance of platform mounds in the Tonto Basin around AD 1250 (Rice 1998); the Salado phenomenon in the Tonto Basin and elsewhere in the southern Southwest (Jeffery J Clark, Huntley, et al. 2013); plaza spaces became larger and more prominent (B. J. Mills 2007); and many long-distance and local migrations generated new coalescent communities (e.g., Bernardini et al. 2021; Jeffery J Clark, Huntley, et al. 2013; Jeffery J Clark, J. A. Birch, et al. 2019; Hill, Jeffery J Clark, et al. 2004; Hill, M. A. Peeples, et al. 2015; M. A. Peeples 2018). These changes represent transformative shifts in religious practices, community integration, and social structure. Although this study does

Figure 3.1: Geographical boundaries of the project area, encompassing parts of the Ancestral Pueblo, Hohokam, Mogollon, and Sinagua archaeological culture regions.

not address temporal change, this period is marked by significant transitions and population movements that are well-documented, offering a well-established context for analyzing projectile points.

3.1.2 Geometric Morphometrics

Traditional projectile point typological analyses define sets of artifacts that share common attributes selected by researchers as potentially diagnostic of distinct cultural, technological, or chronological groupings. The selection of these attributes is not arbitrary but typically relates to a small number of easy to describe and identify features which can sometimes ignore substantial variability in artifact design in features not explicitly included in

the typological schema (Sliva 2017, p. 100). Traditional typologies of all types—including ceramics—often struggle to account for nuance and variation within defined categories, as artifacts are typically assigned to a type without further detailed analysis. For example, in the U.S. Southwest, Roosevelt Red Ware has historically been treated as a uniform ceramic type, yet closer inspection reveals considerable variation in design execution and production techniques that reflect localized traditions and social interactions (e.g., Jeffery J Clark and Lyons 2012; Jeffery J Clark, Huntley, et al. 2013; Jeffery J Clark, J. A. Birch, et al. 2019; Crown 1994). By rigidly categorizing such artifacts, typologies can overemphasize distinctions between groups that may have been culturally or socially interconnected, reinforcing boundaries shaped more by archaeological convention and research history than by the artifacts' actual characteristics. (e.g., G. A. Clark and Riel-Salvatore 2006).

Beyond this, traditional typologies are often created in a geographically bounded context in such a way that similarities or differences that span larger areas might be downplayed. For example, Buchanan and colleagues (Buchanan, Eren, and O'Brien 2018) analyzed projectile point classifications from Justice (Justice 1995; Justice and Kudlaty 2001; Justice 2002b; Justice 2002a) to investigate convergence in point types across the U.S. Out of 84 types identified as potentially convergent—that is, similar in form due to parallel functional or environmental demands rather than shared ancestry—16 were excluded because they originated from the same region and time period. This suggests that, even within a single region like the Southwest, multiple named types may actually represent the same tool form. The inability to consistently distinguish types using 10 morphological attributes implies either that these traits fail to capture meaningful variation, or that the named types are not meaningfully distinct. The results of this study suggest nine projectile point types in the Southwest cannot be easily discriminated, and, indeed, several of the types Buchanan and colleagues identified were in the Southwest and fall within the temporal scope of this study

Table 3.1: Equivalent Projectile Point Types

Type
Awatovi Side-Notched = Buck Taylor Notched
Bonito Notched = Pueblo Alto Side-Notched
Gatlin Side-Notched = Ridge Ruin Side-Notched = White Mountain Side-Notched
Pueblo Side-Notched = Snaketown Side-Notched

(see Table 3.1). As will be noted, Awatovi Side-notched and Buck Taylor Side-notched can be distinguished via the difference between basal notches and a deeply concave base, however, in my experience the other types are difficult to distinguish.

Traditional typological methods have recently been augmented using GMM. Essentially, GMM is a set of methods for the statistical analysis and description of shape variation (Rohlf and Marcus 1993, p. 129). Shape excludes properties related to location, scale, and orientation (Shott and Trail 2010, p. 199). GMM has grown rapidly since its primary origin in the early 1990s and is now a mature field (D. C. Adams, Rohlf, and Slice 2013; Fred L Bookstein 1991; Corti 1993; Mitteroecker and Gunz 2009; Philipp Mitteroecker and Schaefer 2022; Rohlf and Marcus 1993). GMM originated in biological analyses of plant and animal morphology in particular but has been successfully used to characterize the morphology of stone tools and other artifacts in a number of cases (see Okumura and Araujo 2019, for a recent overview). Different GMM methods primarily belong to one of two categories: landmarks or outlines. Landmarks involve placing points at homologous locations across the 2D or 3D object. Theoretically different, but closely related to landmarks are semilandmarks, which are arbitrarily placed along edges or curves at equally spaced intervals. While the distinction between these is important (F L Bookstein 1997; Shott and Trail 2010), I hereafter refer to landmarks and semilandmarks as simply landmarks as they are fundamentally treated the same in this analysis with the exception of their initial placement. Once landmarks are placed on the shape, these landmarks can be aligned, scaled,

and rotated using a generalized Procrustes analysis (GPA) (Gower 1975). Outline analysis translates the shape's outline into numeric data, allowing researchers to mathematically compare different shapes. A common example is elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA) (Kuhl and Giardina 1982). EFA involves transforming an outline into a series of smooth curves, with each harmonic described by four coefficients and a variable number of harmonics used to capture the shape's complexity. These data can then be used in multivariate statistical analyses similar to the landmark data. Typically, a principal components analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the dimensionality of the data before clustering or other statistical analysis is performed. Both landmark and EFA approaches are used in this analysis. Quantitative data have long been used in lithic analyses, however, traditional measurements can significantly reduce geometric information (see Shott and Trail 2010). GMM has the advantage of capturing complex geometric data that captures the majority of shape variation present in the object.

3.2 Dataset

This dataset consists of projectile point images, metric data, and metadata. Metadata includes provenience and site information. All data used in this analysis were stored using the open access Heurist database (Johnson 2011), which is specifically designed for storing and sharing social science data. Much of the data used in this analysis, including images, have been made available for sharing in this database (see data availability) with the exception of site location data, which is protected by U.S. federal law. Some images are unable to be shared publicly due to institutional restrictions.

The sampling strategy was designed to obtain a targeted sample of projectile points from the entire project area with more detailed samples from the Tonto Basin and Cibola areas.

The following data points were captured for each point where possible: (1) a photograph, (2) maximum thickness, (3) total weight, (4) the location of any damage, and (5) the material type (chert, obsidian, etc.). In some cases, images were obtained from other sources and metrics were not obtained. All images were taken with a scale allowing for measurements other than thickness and weight to be obtained directly from the photograph, although no metric measurements were used in this analysis. Archaeological site metadata such as site location and chronology were captured, with much of it coming from the cyberSW database (B. Mills et al. 2020). ArchaMap (Hruschka et al. 2022) was used to merge differences in site names and projectile point types across databases based on a common set of alternate names.

Some of the sites had occupations that began prior to AD 1100 and finding curated projectile points (points from earlier periods found in later contexts) is common. The provenience information available was insufficient to exclude projectile points to ensure only points made after AD 1100 were included. In general, corner-notched projectile points began to decline in frequency around AD 1000 and became rarer after AD 1100 (Justice 2002b; Whittaker and Bryce 2017). For this reason, corner-notched points and archaic points (i.e., atlatl dart points), which are occasionally found in late contexts, were excluded from analysis and were typically excluded from data collection. Table 3.2 describes the organizations/individuals where projectile point data were obtained. Data were collected for a total of 3,114 projectile points from 81 archaeological sites.

Table 3.2: Projectile Point Sources

Source	Projectile Points
Arizona State Museum	1063
Center for Archaeology and Society	1079
Joshua Watts	404
Kellam Throgmorton	14
Museum of Northern Arizona	441
S'edav Va'aki (Pueblo Grande)	175
Wesley Bernardini	39

3.3 Methods

Numerous methods were used in this analysis. They are described here, but all analyses were completed in R (Team, R Core 2024) or Python (Python Software Foundation 2024) and can be viewed in detail in Appendix B, including the specific packages used.

The goals of the GMM analyses here were (1) to define the optimal approach for capturing shape data from the projectile points available, (2) to evaluate variability in shape in relation to traditional typological categorizations, (3) to explore evidence of new groupings of projectile points based on shape characterization, (4) to explore the spatial and contextual distribution of those new shape-based categories, and (5) to evaluate the potential for machine learning based models to assign projectile points to shape-based categories.

The first step in this analysis was to take the raw images collected both from new and archival photographs and preprocess them so that they were consistent. Preprocessing the images involved reorienting the images to a vertical orientation. The rule used was to align the point with the direction it would be hafted to an arrow shaft. In some cases, the base of the point was severely slanted. Orienting the point using a horizontal base would result in odd blade directions. Images were either cropped close to the projectile point shape or the background was completely removed creating a transparent image. These steps were taken

to make it easier to consistently place landmarks on the images and for whole outline GMM analysis.

3.3.1 Landmark analysis

Landmark analysis has two advantages over an outline analysis like EFA. First, EFA struggles to capture side-notch information (Bischoff 2023a), and second, the use of landmarks allows broken points to be used. Landmarks were placed according to a procedure developed in earlier analyses (Bischoff and Allison 2020; Bischoff 2023a) using the TpsDig software (Rohlf 2015).

This procedure uses one corner of the projectile point as the target of the landmark analysis. As mentioned, this allows the analysis to incorporate damaged projectile points that are missing much of the rest of the projectile point. Landmarks were placed at key points (see Figure 3.2): halfway between the tip and basal corner, the basal corner, and the midpoint of the base. Two additional landmarks were placed in between each of these three landmarks. In addition to the five landmarks placed on all projectile points, side-notched projectile points had three landmarks placed at the top of the side-notch, the deepest part of the notch, and the bottom of the side-notch (see results section for more information). The curves function in TpsDig was used to accurately assign landmarks where the position was not obvious (.e.g., the corner of the base).

There were, however, many judgement calls to be made. In some cases it was difficult to judge where the bottom of the point transitioned to the side of the point when the point was curved. Notches could also have gradual transitions into the blade or base. For these reasons the initial batch of several hundred landmarks were reviewed for consistency and landmarks were adjusted as required. The TPS files were imported into R using the **Momocs**

Figure 3.2: Landmark configuration example.

(Bonhomme, Picq, et al. 2014) package. The **Momocs** package was used to apply GPA, and the aligned, scaled, and rotated landmarks were exported for additional analysis.

3.3.2 EFA

EFA analysis requires whole shape outlines. These can be created automatically in the **Momocs** package from imported image masks (black backgrounds with white objects). One potential pitfall for projectile points outlines is that some projectile points have asymmetric shapes as mentioned earlier when describing aligning points. This can affect the analysis if not accounted for, as significant morphometric variation will be ascribed to the orientation of the projectile point.

Of particular concern is the angle of the base. Many of the bases are not perpendicular to the vertical orientation of the projectile point. This variation can be manually addressed

image by image. Another way is to use a GMM analysis. By examining the principal component (PC) space it is possible to determine which PC is related to shifts in the orientation of the base. Images that are aligned to one side of the PC can be identified en masse and flipped via command line instructions rather than manual adjustment to thousands of images. The **Momocs** package by default plots the morphometric variation along each PC axis as shown in Figure 3.3, which demonstrates that, in this example, PC2 is the orientation of the base. Once this process was completed, this axis of variation was eliminated which emphasizes important morphological attributes not related to the rotation of the point. Failing to take this or other issues related to the orientation of the projectile point can introduce considerable error into the analysis.

3.3.3 Dimensionality Reduction

PCA is commonly used for reducing the dimensionality of multivariate data. For a GMM example of PCA, an EFA analysis with only 10 harmonics will generate 40 columns of data without any clear indication whether any particular column is associated with more variation in the morphology. A PCA analysis can capture more than 95% of this variation with only 9 PCs using the data in this analysis. Not only is this a significant reduction in data, but the first two PCs capture 70% of the variation. This allows a simple biplot to show much of the variation in the multivariate data. PCA has been a mainstay in statistical analysis for decades, however, newer methods for reducing dimensionality have shown significant improvements.

A recently developed method called Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) (McInnes, Healy, and Melville 2020) has proven to have many useful features that make it a better option than PCA in many cases where high dimensional data are being

Figure 3.3: Distortion in base orientation revealed by principal component 2 (PC2) in Procrustes analysis of projectile points. The distortion affects the analysis and requires correction by horizontal flipping of the images.

considered. UMAP is a dimensionality reduction technique that operates by creating a weighted graph (network) among a set of points based on high-dimensional data (in this case, EFA harmonics or GPA landmarks) with the strength of the ties between points defined based on their similarity across all dimensions. UMAP then projects this graph to a lower dimensional space that attempts to maximize the retention of the original graph topology in that lower dimensional space. UMAP as a method is designed specifically to attempt to capture a balance of local and global structure in complex high-dimensional data and thus,

is a good fit for the kinds of information provided by GMM. The R **umap** implementation (Konopka 2020) produces just two dimensions from the input data. UMAP projections are primarily relied on in this analysis.

3.3.4 Spatial Analysis

A meaningful projectile point typology should have some correlation with geographic space (e.g., Azevedo, Charlin, and González-José 2014; Hamilton, Buchanan, and Walker 2019). Two primary methods were used in this analysis to compare projectile point types across space: kernel density estimation (KDE) and a network community detection algorithm. KDE was used to create a smoothed estimate of the distribution of data. Hexagon grids were used to minimize edge effects. Each grid was 36 kilometers across, which roughly corresponds to one day's travel on foot (Drennan 1984). While KDE is weighted towards locations with a higher number of points (in this case sites), this was undesirable for this analysis due to the uneven nature of data collection both for this study and for archaeology in general. Thus "hexagon binning" (Bischoff 2018, p. 59) was used where the data in each hexagon was aggregated and generated as a single point. This removed the effects of numerous sites in one location, such as Tonto Basin or Zuni.

The second method first involves a non-geographic method, network community detection, which was then projected across geographic space. First an archaeological similarity network was created by generating a weighted network graph using methods common in archaeological network analysis (M. A. Peeples and J. M. Roberts 2013). This was done by calculating the manhattan distance (more commonly known in archaeology as the Brainerd-Robinson distance) for each pair of sites standardized to a similarity score between one (identical) and zero (no similarity). A commonly used community detection algorithm is

the Louvain method (Blondel et al. 2008), which works by merging groups together to find stable groups that maximize connections within a group while minimizing connections between different groups. This method was used to identify communities based on the projectile point typologies. These communities, which represent archaeological sites that have similar assemblages, were then plotted on a map.

3.3.5 Machine Learning

Given the size of the dataset used in this study, automating as much of the analysis as possible was essential. While geometric morphometric (GMM) methods were applied to quantify the shape variation of projectile points, machine learning models trained on these analyzed specimens were used to classify additional examples. Machine learning is particularly well-suited for this kind of task, as it enables efficient, consistent analysis at scale. However, it typically requires a labeled dataset for training—something this study provides through the prior GMM analysis.

Machine learning is increasingly common in archaeology (Bickler 2021), and its application to lithic analysis is gaining traction (e.g., Castillo Flores et al. 2019; Elliot et al. 2021; Lowe 2024; Nash and Prewitt 2016). At its core, machine learning involves training algorithms to identify patterns in data and make predictions (Bickler 2021, p. 186), though the implementation is often more complex in practice. This complexity brings potential pitfalls—particularly overfitting, where a model becomes too narrowly tailored to its training data and fails to generalize to new cases. To mitigate this, care was taken to follow the best practices recommended by Calder and colleagues (2022), including the use of unseen test data (15% of the total dataset) to validate model performance. For this study, the ResNet-18 model (He et al. 2016) was selected due to its strong accuracy, efficient train-

ing, and low computational demands. As a convolutional neural network, it extracts visual features across multiple layers and uses residual connections to support stable, efficient training. Its smaller size and speed made it particularly well-suited to the scale and goals of this analysis.

A pretrained model was used for all classification. The model had already been trained to extract image features and was fine-tuned on the projectile point dataset (described in a future section). Training was limited to 12 epochs to reduce the risk of overfitting, which occurs when a model learns patterns specific to the training data and fails to generalize to new examples.

3.4 Existing Typologies

The simplest approach to this analysis is to identify an existing typology that can be reliably replicated using a GMM approach. If GMM methods can successfully reproduce established typologies, they can enhance traditional classification by increasing consistency, reducing subjectivity, and enabling scalable, quantitative analysis of projectile points across large datasets. Moreover, replicating existing typologies with GMM at this scale would generate a labeled dataset large enough to train machine learning models capable of automating the classification process.

To implement this, it was first necessary to select a typology that could serve as a reliable reference for both the GMM training phase and subsequent machine learning classification. Excluding projectile point types idiosyncratic to specific projects—such as the Salado and Tonto types from the Roosevelt Platform Mound Study (Rice 1994)—there are nearly 70 projectile point types spanning the period of this analysis across four major typologies (C. M. Hoffman 1997; Justice 2002b; Chris Loendorf and Rice 2004; Sliva 2006).

While each of these typologies defines types based on some combination of morphological and temporal criteria, there is considerable overlap and inconsistency among them, making direct cross-typology comparisons difficult. Two main criteria guided typology selection: (1) broad geographic and temporal coverage across the study region, and (2) sufficient visual or physical representation of point types to support landmark-based analysis. Justice's typology of projectile points in the Southwest (Justice 2002b) best met these requirements. It includes extensive illustrations and descriptions that span the entire Southwest and is further supported by a reference collection at the Museum of Northern Arizona that aligns well with Justice's classifications.

Because the number of landmarks differed between triangular and side-notched points, these forms were analyzed separately. Figures Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5 show individual and mean landmark placements for several projectile point types. While there is some variation in notch shape for side-notched points, base shape is clearly distinguishable in both figures, with concave, convex, and straight bases visually separated.

A UMAP projection of Procrustes-aligned landmarks for side-notched points (Figure 3.6) shows considerable overlap among point types, even when the ellipses are limited to 68% of the data (approximately one standard deviation). There are numerous outliers, but some types—including Awatovi, Bonito, and Buck Taylor—form relatively tight clusters with fewer outliers. These are also more easily distinguished visually. Awatovi points have basal notches, while Buck Taylor points are defined by deeply concave bases (see Figure 3.7). The GMM analysis appears to struggle to distinguish between basal notches and deeply concave bases, which likely contributes to this confusion, however, these attributes are important to some projectile point type definitions. Bonito points, which have convex bases that are uncommon in the dataset, also form a relatively distinct cluster.

The triangular point types show greater separation in the UMAP projection (Figure 3.8),

although there are still several outliers. Sobaipuri points form one of the tightest clusters, but they still overlap with a number of other types.

The statistical validity of each group can be assessed using Hotelling's T^2 test (Hotelling 1931), which compares the means of groups across multiple related variables. This test is useful for evaluating whether the assigned groups are statistically distinct based on their multivariate representations—in this case, the UMAP coordinates. Table 3.3 shows comparisons between selected pairs of projectile point types, listing the number of points in each group (Type 1 Total and Type 2 Total), the Hotelling's T-squared statistic, and the associated p-value. Only comparisons with p-values greater than 0.1 are shown to highlight cases where separation is not statistically supported. The p-value represents the probability of observing a difference as large as the one measured (or larger), assuming there is actually no difference between the two groups.

The results show that most side-notched types are statistically distinguishable from one another based on the UMAP projection of Procrustes-aligned landmarks. However, Table 3.3 highlights the exceptions—pairwise comparisons among side-notched types where Hotelling's T^2 test produced p-values greater than 0.1, indicating insufficient evidence for clear separation. While some comparisons, such as Bonito and Kin Kletso Side-notched, approach significance, each of the listed types has at least one other group with which it overlaps morphometrically. In contrast, triangular types show stronger overall separation, though the comparison between Bull Creek and Snaketown Triangular Concave Base did not yield a statistically significant result. These findings are somewhat unexpected given the simpler outlines of triangular points, but they suggest that side-notched features may introduce variation that is not consistently captured in the GMM-based analysis.

Figure 3.9 highlights a key issue with using typologies for projectile points. The figure shows continuous morphological variation across the dataset, with no clear boundaries

Figure 3.4: Individual (small) and mean (large) landmark placements for side-notched projectile points by type. Small points represent the original landmark coordinates for all specimens within each type, while larger points show the average landmark positions.

Figure 3.5: Individual (small) and mean (large) landmark placements for triangular projectile points by type. Small points represent the original landmark coordinates for all specimens within each type, while larger points show the average landmark positions.

Table 3.3: Hotelling's T^2 Tests for Projectile Point Types

Type 1 (n)	Type 2 (n)	T^2	P-value
Awatovi (15)	Buck Taylor (11)	0.33	0.85
Awatovi (15)	Pueblo Side-notched Concave Base (11)	1.86	0.42
Bonito (48)	Temporal (7)	4.49	0.12
Buck Taylor (11)	Pueblo Side-notched Concave Base (11)	3.78	0.19
Desert Side Notched (25)	Pueblo Side-notched Straight Base (7)	2.02	0.39
Kin Kletso Side-notched (6)	Temporal (7)	5.62	0.13
Pueblo Alto Side-notched (9)	Temporal (7)	0.39	0.84
Bull Creek (8)	Snaketown Triangular Concave Base (9)	2.85	0.30

Figure 3.6: UMAP projection of Procrustes-aligned landmarks for side-notched projectile points. Each point represents an individual specimen, colored and shaped by type. Ellipses enclose approximately 68% of specimens within each type, highlighting areas of clustering and overlap. Distinct clusters are visible for Awatovi, Bonito, and Buck Taylor types, though substantial overlap and outliers suggest morphological similarity across types. Note: x and y axes are flipped for visualization purposes.

Figure 3.7: Examples of Awatovi (bottom) and Buck Taylor (top) projectile points.

between types. While many projectile points appear visually distinct, there is often a morphological continuum that isn't immediately obvious. For example, the difference between a basal notch and a concave base may be gradual when enough examples are considered. Similarly, the distinction between concave and straight bases can range from obvious to nearly indistinguishable. Typological categories can be useful for organizing and interpreting data, but it's important to recognize that they often oversimplify and obscure meaningful variation within and between groups.

Overall, this analysis suggests that traditional regional typologies do not adequately capture patterns of morphological similarity in projectile point design—at least not for side-notched points. The overlain projectile point images in Figure 3.9 show that points located near each other in the projection are morphologically similar, but reducing the variation to a manageable number of clusters requires an impractically high number of groups. Ideally, landmark data alone would allow points to be assigned to clear, well-separated types, but

Figure 3.8: UMAP projection of Procrustes-aligned landmarks for triangular projectile points. Each point represents an individual specimen, colored and shaped by type. Ellipses indicate the distribution of specimens for each type, enclosing approximately 68% of the data. Distinct clustering is evident for types such as Sobaipuri and the Snaketown variants, while other types show more overlap.

that is not the case here. A hybrid approach could be taken, where easily distinguishable types are retained and new types are created as needed. However, to maintain consistency throughout the analysis, existing typological categories were set aside in favor of a strictly attribute-based classification.

3.5 Attribute-based Typology

Based on the existing typologies for late prehistoric projectile points in the region (Chris Loendorf and Rice 2004; Rice 1994; Tagg 1994; Thomas 1981), several attributes were chosen for this analysis. These typologies, while not always consistent, reflect long-standing

Figure 3.9: UMAP projection illustrating continuous morphological variation among side-notched projectile points. A random sample of projectile points is overlain on the plot to show the morphological variation.

expert observations about morphological variation and regional traditions. Selecting attributes from them allows for continuity with prior research and provides a basis for testing whether quantitative methods like GMM can replicate or refine traditional classifications.

These attributes are:

1. Point form (e.g., triangular vs. side-notched)
2. Base shape (e.g., concave vs. convex)
3. Basal notch (e.g., presence/absence)
4. Notch height (for side-notched points)
5. Serration (presence/absence)

One additional attribute was also considered: three morphologically determined shape clusters. All projectile points were grouped into three clusters based on overall shape using elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA), which was chosen because it captures the entire outline of each point. Landmark analysis was initially preferred, as about one-fourth of the points had

damage that distorted their outlines. While in many cases this damage did not significantly affect the EFA results, all assignments were reviewed for consistency, and reassignments were made when necessary. Hierarchical cluster analysis was applied to the UMAP results derived from the EFA coefficients (Figure 3.13), and the number of clusters was selected by identifying major branches in the resulting dendrogram.

With the five attributes mentioned above plus the addition of the shape clusters, the projectile points were assigned to attribute-based types as shown in Figure 3.10. Notably, less than 2% of side-notched points were serrated, while almost 11% of triangular points were serrated. Given this and to reduce the number of potential types, serration was only considered for triangular points. This also matches the projectile point typologies as none of the side-notched types considered in this analysis are defined by their serration.

The identification of each projectile point attribute is described below. Where appropriate, GMM methods were used for attribute assignment, with additional verification through machine learning. Machine learning models were trained for all attributes except for distinguishing triangular versus side-notched points, which were initially identified during data collection.

Each model was developed with three main purposes: (1) to assign attributes to projectile points where values were missing, (2) to evaluate and correct inconsistencies in initial assignments, and (3) to provide trained models for use in future analyses. Model performance was assessed by comparing predicted attributes to initial labels across the full dataset. As shown in Figure 3.11, the classification accuracy ranged from 93.7% (base type) to 98.4% (serration). These results reflect internal consistency rather than out-of-sample performance.

To evaluate initial assignments, each trained model was used to predict attribute values for all projectile points. Any mismatches between the predicted and original assignments

Figure 3.10: Decision tree illustrating the attributes used to assign each projectile point not belonging to a previously assigned type to a newly created type based on shape, base morphology, notching, notch position (for side-notched points), and serration (for triangular points). The numbers shown indicate the total number of projectile points containing that attribute.

were flagged for manual review. This process revealed numerous inconsistencies in the original data, particularly for base type and point cluster, which were corrected where appropriate. After corrections were made, models were retrained, significantly improving overall assignment quality and model reliability.

Further details on machine learning implementation, including architecture and training parameters, can be found in the supplementary Python code and Appendix B.

The determination of side-notched points vs. triangular points was done visually as the landmark data required predetermining whether the point had notches. Likewise, the basal notches and the serration were visually assigned as well, as the GMM methods struggled to

Figure 3.11: Confusion matrices for four machine learning models used to classify projectile point attributes: (A) base shape, (B) notch height, (C) overall point cluster (based on EFA), and (D) serration. Each tile represents the number of projectile points in a predicted–true category combination, with darker shading indicating higher counts. Accuracy values reflect classification agreement on the full dataset. These matrices provide an internal consistency check rather than an evaluation of generalization performance.

Figure 3.12: Hierarchical clustering dendrogram of projectile point outlines based on elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA). Fourier coefficients were reduced using UMAP and clustered using hierarchical clustering. Three major branches were identified and selected as shape clusters. These clusters are primarily differentiated by overall height and width ratios.

differentiate deeply concave points vs. basal notched points as well as serration. A machine learning model was trained on serration primarily to check assignments for errors.

The point clusters were determined by creating outlines of all projectile points and conducting an EFA analysis. This generates fourier coefficients which were subjected to a UMAP transformation (Figure 3.13) and a subsequent hierarchical clustering analysis. Three major branches formed in the tree plot (Figure 3.12), and thus three clusters were chosen for assignments. Hotelling's T^2 tests indicate all three clusters can be clearly differentiated. A machine learning model was created for the shape clusters and used for validation. The three clusters are primarily differentiated by height and width ratios.

The landmark data were best suited for assigning the base type into the categories used for this analysis. Angles between the third and fifth landmarks were calculated and initial visual assignments were used to gauge appropriate angles for assigning categories. These four categories were used for the analysis with the following assignments for angles (0 degrees represents horizontal):

1. deeply concave < -12

Figure 3.13: UMAP result of the EFA coefficients for all projectile points. Hierarchical clustering was used to assign points to three shape clusters. Mean shapes for each cluster are depicted at the centroid of each cluster. Note: x and y axes are flipped for visualization purposes.

2. concave < -5 & ≥ -12
3. straight ≥ -5 & ≤ 5
4. convex > 5

Assignments were then visually checked for errors and modified as needed. A machine learning model was trained as described above and used to assign points that were not landmarked. Again, points were visually checked and modified as needed.

Notch heights were determined using landmark data to assess the relative vertical position of the notch. Specifically, the ratio of the distance from the first landmark to the bottom of the notch to the distance from the third landmark to the base was calculated for each point. This ratio served as a standardized measure of notch height, independent of overall point size. A histogram of these ratios (see Figure 3.14) revealed a clear central

Figure 3.14: Histogram of notch ratios for side-notched projectile points. The x-axis shows the ratio of the first landmark to the bottom of the notch to the third landmark to the bottom of the landmark. The y-axis shows the number of projectile points in each bin. The dashed lines indicate the cutoff points for low, mid, and high notches.

distribution, with most notches falling within a well-defined middle range. To classify the points into low, mid, and high notch categories, quantile-based cutoffs were applied. High-notch points were defined as those above the 0.67 quantile—approximately one standard deviation above the mean—capturing the upper end of the distribution. Low-notch points were defined as those below the 0.025 quantile, a threshold chosen based on a sharp drop observed in the histogram, indicating a natural break in the data. All remaining points were classified as mid-notch. This approach allowed for the classification of notch position in a way that reflects both the overall distribution and notable discontinuities in the data.

Once all attributes were assigned and visually checked for consistency, the projectile

point type was assigned by following the decision tree. The number of attributes involved resulted in 45 side-notched types and 20 triangular types. Six of these types had only a single projectile point. Four of these were side-notched types with a basal notch. Two of these were triangular points with a convex base. Side-notched types had a maximum of 129 projectile points with a median of 11. Triangular types had a maximum of 249 with a median of 20. Figure 3.15 demonstrates how these attribute-based types align with the existing typologies previously tested with GMM. The attribute-based assignments are far better at determining the original assignments than GMM alone. One exception where one attribute-based type was assigned to multiple existing types is caused by a missing attribute for Temporal projectile points, which are defined as having extra notches. This attribute was not considered in this analysis. The other exception is Citrus side-notched, which overlaps somewhat with Desert side-notched. This is not surprising as the Desert side-notched type is somewhat vaguely defined.

Hotelling's T^2 tests indicate that most types were easily distinguishable. There were some exceptions, shown in Table 3.4. This table shows test results with p-values above 0.1. Groups with fewer than 10 projectile points were not included in these tests. In the cases where the groups were not easily distinguished via Hotelling's T^2 tests, the attributes were closely related. For example, types that were identical with the exception of serration were harder to distinguish. In other examples, most attributes were similar. Only 4 of the 12 paired groups had more than 1 attribute that was different than the comparison group, the rest only had 1 different attribute. Each individual attribute, however, when considered as a group, is easily distinguishable via Hotelling's T^2 tests.

Figure 3.16 shows the projectile point outlines for some of the most common types used in this analysis. The shape outlines have been scaled and rotated using an automated GPA process in the Momocs package. These types represent over 75% of the total number of

Figure 3.15: This heatmap visualizes the distribution of projectile point shapes across point type categories as defined using prior typologies compared to the attribute-based types. Color intensity reflects the frequency of each shape within a type, with clustering applied to both axes to highlight similarities in shape composition across point types.

Table 3.4: Hotelling’s T² Tests for Attribute-Based Point Types

Group 1 (n)	Group 2 (n)	T ²	P-value
shape-1_concave_side-notched_low (26)	shape-1_straight_side-notched_low (45)	0.39	0.82
shape-1_concave_side-notched_mid (29)	shape-1_deeply concave_side-notched_mid (11)	1.04	0.61
shape-1_concave_side-notched_mid (29)	shape-1_straight_side-notched_mid (13)	0.14	0.93
shape-1_deeply concave_side-notched_mid (11)	shape-1_straight_side-notched_mid (13)	0.55	0.77
shape-1_deeply concave_side-notched_mid (11)	shape-2_concave_side-notched_mid (46)	3.21	0.22
shape-2_concave_side-notched_high (10)	shape-3_concave_side-notched_high (12)	0.79	0.69
shape-2_concave_side-notched_mid (46)	shape-2_straight_side-notched_mid (56)	3.39	0.19
shape-3_concave_side-notched_mid (61)	shape-3_deeply concave_side-notched_mid (23)	0.62	0.74
shape-1_concave_triangular__serrated (17)	shape-1_deeply concave_triangular (27)	1.70	0.44
shape-1_straight_triangular (103)	shape-2_concave_triangular__serrated (13)	3.26	0.20
shape-2_concave_triangular (76)	shape-3_concave_triangular__serrated (10)	0.89	0.65
shape-3_concave_triangular (88)	shape-3_concave_triangular__serrated (10)	2.73	0.26

assigned projectile points in the database. Several of these points would be easy to visually discriminate, while others are noticeably different but would be difficult to discriminate from a cursory visual examination. The attribute approach used here using a combination of GMM methods and visually identified attributes supplemented with machine learning for replication and additional validation provides an alternative to traditional typological methods. What is yet to be determined, is whether these types can usefully be applied in a regional analysis.

3.6 Geographic Clustering

If, as argued earlier, cultural factors play a significant role in the variation of projectile point morphology, then it is unreasonable to expect a random distribution of projectile point types across such a large region. While some degree of randomness is expected—especially given the extensive population movements discussed previously—a complete lack of spatial patterning would undermine the assumption that point forms are culturally meaningful. In that case, the validity of using projectile point morphology to infer cultural or regional patterns would be questionable. Figure 3.17 shows the distribution of the side-notched

Figure 3.16: Projectile point shapes for newly devised projectile point types (only showing top 9 most common types side-notched and triangular projectile points). Points are aligned using generalized procrustes methods to account for variation in rotation and size. For side-notched types: shape-1_straight_side-notched_low (a), shape-2_concave_side-notched_low (b), shape-2_concave_side-notched_mid (c), shape-2_straight_side-notched_low (d), shape-2_straight_side-notched_mid (e), shape-3_concave_side-notched_low (f), shape-3_concave_side-notched_mid (g), shape-3_straight_side-notched_low (h), shape-3_straight_side-notched_mid (i). For triangular types: shape-1_concave_triangular (a), shape-1_concave_triangular_serrated (b), shape-1_deeply_concave_triangular (c), shape-1_straight_triangular (d), shape-1_straight_triangular_serrated (e), shape-2_concave_triangular (f), shape-2_straight_triangular (g), shape-3_concave_triangular (h), shape-3_straight_triangular (i).

projectile point types and Figure 3.18 shows the triangular types. These maps use the KDE hexagon bins previously described.

Essentially these figures show the general distribution of the projectile point types by showing the frequency of each projectile point type relative to the total number of points in each cell. The KDE function smooths the values to provide a clearer representation of density variations across the study area, reducing the impact of local anomalies and highlighting broader spatial trends. Pronounced geographic patterning is evident, with distinct clusters of specific projectile point types emerging across the study region. These spatial trends reflect underlying social, technological, and environmental factors that influenced the production, use, and exchange of projectile points. The strongest gravitational centers are in the Sinagua and Mogollon regions. Curiously, the Zuni regions have an even mix of projectile point types with no strong tendency towards any particular style.

Figure 3.19 shows a map of the project area with sites assigned to communities based on the network clustering method described earlier. Sites are grouped into communities according to similarities in projectile point assemblages, using the newly defined attribute types. Weak connections—those below the 0.75 similarity quantile—were excluded, and isolated sites with no ties are not shown.

Communities 3 and 4 are small, with five and four sites respectively. Most of these sites are relatively close in proximity, with the exception of the Community 3 site in the Roosevelt region shown in the Figure 3.19 inset. Most sites fall into communities 1, or 2, which show a general east-to-west distribution, although with significant mixing. Hohokam sites appear to predominantly fall into Community 1, but many other sites share projectile point styles and fall in this community. Community 2 is concentrated in the northern portions of the region, but with a major presence in the Roosevelt region as well. Notably, the Roosevelt inset in Figure 3.19 highlights sites from different communities. While several sites belong to

Figure 3.17: Distribution of side-notched projectile point types visualized using hexagon binning and kernel density analysis.

Figure 3.18: Distribution of triangular projectile point types visualized using hexagon binning and kernel density analysis.

community 1, several other outlying communities belong to Community 2 and one belongs to Community 3. The diversity in the Roosevelt area points to complex interaction patterns that are explored further elsewhere [Bischoff (2023b); Chapter 4 of this dissertation]—see also the work by Watts (2013).

These two methods of examining the spatial distribution of the projectile point types demonstrate spatial patterning throughout the project area and successfully demonstrate that the adopted attribute-based projectile point types used in this analysis produce meaningful results in a regional study. Further analysis, particularly in combination with other types of material culture would improve our understanding of these patterns, however, these results are enough to demonstrate the utility of the methods described in this chapter.

3.7 Discussion

The analysis confirms that while GMM methods, especially elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA), are valuable for capturing overall shape, they struggle with specific morphological features like side notches and basal indentations (Bischoff 2023a; Bischoff and Allison 2020; Okumura and Araujo 2016). Landmark-based methods improve this (F L Bookstein 1997; Shott and Trail 2010), but are time-consuming and still fall short in distinguishing features like basal notches versus deeply concave bases—a limitation noted in prior morphometric studies (Charlin and González-José 2012; Petřík et al. 2018).

Importantly, this analysis found that continuous variation is the norm in projectile point morphology (Archer et al. 2015; D. G. Anderson et al. 2010; Barton 1988; Bretzke and Conard 2012; Lycett and Cramon-Taubadel 2015), which complicates efforts to fit points into rigid typological categories. Despite these challenges, GMM has been shown to be highly effective in identifying broad regional shape patterns (Buchanan and Collard 2010;

Figure 3.19: Map of projectile point communities detected through network clustering. Inset area shown as small red rectangle depicts the eastern Tonto Basin where several known immigrant communities have been identified.

Charlin and González-José 2012; Okumura and Araujo 2016; Petřík et al. 2018; Selden 2022), and this study contributes additional support for its use in regional analysis.

Furthermore, emerging approaches that integrate machine learning with GMM have shown promise in improving classification efficiency and accuracy (Bonhomme, Bouby, et al. 2023; MacLeod 2018). Several studies have successfully combined the two methods to automate the classification of lithic forms at scale (Courtenay et al. 2019; Maté-González et al. 2023). In this study, machine learning models also provided critical validation checks, catching inconsistencies in initial attribute assignments and supporting a scalable, replicable workflow.

The spatial patterns identified in this analysis reinforce previous findings that projectile point types correspond with cultural and linguistic boundaries (Ryan 2017; Sliva 2006; Whittaker and Bryce 2017) and migration-related artifact distributions (Jeffery J Clark 2001; Elson 1996; Spielmann et al. 1998; J. S. Wood 2000; Bischoff 2023b). As demonstrated in Chapter 4 of this dissertation, projectile point networks correspond with material culture clusters, especially in areas like the Roosevelt region, where immigrant communities have previously been documented.

3.8 Conclusion

This analysis of over 3,000 projectile points from 81 sites across various culture areas—Ancestral Pueblo, Hohokam, Mogollon, and Sinagua—demonstrates that regional-scale projectile point analyses can be efficiently conducted using geometric morphometric (GMM) and machine learning techniques. The findings show that an attribute-based approach to categorization is more effective than relying solely on overall shape, particularly when dealing with morphologically complex forms like side-notched points. The results

also confirm that 2D image data alone can be sufficient for exploring regional variation in projectile point distributions, making this method highly accessible and cost-effective.

A key contribution of this study is the development and testing of a classification system based on discrete morphological attributes such as base shape, notch height, and serration. While these attributes were drawn from Southwest typologies, they are not regionally specific and have broad applicability to other regions where similar projectile point forms are found. Because the attributes are based on generalizable aspects of shape and form rather than on specific type names, they can be adapted to different contexts, enhancing the utility and flexibility of the method.

Moreover, the integration of GMM and machine learning not only improved reproducibility and efficiency but also helped minimize the subjective biases often involved in manual classification. This approach has significant potential as the foundation for a reusable and extensible classification tool. Once a sufficiently large and diverse training dataset is assembled, a pretrained machine learning model could be used to assign projectile point types rapidly and consistently across different archaeological collections. Such a tool would greatly improve standardization across projects and reduce the time and labor involved in typological analysis.

While continuous variation in lithic technology remains a challenge for any classification system, the methods used here produce results that align with known archaeological patterns and interaction zones. The analysis shows that a hybrid approach—combining manually assigned and machine-validated attributes—is a promising way forward for typology in the digital age. Although GMM remains valuable, many of its functions can be replicated or streamlined using machine learning methods, especially with appropriate visual inputs and well-structured attribute sets.

The main limitation in applying this approach more broadly is the availability of large,

labeled training datasets. Additionally, while the attributes used in this study are generalizable, care should be taken in other regions to validate and adapt attribute definitions based on local variation and cultural context. Nonetheless, this study provides a foundation for scalable, transferable, and transparent projectile point classification that can contribute meaningfully to regional and comparative archaeological research. A generalized machine learning framework—like that proposed by Castillo-Flores and colleagues (Castillo Flores et al. 2019)—represents a logical next step in expanding this approach.

Data Availability

Supplementary material including R and Python code and data used in the analysis can be found in an OSF (Open Science Foundation) repository here <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/CP76J>, as well as in Appendix B of this dissertation. Additional data can be found here: https://heuristic.huma-num.fr/heuristic/?db=rbisc_dissertation&website&id=7920.

Note: This paper is intended for submission to the *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*

References

- Adams, Dean C, F James Rohlf, and Dennis E Slice (2013). “A Field Comes of Age: Geometric Morphometrics in the 21st Century”. en. In: *Hystrix, the Italian Journal of Mammalogy* 24 (1), pp. 7–14. ISSN: 0394-1914,1825-5272. DOI: 10.4404/hystrix-24.1-6283. URL: <http://www.italian-journal-of-mammalogy.it/A-field-comes-of-age-geometric-morphometrics-in-the-21st-century,77238,0,2.html>.
- Adams, E C (1994). “The Katsina Cult: A Western Pueblo Perspective”. In: *Kachinas in the Pueblo World*. Ed. by Polly Schaafsma. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, pp. 35–46.

- Adams, E Charles, Miriam T Stark, and Deborah S Dosh (Jan. 1, 1993). “Ceramic Distribution and Exchange: Jeddito Yellow Ware and Implications for Social Complexity”. In: *Journal of Field Archaeology* 20 (1), pp. 3–21. ISSN: 0093-4690. DOI: 10.1179/009346993791974325. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346993791974325>.
- Anderson, David G et al. (2010). “PIDBA (Paleoindian Database of the Americas) 2010: Current Status and Findings”. en. In: *Archaeology of Eastern North America* 38, pp. 63–90.
- Archer, W et al. (2015). “Diachronic change within the Still Bay at Blombos Cave, South Africa”. In: *PloS one* 10 (7). ISSN: 1932-6203. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0132428. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940055265&doi=10.1371%2fjournal.pone.0132428&partnerID=40&md5=dabc86459d030dfbe5f1fa4a7e589146>.
- Azevedo, Soledad de, Judith Charlin, and Rolando González-José (2014). “Identifying design and reduction effects on lithic projectile point shapes”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 41, pp. 297–307. ISSN: 0305-4403,1095-9238. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.08.013. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2013.08.013>.
- Bamforth, Douglas B (1991). “Flintknapping Skill, Communal Hunting and Paleoindian Projectile Point Typology”. en. In: *Plains Anthropologist* 36, pp. 309–322. ISSN: 0032-0447.
- Barton, C Michael (1988). *Lithic Variability and Middle Paleolithic Behavior: new evidence from the Iberian Peninsula*. Oxford: BAR.
- Bayman, James (2007). “Artisans and their Crafts in Hohokam Society”. In: *The Hohokam Millenium*. Ed. by Suzanne K Fish and Paul R Fish. Santa Fe, N.M.: School for Advanced Research Press, pp. 74–81. ISBN: 9781930618800.
- Beaglehole, Ernest (1936). *Hopi Hunting and Hopi Ritual*. en. Yale University Publication in Anthropology No. 4. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Bernardini, Wesley (2005). *Hopi Oral Tradition and the Archaeology of Identity*. English. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816524266.
- Bernardini, Wesley et al. (2021). “Reconstructing Population in the Context of Migration”. en. In: *Becoming Hopi: A History*. Ed. by Wesley Bernardini et al. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Bickler, Simon H (May 2021). “Machine learning arrives in archaeology”. en. In: *Advances in archaeological practice* 9 (2), pp. 186–191. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.1017/aap.2021.

6. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/418D14FD3BAA55A550D61D710A9A8CE0/S2326376821000061a.pdf/div-class-title-machine-learning-arrives-in-archaeology-div.pdf> (visited on 09/27/2024).

Bischoff, Robert J (2018). *A Temporal and Spatial Analysis of San Juan Red Ware*. Master's thesis, Department of Anthropology, Brigham Young University, Provo, Utah. URL: <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/etd/7003/>.

— (2023a). “Geometric Morphometric Analysis of Projectile Points from the Southwest United States”. In: *Peer Community Journal* 3 (e80). DOI: 10.24072/pcjournal.312. URL: <https://peercommunityjournal.org/articles/10.24072/pcjournal.312/>.

— (Aug. 16, 2023b). “Investigating Material Culture Through Multilayer Network Analysis in Tonto Basin”. In: *KIVA* 89 (3), pp. 247–273. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137>.

Bischoff, Robert J and James R Allison (2020). “Rosegate Projectile Points in the Fremont Region”. In: *Utah Archaeology* 33 (1), pp. 7–48. DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/dwrba. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/dwrba>.

Blondel, Vincent D et al. (Oct. 9, 2008). “Fast Unfolding of Communities in Large Networks”. In: *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment* 2008 (10), P10008. ISSN: 1742-5468. DOI: 10.1088/1742-5468/2008/10/P10008.

Bonhomme, Vincent, Laurent Bouby, et al. (Sept. 15, 2023). “Deep learning versus geometric morphometrics for archaeobotanical domestication study and subspecific identification”. In: *bioRxiv*. DOI: 10.1101/2023.09.15.557939. URL: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.09.15.557939.abstract>.

Bonhomme, Vincent, Sandrine Picq, et al. (2014). “Momocs: Outline Analysis Using R”. In: *Journal of Statistical Software, Articles* 56 (13), pp. 1–24. ISSN: 1548-7660. DOI: 10.18637/jss.v056.i13. URL: <https://www.jstatsoft.org/v056/i13>.

Bookstein, F L (1997). “Landmark Methods for Forms without Landmarks: Morphometrics of Group Differences in Outline Shape”. en. In: *Medical Image Analysis* 1 (3), pp. 225–243. ISSN: 1361-8415. DOI: 10.1016/s1361-8415(97)85012-8. URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1361-8415\(97\)85012-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1361-8415(97)85012-8).

Bookstein, Fred L (1991). *Morphometric Tools for Landmark Data: Geometry and Biology*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

- Bretzke, Knut and Nicholas J Conard (Dec. 2012). “Evaluating morphological variability in lithic assemblages using 3D models of stone artifacts”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 39 (12), pp. 3741–3749. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2012.06.039. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440312003068>.
- Buchanan, Briggs and Mark Collard (Feb. 1, 2010). “A Geometric Morphometrics-Based Assessment of Blade Shape Differences among Paleoindian Projectile Point Types from Western North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 37 (2), pp. 350–359. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2009.09.047. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440309003537>.
- Buchanan, Briggs, Metin I Eren, and Michael J O’Brien (2018). “Assessing the Likelihood of Convergence among North American Projectile-Point Types”. In: *Convergent Evolution in Stone-Tool Technology*. Ed. by Michael J O’Brien, Briggs Buchanan, and Metin I Eren. The MIT Press, pp. 275–287. ISBN: 9780262346160. DOI: 10.7551/mitpress/11554.001.0001. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11554.001.0001>.
- Calder, Jeff et al. (2022). “Use and misuse of machine learning in anthropology”. en. In: *IEEE BITS the Information Theory Magazine* 2 (1), pp. 1–13. ISSN: 2692-4110,2692-4080. DOI: 10.1109/mbits.2022.3205143. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9888777> (visited on 09/25/2024).
- Cameron, Catherine M (2001). “Pink Chert, Projectile Points, and the Chacoan Regional System”. In: *American Antiquity* 66 (1), pp. 79–102. ISSN: 0002-7316.
- Cameron, Catherine M and Andrew I Duff (Jan. 2008). “History and Process in Village Formation: Context and Contrasts from the Northern Southwest”. en. In: *American antiquity* 73 (1), pp. 29–58. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.1017/S0002731600041275. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/history-and-process-in-village-formation-context-and-contrasts-from-the-northern-southwest/07B0297E01B27320A8C786BC98A8BC1E>.
- Castillo Flores, Fernando et al. (June 13, 2019). “Computer Algorithm for Archaeological Projectile Points Automatic Classification”. en. In: *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)* 12 (3), p. 19. ISSN: 1556-4673. DOI: 10.1145/3300972. URL: <https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?doid=3340676.3300972> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Charlin, Judith and Rolando González-José (Apr. 2012). “Size and Shape Variation in Late Holocene Projectile Points of Southern Patagonia: A Geometric Morphometric Study”. In: *American Antiquity* 77 (2), pp. 221–242. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.7183/0002-7316.77.2.221. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/size-and-shape-variation-in-late-holocene->

projectile - points - of - southern - patagonia - a - geometric - morphometric - study / A7922E0F1588F8F9800C8097E7CAC4F9.

Clark, Geoffrey A and Julien Riel-Salvatore (2006). “Observations on Systematics in Paleolithic Archaeology”. In: *Transitions Before the Transition*. Ed. by Erella Hovers and Steven Kuh. Boston, MA: Springer US, pp. 29–56. ISBN: 9780387246581. DOI: 10.1007/0-387-24661-4_3. URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/0-387-24661-4_3.

Clark, Jeffery J (2001). *Tracking Prehistoric Migrations: Pueblo Settlers Among the Tonto Basin Hohokam*. en. Vol. 65. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. 124 pp. ISBN: 9780816520879. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=27Tk3xNT-6UC>.

Clark, Jeffery J, Jennifer A Birch, et al. (Mar. 1, 2019). “Resolving the Migrant Paradox: Two Pathways to Coalescence in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 53, pp. 262–287. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2018.09.004. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416518300801>.

Clark, Jeffery J, Deborah L Huntley, et al. (2013). “The Kayenta Diaspora and Salado Meta-Identity in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Hybrid Material Culture: The Archaeology of Syncretism and Ethnogenesis*. Ed. by Jeb Card. Center for Archaeological Investigations Occasional Paper No. 39. Carbondale: SIU Press, pp. 399–424. DOI: 10.1007/9780809333165. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/9780809333165>.

Clark, Jeffery J and Patrick D Lyons, eds. (2012). *Migrants and mounds: classic period archaeology of the Lower San Pedro Valley*. Tucson: Archaeology Southwest.

Corti, M (1993). “Geometric Morphometrics: An Extension of the Revolution”. en. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 8 (8), pp. 302–303. ISSN: 0169-5347. DOI: 10.1016/0169-5347(93)90261-M. URL: [https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0169-5347\(93\)90261-M](https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0169-5347(93)90261-M).

Courtenay, Lloyd A et al. (Dec. 23, 2019). “A hybrid Geometric Morphometric deep learning approach for cut and trampling Mark classification”. In: *Applied sciences (Basel, Switzerland)*. ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app10010150. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/1/150>.

Crown, Patricia L (1994). *Ceramics and Ideology: Salado Polychrome Pottery*. English. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press. ISBN: 9780826314772.

- Cushing, Frank Hamilton (1883). “Zuni Fetishes”. In: *Second Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1880–1881*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, DC: US Government Printing Office, pp. 9–50.
- Dean, Jeffrey S (2010). “The Environmental, Demographic, and Behavioral Context of the Thirteenth-Century Depopulation of the Northern Southwest”. In: *Leaving Mesa Verde: Peril and Change in the Thirteenth-Century Southwest*, pp. 324–345.
- Dittert, Alfred E (1959). “Culture Change in the Cebolleta Mesa Region Central Western New Mexico”. PhD thesis. Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson, Arizona.
- Drennan, Robert D (Mar. 1984). “Long-distance transport costs in pre-Hispanic Mesoamerica”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 86 (1), pp. 105–112. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100>.
- Duff, Andrew I (2000). “Scale, Interaction, and Regional Analysis in Late Pueblo Prehistory”. English. In: *The Archaeology of Regional Interaction: Religion, Warfare, and Exchange across the American Southwest and Beyond*. Ed. by Michelle Hegmon. University Press of Colorado, pp. 71–98. ISBN: 9780870819049.
- (2002). *Western Pueblo Identities; Region Interaction, Migration, and Transformation*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- (2004). “Settlement Clustering and Village Interaction in the Upper Little Colorado Region”. In: *The Protohistoric Pueblo World, AD 1275*. Ed. by E Charles Adams and Andrew I Duff. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, pp. 75–84.
- Elliot, Tom et al. (May 13, 2021). “Evaluating machine learning techniques for archaeological lithic sourcing: a case study of flint in Britain”. en. In: *Scientific reports* 11 (1), p. 10197. ISSN: 2045-2322. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-87834-3. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-87834-3>.
- Ellis, Christopher J (1997). “Factors Influencing the Use of Stone Projectile Tips: An Ethnographic Perspective”. In: *Projectile Technology*. Ed. by Heidi Knecht. New York: Plenum Press, pp. 37–74.
- Elson, Mark D (Jan. 1996). “A revised chronology and phase sequence for the lower Tonto Basin of central Arizona”. In: *The KIVA* 62 (2), pp. 117–147. ISSN: 0023-1940,2051-6177. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328. URL: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328>.

- Fewkes, Jesse Walter (1898). *Archaeological Expedition to Arizona in 1895*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution.
- Gardner, W M and R A Verrey (1979). “Typology and Chronology of Fluted Points from the Flint Run Area”. en. In: *Pennsylvania Archaeologist* 49, pp. 13–45. ISSN: 0031-4358.
- Gauthier, Nicolas (Jan. 29, 2021). “Hydroclimate Variability Influenced Social Interaction in the Prehistoric American Southwest”. In: *Frontiers in Earth Science* 8. ISSN: 2296-6463. DOI: 10.3389/feart.2020.62085610.3389/feart.2020.620856.s00110.3389/feart.2020.620856.s002. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feart.2020.620856/full>.
- Gower, J C (Mar. 1, 1975). “Generalized Procrustes Analysis”. In: *Psychometrika* 40 (1), pp. 33–51. ISSN: 0033-3123,1860-0980. DOI: 10.1007/BF02291478. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02291478>.
- Hamilton, Marcus J, Briggs Buchanan, and Robert S Walker (Apr. 1, 2019). “Spatiotemporal Diversification of Projectile Point Types in Western North America over 13,000 Years”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 24, pp. 486–495. ISSN: 2352-409X. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2019.01.029. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352409X18305650>.
- He, Kaiming et al. (June 2016). “Deep residual learning for image recognition”. en. In: *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) (Las Vegas, NV, USA). IEEE, pp. 770–778. ISBN: 9781467388511. DOI: 10.1109/cvpr.2016.90. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7780459> (visited on 09/30/2024).
- Hill, J Brett, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (2004). “Prehistoric Demography in the Southwest: Migration, Coalescence, and Hohokam Population Decline”. In: *American Antiquity* 69 (4), pp. 689–716. ISSN: 0002-7316. DOI: 10.2307/4128444. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4128444>.
- Hill, J Brett, Matthew A Peeples, et al. (Feb. 2015). “Spatializing Social Network Analysis in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 3 (1), pp. 63–77. DOI: 10.7183/2326-3768.3.1.63. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7183/2326-3768.3.1.63>.
- Hoffman, Charles Marshall (1985). “Projectile Point Maintenance and Typology: Assessment with Factor Analysis and Canonical Correlation”. In: *For Concordance in Archaeological Analysis: Bridging Data Structure, Quantitative Technique and Theory*. Ed. by Christopher Carr. Prospect Heights, Illinois: Waveland Press, pp. 566–612.

- Hoffman, Charles Marshall (1997). “Alliance Formation and Social Interaction During the Sedentary Period: a Stylistic Analysis of Hohokam Arrowpoints”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, Tempe.
- Hotelling, Harold (Aug. 1931). “The generalization of student’s ratio”. In: *The annals of mathematical statistics* 2 (3), pp. 360–378. ISSN: 0003-4851,2168-8990. DOI: 10.1214/aoms/1177732979. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177732979>.
- Hruschka, Daniel J et al. (Jan. 30, 2022). “CatMapper: A user-friendly tool for integrating data across complex categories”. In: *SocArXiv Papers* 1. URL: <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/n6rty/>.
- Johnson, Ian (2011). “Heurist: a Web 2.0 Approach to Integrating Research, Teaching and Web Publishing”. In: *On the Road to Reconstructing the Past. Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. Proceedings of the 36th International Conference. Budapest, April 2-6, 2008*. Ed. by E Jerem, F Redő, and V Szeverényi. Budapest: Archeaeolingua, pp. 93–99. URL: https://tobias-lib.uni-tuebingen.de/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10900/60640/CD38_Johnson_CAA2008.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y.
- Justice, Noel D (Sept. 1, 1995). *Stone age spear and arrow points of the midcontinental and eastern United States*. Bloomington, MN: Indiana University Press. 304 pp. ISBN: 9780253209856.
- (2002a). *Stone Age Spear and Arrow Points of California and the Great Basin*. en. Kindle Edition. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- (2002b). *Stone Age Spear and Arrow Points of the Southwestern United States*. en. Bloomington, Indiana: Indiana University Press. 456 pp. ISBN: 9780253108821. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=xIFpi41dH_MC.
- Justice, Noel D and Suzanne Kudlaty (Apr. 22, 2001). *Field guide to projectile points of the Midwest*. Bloomington, MN: Indiana University Press. 72 pp. ISBN: 9780253339317.
- Kaldahl, Eric J (2000). “Late Prehistoric Technological and Social Reorganization Along the Mogollon Rim, Arizona”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson.
- Kamp, Kathryn A, John C Whittaker, and William D Bryce (Oct. 1, 2016). “The Magician of Ridge Ruin: Insights into Ceremony and Status from Arrow Points and Bows”. In: *Lithic Technology* 41 (4), pp. 313–334. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2016.1252620. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2016.1252620>.

- Kintigh, Keith W, Donna M Glowacki, and Deborah L Huntley (July 2004). “Long-Term Settlement History and the Emergence of Towns in the Zuni Area”. In: *American antiquity* 69 (3), pp. 432–456. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/4128401. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/longterm-settlement-history-and-the-emergence-of-towns-in-the-zuni-area/140EE169ED8BB7A0AE507BD9E974CD59> (visited on 09/12/2023).
- Konopka, Tomasz (2020). *umap: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=umap>.
- Kuhl, Frank P and Charles R Giardina (1982). “Elliptic Fourier Features of a Closed Contour”. In: *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 18, pp. 236–258.
- Larick, R (1985). “Spears, Style, and Time among Maa-speaking Pastoralists”. en. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 4, pp. 206–220.
- Loendorf, Chris (2010). “Hohokam Core Area Sociocultural Dynamics: Cooperation and Conflict along the Middle Gila River in Southern Arizona during the Classic and Historic Periods”. PhD thesis. Tempe: Arizona State University.
- Loendorf, Chris and Glen E Rice (2004). *Projectile Point Typology Gila River Indian Community, Arizona*. Anthropological Research Papers No. 2. Sacaton, Arizona: Gila River Indian Community Cultural Resource Management Program.
- Loendorf, Chris, Thatcher A Rogers, et al. (Apr. 2019). “Projectile Point Reworking: An Experimental Study of Arrowpoint Use Life”. cs. In: *American Antiquity* 84, pp. 353–365. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.1017/aaq.2018.87. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/projectile-point-reworking-an-experimental-study-of-arrowpoint-use-life/17DB4E93940AA42F4D3103AD78D76F46>.
- Loendorf, Chris, Lynn Simon, et al. (Aug. 2015). “Warfare and Big Game Hunting: Flaked-Stone Projectile Points Along the Middle Gila River in Arizona”. en. In: *Antiquity* 89, pp. 940–953. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.15184/aqy.2015.28. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/warfare-and-big-game-hunting-flakedstone-projectile-points-along-the-middle-gila-river-in-arizona/F8FAF746DA28A11D0A051E3BDC6BB023> (visited on 12/27/2018).
- Lowe, R M (2024). “The Nature of Projectile Point Types From the Denton Site, Mississippi”. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.

- Lycett, Stephen J and Noreen von Cramon-Taubadel (June 1, 2015). “Toward a “Quantitative Genetic” Approach to Lithic Variation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (2), pp. 646–675. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-013-9200-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-013-9200-9>.
- MacLeod, Norman (Dec. 1, 2018). “The Quantitative Assessment of Archaeological Artifact Groups: Beyond Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Quaternary Science Reviews* 201, pp. 319–348. ISSN: 0277-3791. DOI: 10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.08.024. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277379118302907>.
- Mason, Otis T (1894). *North American Bows, Arrows, and Quivers*. en. Washington DC: Government Printing Office. 216 pp. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Fk9BAQAAMAAJ>.
- Maté-González, Miguel Ángel et al. (Mar. 21, 2023). “Geometric morphometrics and machine learning models applied to the study of late Iron Age cut marks from central Spain”. en. In: *Applied sciences (Basel, Switzerland)* 13 (6), p. 3967. ISSN: 2076-3417,2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app13063967. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/13/6/3967>.
- McInnes, Leland, John Healy, and James Melville (2020). *UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction*. DOI: arXiv:1802.03426. arXiv: 1802.03426 [stat.ML]. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426>.
- Mills, Barbara et al. (2020). *CyberSW Version 1.0*. en. Tucson. URL: <https://cybersw.org/>.
- Mills, Barbara J (Apr. 2007). “Performing the Feast: Visual Display and Suprahousehold Commensalism in the Puebloan Southwest”. en. In: *American antiquity* 72 (2), pp. 210–239. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/40035812. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/performing-the-feast-visual-display-and-suprahousehold-commensalism-in-the-puebloan-southwest/014093DF6B246C2C326A3F6ABA3F956E>.
- Mills, Barbara J, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (Apr. 9, 2013). “Transformation of social networks in the late pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110 (15), pp. 5785–5790. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1219966110. URL: <http://www.pnas.org/content/110/15/5785>.
- Mills, Barbara J, Matthew A Peeples, et al. (Jan. 2015). “Multiscalar Perspectives on Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic Southwest”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 80 (1), pp. 3–24. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.7183/0002-7316.79.4.3.

URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/multiscalar-perspectives-on-social-networks-in-the-late-prehispanic-southwest/B40CF133F9E61102185B25AD4DF0FE30>.

Mitteroecker, P and P Gunz (2009). “Advances in Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Evolutionary Biology* 36, pp. 235–247. ISSN: 0071-3260. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11692-009-9055-x>.

Mitteroecker, Philipp and Katrin Schaefer (Aug. 2022). “Thirty years of geometric morphometrics: Achievements, challenges, and the ongoing quest for biological meaningfulness”. en. In: *American journal of biological anthropology* 178 Suppl 74 (S74), pp. 181–210. ISSN: 2692-7691. DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.24531. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9545184/> (visited on 09/09/2024).

Nash, Brendan S and Elton R Prewitt (July 2, 2016). “The Use of Artificial Neural Networks in Projectile Point Typology”. In: *Lithic Technology* 41 (3), pp. 194–211. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2016.1184876. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2016.1184876>.

Okumura, Mercedes and Astolfo G M Araujo (Mar. 15, 2016). “The Southern Divide: Testing Morphological Differences among Bifacial Points from Southern and Southeastern Brazil using Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Journal of Lithic Studies* 3 (1). ISSN: 2055-0472. DOI: 10.2218/jls.v3i1.1379. URL: <http://journals.ed.ac.uk/lithicstudies/article/view/1379>.

— (Jan. 1, 2019). “Archaeology, biology, and borrowing: A critical examination of Geometric Morphometrics in Archaeology”. en. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 101, pp. 149–158. ISSN: 0305-4403,1095-9238. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2017.09.015. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046166965&origin=resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sid=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&sot=a&sdt=cl&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22geometric+morphometrics%22%29+AND+TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22archaeology%22+OR+%22human+evolution%22+OR+%22artifact%22+OR+%22prehistoric%22+OR+%22faunal+remains%22%29&sl=145&sessionSearchId=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&relpos=153>.

Padilla-Iglesias, Cecilia, Javier Blanco-Portillo, et al. (May 27, 2024). “Deep history of cultural and linguistic evolution among Central African hunter-gatherers”. en. In: *Nature human behaviour*. ISSN: 2397-3374. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-024-01891-y. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-01891-y>.

Paige, Jonathan (2022). “The Evolution of Stone Tool Traditions”. Tempe: Arizona State University. URL: https://d1rbsgppyrdq4.cloudfront.net/s3fs-public/c7/paige_

asu_0010E_22345.pdf?versionId=v4bd0rkMBjdqIcV2VTal2iJGR78g0YWr & X-Amz-Content-Sha256=UNSIGNED-PAYLOAD & X-Amz-Algorithm=AWS4-HMAC-SHA256 & X-Amz-Credential=AKIASBVQ3ZQ4YNQVYJLW/20241002/us-west-2/s3/aws4_request & X-Amz-Date=20241002T042151Z & X-Amz-SignedHeaders=host & X-Amz-Expires=120 & X-Amz-Signature=26783e4f5287ac36c7b9e023f00b8863824be7b10ab1504f9381e950f57d6ca9.

Parsons, Elsie Clews (1932). “Isleta, New Mexico”. en. In: *Forty Seventh Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1929–1930*. United States Government Printing Office. Ed. by M W Stirling. Washington, D.C, pp. 193–466.

— (1939). *Pueblo Indian Religion*. English. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Peoples, Matthew et al. (2021). “Connections and Boundaries”. en. In: *Becoming Hopi: A history*. Ed. by Wesley Bernardini et al. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.

Peoples, Matthew A (2018). *Connected Communities: Networks, Identity, and Social Change in the Ancient Cibola World*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816535682. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-fyw-DwAAQBAJ>.

Peoples, Matthew A and W Randall Haas (June 2013). “Brokerage and Social Capital in the Prehispanic U.S. Southwest”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 115 (2), pp. 232–247. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1111/aman.12006. URL: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/aman.12006/abstract>.

Peoples, Matthew A and John M Roberts (July 2013). “To Binarize or not to Binarize: Relational Data and the Construction of Archaeological Networks”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 40 (7), pp. 3001–3010. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.03.014. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440313001040>.

Petřík, J et al. (2018). “Shape Matters: Assessing Regional Variation of Bell Beaker Projectile Points in Central Europe Using Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* 10 (4), pp. 896–904. DOI: 10.1007/s12520-016-0423-z. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12520-016-0423-z>.

Python Software Foundation (2024). *Python 3.8.20 Documentation*. URL: <https://docs.python.org/3.8/index.html> (visited on 09/24/2024).

Rice, Glen E (1994). “Projectile Points, Bifaces, and Drills”. In: *Archaeology of the Salado in the Livingston Area of Tonto Basin, Roosevelt Platform Mound Study: Report on the Livingston Management Group, Pinto Creek Complex. Part 2*. Ed. by Glen E Rice.

Roosevelt Monograph Series 3. Tempe: Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, pp. 727–738. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N>.

Rice, Glen E, ed. (1998). *A synthesis of Tonto Basin prehistory: The Roosevelt archaeology studies, 1989 to 1998*. Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University. DOI: 10.6067/XCV81V5GRZ. URL: <https://core.tdar.org/document/394298/a-synthesis-of-tonto-basin-prehistory-the-roosevelt-archaeology-studies-1989-to-1998>.

Rohlf, F James (Jan. 1, 2015). “The Tps series of software”. In: *Hystrix* 26 (1), pp. 1–4. ISSN: 1825-5272. DOI: 10.4404/hystrix-26.1-11264. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281698770_The_Tps_series_of_software (visited on 04/08/2022).

Rohlf, F James and Leslie F Marcus (1993). “A Revolution in Morphometrics”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 8, pp. 129–129. ISSN: 0169-5347.

Russell, Frank (1908). “The Pima Indians”. en. In: *Twenty-Sixth Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1915–1916*. Ed. by W H Holmes. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 3–390.

Ryan, Stacy L (2017). “Classic Period Projectile Point Design Variation in the Tucson Basin and San Pedro Valley, Arizona”. MA thesis. MA thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson.

Schachner, Gregson (Apr. 2012). *Population Circulation and the Transformation of Ancient Zuni Communities*. English. First edition. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816529865.

Sedig, Jakob W (June 1, 2014). “An Analysis of Non-Utilitarian Stone Point Function in the US Southwest”. en. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 34, pp. 120–132. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2014.03.003. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S027841651400018X>.

Selden Jr, Robert Z (July 5, 2022). “Morphologically similar, but regionally distinct: Perdiz arrow points from Caddo burial contexts in the American southeast”. en. In: *Lithic technology* 48 (1), pp. 1–12. ISSN: 0197-7261,2051-6185. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2022.2095492. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133410828&origin=resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sid=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&sot=a&sdt=cl&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%20%22geometric+morphometrics%20%29+AND+TITLE-ABS-KEY%20%22archaeology%22+OR+%22human+evolution%22>

OR+%22artifact%22+OR+%22prehistoric%22+OR+%22faunal+remains%22%29&sl=145&sessionSearchId=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&relpos=49.

Shott, Michael J and Brian W Trail (Sept. 1, 2010). “Exploring New Approaches to Lithic Analysis: Laser Scanning and Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Lithic Technology* 35 (2), pp. 195–220. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2010.11721090. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2010.11721090>.

Simpson, Ruth Deette (1953). *The Hopi Indians*. en. Vol. 1. Southwest Museum Leaflets, No. 25. Los Angeles: Southwest Museum.

Sliva, R Jane (1997). *An Introduction to the Study and Analysis of Flaked Stone Artifacts and Lithic Technology*. Tucson: Center For Desert Archaeology.

— (Jan. 1, 1999). “Cienega Points and Late Archaic Period Chronology in the Southern Southwest”. In: *The Kiva* 64 (3), pp. 339–367. ISSN: 0023-1940. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.1999.11758388. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.1999.11758388>.

— (2006). “Projectile Points in Regional Perspective”. In: *Sunset Crater Archaeology: The History of a Volcanic Landscape. Stone, Shell, Bone, and Mortuary Analyses*. Ed. by Mark D Elson. Anthropological Papers No. 31. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 31–63.

— (2017). “Evaluating Early Agricultural Period Social Dynamics in Southern Arizona Through Projectile Point Typology”. In: *Journal of Arizona Archaeology* 4 (2), pp. 99–112.

Spielmann, Katherine A et al., eds. (1998). *Environment and subsistence in the Classic period Tonto Basin, the Roosevelt archaeology studies, 1989 to 1998*. Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8FB54V1. URL: <https://core.tdar.org/document/394307/environment-and-subsistence-in-the-classic-period-tonto-basin-the-roosevelt-archaeology-studies-1989-to-1998>.

Stark, Miriam T, Mark D Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark (1998). “Social Boundaries and Technical Choices in Tonto Basin Prehistory”. en. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, D.C: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 208–231.

Stevenson, James (1884). “Illustrated Catalogue of the Collection Obtained from the Pueblos of New Mexico and Arizona in 1881”. en. In: *Third Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1880–1881*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 517–595.

- Stevenson, Matilda Coxe (1894). *The Sia*. en. Ed. by John W Powell. Washington, D.C: Government Printing Office, pp. 9–166.
- (1903). “Zuñi Games”. In: *American Anthropologist* 5 (3), pp. 468–497. ISSN: 0002-7294.
- Tagg, Martyn D (1994). “Projectile Points of East-Central Arizona: Forms and Chronology”. In: *Middle Little Colorado River Archaeology: From the Parks to the People*. Ed. by Ann Trinkle Jones and Martyn D Tagg. The Arizona Archaeologist No. 27. Phoenix: Arizona Archaeological Society, pp. 87–115.
- Team, R Core (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria. URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Thomas, David Hurst (1981). “How to Classify the Projectile Points from Monitor Valley, Nevada”. en. In: *Journal of California and Great Basin Anthropology* 3 (1), pp. 7–43. ISSN: 0191-3557. URL: <http://libproxy.unm.edu/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=ahl&AN=45856169&site=eds-live&scope=site>.
- Waguespack, Nicole M et al. (Sept. 2009). “Making a Point: Wood- Versus Stone-Tipped Projectiles”. In: *Antiquity* 83 (321), pp. 786–800. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/S0003598X00098999. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/making-a-point-wood-versus-stonetipped-projectiles/5D4C59E76AA5D00B9020ACD3CC8DED6C> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Ware, John A (2014). *A Pueblo Social History: Kinship, Sodality, and Community in the Northern Southwest*. en. Santa Fe, New Mexico: SAR Press.
- Watts, Joshua (Aug. 2013). “Traces of the Individual in Prehistory: Flintknappers and the Distribution of Projectile Points in the Eastern Tonto Basin, Arizona”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 1 (1), pp. 25–36. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.7183/2326-3768.1.1.25. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances-in-archaeological-practice/article/traces-of-the-individual-in-prehistory/7941C0F225A22D6D9707A6165FC4E5B0> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Whittaker, John C (1994). *Flintknapping: Making and Understanding Stone Tools*. en. Austin: University of Texas Press. 341 pp. ISBN: 9780292790834. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=4J79DAAAQBAJ>.
- Whittaker, John C and William D Bryce (2017). “Hunting Technologies”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Southwest Archaeology*. Ed. by Barbara Mills and Severin M Fowles. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 627–644. ISBN: 9780199978427. DOI: 10.1093/

oxfordhb/9780199978427.013.33. URL: <https://www.oxfordhandbooks.com/view/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199978427.001.0001/oxfordhb-9780199978427-e-33> (visited on 01/14/2020).

Whittaker, John C and Kathryn A Kamp (2016). “Flint from the Ancestors: Ritualized Use of Stone Tools in the Prehistoric Southwest”. In: *Archaeological Variability and Interpretation in Global Perspective*. Ed. by Alan P Sullivan III and Deborah Irene Olszewski. Boulder: University Press of Colorado, pp. 267–289. DOI: 10.5876/9781607324942.c012. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5876/9781607324942.c012>.

Wood, J Scott (2000). “Vale of Tiers Palimpsest: Salado Settlement and Internal Relationship in the Tonto Basin Area”. en. In: *Salado*. Ed. by Jeffrey S Dean. Dragoon, Arizona and Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation Publication and University of New Mexico Press, pp. 107–142.

CHAPTER 4

INVESTIGATING MATERIAL CULTURE THROUGH MULTILAYER NETWORK ANALYSIS IN TONTO BASIN

4.1 Introduction

Network science has many applications for archaeologists, and it can be particularly useful for breaking out of traditional spatial categories and examining data through new lenses (Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Holland-Lulewicz 2021). Multilayer network analysis combines multiple networks into one analytical framework (Kivela et al. 2014). Social systems are complex webs of interrelations. There is too much involved to model the material culture of even a technologically simple society, but certainly analyzing more than one type of material culture provides an improved understanding of the social dynamics involved in the networks of interaction we wish to understand. Yet, there are few examples of multilayer networks in archaeology (e.g., Giomi 2022; Upton 2019) and none I am aware of that extend beyond ceramics.

Network studies are particularly prominent in the Southwest, and there are examples of network studies that consider multiple types of material culture. To name just two: Mills and colleagues (2013) used ceramics and obsidian to understand the transformation of large-scale social networks; Peeples (2018) used ceramics and architecture to understand identity and social change in the Cibola region. This paper is an application of multilayer network analysis that seeks to further network research by examining multiple types of material culture in one framework. Given the frequent focus on single types of artifacts in network research, a primary question I seek to address is whether networks based on different types

of material culture are positively correlated. This matters because archaeologists often make inferences based solely on ceramics or other types of material culture. Evidence regarding the ways material culture co-vary will help give better context to these studies. Furthermore, I seek causal explanations for the co-variance, or lack thereof, for material culture in the case study I present here.

Tonto Basin holds great potential for archaeological research due to the large cultural resource management projects conducted in the region primarily in the 1980s-1990s (Ahlstrom, Chenault, and K. C. Anderson 1991; Ciolek-Torrello, Shelley, and Benaron 1994; Doelle, Wallace, et al. 1992; Rice 1998), as well as the large number of syntheses and other studies focusing on the area (e.g., Jeffrey J Clark and Vint 2004; Dean 2000; Elson, Gregory, and Stark 1995; Elson, Stark, and Gregory 2000; Lange and Germick 1992; Lyons 2003; Lyons and Lindsay 2006; Oliver 2001; Stark, Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark 1998; Watts 2013). This analysis uses data from the Roosevelt Platform Mounds Study (RPMS), the largest of these projects (Rice 1998), to examine basic architectural data, typed ceramics, and data from a recent projectile point analysis (Bischoff 2023a). There are two null hypotheses tested in this analysis: (1) that the data is spatially correlated—meaning that sites nearest to each other will be most alike—and (2) that the architecture, ceramics, and projectile points will all be positively correlated—meaning that similar types of architecture, ceramics, and projectile points will be found at the same sites. In reality, I expected significant variation between these types of material culture. As will be demonstrated, the results demonstrate substantial differences between the various networks. I posit that differences in the ceramic and projectile point networks (hereafter point networks) can be contributed to gender dynamics in the production and distribution of these artifacts.

4.2 Tonto Basin

Tonto Basin is in east-central Arizona and features Tonto Creek flowing from the Mogollon Rim into the Salt River (Figure 4.1). Parts of the region have been intensively studied, while certain time periods and much of the uplands have been less intensively sampled (see Jeffery J Clark and Caseldine 2021, for a recent overview). The basin was conveniently located along regional travel routes, allowing major settlements—particularly those with platform mounds—to participate and benefit from this exchange (Caseldine 2022; J. S. Wood 2000, pp. 129–133). The junction of the Salt River and Tonto Creek now forms Roosevelt Lake since the damming of the confluence of the Salt River and Tonto Creek. It was the expansion of the dam that precipitated the RPMS and its related projects in the late 1980s–1990s. Some important regional differences may have differentiated sites along the Salt River and Tonto Creek arms of Roosevelt Lake (Lyons 2013; A. W. Simon and Gosser 2001) based on non-local ceramics and obsidian. All of the artifacts/data from the RPMS project are hosted at the Center for Archaeology and Society at Arizona State University, and the data in this study come exclusively from this project.

Tonto Basin was occupied, although likely not continuously, from the Archaic through the late Classic period. The height of occupation, particularly the sites excavated during the project, dates between AD 1275 and 1325, which corresponds to the Roosevelt Phase. The Roosevelt phase is notable for the appearance of Salado pottery and platform mounds—probably introduced from the Phoenix Basin (Elson 1996). Moderate occupation continued into the Gila phase (AD 1325–1450), which was characterized by population loss and aggregation into larger sites. This phase marks the end of recognizable occupation in the area until the historic period.

Tonto Basin's position in a border zone between the Hohokam, Mogollon, and Ances-

Figure 4.1: Map of archaeology sites from the Roosevelt Platform Mounds Study in Tonto Basin. Groups use the original assignments. See Table 1 for site labels.

tral Pueblo regions has received much attention (e.g., Caseldine 2022; Jeffery J Clark 2001; Elson and Lindeman 1994; Lyons 2013; J. S. Wood 2000). Of particular note is the presence of masonry roomblock architecture and pottery uncharacteristic of the local Hohokam traditions, which has been interpreted as Kayenta immigration into Tonto Basin (Jeffery J Clark 2001; Lyons 2003; Lyons and Lindsay 2006; Stark, Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark 1998), although some have attributed the architectural changes to warfare or population aggregation (Oliver 2001; J. S. Wood 2000). This migration into the Tonto Basin was part of a larger migration from north to south and is associated with the origin of the Salado phenomenon. Salado pottery production (formally known as Roosevelt Red Ware) was widespread across southern Arizona and southwest New Mexico, but often the largest sources of production

was centered at the location of a former Kayenta enclave (Neuzil 2008). The connection between immigration and Salado pottery suggests that sites with roomblocks may have higher centrality in ceramic networks. Having high centrality means they have more connections to other nodes (i.e., sites). The presence of migrant communities in Tonto Basin invites questions regarding the relationship between sites—particularly between migrant and local communities. A network approach is an ideal way to examine the relationships between settlements. Evidence that projectile points move between communities in the Tonto Basin (e.g., Sliva 2002; Watts 2013) indicates that this is also a productive line of analysis, and one that is less-commonly pursued compared to architecture and ceramics.

4.3 Data Collection

The ceramic data was collected from the cyberSW database (B. Mills et al. 2020). The architectural data and chronological assignments were obtained from the original RPMS reports (see Rice 1998). An Access database available on tDAR (Roosevelt Platform Mound Study (RPMS) 2014) was used for correlating proveniences between projectile points and ceramics. The projectile point data were obtained from collections held at the Center for Archaeology and Society at Arizona State University.

The major limiting factors in this analysis were the presence of complete projectile points and the dating of artifacts. The sample was limited to all sites in the RPMS database with three or more complete projectile points. The majority of the occupation for the sites in this study occurred during the Roosevelt phase. Some sites lasted into the Gila Phase and some were occupied earlier. To account for chronological problems, the ceramic assemblages were apportioned following Roberts and colleagues (J. M. Roberts et al. 2012) using a uniform probability density analysis procedure described by Ortman (2016) and

implemented in R [RCore2022-a] by Peeples (2021). The R script used to calculate this is included in Appendix C. Essentially, this Bayesian procedure uses the dating of chronologically sensitive ceramic types to estimate the probability that a sherd was deposited at a particular time. The entire assemblage can then be divided into intervals based on these probabilities. Ceramic dating can be troublesome in Hohokam archaeology, but fortunately there are sufficient chronologically sensitive wares, in particular trade wares, to successfully apply this method here. I divided the assemblages into 25 year intervals and then assigned each sherd to either the Roosevelt, Gila, or “other” phases. Only the Roosevelt phase had sufficient data to proceed. Ceramic data from the other phases were dropped. I then used cross-dating to find projectile points located in contexts with sherds that were clearly from the Gila phase and removed these from the analysis. This further reduced the projectile point sample and the number of available sites. Table 4.1 lists the 10 sites with sufficient data to include in this study with the types of architecture present and total number of ceramics and complete projectile points found at each site.

4.4 Network Analysis

Network analysis is a flexible tool for analyzing many types of data (see Tom Brughmans and M. A. Peeples 2023). The key element is that some way must be determined to tie each entity together. This analysis uses sites as nodes in the network and some type of similarity as a tie to connect each node. Each type of similarity depends on the type of data. The networks in this study are not meant to represent complete reconstructions of past networks. Only a limited number of sites are included. They are not meant to be reconstructions of face-to-face interactions. These networks are a way to represent data. They describe how closely connected nodes are to each other.

4.4.1 Defining Networks

Network approaches are best suited where the relationships between entities are of primary interest. In this case, the entities are defined as archaeological sites. The archaeology sites in turn represent a group of individuals who lived or visited the area of the site and left material remains behind. Ideally, studying social relations would be approached at the individual level, but rarely can archaeologists address archaeological data with that level of specificity. Watts (2013), however, used projectile points from Tonto Basin in just such a study. His analysis of flake scar patterning identified individual knappers, or at least clusters of people with similar knapping styles, and the distribution of their projectile points around Tonto Basin. He found strong connections between many parts of the eastern Tonto Basin. Unfortunately, this study will only attempt a site-level analysis. Watt's study does, however, illustrate how relations can be defined between nodes in a network analysis. He used similarity networks where the points that had similar flaking styles were connected. Similarity networks are a commonly used type of network in archaeology (e.g., J. Birch and Hart 2018; Borck et al. 2015; Cochrane and Lipo 2010; Golitko and Feinman 2015; Lulewicz 2019; B. J. Mills, J. M. Roberts J., et al. 2013; M. A. Peeples 2018; John Edward Terrell 2010). These studies use a variety of artifacts and methods to construct their networks, but each has demonstrated the utility of network methods within archaeological contexts. This study also uses similarity networks to group sites by similarity in ceramic assemblages and similarity in projectile point forms.

4.4.2 Interpreting Networks

It can be difficult to understand how a similarity network is related to a past social network. What kinds of interactions are represented by similarities in projectile points or in ceramics? Answering this question is also a crucial step in interpreting networks. One way to examine relations between individuals who make or use similar types of projectile points or pots is to talk about identity. Identity can be a troubling topic for anthropologists. There are numerous meanings given to it and numerous scales at which it applies (Brubaker and Cooper 2000), but Peebles (2018) has introduced an approach that unites prior discussions into a simple model. This approach views identity as existing along two axes: one categorical and the other relational. Relational identification is the process of identifying with someone due to frequent interaction. Categorical identification is the process of identifying with someone because you belong to a recognized social group. For example, members of the same moiety would share a categorical identity. They would likely also share a relational identity if they frequently interacted. These identities can be reflected in material culture. Pottery makes a good example. Peebles (2018, p. 151) notes that bowls in the Cibola region were sometimes painted with a bright, red slip with designs painted on the interior and they were among the first in the Southwest to have designs on the exterior. This is a strong indication of categorical identity. The potters were attempting to make a clear signal for whoever saw the pot. Relational identity can be seen in the way the potter prepares the clay recipe and smooths the coils. The particulars of these actions would be learned from close interaction with a teacher or other potters. In this way, relational identity can be compared to communities of practice (Lave and Wenger 1991; Wenger 1998).

In this analysis, I argue that ceramics and architecture are more likely to represent categorical identity. The architecture discussed is highly visible and representative of group

membership. The ceramics are grouped into types based primarily on decoration, which is strongly indicative of group membership. What this means is that links between nodes in the ceramic network are more likely to indicate belonging to a similar social group. The details of architecture and ceramics used in this study are discussed in a future section, but it is important to note that these designations as categorical or relational are contextually dependent on this study. Clark (2001) has an excellent discussion on material culture and its relationship to identity. He identifies certain patterns, but his synthesis and other research (Carr 1995b; Carr 1995a; Dietler and Herbich 1998; Gosselain 1998; Gosselain 2000; Gosselain 2016; Hodder 1982; Huntley 2008; Lemonnier 1986; Lyons 2003; Sasseman and Rudolphi 2001; Stark, Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark 1998; Wiessner 1983; Wiessner 1997) strongly indicates that the relationship between material culture and identity is culturally relative. Projectile points can in some cases indicate group membership (Wiessner 1983; Wiessner 1997), but in this case the triangular and side-notched points were likely used for different purposes (see Chris Loendorf, L. Simon, et al. 2015; Sliva 2002). Styles were difficult to determine for the original researchers (Rice 1994), and I had the same difficulty. In my opinion, the subtle differences between projectile point outlines are more representative of interactions between knappers than markers of group identity for this particular case. This is indicative of relational identity. There are no environmental reasons to assume differences in projectile points, as each site was in a similar ecozone. Each hunter would have been using the points for the same game and differences in point styles would have been primarily cultural (Sliva 2002).

There is one other aspect to these relations that I believe played an important role. A central way people identify themselves is by gender. Gender roles also vary in complex ways, but for the purposes of this analysis I will use a simplified model. Women made pottery and men made projectile points. This was not always true of course, but this fits the available

data and expectations for the Hohokam (Crown and Fish 1996; Harry and Huntington 2010; Shackley 2005; VanPool and Savage 2010, p. 253; Whittlesey 2010). An examination of the ethnographic record for the O'odham people, recognized descendants of the Hohokam, provides additional references that women made pottery (Bahr 2011, p. 4; Castetter and Underhill 1935, pp. 5–6; Chona 1936, p. 44; Joseph, Spicer, and Chesky 1949, p. 57). An examination of the burial record for the RPMS study shows no obvious indication that women made pottery, only that both men and women were buried with pottery (Christopher Loendorf 1998, Table 10.7). On the other hand, projectile points were almost exclusively buried with males. This does not mean that a man could not move pots from one site to another or that a woman could not do the same with a projectile point, but, in general, differences in point and ceramic networks are most likely to indicate differences in gender networks.

Shackley (2005), using projectile point typology data from Hoffman (1997) as well as obsidian provenience and ceramic data for preclassic Hohokam sites in the Phoenix Basin, found evidence for three distinct projectile point traditions. Shackley and Hoffman believe these may correlate with warrior sodalities, and Shackley argues that the male projectile point exchange systems functioned in different ways than the female ceramic exchange systems. In this case, the projectile points likely correlate with a categorical identity, but this provides an example of how men and women's networks have been argued to vary in Hohokam archaeology.

From this discussion, I expect the ceramic and point networks to differ in two ways. I expect the ceramic network to represent categorical identity among women, and I expect the point network to represent relational identity among men. This makes the networks somewhat more difficult to compare. Ideally, we would have networks of the same identity

type, but it does provide the expectation that we should see significant differences in the networks.

4.4.3 Network Similarity

The network for architecture, ceramics, and projectile points, were created using the Jaccard similarity coefficient (Jaccard 1912) to determine the links between each site. This is calculated as follows:

$$J(A, B) = |A \cap B| / |A \cup B|$$

A and B are sets, $|A|$ represents the number of elements of set A , \cap represents the set of elements that are common to both A and B , and \cup represents the set of elements that are in either A or B or both. The Jaccard similarity $J(A, B)$ is the ratio of the size of the intersection of sets A and B to the size of the union of sets A and B . This is a simple measure of similarity that does not take into account abundance. It was chosen due to the large differences in sample sizes between sites for the ceramics and projectile points and because count data were irrelevant or not readily available for the architectural data.

The types of similarity used in this study are varied depending on the type of network. Part of this analysis is a visual approach and some of the methods require non-weighted links, thus I use only the strongest links. There is rarely a clear dividing line between similar and not similar. This can be a challenge for network analysis, because networks can have every node connected to each other. The decision to binarize a network—remove the weakest links and then consider each link of equal value—has its drawbacks (M. A. Peeples and J. M. Roberts 2013) but is necessary in this case. A solution is to assign weights to each link that defines the strength of the tie. These networks are often difficult to visualize, and some

Table 4.1: Project Sites and Data

id	Site	Area	Architecture	Ceramics	Projectile Points
1	AZ U:4:032 (ASM)	Cline Mesa	compound	133	3
2	AZ V:5:119 (ASM)	Livingston	compound	25	3
3	Bass Point Mound	Rock Island	platform mound	479	13
4	Cline Terrace Mound	Cline Mesa	platform mound	17333	45
5	Indian Point Complex	Cline Mesa	compound, roomblock	1024	3
6	Pinto Point Mound	Livingston	compound, platform mound	1109	21
7	Saguaro Muerto	Livingston	roomblock	373	5
8	Sand Dune Site	Livingston	compound	589	12
9	Schoolhouse Point Mesa Complex	Schoolhouse Mesa	compound	2671	12
10	Schoolhouse Point Mound	Schoolhouse Mesa	platform mound	12782	9

network algorithms do not allow for weights. A common approach is to keep only the strongest ties by either ranking the ties or using a cutoff value.

I used ranked links to keep consistent values between networks. This involved calculating the strength of similarity between each site in the network and then ranking the strength of similarity. The top n connections (n varies between 3 and 10) between each site were kept and the rest were discarded. In practice, not every node will have the same number of connections. Some may have fewer ties if there are not enough nodes that are similar. More ties can exist when there are ties in the ranks. Because the network is not directed (meaning the ties indicate similarity in both directions) one node can have several ties pointing

to it because that node was in the top n of multiple other nodes. In the latter case, this is a good indication of a central node in the network. Because I am using several types of networks, there is no common cutoff value I can use for the number of ties to keep. Instead of arbitrarily picking one value, I have calculated each metric using networks composed of the top 3-10 ties. Meaning that each metric is calculated for a network composed of ties with the top 3 connections, and the process is repeated for new networks composed of ties with the top 4 connections, and so forth. Examining the range of these metrics provides a more robust analysis.

4.4.4 Network Analysis Methods

Two network metrics are discussed in this analysis: eigenvector centrality and multilayer network correlation. Node centrality is a common way to quantify networks (Borgatti 2005). Centrality is a measure of the influence of the node on the network. Nodes with higher centrality generally derive or generate greater benefits from the network. For example, if I have many friends, then I can call in more favors. Eigenvector centrality is one way to measure node centrality and is commonly used in archaeology. This metric describes how well a node is connected to the network as a whole and is helpful in comparing different networks containing the same nodes. For example, if my friends have many friends, then I will have a greater advantage than someone with an equal number of friends, but whose friends have few friends. Essentially, this is a way of measuring second-order and beyond connections. Eigenvector centrality is also more robust to missing nodes than other measures (M. A. Peeples 2017), a major problem in most archaeological studies.

A single network is typically used in network analyses, but multilayer networks can be more informative. Multilayer networks are layered networks where nodes have differ-

ent types of connections (Kivelä et al. 2014). In this analysis, each network has the same nodes—each archaeological site—but different types of relationships between them. The combination of these individual networks is a multilayer network (also called a multiplex network). Multilayer networks allow for methods to be applied on multiple networks at once (see Bródka et al. 2018). The method applicable to this analysis is layer correlation. Either Pearson or Spearman rank correlation can be computed to determine the strength and direction of correlation between each layer. Bródka and colleagues (2018) have provided an R (Team, R Core 2024) package to compute these statistics. They recommend the Pearson correlation in most circumstances. I use the results of the Pearson correlation, but the Spearman correlation provided similar results. Eigenvector centrality was mentioned in the previous section, but it is also calculated as a multilayer eigenvector centrality. In this case the centrality measure is simply the mean of the eigenvector centrality for each separate layer, as the layers are not interdependent (Frost 2022). Multilayer eigenvector centrality results are only presented for the combination of ceramic and point layers. These networks can be thought of as dependent variables for the spatial and architectural networks—meaning spatial distance and architecture are considered important variables determining the structure of the ceramic and point networks.

The robustness of results was tested by randomly sampling the underlying network matrices 1,000 times and comparing the results to the random samples to obtain a p-value. This provides a baseline that determines how likely it is to obtain a given result by chance.

Certain caveats must be acknowledged. All archaeologists deal with missing data, which can greatly affect the results of analysis. Network analysts have grappled with this question and often use resampling or similar methods to deal with this problem (Bischoff, Padilla-Iglesias, and Gravel-Miguel 2021; Bolland 1988; Borgatti, Carley, and Krackhardt 2006; Tom Brughmans and M. A. Peeples 2023; Costenbader and Valente 2003; Galaskiewicz

1991; Gjesfjeld 2015; Lee, Yook, and Kim 2009; Rivera-Hutinel et al. 2012). Regardless of statistical methods, unaccounted for biases will still produce invalid network results (Bischoff, Padilla-Iglesias, and Gravel-Miguel 2021). The most important bias that may affect these findings is chronology. For example, Bass Point Mound and Cline Terrace Mound were probably not occupied at the same time (Jacobs 1997; Lindauer 1995). Does that invalidate the network analysis? I do not think so. While the networks involve nodes as sites, what the networks are really meant to represent are groups of people. Furthermore, they are not individuals, but the aggregate decisions of people over more than one generation. Current models of Hohokam social groups suggest a certain residential stability (Craig and Woodson 2017, p. 336). Perhaps the residents of these sites were not physically located at the site at the same time as the other inhabitants were located at their site, but they may have been at another nearby location. The spacing of settlements may indicate a corporate form of social organization (Jeffrey J Clark and Vint 2004; Rice and Oliver 1998, p. 96). If this is accurate, then the communities inhabiting the sites may likely have existed in some form prior to the establishment of any particular site and have continued on. It is these communities that the network analysis is attempting to capture. Still, evidence indicates that most sites were contemporaneous. For example, Cline Terrace Mound and Schoolhouse Point were most probably occupied at the same time (Lyons 2013). It is best, though, to think of these interpretations as estimations based on incomplete data and to recognize that these networks are an analytical tool and not a representation of an ancient face-to-face interaction network.

4.4.5 Spatial

The simplest network is the spatial network. This network was created by calculating the Euclidean distance from every site to every other site. Euclidean distance is a shortcut that does not represent actual travel routes. Least cost paths provide more accurate data (see Caseldine 2022, for an application in Tonto Basin), yet an analysis in similar terrain indicates that for distances longer than those in this study the benefits of least cost path distances in place of Euclidean distance are negligible (Bischoff 2017). Least cost paths are also hampered by the presence of Roosevelt Lake and other modern impacts on the landscape. The spatial network created here is equivalent to proximal point analysis, which was used in one of the earliest network studies in archaeology (John E Terrell 1977) and continues to be used to study potential pathways of interaction (see Broodbank 2000; Collar 2013). The inclusion of a spatial network serves as a null hypothesis to test the other networks against.

4.4.6 Architecture

The architectural components consisted of compounds, roomblocks, and platform mounds. Compounds were the typical residential structures in the area and featured multiple houses built from masonry and/or adobe around a courtyard. Platform mounds were formed from large masonry and adobe retaining walls with a cell-like interior filled with trash and rubble. They were common in the Hohokam region throughout the Classic period. Some sites had pit houses dating to earlier occupations, so these few pit houses were removed from the analysis (see Rice 1998). Each site was classified as a platform mound if one was present regardless of other architecture or as a roomblock if a platform mound was not present regardless of other architecture. Thus, if a site is labeled a platform mound

it may have other architecture. Sites were labeled in this manner to emphasize the most distinctive form of architecture, but all types of architecture were present in the analysis, and all architectural features included in the analysis can be seen in Table 4.1.

4.4.7 Ceramics

The ceramic network consists of 28 decorated types (plain wares and most undifferentiated types were removed from the analysis). The ceramic data was accessed from the cyberSW database (B. Mills et al. 2020), which keeps the full citations for the ceramic data. The ceramic data was merged with the projectile point and architectural data by site names using the semi-automated ArchaMap application (part of the CatMapper family of tools, Hruschka et al. 2022), which stores the merge for reproducibility (<https://catmapper.org/archamap/AD944>). The standard caveats for ceramic analysis apply to this analysis as well—problems with sherd misidentification and other data errors.

4.4.8 Projectile Points

The ceramic and architectural data are available in suitable formats for analysis, but the original projectile point analysis was too general for the purposes of this study (see Rice 1994, for details). Points were divided into longer or shorter categories and subdivided by several attributes (e.g., blade, base, or notch shape). Geometric morphometrics (GM) is a set of methods designed to quantitatively analyze shapes and is ideal for projectile point analysis. See Bischoff (2023a) for details on GM and the methods used to analyze these projectile points. A GM analysis was conducted on the 2D outlines of each complete triangular or side-notched projectile point. The majority of projectile points were triangular

or side-notched. The few other points were likely curated points from earlier periods. Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 show the results of these analyses. These figures demonstrate how GM methods can calculate the similarity between each projectile point shape. These results were classified into closely related clusters and used in the same way as ceramic types.

4.5 Results

Figure 4.4 shows the networks with the top three strongest ties between each node. Immediately apparent is that the area groupings identifiable in the spatial network are intermixed in the other three networks. Likewise, the main architecture features that are clustered in the architectural network are also intermixed in the other networks. This indicates there is no strong spatial or architectural visual patterning in the networks. Although, there are some elements that appear influenced by space and/or architecture.

Bass Point Mound forms a crucial bridge between the Cline Mesa sites and the rest of the network. Because the network is not complete, one cannot argue that there were no other sites between Cline Mesa and the Schoolhouse Mesa sites, but it still represents an intermediary location. Its geographic position overlooking the confluence of the Salt River and Tonto Creek would make an ideal meeting place for parties coming down from the Tonto Creek arm of what is now Roosevelt Lake or coming up from the Salt River arm. The Rock Island area consists of a single site in this study, Bass Point Mound (a platform mound), although it was not heavily excavated. If spatial distance was an important factor in social interaction, then we would expect Bass Point Mound to consistently be a highly central node due to its central location. This is exactly what we see in the ceramic and point networks in Figure 4.5 with Bass Point Mound always the most central node.

Figure 4.5 also demonstrates several contradictions between networks and between sites

Figure 4.2: Network graph displaying side-notched points from Tonto Basin as nodes with ties showing the morphometric distance between points. Darker colors represent stronger ties. Note that only the strongest 10% of ties are shown. From Bischoff (2022: Figure 14).

Figure 4.3: Network graph displaying triangular points from Tonto Basin as nodes with ties showing the morphometric distance between points. Darker colors represent stronger ties. Note that only the strongest 10% of ties are shown. From Bischoff (2022: Figure 15).

Figure 4.4: Graphs showing the networks used in this chapter. Each network is displayed with the five strongest ties between each node. See prior table for site labels.

Figure 4.5: Boxplots showing the eigenvector centrality for ceramic and point networks. Values were calculated using networks created using between 3 to 10 of the strongest ranking ties. See Table 1 for site labels.

with the same main type of architecture. Only the roomblocks consistently group together, as the compounds and platform mounds are inconsistent in both networks. Only three of the sites (Bass Point Mound, Pinto Point Mound, and the Sand Dune Site) have consistent centrality across both networks. The roomblocks have above average centrality in the ceramic network but the lowest centrality in the point network. Table 4.2 shows the eigenvector centrality vectors for the ceramic and point networks by type of architecture with the mean for both networks. Surprisingly, the platform mounds are the least central, on average, for the ceramic network, but they are the most central for the point network. The roomblocks, on the hand, are the most central for the ceramic network and by far the least central in the point network. Clearly, there are major differences between these two networks.

Table 4.2: Mean Eigenvalues for Ceramic and Point Networks by Type of Architecture

architecture	ceramics	points	mean
compound	0.52	0.48	0.50
platform mound	0.37	0.72	0.54
roomblock	0.46	0.07	0.27

The multilayer Pearson correlation provides a more direct way to compare these layers, as shown in Figure 4.6. This analysis provides a clear contrast between layers. Only the architectural and point networks show a negative correlation—meaning that ties existed in one network where ties did not exist in the other network. And only one comparison has a relatively strong correlation—the architecture and ceramic networks were strongly correlated ($r = 0.546$). The visual inspection and centrality analysis provided some indication of this, but the multilayer network comparison provides further evidence. The other networks all show moderate correlations with space, which is probably driven primarily by Bass Point Mound.

4.6 Discussion

This analysis has three main findings regarding networks in Tonto Basin: (1) that architecture and ceramic networks are correlated; (2) that roomblock sites are moderately central in the ceramic network but have low centrality in the point network; and (3) that ceramic and point networks have significant differences. In terms of the null hypotheses stated in the introduction, there was some spatial correlation, but it appears to have been driven primarily by one site. Given these network results, how might they be interpreted in terms of social behavior?

Exchange would be a primary driver in these network dynamics, and clear evidence exists for exchange of several types of material culture. Trade within the basin does not appear

Figure 4.6: Boxplots showing the Pearson correlation between each network. Values were calculated using networks created from 3 to 10 of the strongest ranking ties.

to have been dominated by any one group and may have been competitive in nature (Rice, A. Simon, and Christopher Loendorf 1998, pp. 127–128). Ceramic exchange certainly occurred at a regional level, but even local ceramics were circulated within the basin (Heidke and E. J. Miksa 2000; E. Miksa and Heidke 1995; Stark and Heidke 1992), possibly in return for food (Jeffrey J Clark and Vint 2004, pp. 290–291). Projectile points (either as part of the arrow or separately) may have also been commonly exchanged. There are several examples of the exchange of bows and arrows ethnographically throughout the world (e.g., Mauss 1966; Nishiaki 2013; Wiessner 1983), in North America generally (e.g., W. J. Hoffman 1896; Radin 1923), and in the Southwest specifically (e.g., Beaglehole 1936; Dittert 1959; Fewkes 1898; Griffen 1969; Parsons 1939; Simpson 1953). Besides Watt’s study of

knappers, Sliva's (2002, p. 539) analysis of sites from another Roosevelt project suggests craft specialization in projectile point production. Mortuary offerings were possibly the intended function for many points (Sliva 2002, p. 543), which may have spurred the increased craft specialization. Shell and stone jewelry, among other artifacts were also produced and exchanged within the basin. Potential loci for exchange are the platform mound sites. The purpose of these sites is debated, but many argue that they served an integrative function (e.g., Abbott, Ingram, and Kober 2006; Adler and Wilshusen 1990; Jeffrey J Clark and Vint 2004; Craig 1995; Craig and Jeffrey J Clark 1994, pp. 112–165; Doelle, Gregory, and Wallace 1995, p. 439). If platform mounds were places where exchange between communities regularly took place, then we would expect platform mounds to have higher centrality. Centrality varied among the platform mounds, but on average, platform mounds did have the highest centrality—if narrowly.

As discussed previously, cultural differences were expected between the Tonto Creek and Salt River arms of Roosevelt Lake. This was due in part to differences in long-distance ceramic exchange and obsidian sourcing (Lyons 2013; A. W. Simon and Gosser 2001). This analysis did not use obsidian or focus on non-local ceramics and therefore did not capture differences based on these factors. There was some expectation that more separation in the material networks would be apparent between the Cline Mesa sites in the Tonto Creek arm and the other sites (minus Bass Point Mound that lies at the confluence). This was not born out in the visual inspection of the analysis with significant mixing of the areas in the network.

There is a potential chain of association between immigrants and roomblocks, roomblocks or locations with roomblocks as centers of Salado production, and Salado pottery as a widespread phenomenon that provides an expectation for roomblock sites to be central to pottery networks. While this association is circumstantial and not expected

to be uniform across the Hohokam region, roomblocks did have the highest centrality in the ceramic networks. Another proposed reason for the high centrality of roomblock sites is that they lacked access to adequate farmland and had to trade pottery for food (Jeffrey J Clark and Vint 2004, p. 291). This second explanation may help explain why roomblock sites had low centrality in the point networks, presuming that points were not exchanged for food. It is beyond this simple analysis to determine the precise reasons, but clearly roomblock sites were important for ceramic circulation. On the other hand, sites with roomblocks had the lowest centrality in the point networks. This suggests that the influence the occupants of roomblock sites had in pottery networks may not have extended to other spheres of interaction.

As discussed previously, my simplistic model of interaction in Tonto Basin assumes that the ceramic network represents categorical identification among women. Recall also that I expected architecture to represent categorical identity. Thus, the correlation between architecture and ceramics is an expected find and good corroborating evidence that these types of material culture represent markers of identity demonstrating belonging to a particular social group.

The point networks were expected to represent relational identification among men, at least in this case study. Because relational identification is related to frequent interaction, spatial distance is a crucial component. It is much harder to interact with someone when they are far away. Thus, the correlation between the point and spatial networks, though weak, also makes theoretical sense.

Perhaps the reason roomblocks were more central to the ceramic network is because immigrants to the basin had less access to farmland and had to make pottery to get food, as mentioned. This would explain higher centrality for roomblocks and lower centrality for point networks. It does not explain the remaining differences between point and ceramic

networks. Projectile points at least were highly gendered, and ceramics probably were as well. The evidence presented here demonstrates that ceramic and point networks vary significantly, and gender likely played an important role. More research will be needed to determine the relationship between gender roles and material culture networks and to determine the relationship that immigration played in these dynamics.

4.7 Conclusion

This is one of the first archaeological applications of multilayer network analysis to consider multiple types of material culture. This is advantageous for studying how types of material culture do or do not co-vary, which aids interpretations of the social interactions that created these patterns. This analysis used architectural, ceramic, projectile point, and spatial data from 10 sites in Tonto Basin focusing on occupations from the Roosevelt phase dating between AD 1275 and 1325. A network was created for each type of data and combined into a multilayer network. Visual network analysis, eigenvector centrality, and multilayer network Pearson correlation were used to study and compare the networks. The findings indicate that the ceramic network was strongly correlated with the architectural network. Furthermore, sites with roomblocks indicative of immigrants from the north and east of Tonto Basin were, on average, the most highly central sites in the ceramic network; however, they were the least central in the point network. Immigrants may have relied on pottery production to integrate with the local networks, but this relationship did not hold for projectile points. Finally, the results demonstrate notable differences between the ceramic and point networks. This finding has major implications for network studies because many rely on only a single artifact type. If different types of material culture do not co-vary regularly, then that indicates archaeologists must do more to include other types of material

culture to better understand the complex social networks that existed in the past. Furthermore, projectile points and ceramics have strong associations with gender. Differences in the ceramic and point networks suggest differences existed between the social networks of men and women.

This analysis used a handful of sites from Tonto Basin. Much more data exists and the results discussed here would be greatly strengthened by including more sites and data. What would be perhaps more useful would be to include sourced obsidian and ceramics. Networks created from artifacts where the origin is known can be used to more strongly infer various types of social interaction. The role immigration played in the social dynamics of Tonto Basin as represented in material culture networks also deserves consideration. This type of multilayer analysis would also be useful to conduct in other regions. It would be particularly useful for comparative studies to know in what circumstances different types of material culture do or do not co-vary. It is my hope that this study highlights the usefulness of a multilayer network approach utilizing multiple types of material culture.

Data Availability

All data and scripts used in this analysis, except site location information, are available at the following DOI: [10.17605/OSF.IO/T8QWF](https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/T8QWF) and Appendix C.

Note: This paper has been published in the journal *Kiva* and is available at DOI: [10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137](https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137).

Permission to publish in the dissertation was retained when the article was submitted—see Taylor and Francis permissions in Appendix E.

References

- Abbott, David R, Scott E Ingram, and Brent G Kober (Jan. 2006). “Hohokam Exchange and Early Classic Period Organization in Central Arizona: Focal Villages or Linear Communities?” In: *Journal of Field Archaeology* 31 (3), pp. 285–305. ISSN: 0093-4690. DOI: 10.1179/009346906791071909. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346906791071909>.
- Adler, Michael A and Richard H Wilshusen (1990). “Large-Scale Integrative Facilities in Tribal Societies: Cross-Cultural and Southwestern U.S. Examples”. In: *World archaeology* 22 (2), pp. 133–144. ISSN: 0043-8243.
- Ahlstrom, Richard V N, Mark L Chenault, and Kirk C Anderson (1991). *The Roosevelt Bajada Survey, Tonto Basin, Gila County, Arizona*. Report No. 91-24. Tucson: SWCA, Inc. Environmental Consultants.
- Bahr, Donald M (2011). *Culture summary: O’odham*. English. New Haven, Conn. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-000>.
- Beaglehole, Ernest (1936). *Hopi Hunting and Hopi Ritual*. en. Yale University Publication in Anthropology No. 4. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Birch, Jennifer and John P Hart (Jan. 2018). “Social Networks and Northern Iroquoian Confederacy Dynamics”. In: *American Antiquity* 83 (1), pp. 13–33. ISSN: 0002-7316. DOI: 10.1017/aaq.2017.59. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0002731617000592/type/journal_article.
- Bischoff, Robert J (2017). *A Spatial Analysis of San Juan Red Ware: Evaluating Fall-off Curves with Straight-line or Least Cost Path Distance*. Poster presented at the 82nd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, Vancouver, BC. March 31, 2017.
- (2023a). “Geometric Morphometric Analysis of Projectile Points from the Southwest United States”. In: *Peer Community Journal* 3 (e80). DOI: 10.24072/pcjournal.312. URL: <https://peercommunityjournal.org/articles/10.24072/pcjournal.312/>.
- Bischoff, Robert J, Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias, and Claudine Gravel-Miguel (2021). *Evaluating the Effects of Randomness on Missing Data in Archaeological Networks*. Paper presented at the Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology Conference, Cyprus (virtual). June 16th, 2021.

- Bolland, John M (Sept. 1, 1988). “Sorting out centrality: An analysis of the performance of four centrality models in real and simulated networks”. In: *Social Networks* 10 (3), pp. 233–253. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/0378-8733(88)90014-7. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378873388900147>.
- Borck, Lewis et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Are Social Networks Survival Networks? An Example from the Late Pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 33–57. ISSN: 1573-7764,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5>.
- Borgatti, Stephen P (2005). “Centrality and Network Flow”. In: *Social Networks* 27 (1), pp. 55–71. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2004.11.008. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873304000693>.
- Borgatti, Stephen P, Kathleen M Carley, and David Krackhardt (May 1, 2006). “On the robustness of centrality measures under conditions of imperfect data”. In: *Social networks* 28 (2), pp. 124–136. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2005.05.001. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873305000353>.
- Bródka, Piotr et al. (2018). “Quantifying Layer Similarity in Multiplex Networks: a Systematic Study”. en. In: *Royal Society Open Science* 5 (8), p. 171747. ISSN: 2054-5703. DOI: 10.1098/rsos.171747. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171747>.
- Broodbank, Cyprian (2000). *An Island Archaeology of the Early Cyclades*. en. Cambridge University Press. 436 pp. ISBN: 9780521528443. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=qbYiW13TJ6UC>.
- Brubaker, Rogers and Frederick Cooper (2000). “Beyond” identity””. In: *Theory and Society* 29 (1), pp. 1–47. ISSN: 0304-2421,1573-7853. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3108478>.
- Brughmans, Tom and Matthew A Peeples (2023). *Network Science in Archaeology*. Cambridge Manuals in Archaeology. Cambridge University Press.
- Carr, Christopher (1995a). “A Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Carr C. and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 171–258. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- (1995b). “Building a Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Christopher Carr and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions

to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 151–170. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.

Caseldine, Christopher R (Jan. 2, 2022). “Least Cost Paths and Movement in Tonto Basin, Central Arizona”. In: *The KIVA* 88 (1), pp. 112–141. ISSN: 0023-1940. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.2021.1996517. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2021.1996517>.

Castetter, Edward Franklin and Ruth Murray Underhill (1935). *The ethnobiology of the Papago Indians*. en. Vol. 4. Ethnobiological studies in the American Southwest No. 3. Albuquerque: The University of New Mexico press. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-017> (visited on 12/28/2022).

Chona, Maria (1936). *Autobiography of a Papago Woman*. English. Ed. by Ruth Underhill. Menasha: American Anthropological Association, pp. ii, 64. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-003>.

Ciolek-Torrello, Richard, Steven D Shelley, and Su Benaron (1994). *The Roosevelt Rural Sites Study: Prehistoric Rural Settlements in the Tonto Basin*. en. Tucson: Statistical Research, Inc.

Clark, Jeffery J (2001). *Tracking Prehistoric Migrations: Pueblo Settlers Among the Tonto Basin Hohokam*. en. Vol. 65. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. 124 pp. ISBN: 9780816520879. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=27Tk3xNT-6UC>.

Clark, Jeffery J and Christopher R Caseldine (2021). *Research Design for Late Pre-Hispanic Backcountry Sites on Tonto National Monument: Contextualizing the Monument in Tonto Basin and Beyond*. Vol. Technical Report No. 2021-101. Tucson: Archaeology Southwest.

Clark, Jeffrey J and James M Vint, eds. (2004). *2000 Years of Settlement in the Tonto Basin: Overview and Synthesis of the Tonto Creek Archaeological Project*. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology.

Cochrane, Ethan E and Carl P Lipo (Dec. 12, 2010). “Phylogenetic analyses of Lapita decoration do not support branching evolution or regional population structure during colonization of Remote Oceania”. en. In: *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences* 365 (1559), pp. 3889–3902. ISSN: 0962-8436,1471-2970. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2010.0091. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0091>.

- Collar, Anna (Dec. 12, 2013). *Religious Networks in the Roman Empire: The Spread of New Ideas*. en. Cambridge University Press. 312 pp. ISBN: 9781107729711. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Av5GAgAAQBAJ>.
- Costenbader, Elizabeth and Thomas W Valente (Oct. 1, 2003). “The stability of centrality measures when networks are sampled”. In: *Social networks* 25 (4), pp. 283–307. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/S0378-8733(03)00012-1. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873303000121>.
- Craig, Douglas B (1995). “The Social Consequences of Irrigation Agriculture: A Perspective from Meddler Point”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory*. Ed. by M D Elson, M T Stark, and D A Gregory. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 227–249.
- Craig, Douglas B and Jeffery J Clark (1994). “The Meddler Point Site, AZ V:5:4/26 (ASM/TNF)”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: Vol. 2. Meddler Point, Pyramid Point, and Griffin Wash Sites*. Ed. by M D Elson et al. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 13. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 1–198.
- Craig, Douglas B and M Kyle Woodson (2017). “Preclassic Hohokam”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Southwest Archaeology*. Ed. by Barbara J Mills and Severin M Fowles. Oxford University Press, pp. 323–351.
- Crown, Patricia L and Suzanne K Fish (1996). “Gender and Status in the Hohokam Preclassic to Classic Transition”. In: *American anthropologist* 98 (4), pp. 803–817. ISSN: 0002-7294.
- Dean, Jeffrey S (2000). *Salado*. Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation, Dragoon, Arizona and University of New Mexico Press, pp. 3–16.
- Dietler, Michael and Ingrid Herbich (1998). “Habitus, Techniques, Style: An Integrated Approach to the Social Understanding of Material Culture and Boundaries”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution, pp. 232–263.
- Dittert, Alfred E (1959). “Culture Change in the Cebolleta Mesa Region Central Western New Mexico”. PhD thesis. Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson, Arizona.
- Doelle, William H, David A Gregory, and Henry D Wallace (1995). “Classic Period Platform Mound Systems in Southern Arizona”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Develop-*

ment Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory. Ed. by M D Elson, M T Stark, and D A Gregory. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 385–440.

Doelle, William H, Henry D Wallace, et al. (1992). *Research Design for the Roosevelt Community Development Study*. Vol. Anthropological Papers ,12. Tucson, Arizona: Center for Desert Archaeology.

Elson, Mark D (Jan. 1996). “A revised chronology and phase sequence for the lower Tonto Basin of central Arizona”. In: *The KIVA* 62 (2), pp. 117–147. ISSN: 0023-1940,2051-6177. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328. URL: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328>.

Elson, Mark D, David A Gregory, and Miriam T Stark (1995). *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory*. en. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology.

Elson, Mark D and Michael Lindeman (1994). “The Eagle Ridge Site, AZ V:5:104/1045 (ASM/TNF)”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: Vol. 1. Introduction and Small Sites*. Ed. by M D Elson and D L Swartz. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 13. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 23–116.

Elson, Mark D, Miriam T Stark, and David A Gregory (2000). “Tonto Basin Local Systems: Implications for Cultural Affiliation and Migration”. en. In: *Salado*. Ed. by J S Dean. Dragoon, Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation Publication, Dragoon, Arizona. University of New Mexico Press, pp. 167–192 4.

Feinman, Gary M and Jill E Neitzel (Dec. 1, 2020). “Excising Culture History from Contemporary Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 60, p. 101230. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101230. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416520302038>.

Fewkes, Jesse Walter (1898). *Archaeological Expedition to Arizona in 1895*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution.

Frost, Robert H (May 3, 2022). “Eigenvector centrality for multilayer networks with dependent node importance”. In: *ArXiv*, pp. 1–9. ArXiv: 2205.01478 (physics.soc-ph). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01478>.

Galaskiewicz, Joseph (Dec. 1, 1991). “Estimating point centrality using different network sampling techniques”. In: *Social networks* 13 (4), pp. 347–386. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI:

10.1016/0378-8733(91)90002-B. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/037887339190002B>.

Giomi, Evan (2022). *Exploring the development and persistence of the Eastern Puebloan economy: Rio Grande glaze ware as a window on regional interaction*. URL: https://repository.arizona.edu/bitstream/handle/10150/663236/azu_etd_19397_sip1_m.pdf?sequence=1 (visited on 10/03/2022).

Gjesfjeld, Erik (Mar. 1, 2015). “Network Analysis of Archaeological Data from Hunter-Gatherers: Methodological Problems and Potential Solutions”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 182–205. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9>.

Golitko, Mark and Gary M Feinman (Mar. 2015). “Procurement and distribution of pre-Hispanic Mesoamerican obsidian 900 BC–AD 1520: A social network analysis”. en. In: *Journal of archaeological method and theory* 22 (1), pp. 206–247. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9211-1. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9211-1>.

Gosselain, Olivier P (1998). “Social and Technical Identity in a Clay Cristal Ball”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam Stark. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 78–106.

— (Sept. 1, 2000). “Materializing Identities: An African Perspective”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 7 (3), pp. 187–217. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1023/A:1026558503986. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026558503986>.

— (2016). “The World is Like a Beanstalk: Historicizing Potting Practice and Social Relations in the Niger River Area”. en. In: *Knowledge in Motion: Constellations of Learning Across Time and Place*. Ed. by Andrew P Roddick and Ann B Stahl. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, pp. 36–66. ISBN: 9780816533749. URL: <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/44808> (visited on 03/11/2019).

Griffen, William B (Apr. 30, 1969). *Culture change and shifting populations in central northern Mexico*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona, no. 13. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press. 208 pp. ISBN: 9780816501403. DOI: 10.2307/j.ctv1bxgw4f. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/j.ctv1bxgw4f>.

Harry, Karen G and Fred Huntington (2010). “Households, Gender, and Specialized Pottery Production: Exploring the Nature, Causes, and Consequences of a Prehistoric Cottage Industry for Women at the West Branch Settlement”. In: *Engendering households in the prehistoric southwest*. Ed. by B J Roth. University of Arizona Press, pp. 76–97.

- Heidke, James M and Elizabeth J Miksa (2000). “Ceramic Temper Provenance Studies”. en. In: *Tonto Creek Archaeological Project: Artifact and Environmental Analyses*. Ed. by J M Vint and J M Heidke. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 95–146.
- Hodder, Ian (1982). *Symbols in Action: Ethnoarchaeological Studies of Material Culture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9780521241762. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-TSE9AAAAIAAJ>.
- Hoffman, Charles Marshall (1997). “Alliance Formation and Social Interaction During the Sedentary Period: a Stylistic Analysis of Hohokam Arrowpoints”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, Tempe.
- Hoffman, Walter James (1896). “The Menomini Indians”. In: *The Fourteenth Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1892–1893 pt 1*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C.: Government Printing Office, pp. 11–338.
- Holland-Lulewicz, Jacob (Jan. 4, 2021). “From Categories to Connections in the Archaeology of Eastern North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research* 29, pp. 537–579. ISSN: 1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w>.
- Hruschka, Daniel J et al. (Jan. 30, 2022). “CatMapper: A user-friendly tool for integrating data across complex categories”. In: *SocArXiv Papers* 1. URL: <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/n6rty/>.
- Huntley, Deborah L (2008). *Ancestral Zuni Glaze-Decorated Pottery: Viewing Pueblo IV Regional Organization through Ceramic Production and Exchange*. Vol. No. 72. Anthropological Papers. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Jaccard, Paul (Feb. 1912). “The Distribution of the Flora in the Alpine Zone”. en. In: *The New Phytologist* 11 (2), pp. 37–50. ISSN: 0028-646X,1469-8137. DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.1912.tb05611.x. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1469-8137.1912.tb05611.x>.
- Jacobs, David, ed. (1997). *A Salado Platform Mound on Tonto Creek, Roosevelt Platform Mound*. Tempe, Arizona: Roosevelt Monograph Studies ,7. Tempe, Arizona: Department of.
- Joseph, Alice, Rosamond B Spicer, and Jane Chesky (1949). “Desert people: a study of the Papago Indians”. English. In: *Indian education research series*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, xviii, 288, 21 plates. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-004>.

- Kivelä, Mikko et al. (2014). “Multilayer Networks”. In: *Journal of Complex Networks* 2 (3), pp. 203–271. ISSN: 2051-1310. DOI: 10.1093/comnet/cnu016. URL: <https://academic.oup.com/comnet/article-abstract/2/3/203/2841130>.
- Lange, Richard C and Stephen Germick, eds. (1992). *Proceedings of the Second Salado Conference, Globe, Arizona, 1992*. en. Phoenix: Arizona Archaeological Society.
- Lave, Jean and Etienne Wenger (1991). *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. en. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 138 pp. ISBN: 9780521423748. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-CAVIOrW3vYAC>.
- Lee, S, S-H Yook, and Y Kim (Mar. 2009). “Centrality measure of complex networks using biased random walks”. en. In: *The European physical journal. B* 68 (2), pp. 277–281. ISSN: 1434-6028,1434-6036. DOI: 10.1140/epjb/e2009-00095-5. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1140/epjb/e2009-00095-5>.
- Lemonnier, Pierre (June 1, 1986). “The Study of Material Culture Today: Toward an Anthropology of Technical Systems”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 5 (2), pp. 147–186. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90012-7. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416586900127>.
- Lindauer, Owen (1995). *Where the Rivers Converge: Roosevelt Platform Mound Study: Report on the Rock Island Complex*. Vol. Roosevelt Monograph Series 4. Tempe: Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University.
- Loendorf, Chris, Lynn Simon, et al. (Aug. 2015). “Warfare and Big Game Hunting: Flaked-Stone Projectile Points Along the Middle Gila River in Arizona”. en. In: *Antiquity* 89, pp. 940–953. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.15184/aqy.2015.28. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/warfare-and-big-game-hunting-flakedstone-projectile-points-along-the-middle-gila-river-in-arizona/F8FAF746DA28A11D0A051E3BDC6BB023> (visited on 12/27/2018).
- Loendorf, Christopher (1998). “Salado Burial Practices and Social Organization”. In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeology Studies, 1989 to 1998*. Ed. by Glen Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 10 Anthropological Field Studies 40. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 193–230. ISBN: 9781886067004.
- Lulewicz, Jacob (Apr. 2, 2019). “The social networks and structural variation of Mississippian sociopolitics in the southeastern United States”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 116 (14), pp. 6707–6712.

ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1818346116. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1818346116>.

Lyons, Patrick D (2003). *Ancestral Hopi Migrations*. English. First Edition edition. Anthropological Paper Number 68. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816522804.

— (2013). *Placing the Tonto Cliff Dwellings in the Larger Context of Tonto Basin and the Southern US Southwest*. en. Tucson: Western National Parks Association.

Lyons, Patrick D and Alexander Johnston Lindsay Jr. (2006). “Perforated Plates and the Salado Phenomenon”. In: *The Kiva* 72 (1), pp. 5–54. ISSN: 0023-1940.

Mauss, Marcel (1966). *The Gift: Forms and Functions of Exchange in Archaic Societies*. London: Cohen & West.

Miksa, Elizabeth and James M Heidke (1995). “Drawing a Line in the Sands: Models of Ceramic Temper Provenance”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study*. Ed. by J M Heidke and M T Stark. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 14. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 133–204.

Mills, Barbara et al. (2020). *CyberSW Version 1.0*. en. Tucson. URL: <https://cybersw.org/>.

Mills, Barbara J, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (Apr. 9, 2013). “Transformation of social networks in the late pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110 (15), pp. 5785–5790. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1219966110. URL: <http://www.pnas.org/content/110/15/5785>.

Mills, Barbara J, John M Roberts Jr, et al. (2013). “The Dynamics of Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic U.S. Southwest”. en. In: *Network Analysis in Archaeology: New Approaches to Regional Interaction*. Ed. by Carl Knappett. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 181–202. DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199697090.003.0008.

Neuzil, Anna A (2008). *In the Aftermath of Migration: Renegotiating Ancient Identity in Southeastern Arizona*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona No. 73. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.

Nishiaki, Yoshihiro (2013). ““Gifting” As a Means of Cultural Transmission: The Archaeological Implications of Bow-and-Arrow Technology in Papua New Guinea”. In: *Dynamics of Learning in Neanderthals and Modern Humans Volume 1: Cultural Perspectives*. Ed. by Takeru Akazawa, Yoshihiro Nishiaki, and Kenichi Aoki. Tokyo: Springer Japan,

pp. 173–185. ISBN: 9784431545118. DOI: 10.1007/978-4-431-54511-8_10. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-54511-8_10.

Oliver, Theodore J (2001). “Warfare in Tonto Basin”. en. In: *Deadly Landscapes: Case Studies of Prehistoric Southwestern Warfare*. Ed. by G E Rice and Steven A LeBlanc. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, pp. 195–217.

Ortman, Scott G (Mar. 2016). “Uniform Probability Density Analysis and Population History in the Northern Rio Grande”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 23 (1), pp. 95–126. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9227-6. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10816-014-9227-6>.

Parsons, Elsie Clews (1939). *Pueblo Indian Religion*. English. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Peeples, Matthew A (2017). *Network Science and Statistical Techniques for Dealing with Uncertainties in Archaeological Datasets*.

— (2018). *Connected Communities: Networks, Identity, and Social Change in the Ancient Cibola World*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816535682. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-fyw-DwAAQBAJ>.

— (2021). *UniformProbabilityDensityAnalysis*. en. Comp. software. URL: <https://github.com/mpeeples2008/UniformProbabilityDensityAnalysis> (visited on 04/25/2023).

Peeples, Matthew A and John M Roberts (July 2013). “To Binarize or not to Binarize: Relational Data and the Construction of Archaeological Networks”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 40 (7), pp. 3001–3010. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.03.014. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440313001040>.

Radin, Paul (1923). “The Winnebago Tribe”. en. In: *Thirty Seventh Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1915–1916*. Ed. by F W Hodge. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 33–560.

Rice, Glen E (1994). “Projectile Points, Bifaces, and Drills”. In: *Archaeology of the Salado in the Livingston Area of Tonto Basin, Roosevelt Platform Mound Study: Report on the Livingston Management Group, Pinto Creek Complex. Part 2*. Ed. by Glen E Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 3. Tempe: Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, pp. 727–738. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N>.

- Rice, Glen E, ed. (1998). *A synthesis of Tonto Basin prehistory: The Roosevelt archaeology studies, 1989 to 1998*. Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University. DOI: 10.6067/XCV81V5GRZ. URL: <https://core.tdar.org/document/394298/a-synthesis-of-tonto-basin-prehistory-the-roosevelt-archaeology-studies-1989-to-1998>.
- Rice, Glen E and Theodore J Oliver (1998). "Settlement Patterns and Subsistence". en. In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeological Studies, 1989-1998*. Ed. by Glen E Rice. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 85–104.
- Rice, Glen E, Arleyn Simon, and Christopher Loendorf (1998). "Production and Exchange of Economic Goods". In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeology Studies, 1989 to 1998*. Ed. by Glen Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 10 Anthropological Field Studies 40. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 105–130. ISBN: 9781886067004.
- Rivera-Hutinel, A et al. (July 2012). "Effects of sampling completeness on the structure of plant-pollinator networks". en. In: *Ecology* 93 (7), pp. 1593–1603. ISSN: 0012-9658,1939-9170. DOI: 10.1890/11-1803.1. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1890/11-1803.1>.
- Roberts, John M et al. (May 1, 2012). "A Method for Chronological Apportioning of Ceramic Assemblages". In: *Journal of archaeological science* 39 (5), pp. 1513–1520. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2011.12.022. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440311004699>.
- Roosevelt Platform Mound Study (RPMS) (2014). *Access Database (tDAR id: 427111)*. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8TQ63KK. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6067/XCV8TQ63KK>.
- Sassman, Kenneth E and Victoria Rudolphi (2001). "Communities of Practice in the Early Ceramic Traditions of the American Southeast". In: *Journal of Anthropological Research* 57, pp. 407–425. ISSN: 0091-7710.
- Shackley, Michael S (2005). *Obsidian: Geology and Archaeology in the North American Southwest*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Simon, Arelyn W and Dennis C Gosser (2001). "Conflict and Exchange among the Salado of Tonto Basin: Warfare Motivation or Alleviation?" en. In: *Deadly Landscapes: Case Studies of Prehistoric Southwestern Warfare*. Ed. by G E Rice and Steven A LeBlanc. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, pp. 219–238.

- Simpson, Ruth Deette (1953). *The Hopi Indians*. en. Vol. 1. Southwest Museum Leaflets, No. 25. Los Angeles: Southwest Museum.
- Sliva, R Jane (2002). “Temporal, Spatial, and Functional Variability in the Flaked Stone Assemblage”. en. In: *Tonto Creek Archaeological Project: Artifact and Environmental Analyses. Vol. 2: Stone Tool and Subsistence Studies*. Ed. by J J Clark. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 23. Anthropological Papers No. 23. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 487–558.
- Stark, Miriam T, Mark D Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark (1998). “Social Boundaries and Technical Choices in Tonto Basin Prehistory”. en. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, D.C: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 208–231.
- Stark, Miriam T and James M Heidke (1992). “The Plainware and Redware Ceramic Assemblages”. en. In: *The Rye Creek Project: Archaeology in the Upper Tonto Basin: Vol. 2. Artifact and Specific Analyses*. Ed. by M D Elson and D B Craig. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 11. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 89–214.
- Team, R Core (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria. URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Terrell, John E (1977). “Human Biogeography in the Solomon Islands”. In: *Fieldiana* 68 (1), pp. 1–47. ISSN: 0071-4739.
- Terrell, John Edward (2010). “Social Network Analysis of the Genetic Structure of Pacific Islanders”. In: *Annals of Human Genetics* 74 (3), p. 211.
- Upton, Andrew James (2019). “Multilayer Network Relationships and Culture Contact in Mississippian West-central Illinois, A.D. 1200 - 1450”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Michigan State University, East Lansing.
- VanPool, Todd L and Chet Savage (2010). “War, women, and religion: The spread of Salado Polychrome in the American Southwest”. In: *Innovation in Cultural System: Contributions from Evolutionary Anthropology*. Ed. by Michael J O’Brien and Stephen J Shennan. Cambridge: MIT Press, pp. 251–265. URL: <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=IOoiwbJg1jUC&oi=fnd&pg=PA251&ots=7umBczM58w&sig=bf3gC1eMgm3SAZW3IECYyVpC7L0>.
- Watts, Joshua (Aug. 2013). “Traces of the Individual in Prehistory: Flintknappers and the Distribution of Projectile Points in the Eastern Tonto Basin, Arizona”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 1 (1), pp. 25–36. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.7183/2326-3768.1.1.25. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances>

in - archaeological - practice / article / traces - of - the - individual - in - prehistory / 7941C0F225A22D6D9707A6165FC4E5B0 (visited on 01/14/2020).

Wenger, Etienne (1998). *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Vol. 9. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. URL: <https://valenciacollege.edu/faculty/development/teaching-learning-academy/documents/CommunityofPractice.pdf>.

Whittlesey, Stephanie M (2010). “House, Home, and Hearth: Gender in the Pre-Classic Hohokam Household”. In: *Engendering households in the prehistoric southwest*. Ed. by B J Roth. University of Arizona Press, pp. 50–75.

Wiessner, Polly (1983). “Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 48 (2), pp. 253–276. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280450. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-and-social-information-in-kalahari-san-projectile-points/52D6230881B0C69260ABE226BD82EC0E>.

— (1997). “Seeking Guidelines through an Evolutionary Approach: Style Revisited among the !Kung San of the 1990s”. In: *Rediscovering Darwin*. Ed. by C Michael Barton and Geoffrey A Clark. Vol. 7. Archeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association. Arlington: American Anthropological Association, pp. 157–176.

Wood, J Scott (2000). “Vale of Tiers Palimpsest: Salado Settlement and Internal Relationship in the Tonto Basin Area”. en. In: *Salado*. Ed. by Jeffrey S Dean. Dragoon, Arizona and Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation Publication and University of New Mexico Press, pp. 107–142.

CHAPTER 5

SYNTHESIZING MATERIAL CULTURE AND NETWORK DATA

The previous three chapters approached the relationship between material culture and social networks from distinct but complementary angles. Chapter 3 focused on refining typological classification for projectile points, while Chapters 2 and 4 evaluated network dynamics through simulated and empirical data, respectively.

Because Chapter 4 did not incorporate the latest projectile point analysis or the most recent results from the ArchMatNet agent-based model, this chapter presents a final integrative analysis. The goal is to bring those elements together and reassess the potential for material culture networks to serve as proxies for social networks—especially in the context of the Western Pueblo region.

5.1 Multilayer Analysis

This analysis uses multilayer network analysis to evaluate how ceramics and projectile points represent different patterns of interaction. Methods follow those used in Chapter 4, with some modifications. The details of the code can be found in Appendix D.

5.1.1 Dataset and Methods

Sites were selected based on three criteria: (1) at least 25 ceramic sherds, (2) at least 5 projectile points, and (3) occupation dates between AD 1200 and 1300. Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 show the temporal and spatial distribution of these sites.

Figure 5.1: Site occupations for selected archaeological sites used in this analysis. Arrows indicate the start and end dates of occupation, colored by region. Some site occupations extend beyond the temporal bounds shown in this figure.

As in previous chapters, I created Brainerd-Robinson similarity networks based on ceramic and projectile point assemblages. Unlike earlier ceramic analyses, this version includes both decorated and undecorated types to better capture local production and use. A spatial network was also constructed based on geographic distance.

Each network was pruned by removing the weakest 50% of links and retaining only the top three ties for each site. While arbitrary, these thresholds are grounded in experimentation and insights from ArchMatNet, which indicate that strong ties are most representative of social connections. I then calculated eigenvector centrality and pairwise graph correlations for all networks.

Figure 5.2: Site locations discussed in this analysis.

5.1.2 Results

Figure 5.3 shows the three networks. The ceramic and projectile point networks form single, connected components, but they differ in structure. The spatial network shows a north–south divide, as expected based on geographic distance.

Inscription House, a Kayenta-region site, stands out in both the ceramic and projectile point networks for its strong connections to sites in the Tonto Basin, despite its geographic

isolation. This pattern aligns with prior findings on Kayenta migration and shows how material culture can capture non-local interaction.

Figure 5.4 shows eigenvector centrality scores. Sites with high centrality in the ceramic network tend not to be central in the projectile point network. This again suggests that these networks reflect different social processes.

The Louvain algorithm was applied to the multilayer network (Figure 5.5), but results were inconclusive. The two detected communities did not align well with known social or regional groupings. This suggests that in this case, ceramics and projectile points should be analyzed as distinct layers rather than combined.

Graph correlation values further support this conclusion (Figure 5.6). Correlations between spatial, ceramic, and projectile point networks were generally low. When split into northern and southern subregions, only a weak, positive correlation was observed between ceramics and space in the north and a weak negative correlation was seen between projectile points and space in the south.

5.1.3 Multilayer Discussion

The ceramic and projectile point networks are clearly distinct. The ceramic data show regional patterning consistent with expectations and known migration patterns. In contrast, projectile point networks display less structure, though key ties—such as Inscription House and Tonto Basin—still highlight meaningful connections.

As suggested by the ArchMatNet results, distinctiveness in material culture is necessary for it to reflect social processes. Ceramic typologies are relatively localized and well-defined, making them better suited for inferring group affiliation or migration. Projectile points, while useful, may require more caution. Their forms are less visibly distinct, and the

Figure 5.3: Multilayer network graphs showing relationships among archaeological sites based on three different similarity networks: ceramics (top), projectile points (middle), and spatial proximity (bottom). Node colors indicate regional affiliations, and edge thickness represents the relative strength of similarity or spatial closeness between sites (normalized weight from 0 to 1.0).

Figure 5.4: Eigenvector centrality scores for each site in the ceramic (tan points) and projectile point (black points) similarity networks. Higher values on the x-axis indicate greater influence or connectivity within the respective network. Colored lines indicate each site's associated region. Differences between black and tan point positions reflect variation in centrality across artifact types. Sites are ordered by the ceramic centrality score.

relevant parts are often hidden by hafting. The arrow shaft itself is likely more indicative of social differences, and they were often painted (Holly 2010; Justice 2002b; Sinopoli 1991; Rudy 1953). This low-visibility for projectile points reduces their communicative potential in social contexts and likely ties them more closely to relational identity or individual practice.

This analysis reinforces the broader point: different types of material culture reflect different social processes. Combining them can be powerful, but only when we understand how and why they differ.

Figure 5.5: Map of Louvain communities detected from a multilayer network combining ceramics and projectile points. Each site is symbolized by its community assignment, with red (Community 1) and yellow (Community 2) indicating distinct clusters of sites based on integrated network structure.

Figure 5.6: Graph correlation matrices comparing spatial, ceramic, and projectile point similarity networks. Correlation values range from -1 to 1 and are equivalent to Pearson correlation coefficients, indicating how structurally similar each network is. Panel A (top) shows correlations for the full network; Panel B (middle) shows results for the northern subset of sites; and Panel C (bottom) shows results for the southern subset.

5.2 Evaluating Material Culture Networks

The core aim of this dissertation was to assess how effectively material culture networks—also referred to as archaeological similarity networks (Collar et al. 2015, p. 16)—can serve as proxies for social networks. The results from both simulated and empirical analyses suggest that material culture can meaningfully reflect social connections under certain conditions, though important limitations remain.

This evaluation was carried out through two primary avenues: (1) the ArchMatNet agent-based model (ABM), which allowed for controlled experimentation with known social and material outcomes; and (2) a case study in the central U.S. Southwest, one of the best-documented archaeological regions in the world. As has been noted, the granularity of data available in the Southwest enables studies that are simply not feasible elsewhere (Perreault 2019).

Taken together, these two approaches provide a strong foundation for evaluating material culture networks. Ethnographic studies would represent the only more direct way to answer these questions, but compiling a dataset with detailed records of both material culture and social relationships remains a major challenge.

As discussed in Chapter 2, Golitko's study (2023) provides a rare example of such an ethnographic approach. His work revealed weak correlations between social interaction and material culture networks, and centrality measures performed poorly. These results mirror many of the findings presented here and reinforce the need for caution when interpreting archaeological networks.

The results from this dissertation confirm that Golitko's findings should be expected in certain contexts. That said, the discrepancies in strength between his results and those from ArchMatNet may be due to limitations in the bone dagger dataset, the nature of the interac-

tion data, or the binary representation of ties. Still, his study offers an important benchmark and underscores the utility of using ABMs like ArchMatNet to test the assumptions behind archaeological network inference.

5.2.1 ArchMatNet

The ArchMatNet model provided a robust experimental tool for assessing how well material culture networks can reflect social interaction under controlled conditions. One of the most important takeaways is that material culture networks can perform well when traits are sufficiently variable and transmission is structured by both prestige and conformity. But when those conditions are not met, material culture networks can become unreliable or misleading.

One consistent finding was that material culture networks tend to overemphasize weak ties while slightly dampening strong ones. This smoothing effect should be kept in mind when interpreting archaeological similarity networks.

ArchMatNet also showed that different classes of material culture can generate different network structures—an observation echoed by only a few archaeological studies (c.f., B. J. Mills, M. A. Peeples, et al. 2015; Giomi 2022; Upton 2019). These differences are important. If we interpret network structure without accounting for material-specific dynamics, we risk mischaracterizing the social phenomena we hope to understand.

Trait visibility also proved important to the model. Highly visible traits were designed to be more likely to be copied and dispersed, while low-visibility traits were less likely to be copied. This aligns with the theoretical model discussed in Chapter 1, in which high-visibility traits relate to categorical identity—used to signal group affiliation—while low-visibility traits reflect relational identity, grounded in close, often face-to-face interaction.

The visibility parameter in ArchMatNet confirmed that this parameter has a strong outcome on the model results, although the precise effects require further study.

5.2.2 Central U.S. Southwest

Chapters 3, 4, and the synthesis presented here draw on datasets from the central U.S. Southwest to evaluate how well material culture networks align with known patterns of social interaction. These results generally support the findings from ArchMatNet: while material culture can signal interaction, results vary depending on the material type and social context.

The network analysis in Chapter 3 was limited in scope, but the more extensive analyses in Chapters 4 and 5 show that material culture networks can capture known processes, such as the Kayenta migrations into the Tonto Basin. Importantly, these analyses also reinforce the ArchMatNet finding that different artifact classes—ceramics and projectile points, in this case—generate different network structures.

This difference may reflect distinct social processes. Ceramics tend to be more localized and stylistically constrained, allowing clearer inferences about group identity and affiliation. Projectile points, on the other hand, are often distributed across broader regions and may not vary enough to track local social dynamics, especially when starting traits are homogeneous. In such cases, as shown in ArchMatNet, the resulting networks are weak proxies for social interaction.

Even so, broad patterns—such as regional connectivity during periods of migration and aggregation, such as the periods studied here, are well represented in the material culture networks. These patterns reinforce long-standing interpretations of regional social organization while offering new ways to quantify and model them. Moreover, the new projectile

point typology developed in this study highlights the value of analyzing multiple types of material culture to capture different dimensions of interaction.

5.3 Computational Archaeology

This dissertation draws on a number of computational methods—including agent-based modeling, network analysis, geometric morphometrics, GIS, and machine learning—to address a central question in archaeology: how do patterns in material culture reflect underlying patterns of social interaction?

These methods were not chosen for novelty's sake, but because each provided the most appropriate framework for a specific part of the research. When used in concert, these approaches allowed for a more comprehensive and theoretically grounded understanding of the material and social processes at play. Each comes with its own strengths and weaknesses, and this dissertation demonstrates that combining multiple methods can help balance those trade-offs.

The agent-based model was arguably the most powerful tool in this project. It allowed for systematic testing of specific variables—learning mechanisms, visibility, population structure—while holding other factors constant. This level of control is impossible in real-world archaeological settings. However, like any model, it is limited by its assumptions. It cannot replicate past societies, but it can reveal the conditions under which archaeological proxies are more or less reliable.

Geometric morphometric (GMM) analysis proved valuable but also revealed its limits—particularly for classifying projectile points. Chapter 3 showed that GMM is most effective for understanding variation within a type rather than distinguishing between types. Projectile points exist on a continuous morphometric spectrum, and without considering categori-

cal attributes, GMM alone is insufficient for typology construction. That said, it was useful for identifying consistent shape clusters and for quantifying variation in a replicable way for constructing the typology used here.

Machine learning, by contrast, showed greater promise for classification once a reliable training dataset was created. Its strength lies in scalability and consistency, and when paired with a well-constructed typology, it can be a powerful tool for archaeological classification. Unlike GMM, machine learning can incorporate both geometric and categorical variables, offering a hybrid approach that builds on the strengths of each.

Together, these computational approaches provided a diverse toolkit for addressing a longstanding archaeological problem. More importantly, they offered new ways to evaluate assumptions, test models, and refine interpretations.

5.4 Conclusion

This dissertation set out to examine the relationship between material culture and social networks. While this is a common assumption in archaeological network studies, it has rarely been tested in a systematic way (c.f., Golitko 2023). The goal here was to move beyond assumption and evaluate the conditions under which material culture can serve as a reasonable proxy for social ties.

I used a combination of agent-based modeling, geometric morphometrics, machine learning, and multilayer network analysis to address this question and build my dataset. The ArchMatNet model, introduced in Chapter 2, allowed for controlled testing of these relationships. The model showed that material culture networks can approximate interaction networks, but only under specific conditions—particularly when traits vary significantly between groups. Importantly, material culture tends to have a smoothing effect: strong

ties are weaker, but weak interactions are over-emphasized in the material culture networks. This should serve as a caution for archaeological interpretations based solely on artifact similarity.

In Chapter 3, I developed a regional projectile point dataset and showed that geometric morphometrics, combined with machine learning, can replicate and improve on traditional typologies. The new typology—developed for this research project, not for general usage—was based on measurable attributes and reduces subjectivity. It also allows for scalable classification across large datasets. Additionally, the methods are not restricted to the Southwest but are adaptable to other areas.

Chapter 4 integrated ceramics, architecture, and projectile points into a multilayer network analysis focused on Tonto Basin. The different material categories produced distinct network structures, which likely reflect different aspects of social life. Ceramic and architectural patterns—being more visible and often tied to group-level identities—appear to represent categorical connections. In contrast, projectile points showed more variation at the individual or household level and likely reflect relational identities tied to learning and craft practice. These differences may also correspond to gendered social roles, with ceramics more associated with women and projectile points with men.

Taken together, the results across these chapters show that material culture networks can be useful proxies for social networks, but only if we're careful about the assumptions we bring to the analysis. Visibility, trait variation, and modes of learning all affect how well material patterns track with interaction. The findings here point to the value of using multiple proxies, evaluating each on its own terms, and avoiding overconfidence in neat, symmetrical network structures.

Ultimately, this dissertation contributes a framework for evaluating how material culture relates to social processes and how different lines of evidence can be used to model inter-

action at multiple scales. The methods presented here are transferable to other datasets and regions, but future work will need to account for regional variation and continue refining the link between material and social networks. Material culture is not a perfect mirror of past social life, but under the right conditions, it can reflect it in meaningful and interpretable ways.

References

- Collar, Anna et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Networks in Archaeology: Phenomena, Abstraction, Representation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 1–32. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6>.
- Giomi, Evan (2022). *Exploring the development and persistence of the Eastern Puebloan economy: Rio Grande glaze ware as a window on regional interaction*. URL: https://repository.arizona.edu/bitstream/handle/10150/663236/azu_etd_19397_sip1_m.pdf?sequence=1 (visited on 10/03/2022).
- Golitko, Mark (Dec. 1, 2023). “A performance test of archaeological similarity-based network inference using New Guinean ethnographic data”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 72, p. 101550. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2023.101550. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416523000661>.
- Holly, Lance Ebbert (2010). “Beyond the Point: Arrow Shaft Technology of the Prehistoric Southwest”. Master’s thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Colorado, Boulder.
- Justice, Noel D (2002b). *Stone Age Spear and Arrow Points of the Southwestern United States*. en. Bloomington, Indiana: Indiana University Press. 456 pp. ISBN: 9780253108821. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=xlFpi41dH_MC.
- Mills, Barbara J, Matthew A Peeples, et al. (Jan. 2015). “Multiscalar Perspectives on Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic Southwest”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 80 (1), pp. 3–24. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.7183/0002-7316.79.4.3. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/>

multiscalar - perspectives - on - social - networks - in - the - late - prehispanic - southwest/
B40CF133F9E61102185B25AD4DF0FE30.

Perreault, Charles (2019). *The Quality of the Archaeological Record*. en. University of Chicago Press. 280 pp. ISBN: 9780226631011. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=TwyiDwAAQBAJ>.

Rudy, Jack R (1953). *Archeological Survey of Western Utah*. Anthropological Papers No. 12. Salt Lake City, Utah: University of Utah Press.

Sinopoli, Carla (1991). "Style in Arrow: A Study of an Ethnographic Collection from the Western United States". In: *Foragers in Context: Long-term, Regional and Historical Perspectives in Hunter-gatherer Studies*. Ed. by Preston T Miracle, Lynn E Fisher, and Jody Brown. Michigan Discussions in Anthropology, v. 10. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, pp. 63–87.

Upton, Andrew James (2019). "Multilayer Network Relationships and Culture Contact in Mississippian West-central Illinois, A.D. 1200 - 1450". PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Michigan State University, East Lansing.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, David R, Scott E Ingram, and Brent G Kober (Jan. 2006). "Hohokam Exchange and Early Classic Period Organization in Central Arizona: Focal Villages or Linear Communities?" In: *Journal of Field Archaeology* 31 (3), pp. 285–305. ISSN: 0093-4690. DOI: 10.1179/009346906791071909. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346906791071909>.
- Adams, Dean C, F James Rohlf, and Dennis E Slice (2013). "A Field Comes of Age: Geometric Morphometrics in the 21st Century". en. In: *Hystrix, the Italian Journal of Mammalogy* 24 (1), pp. 7–14. ISSN: 0394-1914,1825-5272. DOI: 10.4404/hystrix-24.1-6283. URL: <http://www.italian-journal-of-mammalogy.it/A-field-comes-of-age-geometric-morphometrics-in-the-21st-century,77238,0,2.html>.
- Adams, E C (1994). "The Katsina Cult: A Western Pueblo Perspective". In: *Kachinas in the Pueblo World*. Ed. by Polly Schaafsma. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, pp. 35–46.
- Adams, E Charles, Miriam T Stark, and Deborah S Dosh (Jan. 1, 1993). "Ceramic Distribution and Exchange: Jeddito Yellow Ware and Implications for Social Complexity". In: *Journal of Field Archaeology* 20 (1), pp. 3–21. ISSN: 0093-4690. DOI: 10.1179/009346993791974325. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346993791974325>.
- Adler, Michael A and Richard H Wilshusen (1990). "Large-Scale Integrative Facilities in Tribal Societies: Cross-Cultural and Southwestern U.S. Examples". In: *World archaeology* 22 (2), pp. 133–144. ISSN: 0043-8243.
- Ahlstrom, Richard V N, Mark L Chenault, and Kirk C Anderson (1991). *The Roosevelt Bajada Survey, Tonto Basin, Gila County, Arizona*. Report No. 91-24. Tucson: SWCA, Inc. Environmental Consultants.
- Amati, Viviana et al. (June 19, 2020). "A Framework for Reconstructing Archaeological Networks Using Exponential Random Graph Models". In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 27 (2), pp. 192–219. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-019-09423-z. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10816-019-09423-z>.
- Anderson, David G et al. (2010). "PIDBA (Paleoindian Database of the Americas) 2010: Current Status and Findings". en. In: *Archaeology of Eastern North America* 38, pp. 63–90.

- Archer, W et al. (2015). “Diachronic change within the Still Bay at Blombos Cave, South Africa”. In: *PloS one* 10 (7). ISSN: 1932-6203. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0132428. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84940055265&doi=10.1371%2fjournal.pone.0132428&partnerID=40&md5=dabc86459d030dfbe5f1fa4a7e589146>.
- Azevedo, Soledad de, Judith Charlin, and Rolando González-José (2014). “Identifying design and reduction effects on lithic projectile point shapes”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 41, pp. 297–307. ISSN: 0305-4403,1095-9238. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.08.013. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2013.08.013>.
- Bahr, Donald M (2011). *Culture summary: O’odham*. English. New Haven, Conn. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-000>.
- Bamforth, Douglas B (1991). “Flintknapping Skill, Communal Hunting and Paleoindian Projectile Point Typology”. en. In: *Plains Anthropologist* 36, pp. 309–322. ISSN: 0032-0447.
- Barton, C Michael (1988). *Lithic Variability and Middle Paleolithic Behavior: new evidence from the Iberian Peninsula*. Oxford: BAR.
- Barton, C Michael and Julien Riel-Salvatore (June 1, 2014). “The Formation of Lithic Assemblages”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 46, pp. 334–352. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2014.03.031. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440314001204>.
- Barton, C Michael, Julien Riel-Salvatore, et al. (Dec. 1, 2011). “Modeling Human Ecodynamics and Biocultural Interactions in the Late Pleistocene of Western Eurasia”. In: *Human Ecology* 39 (6), pp. 705–725. ISSN: 0046-8169,1572-9915. DOI: 10.1007/s10745-011-9433-8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-011-9433-8>.
- Bayman, James (2007). “Artisans and their Crafts in Hohokam Society”. In: *The Hohokam Millenium*. Ed. by Suzanne K Fish and Paul R Fish. Santa Fe, N.M.: School for Advanced Research Press, pp. 74–81. ISBN: 9781930618800.
- Beaglehole, Ernest (1936). *Hopi Hunting and Hopi Ritual*. en. Yale University Publication in Anthropology No. 4. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Bernardini, Wesley (2005). *Hopi Oral Tradition and the Archaeology of Identity*. English. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816524266.

- Bernardini, Wesley et al. (2021). “Reconstructing Population in the Context of Migration”. en. In: *Becoming Hopi: A History*. Ed. by Wesley Bernardini et al. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Bickler, Simon H (May 2021). “Machine learning arrives in archaeology”. en. In: *Advances in archaeological practice* 9 (2), pp. 186–191. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.1017/aap.2021.6. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/418D14FD3BAA55A550D61D710A9A8CE0/S2326376821000061a.pdf/div-class-title-machine-learning-arrives-in-archaeology-div.pdf> (visited on 09/27/2024).
- Birch, Jennifer and John P Hart (Jan. 2018). “Social Networks and Northern Iroquoian Confederacy Dynamics”. In: *American Antiquity* 83 (1), pp. 13–33. ISSN: 0002-7316. DOI: 10.1017/aaq.2017.59. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0002731617000592/type/journal_article.
- Bischoff, Robert J (2017). *A Spatial Analysis of San Juan Red Ware: Evaluating Fall-off Curves with Straight-line or Least Cost Path Distance. Poster presented at the 82nd Annual Meeting of the Society for American Archaeology, Vancouver, BC. March 31, 2017.*
- (2018). *A Temporal and Spatial Analysis of San Juan Red Ware. Master’s thesis, Department of Anthropology, Brigham Young University, Provo, Utah.* URL: <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/etd/7003/>.
- (2023a). “Geometric Morphometric Analysis of Projectile Points from the Southwest United States”. In: *Peer Community Journal* 3 (e80). DOI: 10.24072/pcjournal.312. URL: <https://peercommunityjournal.org/articles/10.24072/pcjournal.312/>.
- (Aug. 16, 2023b). “Investigating Material Culture Through Multilayer Network Analysis in Tonto Basin”. In: *KIVA* 89 (3), pp. 247–273. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137>.
- Bischoff, Robert J and James R Allison (2020). “Rosegate Projectile Points in the Fremont Region”. In: *Utah Archaeology* 33 (1), pp. 7–48. DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/dwrba. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/dwrba>.
- Bischoff, Robert J and Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias (July 10, 2023). “A description and sensitivity analysis of the ArchMatNet agent-based model”. en. In: *PeerJ Computer Science* 9, e1419. ISSN: 2376-5992. DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.1419. URL: <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-1419/> (visited on 07/24/2023).

- Bischoff, Robert J, Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias, and Claudine Gravel-Miguel (2021). *Evaluating the Effects of Randomness on Missing Data in Archaeological Networks*. Paper presented at the *Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology Conference, Cyprus (virtual)*. June 16th, 2021.
- (2024). “Evaluating the Effects of Randomness on Missing Data in Archaeological Networks”. In: *Accepted to CAA 2021 Conference: Limassol, Cyprus*. DOI: 10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/vdy9b>.
- Blondel, Vincent D et al. (Oct. 9, 2008). “Fast Unfolding of Communities in Large Networks”. In: *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment* 2008 (10), P10008. ISSN: 1742-5468. DOI: 10.1088/1742-5468/2008/10/P10008.
- Bolland, John M (Sept. 1, 1988). “Sorting out centrality: An analysis of the performance of four centrality models in real and simulated networks”. In: *Social Networks* 10 (3), pp. 233–253. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/0378-8733(88)90014-7. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378873388900147>.
- Bonhomme, Vincent, Laurent Bouby, et al. (Sept. 15, 2023). “Deep learning *versus* geometric morphometrics for archaeobotanical domestication study and subspecific identification”. In: *bioRxiv*. DOI: 10.1101/2023.09.15.557939. URL: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.09.15.557939.abstract>.
- Bonhomme, Vincent, Sandrine Picq, et al. (2014). “Momocs: Outline Analysis Using R”. In: *Journal of Statistical Software, Articles* 56 (13), pp. 1–24. ISSN: 1548-7660. DOI: 10.18637/jss.v056.i13. URL: <https://www.jstatsoft.org/v056/i13>.
- Bookstein, F L (1997). “Landmark Methods for Forms without Landmarks: Morphometrics of Group Differences in Outline Shape”. en. In: *Medical Image Analysis* 1 (3), pp. 225–243. ISSN: 1361-8415. DOI: 10.1016/s1361-8415(97)85012-8. URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1361-8415\(97\)85012-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1361-8415(97)85012-8).
- Bookstein, Fred L (1991). *Morphometric Tools for Landmark Data: Geometry and Biology*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Borck, Lewis et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Are Social Networks Survival Networks? An Example from the Late Pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 33–57. ISSN: 1573-7764,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9236-5>.

- Borgatti, Stephen P (2005). “Centrality and Network Flow”. In: *Social Networks* 27 (1), pp. 55–71. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2004.11.008. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873304000693>.
- Borgatti, Stephen P, Kathleen M Carley, and David Krackhardt (May 1, 2006). “On the robustness of centrality measures under conditions of imperfect data”. In: *Social networks* 28 (2), pp. 124–136. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2005.05.001. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873305000353>.
- Brandes, Ulrik et al. (Apr. 2013). “What is Network Science?” In: *Network Science* 1 (1), pp. 1–15. ISSN: 2050-1242,2050-1250. DOI: 10.1017/nws.2013.2. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/network-science/article/what-is-network-science/C0794B28C613757F09C3FB315500E3A1>.
- Brantingham, P Jeffrey (2003). “A Neutral Model of Stone Raw Material Procurement”. In: *American Anthropologist* 68 (3), pp. 487–509.
- Bretzke, Knut and Nicholas J Conard (Dec. 2012). “Evaluating morphological variability in lithic assemblages using 3D models of stone artifacts”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 39 (12), pp. 3741–3749. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2012.06.039. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440312003068>.
- Bródka, Piotr et al. (2018). “Quantifying Layer Similarity in Multiplex Networks: a Systematic Study”. en. In: *Royal Society Open Science* 5 (8), p. 171747. ISSN: 2054-5703. DOI: 10.1098/rsos.171747. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171747>.
- Broodbank, Cyprian (2000). *An Island Archaeology of the Early Cyclades*. en. Cambridge University Press. 436 pp. ISBN: 9780521528443. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=qbYiW13TJ6UC>.
- Brubaker, Rogers and Frederick Cooper (2000). “Beyond” identity””. In: *Theory and Society* 29 (1), pp. 1–47. ISSN: 0304-2421,1573-7853. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3108478>.
- Brughmans, T and U Brandes (2017). “Visibility Network Patterns and Methods for Studying Visual Relational Phenomena in Archeology”. In: *Frontiers in Digital Humanities* 4.
- Brughmans, Tom, Simon Keay, and Graeme Earl (Sept. 2014). “Introducing exponential random graph models for visibility networks”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 49, pp. 442–454. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2014.05.027. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440314002052>.

- Brughmans, Tom and Matt Peeples (Oct. 14, 2017). “Trends in Archaeological Network Research: A Bibliometric Analysis”. en. In: *Journal of Historical Network Research* 1 (1), pp. 1–24. ISSN: 2535-8863,2535-8863. DOI: 10.25517/jhnr.v1i1.10. URL: <https://jhnr.uni.lu/index.php/jhnr/article/view/10>.
- Brughmans, Tom and Matthew A Peeples (2023). *Network Science in Archaeology*. Cambridge Manuals in Archaeology. Cambridge University Press.
- Brughmans, Tom and Jeroen Poblome (Apr. 2016). “Roman bazaar or market economy? Explaining tableware distributions through computational modelling”. In: *Antiquity* 90 (350), pp. 393–408. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.15184/aqy.2016.35. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/roman-bazaar-or-market-economy-explaining-tableware-distributions-through-computational-modelling/6C64CA37C247869A21A6DE6CE18F55FD> (visited on 09/09/2019).
- Buchanan, Briggs and Mark Collard (Feb. 1, 2010). “A Geometric Morphometrics-Based Assessment of Blade Shape Differences among Paleoindian Projectile Point Types from Western North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 37 (2), pp. 350–359. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2009.09.047. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440309003537>.
- Buchanan, Briggs, Metin I Eren, and Michael J O’Brien (2018). “Assessing the Likelihood of Convergence among North American Projectile-Point Types”. In: *Convergent Evolution in Stone-Tool Technology*. Ed. by Michael J O’Brien, Briggs Buchanan, and Metin I Eren. The MIT Press, pp. 275–287. ISBN: 9780262346160. DOI: 10.7551/mitpress/11554.001.0001. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11554.001.0001>.
- Butts, Carter T (2023). *sna: Tools for Social Network Analysis*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=sna>.
- Calder, Jeff et al. (2022). “Use and misuse of machine learning in anthropology”. en. In: *IEEE BITS the Information Theory Magazine* 2 (1), pp. 1–13. ISSN: 2692-4110,2692-4080. DOI: 10.1109/mbits.2022.3205143. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9888777> (visited on 09/25/2024).
- Calhoun, Craig J (Jan. 1995). *Critical Social Theory: Culture, History, and the Challenge of Difference*. en. Blackwell. 326 pp. ISBN: 9781557861382. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=_WgDnwEACAAJ.
- (1997). *Nationalism*. Concepts in social thought. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press. 120 pp. ISBN: 9780816631209.

- Cameron, Catherine M (2001). “Pink Chert, Projectile Points, and the Chacoan Regional System”. In: *American Antiquity* 66 (1), pp. 79–102. ISSN: 0002-7316.
- Cameron, Catherine M and Andrew I Duff (Jan. 2008). “History and Process in Village Formation: Context and Contrasts from the Northern Southwest”. en. In: *American antiquity* 73 (1), pp. 29–58. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.1017/S0002731600041275. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/history-and-process-in-village-formation-context-and-contrasts-from-the-northern-southwest/07B0297E01B27320A8C786BC98A8BC1E>.
- Carr, Christopher (1995a). “A Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Carr C. and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 171–258. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- (1995b). “Building a Unified Middle-Range Theory of Artifact Design”. In: *Style, Society, and Person*. Ed. by Christopher Carr and J E Neitzel. Interdisciplinary Contributions to Archaeology. Boston: Springer, pp. 151–170. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6. URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-1097-4_6.
- Caseldine, Christopher R (Jan. 2, 2022). “Least Cost Paths and Movement in Tonto Basin, Central Arizona”. In: *The KIVA* 88 (1), pp. 112–141. ISSN: 0023-1940. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.2021.1996517. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2021.1996517>.
- Castetter, Edward Franklin and Ruth Murray Underhill (1935). *The ethnobiology of the Papago Indians*. en. Vol. 4. Ethnobiological studies in the American Southwest No. 3. Albuquerque: The University of New Mexico press. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-017> (visited on 12/28/2022).
- Castillo Flores, Fernando et al. (June 13, 2019). “Computer Algorithm for Archaeological Projectile Points Automatic Classification”. en. In: *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)* 12 (3), p. 19. ISSN: 1556-4673. DOI: 10.1145/3300972. URL: <https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?doid=3340676.3300972> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Cegielski, W H (2024). “Networks, Agent-Based Modeling, and Archaeology”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Tom Brughmans et al. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press, pp. 280–293.
- Charlin, Judith and Rolando González-José (Apr. 2012). “Size and Shape Variation in Late Holocene Projectile Points of Southern Patagonia: A Geometric Morphometric Study”. In: *American Antiquity* 77 (2), pp. 221–242. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.1017/S0002-7316.77.2.221. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/>

journals / american - antiquity / article / size - and - shape - variation - in - late - holocene - projectile - points - of - southern - patagonia - a - geometric - morphometric - study / A7922E0F1588F8F9800C8097E7CAC4F9.

Chona, Maria (1936). *Autobiography of a Papago Woman*. English. Ed. by Ruth Underhill. Menasha: American Anthropological Association, pp. ii, 64. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-003>.

Chudek, Maciej et al. (Jan. 1, 2012). “Prestige-biased cultural learning: bystander’s differential attention to potential models influences children’s learning”. en. In: *Evolution and human behavior: official journal of the Human Behavior and Evolution Society* 33 (1), pp. 46–56. ISSN: 1090-5138,1879-0607. DOI: 10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2011.05.005. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2011.05.005> (visited on 09/16/2024).

Ciolek-Torrello, Richard, Steven D Shelley, and Su Benaron (1994). *The Roosevelt Rural Sites Study: Prehistoric Rural Settlements in the Tonto Basin*. en. Tucson: Statistical Research, Inc.

Clark, Geoffrey A and Julien Riel-Salvatore (2006). “Observations on Systematics in Paleolithic Archaeology”. In: *Transitions Before the Transition*. Ed. by Erella Hovers and Steven Kuh. Boston, MA: Springer US, pp. 29–56. ISBN: 9780387246581. DOI: 10.1007/0-387-24661-4_3. URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/0-387-24661-4_3.

Clark, Jeffery J (2001). *Tracking Prehistoric Migrations: Pueblo Settlers Among the Tonto Basin Hohokam*. en. Vol. 65. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. 124 pp. ISBN: 9780816520879. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=27Tk3xNT-6UC>.

Clark, Jeffery J, Jennifer A Birch, et al. (Mar. 1, 2019). “Resolving the Migrant Paradox: Two Pathways to Coalescence in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 53, pp. 262–287. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2018.09.004. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416518300801>.

Clark, Jeffery J and Christopher R Caseldine (2021). *Research Design for Late Pre-Hispanic Backcountry Sites on Tonto National Monument: Contextualizing the Monument in Tonto Basin and Beyond*. Vol. Technical Report No. 2021-101. Tucson: Archaeology Southwest.

Clark, Jeffery J, Deborah L Huntley, et al. (2013). “The Kayenta Diaspora and Salado Meta-Identity in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Hybrid Material Culture: The Archaeology of Syncretism and Ethnogenesis*. Ed. by Jeb Card. Center for Archaeologi-

cal Investigations Occasional Paper No. 39. Carbondale: SIU Press, pp. 399–424. DOI: 10.1007/9780809333165. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/9780809333165>.

Clark, Jeffery J and Patrick D Lyons, eds. (2012). *Migrants and mounds: classic period archaeology of the Lower San Pedro Valley*. Tucson: Archaeology Southwest.

Clark, Jeffery J, Patrick D Lyons, et al. (2008). “Immigrants and Population Collapse in the Southern Southwest”. In: *Archaeology Southwest* 22 (4).

Clark, Jeffrey J and James M Vint, eds. (2004). *2000 Years of Settlement in the Tonto Basin: Overview and Synthesis of the Tonto Creek Archaeological Project*. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology.

Cochrane, Ethan E and Carl P Lipo (Dec. 12, 2010). “Phylogenetic analyses of Lapita decoration do not support branching evolution or regional population structure during colonization of Remote Oceania”. en. In: *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences* 365 (1559), pp. 3889–3902. ISSN: 0962-8436,1471-2970. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2010.0091. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0091>.

Collar, Anna (Dec. 12, 2013). *Religious Networks in the Roman Empire: The Spread of New Ideas*. en. Cambridge University Press. 312 pp. ISBN: 9781107729711. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Av5GAgAAQBAJ>.

Collar, Anna et al. (Mar. 1, 2015). “Networks in Archaeology: Phenomena, Abstraction, Representation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 1–32. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9235-6>.

Corti, M (1993). “Geometric Morphometrics: An Extension of the Revolution”. en. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 8 (8), pp. 302–303. ISSN: 0169-5347. DOI: 10.1016/0169-5347(93)90261-M. URL: [https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0169-5347\(93\)90261-M](https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0169-5347(93)90261-M).

Costenbader, Elizabeth and Thomas W Valente (Oct. 1, 2003). “The stability of centrality measures when networks are sampled”. In: *Social networks* 25 (4), pp. 283–307. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/S0378-8733(03)00012-1. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378873303000121>.

Courtenay, Lloyd A et al. (Dec. 23, 2019). “A hybrid Geometric Morphometric deep learning approach for cut and trampling Mark classification”. In: *Applied sciences (Basel,*

Switzerland). ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app10010150. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/1/150>.

Crabtree, Stefani A (Mar. 2015). “Inferring Ancestral Pueblo Social Networks from Simulation in the Central Mesa Verde”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 144–181. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9233-8. URL: <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10816-014-9233-8>.

Craig, Douglas B (1995). “The Social Consequences of Irrigation Agriculture: A Perspective from Meddler Point”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory*. Ed. by M D Elson, M T Stark, and D A Gregory. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 227–249.

Craig, Douglas B and Jeffery J Clark (1994). “The Meddler Point Site, AZ V:5:4/26 (AS-M/TNF)”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: Vol. 2. Meddler Point, Pyramid Point, and Griffin Wash Sites*. Ed. by M D Elson et al. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 13. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 1–198.

Craig, Douglas B and M Kyle Woodson (2017). “Preclassic Hohokam”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Southwest Archaeology*. Ed. by Barbara J Mills and Severin M Fowles. Oxford University Press, pp. 323–351.

Creanza, Nicole, Oren Kolodny, and Marcus W Feldman (May 2017). “Greater than the Sum of Its Parts? Modelling Population Contact and Interaction of Cultural Repertoires”. en. In: *Journal of the Royal Society, Interface / the Royal Society* 14 (130), p. 20170171. ISSN: 1742-5689,1742-5662. DOI: 10.1098/rsif.2017.0171. URL: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsif.2017.0171>.

Crown, Patricia L (1994). *Ceramics and Ideology: Salado Polychrome Pottery*. English. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press. ISBN: 9780826314772.

Crown, Patricia L and Suzanne K Fish (1996). “Gender and Status in the Hohokam Preclassic to Classic Transition”. In: *American anthropologist* 98 (4), pp. 803–817. ISSN: 0002-7294.

Cushing, Frank Hamilton (1883). “Zuni Fetishes”. In: *Second Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1880–1881*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, DC: US Government Printing Office, pp. 9–50.

Dean, Jeffrey S (2000). *Salado*. Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation, Dragoon, Arizona and University of New Mexico Press, pp. 3–16.

- Dean, Jeffrey S (2010). “The Environmental, Demographic, and Behavioral Context of the Thirteenth-Century Depopulation of the Northern Southwest”. In: *Leaving Mesa Verde: Peril and Change in the Thirteenth-Century Southwest*, pp. 324–345.
- Dietler, Michael and Ingrid Herbich (1998). “Habitus, Techniques, Style: An Integrated Approach to the Social Understanding of Material Culture and Boundaries”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution, pp. 232–263.
- Dittert, Alfred E (1959). “Culture Change in the Cebolleta Mesa Region Central Western New Mexico”. PhD thesis. Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson, Arizona.
- Doelle, William H, David A Gregory, and Henry D Wallace (1995). “Classic Period Platform Mound Systems in Southern Arizona”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory*. Ed. by M D Elson, M T Stark, and D A Gregory. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 385–440.
- Doelle, William H, Henry D Wallace, et al. (1992). *Research Design for the Roosevelt Community Development Study*. Vol. Anthropological Papers ,12. Tucson, Arizona: Center for Desert Archaeology.
- Drennan, Robert D (Mar. 1984). “Long-distance transport costs in pre-Hispanic Mesoamerica”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 86 (1), pp. 105–112. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00100>.
- Duff, Andrew I (2000). “Scale, Interaction, and Regional Analysis in Late Pueblo Prehistory”. English. In: *The Archaeology of Regional Interaction: Religion, Warfare, and Exchange across the American Southwest and Beyond*. Ed. by Michelle Hegmon. University Press of Colorado, pp. 71–98. ISBN: 9780870819049.
- (2002). *Western Pueblo Identities; Region Interaction, Migration, and Transformation*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- (2004). “Settlement Clustering and Village Interaction in the Upper Little Colorado Region”. In: *The Protohistoric Pueblo World, AD 1275*. Ed. by E Charles Adams and Andrew I Duff. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, pp. 75–84.
- Elliot, Tom et al. (May 13, 2021). “Evaluating machine learning techniques for archaeological lithic sourcing: a case study of flint in Britain”. en. In: *Scientific reports* 11 (1),

p. 10197. ISSN: 2045-2322. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-87834-3. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-87834-3>.

Ellis, Christopher J (1997). “Factors Influencing the Use of Stone Projectile Tips: An Ethnographic Perspective”. In: *Projectile Technology*. Ed. by Heidi Knecht. New York: Plenum Press, pp. 37–74.

Elson, Mark D (Jan. 1996). “A revised chronology and phase sequence for the lower Tonto Basin of central Arizona”. In: *The KIVA* 62 (2), pp. 117–147. ISSN: 0023-1940,2051-6177. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328. URL: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00231940.1996.11758328>.

Elson, Mark D, David A Gregory, and Miriam T Stark (1995). *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: New Perspectives on Tonto Basin Prehistory*. en. Anthropological Papers No. 15. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology.

Elson, Mark D and Michael Lindeman (1994). “The Eagle Ridge Site, AZ V:5:104/1045 (ASM/TNF)”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study: Vol. 1. Introduction and Small Sites*. Ed. by M D Elson and D L Swartz. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 13. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 23–116.

Elson, Mark D, Miriam T Stark, and David A Gregory (2000). “Tonto Basin Local Systems: Implications for Cultural Affiliation and Migration”. en. In: *Salado*. Ed. by J S Dean. Dragoon, Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation Publication, Dragoon, Arizona. University of New Mexico Press, pp. 167–192 4.

Epstein, Joshua M (2006). *Generative Social Science: Studies in Agent-Based Computational Modeling*. en. Princeton University Press. 356 pp. ISBN: 9780691125473. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=T8_zh3F7rMIC.

Feinman, Gary M and Jill E Neitzel (Dec. 1, 2020). “Excising Culture History from Contemporary Archaeology”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 60, p. 101230. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101230. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416520302038>.

Fewkes, Jesse Walter (1898). *Archaeological Expedition to Arizona in 1895*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution.

Fraser, D (1980). “The Cutpoint Index: A Simple Measure of Point Connectivity”. In: *Area* 12 (1), pp. 301–304.

- Frost, Robert H (May 3, 2022). “Eigenvector centrality for multilayer networks with dependent node importance”. In: *ArXiv*, pp. 1–9. ArXiv: 2205.01478 (physics.soc-ph). URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01478>.
- Galaskiewicz, Joseph (Dec. 1, 1991). “Estimating point centrality using different network sampling techniques”. In: *Social networks* 13 (4), pp. 347–386. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/0378-8733(91)90002-B. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/037887339190002B>.
- Gardner, W M and R A Verrey (1979). “Typology and Chronology of Fluted Points from the Flint Run Area”. en. In: *Pennsylvania Archaeologist* 49, pp. 13–45. ISSN: 0031-4358.
- Gauthier, Nicolas (Jan. 29, 2021). “Hydroclimate Variability Influenced Social Interaction in the Prehistoric American Southwest”. In: *Frontiers in Earth Science* 8. ISSN: 2296-6463. DOI: 10.3389/feart.2020.62085610.3389/feart.2020.620856.s00110.3389/feart.2020.620856.s002. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feart.2020.620856/full>.
- Giomi, Evan (2022). *Exploring the development and persistence of the Eastern Puebloan economy: Rio Grande glaze ware as a window on regional interaction*. URL: https://repository.arizona.edu/bitstream/handle/10150/663236/azu_etd_19397_sip1_m.pdf?sequence=1 (visited on 10/03/2022).
- Gjesfjeld, Erik (Mar. 1, 2015). “Network Analysis of Archaeological Data from Hunter-Gatherers: Methodological Problems and Potential Solutions”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (1), pp. 182–205. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9232-9>.
- Golitko, Mark (Dec. 1, 2023). “A performance test of archaeological similarity-based network inference using New Guinean ethnographic data”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 72, p. 101550. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2023.101550. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278416523000661>.
- Golitko, Mark and Gary M Feinman (Mar. 2015). “Procurement and distribution of pre-Hispanic Mesoamerican obsidian 900 BC–AD 1520: A social network analysis”. en. In: *Journal of archaeological method and theory* 22 (1), pp. 206–247. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9211-1. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10816-014-9211-1>.
- Golitko, Mark, James Meierhoff, et al. (June 2012). “Complexities of collapse: the evidence of Maya obsidian as revealed by social network graphical analysis”. en. In: *Antiquity* 86 (332), pp. 507–523. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/s0003598x00062906.

URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0003598X00062906/type/journal_article.

- Gosselain, Olivier P (1998). “Social and Technical Identity in a Clay Cristal Ball”. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam Stark. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 78–106.
- (Sept. 1, 2000). “Materializing Identities: An African Perspective”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 7 (3), pp. 187–217. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1023/A:1026558503986. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026558503986>.
- (2016). “The World is Like a Beanstalk: Historicizing Potting Practice and Social Relations in the Niger River Area”. en. In: *Knowledge in Motion: Constellations of Learning Across Time and Place*. Ed. by Andrew P Roddick and Ann B Stahl. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, pp. 36–66. ISBN: 9780816533749. URL: <https://muse.jhu.edu/book/44808> (visited on 03/11/2019).
- Gower, J C (Mar. 1, 1975). “Generalized Procrustes Analysis”. In: *Psychometrika* 40 (1), pp. 33–51. ISSN: 0033-3123,1860-0980. DOI: 10.1007/BF02291478. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02291478>.
- Gravel-Miguel, Claudine (2017). “The Impacts of Geography and Climate Change on Magdalenian Social Networks”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, School of Human Evolution and Social Change, Arizona State University, Tempe. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/2286/R.I.44052>.
- Gravel-Miguel, Claudine and Fiona Coward (2024). “Palaeolithic Social Networks and Behavioural Modernity”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Matthew A Peoples et al. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 443–458.
- Griffen, William B (Apr. 30, 1969). *Culture change and shifting populations in central northern Mexico*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona, no. 13. Tucson, AZ: University of Arizona Press. 208 pp. ISBN: 9780816501403. DOI: 10.2307/j.ctv1bxgw4f. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.2307/j.ctv1bxgw4f>.
- Hamilton, Marcus J, Briggs Buchanan, and Robert S Walker (Apr. 1, 2019). “Spatiotemporal Diversification of Projectile Point Types in Western North America over 13,000 Years”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 24, pp. 486–495. ISSN: 2352-409X. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2019.01.029. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352409X18305650>.

- Handcock, Mark S et al. (2018). *ergm: Fit, Simulate and Diagnose Exponential-Family Models for Networks*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ergm>.
- Harry, Karen G and Fred Huntington (2010). “Households, Gender, and Specialized Pottery Production: Exploring the Nature, Causes, and Consequences of a Prehistoric Cottage Industry for Women at the West Branch Settlement”. In: *Engendering households in the prehistoric southwest*. Ed. by B J Roth. University of Arizona Press, pp. 76–97.
- Hastie, T J and R J Tibshirani (1990). *Generalized additive models*. en. London: Chapman and Hall.
- He, Kaiming et al. (June 2016). “Deep residual learning for image recognition”. en. In: *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) (Las Vegas, NV, USA). IEEE, pp. 770–778. ISBN: 9781467388511. DOI: 10.1109/cvpr.2016.90. URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7780459> (visited on 09/30/2024).
- Hegmon, Michelle (Jan. 1, 1992). “Archaeological Research on Style”. In: *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21 (1), pp. 517–536. ISSN: 0084-6570. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.anthro.21.1.517. URL: https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev.an.21.100192.002505?casa_token=6qKr2S4fTBMAAAAA:WKU4gaCaBHKmkj-Kv2CAYnC0mbdzfIXxVG7XfIlho10RvGx23v8LM7uestyIFA-5JuHMqLAlJcZrFFA.
- ed. (2000). *The Archaeology of Regional Interaction: Religion, Warfare, and Exchange across the American Southwest and Beyond*. English. University Press of Colorado. ISBN: 9780870819049.
- Heidke, James M and Elizabeth J Miksa (2000). “Ceramic Temper Provenance Studies”. en. In: *Tonto Creek Archaeological Project: Artifact and Environmental Analyses*. Ed. by J M Vint and J M Heidke. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 95–146.
- Henrich, Joseph (2004). “Cultural Group Selection, Coevolutionary Processes and Large-Scale Cooperation”. en. In: *Journal of theoretical biology* 220 (4), pp. 577–590. ISSN: 0022-5193,1095-8541.
- Henrich, Joseph and Robert Boyd (July 1, 1998). “The Evolution of Conformist Transmission and the Emergence of Between-Group Differences”. In: *Evolution and Human Behavior* 19 (4), pp. 215–241. ISSN: 1090-5138. DOI: 10.1016/S1090-5138(98)00018-X. URL: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S109051389800018X?casa_token=X6ZIYQeGMRgAAAAA:pgCEIAE-46nIUh7IOg3TDAeZeZNf3XcKDVomg48JAt6LTIxnWOB1oSiaDN715wOxPflyBiA3.

- Henrich, Joseph and James Broesch (Apr. 12, 2011). “On the nature of cultural transmission networks: evidence from Fijian villages for adaptive learning biases”. en. In: *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological sciences* 366 (1567), pp. 1139–1148. ISSN: 0962-8436,1471-2970. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2010.0323. URL: https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/abs/10.1098/rstb.2010.0323?casa_token=RJ9t4MK7qKoAAAAA:Yc_yW5N5VKWDOMLfbz0-4EHP-a7G_CQP4xVgjLXPsQEKw8Zs52A_jdw8Y64QVW36GIq-zOzWSul&casa_token=tfIMRw4goysAAAAA:Mt44Db-HUAQHSEFywCi1Gj8qYjTPKAvV0T5RAVsW-A-OMG8Ha9-CNIy72dCBLvpR3ErGM05E1iGm.
- Henrich, Joseph and Richard McElreath (Jan. 2003). “The evolution of cultural evolution”. en. In: *Evolutionary anthropology* 12 (3), pp. 123–135. ISSN: 1060-1538,1520-6505. DOI: 10.1002/evan.10110. URL: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/evan.10110?casa_token=NxPG9otvpAoAAAAA:EuT8mLXtRkSdaHAHH1AMxamjjQG-HvNXOJxoEumyulsWlYA0yTFqvIWY0tG_Fw9N5te2Z7fGuq5fDQ.
- Hill, J Brett, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (2004). “Prehistoric Demography in the Southwest: Migration, Coalescence, and Hohokam Population Decline”. In: *American Antiquity* 69 (4), pp. 689–716. ISSN: 0002-7316. DOI: 10.2307/4128444. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4128444>.
- Hill, J Brett, Matthew A Peeples, et al. (Feb. 2015). “Spatializing Social Network Analysis in the Late Precontact U.S. Southwest”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 3 (1), pp. 63–77. DOI: 10.7183/2326-3768.3.1.63. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7183/2326-3768.3.1.63>.
- Hodder, Ian (1982). *Symbols in Action: Ethnoarchaeological Studies of Material Culture*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 9780521241762. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-TSE9AAAAIAAJ>.
- Hoffman, Charles Marshall (1985). “Projectile Point Maintenance and Typology: Assessment with Factor Analysis and Canonical Correlation”. In: *For Concordance in Archaeological Analysis: Bridging Data Structure, Quantitative Technique and Theory*. Ed. by Christopher Carr. Prospect Heights, Illinois: Waveland Press, pp. 566–612.
- (1997). “Alliance Formation and Social Interaction During the Sedentary Period: a Stylistic Analysis of Hohokam Arrowpoints”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, Tempe.
- Hoffman, Walter James (1896). “The Menomini Indians”. In: *The Fourteenth Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1892–1893 pt 1*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C.: Government Printing Office, pp. 11–338.

- Holland-Lulewicz, Jacob (Jan. 4, 2021). “From Categories to Connections in the Archaeology of Eastern North America”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research* 29, pp. 537–579. ISSN: 1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-020-09154-w>.
- Holly, Lance Ebbert (2010). “Beyond the Point: Arrow Shaft Technology of the Prehistoric Southwest”. Master’s thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Colorado, Boulder.
- Hotelling, Harold (Aug. 1931). “The generalization of student’s ratio”. In: *The annals of mathematical statistics* 2 (3), pp. 360–378. ISSN: 0003-4851,2168-8990. DOI: 10.1214/aoms/1177732979. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177732979>.
- Hruschka, Daniel J et al. (Jan. 30, 2022). “CatMapper: A user-friendly tool for integrating data across complex categories”. In: *SocArXiv Papers* 1. URL: <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/n6rty/>.
- Hunter, David R et al. (2008). “ergm: A Package to Fit, Simulate and Diagnose Exponential-Family Models for Networks”. In: *Journal of Statistical Software* 24 (3), pp. 1–29.
- Huntley, Deborah L (2008). *Ancestral Zuni Glaze-Decorated Pottery: Viewing Pueblo IV Regional Organization through Ceramic Production and Exchange*. Vol. No. 72. Anthropological Papers. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Jaccard, Paul (Feb. 1912). “The Distribution of the Flora in the Alpine Zone”. en. In: *The New Phytologist* 11 (2), pp. 37–50. ISSN: 0028-646X,1469-8137. DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.1912.tb05611.x. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1469-8137.1912.tb05611.x>.
- Jacobs, David, ed. (1997). *A Salado Platform Mound on Tonto Creek, Roosevelt Platform Mound*. Tempe, Arizona: Roosevelt Monograph Studies ,7. Tempe, Arizona: Department of.
- Jennewein, Douglas M et al. (Sept. 10, 2023). “The Sol Supercomputer at Arizona State University”. In: *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing* (Portland, OR, USA). PEARC ’23. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 296–301. ISBN: 9781450399852. DOI: 10.1145/3569951.3597573. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569951.3597573> (visited on 05/02/2024).
- Johnson, Ian (2011). “Heurist: a Web 2.0 Approach to Integrating Research, Teaching and Web Publishing”. In: *On the Road to Reconstructing the Past. Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. Proceedings of the 36th International Con-*

ference. *Budapest, April 2-6, 2008*. Ed. by E Jerem, F Redó, and V Szeverényi. Budapest: Archeaeolingua, pp. 93–99. URL: https://tobias-lib.ub.uni-tuebingen.de/xmlui/bitstream/handle/10900/60640/CD38_Johnson_CAA2008.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y.

Joseph, Alice, Rosamond B Spicer, and Jane Chesky (1949). “Desert people: a study of the Papago Indians”. English. In: *Indian education research series*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, xviii, 288, 21 plates. URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nu79-004>.

Justice, Noel D (Sept. 1, 1995). *Stone age spear and arrow points of the midcontinental and eastern United States*. Bloomington, MN: Indiana University Press. 304 pp. ISBN: 9780253209856.

— (2002a). *Stone Age Spear and Arrow Points of California and the Great Basin*. en. Kindle Edition. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.

— (2002b). *Stone Age Spear and Arrow Points of the Southwestern United States*. en. Bloomington, Indiana: Indiana University Press. 456 pp. ISBN: 9780253108821. URL: https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=xlFpi41dH_MC.

Justice, Noel D and Suzanne Kudlaty (Apr. 22, 2001). *Field guide to projectile points of the Midwest*. Bloomington, MN: Indiana University Press. 72 pp. ISBN: 9780253339317.

Kaldahl, Eric J (2000). “Late Prehistoric Technological and Social Reorganization Along the Mogollon Rim, Arizona”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson.

Kamp, Kathryn A, John C Whittaker, and William D Bryce (Oct. 1, 2016). “The Magician of Ridge Ruin: Insights into Ceremony and Status from Arrow Points and Bows”. In: *Lithic Technology* 41 (4), pp. 313–334. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2016.1252620. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2016.1252620>.

Kintigh, Keith W, Donna M Glowacki, and Deborah L Huntley (July 2004). “Long-Term Settlement History and the Emergence of Towns in the Zuni Area”. In: *American antiquity* 69 (3), pp. 432–456. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/4128401. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/longterm-settlement-history-and-the-emergence-of-towns-in-the-zuni-area/140EE169ED8BB7A0AE507BD9E974CD59> (visited on 09/12/2023).

- Kivelä, Mikko et al. (2014). “Multilayer Networks”. In: *Journal of Complex Networks* 2 (3), pp. 203–271. ISSN: 2051-1310. DOI: 10.1093/comnet/cnu016. URL: <https://academic.oup.com/comnet/article-abstract/2/3/203/2841130>.
- Konopka, Tomasz (2020). *umap: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection*. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=umap>.
- Krackardt, David (1987). “QAP Partialling as a Test of Spuriousness”. In: *Social Networks* 9 (2), pp. 171–186. ISSN: 0378-8733. DOI: 10.1016/0378 - 8733(87)90012 - 8. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0378873387900128>.
- Kuhl, Frank P and Charles R Giardina (1982). “Elliptic Fourier Features of a Closed Contour”. In: *Computer Graphics and Image Processing* 18, pp. 236–258.
- Lange, Richard C and Stephen Germick, eds. (1992). *Proceedings of the Second Salado Conference, Globe, Arizona, 1992*. en. Phoenix: Arizona Archaeological Society.
- Larick, R (1985). “Spears, Style, and Time among Maa-speaking Pastoralists”. en. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 4, pp. 206–220.
- Lave, Jean and Etienne Wenger (1991). *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. en. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 138 pp. ISBN: 9780521423748. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-CAVIOrW3vYAC>.
- Lechtman, Heather (1977). “Style in Technology, Some Early Thoughts”. In: *Material Culture: Style, Organization, and Dynamics of Technology*. Ed. by H Lechtman and R S Merrill. New York: West Publishing, pp. 3–20.
- Lee, S, S-H Yook, and Y Kim (Mar. 2009). “Centrality measure of complex networks using biased random walks”. en. In: *The European physical journal. B* 68 (2), pp. 277–281. ISSN: 1434-6028,1434-6036. DOI: 10.1140/epjb/e2009 - 00095 - 5. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1140/epjb/e2009-00095-5>.
- Lemonnier, Pierre (June 1, 1986). “The Study of Material Culture Today: Toward an Anthropology of Technical Systems”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 5 (2), pp. 147–186. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90012-7. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416586900127>.
- (1989). “Bark Capes, Arrowheads and Concorde: On Social Representations of Technology”. In: *The Meaning of Things: Material Culture and Symbolic Expressions*. Ed. by Ian Hodder. London: Hyman, Unwin, pp. 156–171.

- Lemonnier, Pierre (1992). *Elements for an Anthropology of Technology*. Ann Arbor: Museum of Anthropology, University of Michigan. URL: <https://philpapers.org/rec/LEMEFA>.
- Lindauer, Owen (1995). *Where the Rivers Converge: Roosevelt Platform Mound Study: Report on the Rock Island Complex*. Vol. Roosevelt Monograph Series 4. Tempe: Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University.
- Loendorf, Chris (2010). “Hohokam Core Area Sociocultural Dynamics: Cooperation and Conflict along the Middle Gila River in Southern Arizona during the Classic and Historic Periods”. PhD thesis. Tempe: Arizona State University.
- Loendorf, Chris and Glen E Rice (2004). *Projectile Point Typology Gila River Indian Community, Arizona*. Anthropological Research Papers No. 2. Sacaton, Arizona: Gila River Indian Community Cultural Resource Management Program.
- Loendorf, Chris, Thatcher A Rogers, et al. (Apr. 2019). “Projectile Point Reworking: An Experimental Study of Arrowpoint Use Life”. cs. In: *American Antiquity* 84, pp. 353–365. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.1017/aaq.2018.87. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/projectile-point-reworking-an-experimental-study-of-arrowpoint-use-life/17DB4E93940AA42F4D3103AD78D76F46>.
- Loendorf, Chris, Lynn Simon, et al. (Aug. 2015). “Warfare and Big Game Hunting: Flaked-Stone Projectile Points Along the Middle Gila River in Arizona”. en. In: *Antiquity* 89, pp. 940–953. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.15184/aqy.2015.28. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/warfare-and-big-game-hunting-flakedstone-projectile-points-along-the-middle-gila-river-in-arizona/F8FAF746DA28A11D0A051E3BDC6BB023> (visited on 12/27/2018).
- Loendorf, Christopher (1998). “Salado Burial Practices and Social Organization”. In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeology Studies, 1989 to 1998*. Ed. by Glen Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 10 Anthropological Field Studies 40. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 193–230. ISBN: 9781886067004.
- Lowe, R M (2024). “The Nature of Projectile Point Types From the Denton Site, Mississippi”. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.
- Lulewicz, Jacob (Apr. 2, 2019). “The social networks and structural variation of Mississippian sociopolitics in the southeastern United States”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 116 (14), pp. 6707–6712.

ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1818346116. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1818346116>.

Lycett, Stephen J and Noreen von Cramon-Taubadel (June 1, 2015). “Toward a “Quantitative Genetic” Approach to Lithic Variation”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 22 (2), pp. 646–675. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-013-9200-9. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-013-9200-9>.

Lyons, Patrick D (2003). *Ancestral Hopi Migrations*. English. First Edition edition. Anthropological Paper Number 68. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816522804.

— (2013). *Placing the Tonto Cliff Dwellings in the Larger Context of Tonto Basin and the Southern US Southwest*. en. Tucson: Western National Parks Association.

Lyons, Patrick D and Alexander Johnston Lindsay Jr. (2006). “Perforated Plates and the Salado Phenomenon”. In: *The Kiva* 72 (1), pp. 5–54. ISSN: 0023-1940.

Macdonald, W K (1990). “Investigating Style: An Exploratory Analysis of some Plains Burials”. en. In: *Uses of Style in Archaeology*. Cambridge: Cambridge Univ. Press, pp. 52–60.

MacLeod, Norman (Dec. 1, 2018). “The Quantitative Assessment of Archaeological Artifact Groups: Beyond Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Quaternary Science Reviews* 201, pp. 319–348. ISSN: 0277-3791. DOI: 10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.08.024. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277379118302907>.

Mason, Otis T (1894). *North American Bows, Arrows, and Quivers*. en. Washington DC: Government Printing Office. 216 pp. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Fk9BAQAAMAAJ>.

Maté-González, Miguel Ángel et al. (Mar. 21, 2023). “Geometric morphometrics and machine learning models applied to the study of late Iron Age cut marks from central Spain”. en. In: *Applied sciences (Basel, Switzerland)* 13 (6), p. 3967. ISSN: 2076-3417,2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app13063967. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/13/6/3967>.

Mauss, Marcel (1966). *The Gift: Forms and Functions of Exchange in Archaic Societies*. London: Cohen & West.

- McInnes, Leland, John Healy, and James Melville (2020). *UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction*. DOI: arXiv:1802.03426. arXiv: 1802.03426 [stat.ML]. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426>.
- Miksa, Elizabeth and James M Heidke (1995). “Drawing a Line in the Sands: Models of Ceramic Temper Provenance”. en. In: *The Roosevelt Community Development Study*. Ed. by J M Heidke and M T Stark. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 14. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 133–204.
- Mills, Barbara et al. (2020). *CyberSW Version 1.0*. en. Tucson. URL: <https://cybersw.org/>.
- Mills, Barbara J (Apr. 2007). “Performing the Feast: Visual Display and Suprahousehold Commensalism in the Puebloan Southwest”. en. In: *American antiquity* 72 (2), pp. 210–239. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/40035812. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/performing-the-feast-visual-display-and-suprahousehold-commensalism-in-the-puebloan-southwest/014093DF6B246C2C326A3F6ABA3F956E>.
- Mills, Barbara J, Jeffery J Clark, et al. (Apr. 9, 2013). “Transformation of social networks in the late pre-Hispanic US Southwest”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110 (15), pp. 5785–5790. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1219966110. URL: <http://www.pnas.org/content/110/15/5785>.
- Mills, Barbara J, Matthew A Peeples, et al. (Jan. 2015). “Multiscalar Perspectives on Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic Southwest”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 80 (1), pp. 3–24. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.7183/0002-7316.79.4.3. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/multiscalar-perspectives-on-social-networks-in-the-late-prehispanic-southwest/B40CF133F9E61102185B25AD4DF0FE30>.
- Mills, Barbara J, John M Roberts Jr, et al. (2013). “The Dynamics of Social Networks in the Late Prehispanic U.S. Southwest”. en. In: *Network Analysis in Archaeology: New Approaches to Regional Interaction*. Ed. by Carl Knappett. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 181–202. DOI: 10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199697090.003.0008.
- Mitteroecker, P and P Gunz (2009). “Advances in Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Evolutionary Biology* 36, pp. 235–247. ISSN: 0071-3260. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11692-009-9055-x>.
- Mitteroecker, Philipp and Katrin Schaefer (Aug. 2022). “Thirty years of geometric morphometrics: Achievements, challenges, and the ongoing quest for biological meaningful-

ness”. en. In: *American journal of biological anthropology* 178 Suppl 74 (S74), pp. 181–210. ISSN: 2692-7691. DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.24531. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9545184/> (visited on 09/09/2024).

Morgan, Thomas J H, Catharine P Cross, and Luke E Rendell (2015). “Nothing in human behavior makes sense except in the light of culture: Shared interests of social psychology and cultural evolution”. en. In: *Evolutionary Perspectives on Social Psychology*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 215–228. ISBN: 9783319126968. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-12697-5_17. URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-12697-5_17.

Muthukrishna, Michael, Thomas J H Morgan, and Joseph Henrich (Jan. 2016). “The when and who of social learning and conformist transmission”. In: *Evolution and human behavior: official journal of the Human Behavior and Evolution Society* 37 (1), pp. 10–20. ISSN: 1090-5138,1879-0607. DOI: 10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2015.05.004.

Nash, Brendan S and Elton R Prewitt (July 2, 2016). “The Use of Artificial Neural Networks in Projectile Point Typology”. In: *Lithic Technology* 41 (3), pp. 194–211. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2016.1184876. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2016.1184876>.

Neuzil, Anna A (2008). *In the Aftermath of Migration: Renegotiating Ancient Identity in Southeastern Arizona*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona No. 73. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.

Nishiaki, Yoshihiro (2013). ““Gifting” As a Means of Cultural Transmission: The Archaeological Implications of Bow-and-Arrow Technology in Papua New Guinea”. In: *Dynamics of Learning in Neanderthals and Modern Humans Volume 1: Cultural Perspectives*. Ed. by Takeru Akazawa, Yoshihiro Nishiaki, and Kenichi Aoki. Tokyo: Springer Japan, pp. 173–185. ISBN: 9784431545118. DOI: 10.1007/978-4-431-54511-8_10. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-4-431-54511-8_10.

Okumura, Mercedes and Astolfo G M Araujo (Mar. 15, 2016). “The Southern Divide: Testing Morphological Differences among Bifacial Points from Southern and Southeastern Brazil using Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Journal of Lithic Studies* 3 (1). ISSN: 2055-0472. DOI: 10.2218/jls.v3i1.1379. URL: <http://journals.ed.ac.uk/lithicstudies/article/view/1379>.

— (Jan. 1, 2019). “Archaeology, biology, and borrowing: A critical examination of Geometric Morphometrics in Archaeology”. en. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 101, pp. 149–158. ISSN: 0305-4403,1095-9238. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2017.09.015. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85046166965&origin=>

resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sid=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&sot=a&sdt=cl&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22geometric+morphometrics%22%29+AND+TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22archaeology%22+OR+%22human+evolution%22+OR+%22artifact%22+OR+%22prehistoric%22+OR+%22faunal+remains%22%29&sl=145&sessionSearchId=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&relpos=153.

Oliver, Theodore J (2001). “Warfare in Tonto Basin”. en. In: *Deadly Landscapes: Case Studies of Prehistoric Southwestern Warfare*. Ed. by G E Rice and Steven A LeBlanc. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, pp. 195–217.

Ortman, Scott G (Mar. 2016). “Uniform Probability Density Analysis and Population History in the Northern Rio Grande”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 23 (1), pp. 95–126. ISSN: 1072-5369,1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-014-9227-6. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10816-014-9227-6>.

Padilla-Iglesias, Cecilia and Robert J Bischoff (Oct. 9, 2024). “Hunter-gatherer mobility patterns influence the reconstruction of social networks from archaeological assemblages”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 59, p. 104798. ISSN: 2352-409X,2352-4103. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2024.104798>.

Padilla-Iglesias, Cecilia, Javier Blanco-Portillo, et al. (May 27, 2024). “Deep history of cultural and linguistic evolution among Central African hunter-gatherers”. en. In: *Nature human behaviour*. ISSN: 2397-3374. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-024-01891-y. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41562-024-01891-y>.

Paige, Jonathan (2022). “The Evolution of Stone Tool Traditions”. Tempe: Arizona State University. URL: https://d1rbsgppyrdq4.cloudfront.net/s3fs-public/c7/paige_asu_0010E_22345.pdf?versionId=v4bd0rkMBjdqIcV2VTal2iJGR78g0YWr&X-Amz-Content-Sha256=UNSIGNED-PAYLOAD&X-Amz-Algorithm=AWS4-HMAC-SHA256&X-Amz-Credential=AKIASBVQ3ZQ4YNQVYJLW/20241002/us-west-2/s3/aws4_request&X-Amz-Date=20241002T042151Z&X-Amz-SignedHeaders=host&X-Amz-Expires=120&X-Amz-Signature=26783e4f5287ac36c7b9e023f00b8863824be7b10ab1504f9381e950f57d6ca9.

Parsons, Elsie Clews (1932). “Isleta, New Mexico”. en. In: *Forty Seventh Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1929–1930*. United States Government Printing Office. Ed. by M W Stirling. Washington, D.C, pp. 193–466.

— (1939). *Pueblo Indian Religion*. English. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Peeples, Matthew et al. (2021). “Connections and Boundaries”. en. In: *Becoming Hopi: A history*. Ed. by Wesley Bernardini et al. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Peeples, Matthew A (2017). *Network Science and Statistical Techniques for Dealing with Uncertainties in Archaeological Datasets*.
- (2018). *Connected Communities: Networks, Identity, and Social Change in the Ancient Cibola World*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816535682. URL: <https://market.android.com/details?id=book-fyw-DwAAQBAJ>.
- (Feb. 4, 2019). “Finding a Place for Networks in Archaeology”. en. In: *Journal of Archaeological Research*, pp. 1–49. ISSN: 1059-0161,1573-7756. DOI: 10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10814-019-09127-8>.
- (2021). *UniformProbabilityDensityAnalysis*. en. Comp. software. URL: <https://github.com/mpeeples2008/UniformProbabilityDensityAnalysis> (visited on 04/25/2023).
- Peeples, Matthew A and Tom Brughmans (2023). *Online Companion to Network Science in Archaeology*. URL: <https://archnetworks.ne>.
- Peeples, Matthew A and W Randall Haas (June 2013). “Brokerage and Social Capital in the Prehispanic U.S. Southwest”. en. In: *American anthropologist* 115 (2), pp. 232–247. ISSN: 0002-7294,1548-1433. DOI: 10.1111/aman.12006. URL: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/aman.12006/abstract>.
- Peeples, Matthew A, Barbara J Mills, et al. (2016). “Analytical Challenges for the Application of Social Network Analysis in Archaeology”. In: *The Connected Past: Challenges to Network Studies in Archaeology and History*. Ed. by Tom Brughmans, Anna Collar, and Fiona Coward. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 59–84.
- Peeples, Matthew A and John M Roberts (July 2013). “To Binarize or not to Binarize: Relational Data and the Construction of Archaeological Networks”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 40 (7), pp. 3001–3010. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2013.03.014. URL: <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0305440313001040>.
- Peeples, Matthew A, Jr Roberts John M, and Yi Yin (2024). “Challenges for network research in archaeology”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Network Research*. Ed. by Matthew A Peeples et al. Oxford University Press, pp. 34–49. ISBN: 9780198854265. DOI: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198854265.013.2. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198854265.013.2>.

- Perreault, Charles (2019). *The Quality of the Archaeological Record*. en. University of Chicago Press. 280 pp. ISBN: 9780226631011. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=TwyiDwAAQBAJ>.
- Petřík, J et al. (2018). “Shape Matters: Assessing Regional Variation of Bell Beaker Projectile Points in Central Europe Using Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences* 10 (4), pp. 896–904. DOI: 10.1007/s12520-016-0423-z. URL: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12520-016-0423-z>.
- Pfaffenberger, Bryan (1988). “Fetishised Objects and Humanised Nature: Towards an Anthropology of Technology”. In: *Man* 23 (2), pp. 236–252. ISSN: 0025-1496. DOI: 10.2307/2802804. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2802804>.
- Premo, Luke S (2006). “Agent-Based Models as Behavioral Laboratories for Evolutionary Anthropological Research”. In: *Arizona Anthropologist* 17, pp. 91–113.
- Prignano, Luce, Ignacio Morer, and Albert Diaz-Guilera (2017). “Wiring the Past: A Network Science Perspective on the Challenge of Archeological Similarity Networks”. In: *Frontiers in Digital Humanities* 4. ISSN: 2297-2668. DOI: 10.3389/fdigh.2017.00013. URL: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fdigh.2017.00013>.
- Python Software Foundation (2024). *Python 3.8.20 Documentation*. URL: <https://docs.python.org/3.8/index.html> (visited on 09/24/2024).
- Radin, Paul (1923). “The Winnebago Tribe”. en. In: *Thirty Seventh Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1915–1916*. Ed. by F W Hodge. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 33–560.
- Rice, Glen E (1994). “Projectile Points, Bifaces, and Drills”. In: *Archaeology of the Salado in the Livingston Area of Tonto Basin, Roosevelt Platform Mound Study: Report on the Livingston Management Group, Pinto Creek Complex. Part 2*. Ed. by Glen E Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 3. Tempe: Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University, pp. 727–738. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6067/XCV8HT2R9N>.
- ed. (1998). *A synthesis of Tonto Basin prehistory: The Roosevelt archaeology studies, 1989 to 1998*. Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University. DOI: 10.6067/XCV81V5GRZ. URL: <https://core.tdar.org/document/394298/a-synthesis-of-tonto-basin-prehistory-the-roosevelt-archaeology-studies-1989-to-1998>.

- Rice, Glen E and Theodore J Oliver (1998). “Settlement Patterns and Subsistence”. en. In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeological Studies, 1989-1998*. Ed. by Glen E Rice. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 85–104.
- Rice, Glen E, Arleyn Simon, and Christopher Loendorf (1998). “Production and Exchange of Economic Goods”. In: *A Synthesis of Tonto Basin Prehistory: The Roosevelt Archaeology Studies, 1989 to 1998*. Ed. by Glen Rice. Roosevelt Monograph Series 10 Anthropological Field Studies 40. Tempe: Arizona State University, Office of Cultural Resource Management, Dept. of Anthropology, pp. 105–130. ISBN: 9781886067004.
- Rivera-Hutinel, A et al. (July 2012). “Effects of sampling completeness on the structure of plant-pollinator networks”. en. In: *Ecology* 93 (7), pp. 1593–1603. ISSN: 0012-9658,1939-9170. DOI: 10.1890/11-1803.1. URL: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1890/11-1803.1>.
- Roberts, John M et al. (May 1, 2012). “A Method for Chronological Apportioning of Ceramic Assemblages”. In: *Journal of archaeological science* 39 (5), pp. 1513–1520. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2011.12.022. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440311004699>.
- Rogers, J Daniel and Wendy H Cegielski (2017). “Building a better past with the help of agent-based modeling”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 114 (49), pp. 12841–12844. ISSN: 0027-8424,1091-6490. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1718277114. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1718277114>.
- Rohlf, F James (Jan. 1, 2015). “The Tps series of software”. In: *Hystrix* 26 (1), pp. 1–4. ISSN: 1825-5272. DOI: 10.4404/hystrix-26.1-11264. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281698770_The_Tps_series_of_software (visited on 04/08/2022).
- Rohlf, F James and Leslie F Marcus (1993). “A Revolution in Morphometrics”. In: *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 8, pp. 129–129. ISSN: 0169-5347.
- Romanowska, Iza, Stefani A Crabtree, et al. (May 2019). “Agent-Based Modeling for Archaeologists: Part 1 of 3”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 7 (2), pp. 178–184. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.1017/aap.2019.6. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances-in-archaeological-practice/article/agentbased-modeling-for-archaeologists-part-1-of-3/B044D059FABC3F793205C6407BF32B09>.
- Romanowska, Iza, Colin D Wren, and Stefani A Crabtree (2021). *Agent-Based Modeling for Archaeology: Simulating the Complexity of Societies*. Santa Fe: The Santa Fe Institute Press.

- Roosevelt Platform Mound Study (RPMS) (2014). *Access Database (tDAR id: 427111)*. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8TQ63KK. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6067/XCV8TQ63KK>.
- Rudy, Jack R (1953). *Archeological Survey of Western Utah*. Anthropological Papers No. 12. Salt Lake City, Utah: University of Utah Press.
- Russell, Frank (1908). "The Pima Indians". en. In: *Twenty-Sixth Annual Report of the Bureau of American Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1915–1916*. Ed. by W H Holmes. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 3–390.
- Ryan, Stacy L (2017). "Classic Period Projectile Point Design Variation in the Tucson Basin and San Pedro Valley, Arizona". MA thesis. MA thesis, Department of Anthropology, University of Arizona, Tucson.
- Sackett, J R (1982). "Approaches to Style in Lithic Archaeology". In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 1, pp. 59–112.
- Sackett, James R (Sept. 1, 1986). "Isochrestism and style: A clarification". en. In: *Journal of anthropological archaeology* 5 (3), pp. 266–277. ISSN: 0278-4165,1090-2686. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(86)90008-5. URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0278-4165\(86\)90008-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0278-4165(86)90008-5) (visited on 02/21/2025).
- Sassman, Kenneth E and Victoria Rudolphi (2001). "Communities of Practice in the Early Ceramic Traditions of the American Southeast". In: *Journal of Anthropological Research* 57, pp. 407–425. ISSN: 0091-7710.
- Schachner, Gregson (Apr. 2012). *Population Circulation and the Transformation of Ancient Zuni Communities*. English. First edition. Tucson: University of Arizona Press. ISBN: 9780816529865.
- Scheidel, W (2014). "The Shape of the Roman World: Modelling Imperial Connectivity". In: *Journal of Roman Archaeology* 27, pp. 7–32. ISSN: 1047-7594,2331-5709. DOI: 10.1017/S1047759414001147. URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S1047759414001147/type/journal_article.
- Sedig, Jakob W (June 1, 2014). "An Analysis of Non-Utilitarian Stone Point Function in the US Southwest". en. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 34, pp. 120–132. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/j.jaa.2014.03.003. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S027841651400018X>.

- Selden Jr, Robert Z (July 5, 2022). “Morphologically similar, but regionally distinct: Perdiz arrow points from Caddo burial contexts in the American southeast”. en. In: *Lithic technology* 48 (1), pp. 1–12. ISSN: 0197-7261,2051-6185. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2022.2095492. URL: <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85133410828&origin=resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sid=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&sot=a&sdt=cl&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22geometric+morphometrics%22%29+AND+TITLE-ABS-KEY%28%22archaeology%22+OR+%22human+evolution%22+OR+%22artifact%22+OR+%22prehistoric%22+OR+%22faunal+remains%22%29&sl=145&sessionSearchId=24d0b541c0ccf7023da41b5d94fcea23&relpos=49>.
- Shackley, Michael S (2005). *Obsidian: Geology and Archaeology in the North American Southwest*. en. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Shott, Michael J and Brian W Trail (Sept. 1, 2010). “Exploring New Approaches to Lithic Analysis: Laser Scanning and Geometric Morphometrics”. In: *Lithic Technology* 35 (2), pp. 195–220. ISSN: 0197-7261. DOI: 10.1080/01977261.2010.11721090. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01977261.2010.11721090>.
- Simon, Arelyn W and Dennis C Gosser (2001). “Conflict and Exchange among the Salado of Tonto Basin: Warfare Motivation or Alleviation?” en. In: *Deadly Landscapes: Case Studies of Prehistoric Southwestern Warfare*. Ed. by G E Rice and Steven A LeBlanc. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, pp. 219–238.
- Simpson, Ruth Deette (1953). *The Hopi Indians*. en. Vol. 1. Southwest Museum Leaflets, No. 25. Los Angeles: Southwest Museum.
- Sindbæk, Søren M (Mar. 1, 2007). “Networks and nodal points: the emergence of towns in early Viking Age Scandinavia”. en. In: *Antiquity* 81 (311), pp. 119–132. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/s0003598x00094886. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00094886>.
- Sinopoli, Carla (1991). “Style in Arrow: A Study of an Ethnographic Collection from the Western United States”. In: *Foragers in Context: Long-term, Regional and Historical Perspectives in Hunter-gatherer Studies*. Ed. by Preston T Miracle, Lynn E Fisher, and Jody Brown. Michigan Discussions in Anthropology, v. 10. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, pp. 63–87.
- Sliva, R Jane (1997). *An Introduction to the Study and Analysis of Flaked Stone Artifacts and Lithic Technology*. Tucson: Center For Desert Archaeology.

- Sliva, R Jane (Jan. 1, 1999). "Cienega Points and Late Archaic Period Chronology in the Southern Southwest". In: *The Kiva* 64 (3), pp. 339–367. ISSN: 0023-1940. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.1999.11758388. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.1999.11758388>.
- (2002). "Temporal, Spatial, and Functional Variability in the Flaked Stone Assemblage". en. In: *Tonto Creek Archaeological Project: Artifact and Environmental Analyses. Vol. 2: Stone Tool and Subsistence Studies*. Ed. by J J Clark. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 23. Anthropological Papers No. 23. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 487–558.
- (2006). "Projectile Points in Regional Perspective". In: *Sunset Crater Archaeology: The History of a Volcanic Landscape. Stone, Shell, Bone, and Mortuary Analyses*. Ed. by Mark D Elson. Anthropological Papers No. 31. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 31–63.
- (2017). "Evaluating Early Agricultural Period Social Dynamics in Southern Arizona Through Projectile Point Typology". In: *Journal of Arizona Archaeology* 4 (2), pp. 99–112.
- Somers, Margaret R (Oct. 1994). "The narrative constitution of identity: A relational and network approach". en. In: *Theory and society* 23 (5), pp. 605–649. ISSN: 0304-2421,1573-7853. DOI: 10.1007/bf00992905. URL: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/BF00992905>.
- Spielmann, Katherine A et al., eds. (1998). *Environment and subsistence in the Classic period Tonto Basin, the Roosevelt archaeology studies, 1989 to 1998*. Department of Anthropology, Arizona State University. DOI: 10.6067/XCV8FB54V1. URL: <https://core.tdar.org/document/394307/environment-and-subsistence-in-the-classic-period-tonto-basin-the-roosevelt-archaeology-studies-1989-to-1998>.
- Stark, Miriam T, Mark D Elson, and Jeffrey J Clark (1998). "Social Boundaries and Technical Choices in Tonto Basin Prehistory". en. In: *The Archaeology of Social Boundaries*. Ed. by Miriam T Stark. Washington, D.C: Smithsonian Institution Press, pp. 208–231.
- Stark, Miriam T and James M Heidke (1992). "The Plainware and Redware Ceramic Assemblages". en. In: *The Rye Creek Project: Archaeology in the Upper Tonto Basin: Vol. 2. Artifact and Specific Analyses*. Ed. by M D Elson and D B Craig. Vol. Anthropological Papers No. 11. Tucson: Center for Desert Archaeology, pp. 89–214.
- Stevenson, James (1884). "Illustrated Catalogue of the Collection Obtained from the Pueblos of New Mexico and Arizona in 1881". en. In: *Third Annual Report of the Bureau of Ethnology to the Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution 1880–1881*. Ed. by J W Powell. Washington, D.C: United States Government Printing Office, pp. 517–595.

- Stevenson, Matilda Coxe (1894). *The Sia*. en. Ed. by John W Powell. Washington, D.C: Government Printing Office, pp. 9–166.
- (1903). “Zuñi Games”. In: *American Anthropologist* 5 (3), pp. 468–497. ISSN: 0002-7294.
- Stokke, Hugo and Marit Tjomsland (1996). *Collective Identities and Social Movements*. en. Bergen, Norway: Chr. Michelsen Institute.
- Tagg, Martyn D (1994). “Projectile Points of East-Central Arizona: Forms and Chronology”. In: *Middle Little Colorado River Archaeology: From the Parks to the People*. Ed. by Ann Trinkle Jones and Martyn D Tagg. The Arizona Archaeologist No. 27. Phoenix: Arizona Archaeological Society, pp. 87–115.
- Team, R Core (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria. URL: <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Terrell, John E (1977). “Human Biogeography in the Solomon Islands”. In: *Fieldiana* 68 (1), pp. 1–47. ISSN: 0071-4739.
- Terrell, John Edward (2010). “Social Network Analysis of the Genetic Structure of Pacific Islanders”. In: *Annals of Human Genetics* 74 (3), p. 211.
- Terrell, John Edward et al. (Mar. 10, 2023). *Modeling the Past: Archaeology, History, and Dynamic Networks*. en. Berghahn Books. 248 pp. ISBN: 9781800738706. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=ziWBEEAAQBAJ>.
- Thomas, David Hurst (1981). “How to Classify the Projectile Points from Monitor Valley, Nevada”. en. In: *Journal of California and Great Basin Anthropology* 3 (1), pp. 7–43. ISSN: 0191-3557. URL: <http://libproxy.unm.edu/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=ahl&AN=45856169&site=eds-live&scope=site>.
- Tilly, Charles (1978). *From Mobilization to Revolution*. en. Reading, Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley.
- (June 1, 2001). “Mechanisms in Political Processes”. In: *Annual Review of Political Science* 4 (1), pp. 21–41. ISSN: 1094-2939. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.polisci.4.1.21. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.polisci.4.1.21>.
- (2002). *Stories, Identities, and Political Change*. en. Lanham, Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield. 257 pp. ISBN: 9780742518810. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=x465AAAAIAAJ>.

- Tilly, Charles (2004). “Social Boundary Mechanisms”. In: *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* 34 (2), pp. 211–236. ISSN: 0048-3931. DOI: 10.1177/0048393103262551. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0048393103262551>.
- (2005). *Identities, Boundaries, and Social Ties*. en. Boulder, Colorado: Paradigm Publishers.
- Torres, Marcos Martínón (2002). “Chaîne Opératoire: The concept and its applications within the study of technology”. In: *Gallaecia* 21, pp. 29–44. URL: <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/descarga/articulo/265493.pdf>.
- Upton, Andrew James (2019). “Multilayer Network Relationships and Culture Contact in Mississippian West-central Illinois, A.D. 1200 - 1450”. PhD thesis. PhD dissertation, Department of Anthropology, Michigan State University, East Lansing.
- Van Oyen, Astrid (Mar. 1, 2016). “Historicising Material Agency: from Relations to Relational Constellations”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 23 (1), pp. 354–378. ISSN: 1573-7764. DOI: 10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-015-9244-0>.
- VanPool, Todd L and Chet Savage (2010). “War, women, and religion: The spread of Salado Polychrome in the American Southwest”. In: *Innovation in Cultural System: Contributions from Evolutionary Anthropology*. Ed. by Michael J O’Brien and Stephen J Shennan. Cambridge: MIT Press, pp. 251–265. URL: <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=IOoiwbJg1jUC&oi=fnd&pg=PA251&ots=7umBczM58w&sig=bf3gC1eMgm3SAZW3IECYyVpC7L0>.
- Waguespack, Nicole M et al. (Sept. 2009). “Making a Point: Wood- Versus Stone-Tipped Projectiles”. In: *Antiquity* 83 (321), pp. 786–800. ISSN: 0003-598X,1745-1744. DOI: 10.1017/S0003598X00098999. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/antiquity/article/making-a-point-wood-versus-stonetipped-projectiles/5D4C59E76AA5D00B9020ACD3CC8DED6C> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Wang, Li-Ying and Ben Marwick (Oct. 1, 2021). “A Bayesian networks approach to infer social changes from burials in northeastern Taiwan during the European colonization period”. In: *Journal of Archaeological Science* 134, p. 105471. ISSN: 0305-4403. DOI: 10.1016/j.jas.2021.105471. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440321001412>.
- Ware, John A (2014). *A Pueblo Social History: Kinship, Sodality, and Community in the Northern Southwest*. en. Santa Fe, New Mexico: SAR Press.

- Watts, Joshua (Aug. 2013). “Traces of the Individual in Prehistory: Flintknappers and the Distribution of Projectile Points in the Eastern Tonto Basin, Arizona”. In: *Advances in Archaeological Practice* 1 (1), pp. 25–36. ISSN: 2326-3768. DOI: 10.7183/2326-3768.1.1.25. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/advances-in-archaeological-practice/article/traces-of-the-individual-in-prehistory/7941C0F225A22D6D9707A6165FC4E5B0> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Wenger, Etienne (1998). *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Vol. 9. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. URL: <https://valenciacollege.edu/faculty/development/teaching-learning-academy/documents/CommunityofPractice.pdf>.
- White, Andrew (2013). “An Abstract Model Showing That the Spatial Structure of Social Networks Affects the Outcomes of Cultural Transmission Processes”. In: *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 16 (3). ISSN: 1460-7425. DOI: 10.18564/jasss.2219. URL: <http://jasss.soc.surrey.ac.uk/16/3/9.html>.
- White, Harrison (1992). *Identity and Control: A Structural Theory of Social Action*. en. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- (2008). *Identity and Control: How Social Formations Emerge*. en. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- Whittaker, John C (1994). *Flintknapping: Making and Understanding Stone Tools*. en. Austin: University of Texas Press. 341 pp. ISBN: 9780292790834. URL: <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=4J79DAAAQBAJ>.
- Whittaker, John C and William D Bryce (2017). “Hunting Technologies”. In: *The Oxford Handbook of Southwest Archaeology*. Ed. by Barbara Mills and Severin M Fowles. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 627–644. ISBN: 9780199978427. DOI: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199978427.013.33. URL: <https://www.oxfordhandbooks.com/view/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199978427.001.0001/oxfordhb-9780199978427-e-33> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- Whittaker, John C and Kathryn A Kamp (2016). “Flint from the Ancestors: Ritualized Use of Stone Tools in the Prehistoric Southwest”. In: *Archaeological Variability and Interpretation in Global Perspective*. Ed. by Alan P Sullivan III and Deborah Irene Olszewski. Boulder: University Press of Colorado, pp. 267–289. DOI: 10.5876/9781607324942.c012. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5876/9781607324942.c012>.
- Whittlesey, Stephanie M (2010). “House, Home, and Hearth: Gender in the Pre-Classic Hohokam Household”. In: *Engendering households in the prehistoric southwest*. Ed. by B J Roth. University of Arizona Press, pp. 50–75.

- Wiessner, Polly (1983). “Style and Social Information in Kalahari San Projectile Points”. en. In: *American Antiquity* 48 (2), pp. 253–276. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280450. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-and-social-information-in-kalahari-san-projectile-points/52D6230881B0C69260ABE226BD82EC0E>.
- (1984). “Reconsidering the Behavioral Basis for Style: a Case Study among the Kalahari San”. In: *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 3 (3), pp. 190–234. ISSN: 0278-4165. DOI: 10.1016/0278-4165(84)90002-3. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0278416584900023>.
- (Jan. 1985). “Style or Isochrestic Variation? A Reply to Sackett”. In: *American Antiquity* 50 (1), pp. 160–166. ISSN: 0002-7316,2325-5064. DOI: 10.2307/280643. URL: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-antiquity/article/style-or-isochrestic-variation-a-reply-to-sackett/206F9510A8BF0402883F6A436A9BB787> (visited on 01/14/2020).
- (1997). “Seeking Guidelines through an Evolutionary Approach: Style Revisited among the !Kung San of the 1990s”. In: *Rediscovering Darwin*. Ed. by C Michael Barton and Geoffrey A Clark. Vol. 7. Archeological Papers of the American Anthropological Association. Arlington: American Anthropological Association, pp. 157–176.
- Wobst, H Martin (1977). “Stylistic Behavior and Information Exchange”. In: *For the Director: Research Essays in Honour of the Late James B. Griffin*. Ed. by C E Cleland. Vol. 61. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan, pp. 317–342.
- Wood, J Scott (2000). “Vale of Tiers Palimpsest: Salado Settlement and Internal Relationship in the Tonto Basin Area”. en. In: *Salado*. Ed. by Jeffrey S Dean. Dagoon, Arizona and Albuquerque: Amerind Foundation Publication and University of New Mexico Press, pp. 107–142.
- Wood, S N (2017). *Generalized Additive Models: An Introduction with R*.

APPENDIX A

PERMISSIONS AND CODE FOR CHAPTER 2

This chapter contains the code used for the analysis in chapter 2 and the ODD (Overview, Design concepts, Details) protocol for the agent-based model ArchMatNet. The code is organized into three sections: **R**, **Functions**, and **R Environment**. The **R** section contains the code for the analysis, the **Functions** section contains the functions used in the analysis, and the **R Environment** section contains the R environment used to run the analysis. The final section contains the ODD protocol which is an enhanced description of the agent-based model.

R Code

```
library(tidyverse)
library(here)
library(rio)
library(ggpubr)
library(igraph)
library(ggnetwork)
library(tictoc)
# library(patchwork)
library(magick)
library(BayesFactor)
i_am("Analysis/Chap2Analysis.R")
source("Analysis/functions.R")

vars <- c(
  "uniqueTraits",
  "nTicks",
```

```
"huntingGroupSize",
"pHunting",
"genderedMigration",
"pNewAlliance",
"maximumAlliesN",
"pTrading",
"visibility",
"pLoss",
"pLuckyLeap",
"pVisiting",
"learningMethod",
"gradualEnvChange",
"pEnvChange",
"aggregationDuration",
"transmissionRate",
"pMigration",
"nOfBands",
"campPopulation",
"potteryPrestige",
"pNewVariant",
"pNewObject",
"aggregationFreq"
)
```

```
#### load results ####
```

```

library(arrow)

runs <- read_feather(here("data/modelOutput.parquet"))

#### look at range of experiments ####
expDF <- runs %>%
  select(expID) %>%
  group_by(expID) %>%
  count()

#### examine network comparisons ####

table_df <- tibble()

plotdf <- runs %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
  # filter(pTrading > 0) %>%
  # filter(nOfBands > 3) %>%
  select(contains("_corZscore")) %>%
  pivot_longer(contains("_corZscore"), names_to = "Network
  ↳ Comparison", values_to = "Correlation Comparison") %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = gsub("_corZscore", "", `Network
  ↳ Comparison`)) %>%
  filter(!str_detect(`Network Comparison`, "Hunting")) %>%
  drop_na()

meanAll <- plotdf %>%

```

```

group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`Correlation Comparison`, na.rm = T)) %>%
  arrange(mean)

table_df <- meanAll %>%
  mutate(metric = "Graph Correlation")

meanPotPoint <- plotdf %>%
  filter(`Network Comparison` != "Point_Pot") %>%
  filter(str_detect(`Network Comparison`, "Point|Pot")) %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = case_when(`Network Comparison` %>%
    ↪ str_detect("Point") ~ "Point", TRUE ~ "Pot")) %>%
  group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`Correlation Comparison`)) %>%
  arrange(`Network Comparison`)

plotSum <- plotdf %>%
  group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`Correlation Comparison`, na.rm = T)) %>%
  arrange(desc(mean))

p <- plotdf %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = fct_relevel(`Network Comparison`,
    ↪ plotSum$`Network Comparison`)) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = `Network Comparison`, y = `Correlation Comparison`,
    ↪ fill = `Network Comparison`)) +
  geom_boxplot(alpha = .25, notch = T) +

```

```

guides(fill = "none") +
theme_bw() +
xlab("") +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1))
p
# ggsave(here('figures/corComparisonZScoreBoxplot.png'),p,width =
↪ 7,height = 4.5, dpi = 600)
# ggsave(here('figures/corComparisonZScoreBoxplot.tiff'),p,width =
↪ 7,height = 4.5, compression = "lzw", dpi = 900)

plotdf <- runs %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
  select(contains("_QAP")) %>%
  pivot_longer(contains("_QAP"), names_to = "Network Comparison",
  ↪ values_to = "QAP Test") %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = gsub("_QAP", "", `Network
  ↪ Comparison`)) %>%
  filter(!str_detect(`Network Comparison`, "Hunting")) %>%
  drop_na()

meanAll <- plotdf %>%
  group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`QAP Test`)) %>%
  arrange(mean)

table_df <- bind_rows(table_df, meanAll %>%

```

```

mutate(metric = "QAP Test"))

meanPotPoint <- plotdf %>%
  filter(`Network Comparison` != "Point_Pot") %>%
  filter(str_detect(`Network Comparison`, "Point|Pot")) %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = case_when(`Network Comparison` %>%
    ↪ str_detect("Point") ~ "Point", TRUE ~ "Pot")) %>%
  group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`QAP Test`)) %>%
  arrange(`Network Comparison`)

plotSum <- plotdf %>%
  group_by(`Network Comparison`) %>%
  summarize(mean = mean(`QAP Test`, na.rm = T)) %>%
  arrange(mean)

p <- plotdf %>%
  mutate(`Network Comparison` = fct_relevel(`Network Comparison`,
    ↪ plotSum$`Network Comparison`)) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = `Network Comparison`, y = `QAP Test`)) +
  geom_point(position = position_jitter(), alpha = .1) +
  theme_bw() +
  xlab("") +
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1))
p

```

```

# ggsave(here('figures/QAPTest.tiff'),p,width = 7,height = 4.5,
↪  compression = "lzw", dpi = 900)
# browseURL(here('figures/QAPTest.tiff'))

# table_df %>%
# pivot_wider(names_from = metric, values_from = mean) %>%
# write_csv("tables/MetricResults.csv")

#### explore variables ####

experiments <- runs$expID %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
experiments

# unique traits

i <- 24
variables_df <- runs %>%
  select(expID, any_of(vars), any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  filter(!str_detect(name, "Hunting")) %>%
  filter(str_detect(name, "Pot|Point")) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(vars), names_to = "Variable", values_to =
↪  "parameter") %>%
  mutate(parameter = factor(parameter)) %>%

```

```

group_by(name, Variable, parameter) %>%
  summarize(cor = mean(value, na.rm = T), count = n())

visiting_point_df <- variables_df %>%
  filter(name == "Visiting_Point_corZscore") %>%
  filter(Variable == vars[i])

visiting_point_df

runs %>%
  select(uniqueTraits, nTicks, Visiting_Point_corZscore) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(-Visiting_Point_corZscore), factor) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = Visiting_Point_corZscore, group = nTicks, color =
  ↪ nTicks)) +
  geom_boxplot() +
  theme_minimal() +
  facet_wrap(~uniqueTraits, scales = "free_y") +
  ggtitle("uniqueTraits")

variables_df <- runs %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
  select(-uniqueTraits) %>%
  select(expID, any_of(vars), any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  filter(!str_detect(name, "Hunting")) %>%
  filter(str_detect(name, "Pot|Point")) %>%

```

```

filter(name == "Visiting_Pot_corZscore") %>%
janitor::remove_constant()

library(mgcv)

dvars <- vars[which(vars %in% names(variables_df))]

fmla <- as.formula("value ~ nTicks + huntingGroupSize + pHunting +
  factor(genderedMigration) + pNewAlliance + maximumAlliesN +
  pTrading + factor(visibility) + pLoss + pLuckyLeap +
  pVisiting + factor(learningMethod) + factor(gradualEnvChange) +
  pEnvChange + aggregationDuration + transmissionRate +
  pMigration + nOfBands + campPopulation +
  factor(potteryPrestige) + pNewVariant + pNewObject +
  aggregationFreq")
gam_mdl <- gam(fmla, data = variables_df)
summary(gam_mdl)
gam_summary <- summary(gam_mdl)

# Extract parametric and smooth terms
parametric_df <- as.data.frame(gam_summary$p.table)
smooth_df <- as.data.frame(gam_summary$s.table)

# Add type column and combine tables
parametric_df$type <- "Parametric"

```

```

# Format table
names(parametric_df) <- c("Estimate", "Std. Error", "t-value",
  ↪ "p-value", "Type")

parametric_df <- rownames_to_column(parametric_df, "Parameter")

parametric_df <- parametric_df %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round, 2)

# write_csv(parametric_df, here('tables/ParametricEstimates.csv'))

# variables that don't make a difference
xvars <- c("pNewAlliance", "maximumAlliesN", "pLoss", "pEnvChange",
  ↪ "aggregationDuration", "potteryPrestige", "pNewVariant",
  ↪ "transmissionRate", "pMigration", "nOfBands", "pNewVariant",
  ↪ "pLuckyLeap", "pHunting")

dvars <- vars[which(!vars %in% xvars)]
dvars <- dvars[which(dvars %in% names(variables_df))]

# fmla = as.formula(paste("value ~ ", paste(dvars, collapse = "+")))
fmla <- as.formula("value ~ nTicks +
  huntingGroupSize +
  factor(genderedMigration) +
  pTrading + factor(visibility) +

```

```

pVisiting + factor(learningMethod) + factor(gradualEnvChange) +
↪  campPopulation + pNewObject +
  aggregationFreq")

gam_md12 <- gam(fmla, data = variables_df)
summary(gam_md12)

xvars2 <- c("pNewAlliance", "maximumAlliesN", "pLoss", "pEnvChange",
↪  "aggregationDuration", "potteryPrestige", "pNewVariant",
↪  "transmissionRate", "pMigration", "nOfBands", "pNewVariant",
↪  "pLuckyLeap", "genderedMigration", "pHunting", "pTrading",
↪  "gradualEnvChange", "huntingGroupSize", "pNewObject",
↪  "pVisiting", "campPopulation")

dvars <- vars[which(!vars %in% xvars2)]
dvars <- dvars[which(dvars %in% names(variables_df))]

# fmla = as.formula(paste("value ~
↪  ",paste("factor(",dvars,")",collapse = "+")))
fmla <- as.formula("value ~
  nTicks +
  factor(visibility) +
  factor(learningMethod) +
  aggregationFreq")

gam_md13 <- gam(fmla, data = variables_df)

```

```

summary(gam_md13)

gam_nTicks <- gam(value ~ factor(nTicks), data = variables_df)
gam_visibility <- gam(value ~ factor(visibility), data =
  ↪ variables_df)
gam_pVisiting <- gam(value ~ pVisiting, data = variables_df)
gam_learningMethod <- gam(value ~ factor(learningMethod), data =
  ↪ variables_df)
gam_aggregationFreq <- gam(value ~ aggregationFreq, data =
  ↪ variables_df)
gam_campPopulation <- gam(value ~ campPopulation, data =
  ↪ variables_df)
summary(gam_nTicks)
summary(gam_visibility)
summary(gam_pVisiting)
summary(gam_learningMethod)
summary(gam_aggregationFreq)
summary(gam_campPopulation)

variables_df %>%
  select(-any_of(xvars2)) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(vars), names_to = "Variable", values_to =
  ↪ "parameter") %>%
  mutate(parameter = factor(parameter)) %>%
  rename(cor = value) %>%

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = parameter, y = cor, color = Variable)) +
geom_boxplot() +
guides(color = "none") +
theme_minimal() +
facet_wrap(~Variable, scales = "free_x")

# ggsave(here('figures/VariableCorrelations.tiff'),width = 7,height =
↪ 4.5, compression = "lzw", dpi = 900)
# ggsave(here('figures/VariableCorrelations.png'),width = 7,height =
↪ 4.5, dpi = 150)
# browseURL(here('figures/VariableCorrelations.tiff'))

#### look at individual networks ####
tictoc::tic()
g <- runs %>%
  filter(nOfBands == 5) %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 0) %>%
  filter(!is.na(wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency)) %>%
  slice_sample(n = 100) %>%
  mutate_all(as.character) %>%
  select(-runNumber) %>%
  rowid_to_column("runNumber") %>%
  pivot_longer(-runNumber,
  names_to = "property",
  values_to = "value"
) %>%

```

```

filter(property %in% vars | str_detect(property,
↪ "wordMatrixToRowListCamp|runNumber")) %>%
mutate(property = str_remove_all(
  property,
  "wordMatrixToRowListCamp|Adjacency"
)) %>%
pivot_wider(names_from = property, values_from = value) %>%
pivot_longer(Visiting:Pot, names_to = "property", values_to = "adj")
↪ %>%
filter(!is.na(adj)) %>%
mutate(property = tolower(property)) %>%
# rowwise() %>%
mutate(adj = formatNLAdjTables(adj)) %>%
pivot_wider(names_from = property, values_from = adj)
# ungroup()
tictoc::toc()
bands <- g$point[1][[1]] %>%
  select(name = from) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  bind_rows(g$point[1][[1]] %>%
    select(name = to)) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  mutate(band = sort(rep(0:4, 3)))

getGraphDF <- function(network, i = 1) {
  cutoff <- quantile(g[[network]][[i]]$weight, .5)

```

```

gdf <- g[[network]][[i]] %>%
  filter(weight > cutoff)
n <- graph_from_data_frame(gdf, directed = F)
# summary(n)
plotdf <- ggnetwork(n) %>%
  select(-band) %>%
  left_join(bands) %>%
  mutate(
    band = factor(band),
    network = !!network
  )

return(plotdf)
}

variables <- c("visiting", "learning", "trading", "point", "pot")
combined_df <- map_df(variables, getGraphDF) %>%
  mutate(network = factor(network, levels = variables))

p <- ggplot(combined_df, aes(x = x, y = y, xend = xend, yend = yend))
  ↪ +
  geom_edges(aes(color = weight, alpha = weight), linewidth = 1) +
  geom_nodelabel(aes(fill = band, label = name), size = 3, color =
  ↪ "white") +
  scale_fill_viridis_d() +

```

```

theme_void() +
coord_equal(ratio = 1 / 2, clip = "off", expand = T) +
theme(
  legend.position = "none",
  plot.background = element_rect(colour = "#404040", fill = NA,
  ↪ linewidth = .5),
  plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5),
  plot.margin = unit(c(2, 2, 2, 2), "mm"),
  strip.placement = "outside",
  strip.text = element_text(margin = margin(b = 10))
) +
facet_wrap(~network)

p

# ggsave("MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\SameTraits.png", dpi
↪ = 600, width = 8, height = 4.5, bg = "white")
# fn = "MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\SameTraits.tiff"
# ggsave(fn, dpi = 900, width = 7, height = 5, bg = "white",
↪ compression = "lzw")

# img = image_read(fn)
# img = image_trim(img)
# img = image_write(img, fn)
#

```

```

# image1 =
↪ image_read("MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\SameTraits.tiff")
# image2 =
↪ image_read("MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\UniqueTraits.tiff")

# image1_annotated <- image_annotate(image1, text = "a",
#                                     gravity = "northwest",
#                                     location = "+20+20",
#                                     size = 200, color = "black")
#
# image2_annotated <- image_annotate(image2, text = "b",
#                                     gravity = "northwest",
#                                     location = "+20+20",
#                                     size = 200, color = "black")

# stacked_images <- image_append(c(image1_annotated,
↪ image2_annotated), stack = TRUE)
# image_write(stacked_images,
↪ "MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\combined_networks.tiff")

# g1 = getGraph("visiting",2)
# g2 = getGraph("learning",2)
# g3 = getGraph("trading",2)
# g4 = getGraph("point",2)
# g5 = getGraph("pot",2)
#

```

```

# g1 + g2 + g3 + g4 + g5
# ggsave("MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\SameTraits2.png", dpi
↪ = 600, width = 8, height = 4.5, bg = "white")

g <- runs %>%
  filter(nOfBands > 3) %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
  filter(!is.na(wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency)) %>%
  slice_sample(n = 100) %>%
  mutate_all(as.character) %>%
  select(-runNumber) %>%
  rowid_to_column("runNumber") %>%
  pivot_longer(-runNumber,
    names_to = "property",
    values_to = "value"
  ) %>%
  filter(property %in% vars | str_detect(property,
↪ "wordMatrixToRowListCamp|runNumber")) %>%
  mutate(property = str_remove_all(
    property,
    "wordMatrixToRowListCamp|Adjacency"
  )) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = property, values_from = value) %>%
  pivot_longer(Visiting:Pot, names_to = "property", values_to = "adj")
↪ %>%
  filter(!is.na(adj)) %>%

```

```

mutate(property = tolower(property)) %>%
# rowwise() %>%

mutate(adj = formatNLAdjTables(adj)) %>%

pivot_wider(names_from = property, values_from = adj)

variables <- c("visiting", "learning", "trading", "point", "pot")
combined_df <- map_df(variables, getGraphDF) %>%
mutate(network = factor(network, levels = variables))

p <- ggplot(combined_df, aes(x = x, y = y, xend = xend, yend = yend))
↪ +
geom_edges(aes(color = weight, alpha = weight), linewidth = 1) +
geom_nodelabel(aes(fill = band, label = name), size = 3, color =
↪ "white") +
scale_fill_viridis_d() +
theme_void() +
coord_equal(ratio = 1 / 2, clip = "off", expand = T) +
theme(
  legend.position = "none",
  plot.background = element_rect(colour = "#404040", fill = NA,
↪ linewidth = .5),
  plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5),
  plot.margin = unit(c(2, 2, 2, 2), "mm"),
  strip.placement = "outside",
  strip.text = element_text(margin = margin(b = 10))
) +

```

```

facet_wrap(~network)

P

# fn = "MaterialCultureNetworksPaper\\figures\\UniqueTraits.tif"
# ggsave(fn, dpi = 900, width = 7, height = 5, bg = "white",
↪  compression = "lzw")
#
# img = image_read(fn)
# img = image_trim(img)
# img = image_write(img, fn)

#### centrality ####

largeNetworks <- runs %>%
  filter(nOfBands > 3) %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1)
results_point_e <- list()
results_pot_e <- list()
for (i in 1:nrow(largeNetworks)) {
  print(paste(i, "of", nrow(largeNetworks)))
  x <- largeNetworks[i, ]

  n1 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency"]])
  diag(n1) <- 0
  ec1 <- sna::evcent(n1)

```

```

n2 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPointAdjacency"]])
diag(n2) <- 0
ec2 <- sna::evcent(n2)
n3 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency"]])
diag(n3) <- 0
ec3 <- sna::evcent(n3)
r1 <- cor(ec2, ec1) %>% round(., 2)
r2 <- cor(ec3, ec1) %>% round(., 2)
results_point_e[[i]] <- r1
results_pot_e[[i]] <- r2
}

results_point_e <- unlist(results_point_e)
results_pot_e <- unlist(results_pot_e)
hist(results_point_e)
hist(results_pot_e)
results_point_e %>% summary()
results_pot_e %>% summary()

cor(largeNetworks$nOfBands, results_point_e)

plot(largeNetworks$nOfBands, results_point_e)

results_point_d <- list()
results_pot_d <- list()

```

```

for (i in 1:nrow(largeNetworks)) {
  print(paste(i, "of", nrow(largeNetworks)))
  x <- largeNetworks[i, ]

  n1 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency"]])
  diag(n1) <- 0
  dc1 <- sna::degree(n1)
  n2 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPointAdjacency"]])
  diag(n2) <- 0
  dc2 <- sna::degree(n2)
  n3 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency"]])
  diag(n3) <- 0
  dc3 <- sna::degree(n3)
  r1 <- cor(dc2, dc1) %>% round(., 2)
  r2 <- cor(dc3, dc1) %>% round(., 2)
  results_point_d[[i]] <- r1
  results_pot_d[[i]] <- r2
}

results_point_d <- unlist(results_point_d)
results_pot_d <- unlist(results_pot_d)
hist(results_point_d)
hist(results_pot_d)
results_point_d %>% summary()
results_pot_d %>% summary()

```

```

results_point_b <- list()
results_pot_b <- list()
for (i in 1:nrow(largeNetworks)) {
  print(paste(i, "of", nrow(largeNetworks)))
  x <- largeNetworks[i, ]

  n1 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency"]])
  diag(n1) <- 0
  bc1 <- sna::betweenness(n1)
  n2 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPointAdjacency"]])
  diag(n2) <- 0
  bc2 <- sna::betweenness(n2)
  n3 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency"]])
  diag(n3) <- 0
  bc3 <- sna::betweenness(n3)
  r1 <- cor(bc2, bc1) %>% round(., 2)
  r2 <- cor(bc3, bc1) %>% round(., 2)
  results_point_b[[i]] <- r1
  results_pot_b[[i]] <- r2
}

results_point_b <- unlist(results_point_b)
results_pot_b <- unlist(results_pot_b)
hist(results_point_b)
hist(results_pot_b)
results_point_b %>% summary()

```

```

results_pot_b %>% summary()

results_point_c <- list()
results_pot_c <- list()
for (i in 1:nrow(largeNetworks)) {
  print(paste(i, "of", nrow(largeNetworks)))
  x <- largeNetworks[i, ]

  n1 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampVisitingAdjacency"]])
  diag(n1) <- 0
  bc1 <- sna::closeness(n1)
  n2 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPointAdjacency"]])
  diag(n2) <- 0
  bc2 <- sna::closeness(n2)
  n3 <- matrix2zscore(x[["wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency"]])
  diag(n3) <- 0
  bc3 <- sna::closeness(n3)
  r1 <- cor(bc2, bc1) %>% round(., 2)
  r2 <- cor(bc3, bc1) %>% round(., 2)
  results_point_c[[i]] <- r1
  results_pot_c[[i]] <- r2

  # ng = n1
  # ng[ng > .75] = 1
  # ng[ng <= .75] = 0

```

```

# g = ng %>% graph_from_adjacency_matrix(mode = "undirected",
↪ weighted = F)
# degree_distribution(g)
}

results_point_c <- unlist(results_point_c)
results_pot_c <- unlist(results_pot_c)
hist(results_point_c)
hist(results_pot_c)
results_point_c %>% summary()
results_pot_c %>% summary()

# examine bad network correlation
library(mgcv)
points_df <- runs %>%
  filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
  select(expID, any_of(vars), any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(contains("_corZscore"))) %>%
  filter(name == "Visiting_Point_corZscore") %>%
  pivot_longer(vars, names_to = "variable", values_to = "parameter")
↪ %>%
  group_by(variable, parameter) %>%
  summarize(cor = mean(value, na.rm = T)) %>%
  mutate(parameter = as.character(parameter))

run_sample <- runs %>%

```

```

filter(uniqueTraits == 1) %>%
filter(pTrading > 0) %>%
filter(learningMethod == 50) %>%
filter(Visiting_Point_corZscore < 0) %>%
slice_sample(n = 1)
run_sample$experiment
run_sample$runNumber
run_sample$nTicks

default_vars <- defaults %>%
mutate(default = TRUE) %>%
select(parameters = Parameter, default_values = Default, default)

#### ERGM ####

library(statnet)
library(Rglpk)
library(ergm)
library(dplyr)
library(igraph)

# compare visiting and other networks to pot and point
# compare nonunique traits to unique traits

# statistics to include mcmc.diagnostics - check simulated
↪ distributions have a peak at the estimate and goodness of fit
↪ diagnostics

```

```

# are the same generative processes responsible for all networks? If
↪ we just had the material culture then would we still come to the
↪ same conclusions?

set.seed(1010)

run_ergm <- function(i, network, formula_type) {
  formula <- switch(formula_type,
    "edges" = ns ~ edges + nodematch("band"),
    "triangle" = ns ~ edges + triangle + nodematch("band"),
    "threetrail" = ns ~ edges + triangle + threetrail +
    ↪ nodematch("band"),
    "gwesp" = ns ~ edges + gwesp(0.25, fixed = TRUE) + threetrail +
    ↪ nodematch("band"),
    stop("Unknown formula type")
  )

  library(statnet)
  library(igraph)
  library(dplyr)
  g <- readRDS("data/graphSample.Rds")
  tryCatch(
    {
      cutoff <- quantile(g[[network]][[i]]$weight, .75)
      gdf <- g[[network]][[i]] %>%
        filter(weight > cutoff)
    }
  )
}

```

```

n <- graph_from_data_frame(gdf, directed = F)

nodeList <- gdf %>%
  select(id = from, band) %>%
  distinct_all()
ns <- intergraph::asNetwork(n)
ns %v% "band" <- nodeList$band
controlVals <- control.ergm(
  parallel = 14,
  seed = 1010,
  MCMLE.confidence = 0.9,
  MPLE.maxit = 1000
)
x <- tryCatch(
  ergm(formula, control = controlVals),
  error = function(e) {
    print(e)
    return(NA)
  }
)
e <- tryCatch(
  summary(x),
  error = function(e) {
    return(NA)
  }
)

```

```

gf <- tryCatch(
  gof(x),
  error = function(e) {
    return(NA)
  }
)
f <- tryCatch(
  x$formula %>% as.character() %>% paste(collapse = " "),
  error = function(e) {
    return(NA)
  }
)
aic <- tryCatch(
  e$aic,
  error = function(e) {
    return(NA)
  }
)
gf_pval <- tryCatch(
  gf$pval.model[1, 5],
  error = function(e) {
    return(NA)
  }
)
edges <- tryCatch(
  e$coefficients["edges", "Pr(>|z|)"],

```

```

    error = function(e) {
      return(NA)
    }
  )
result <- tibble(
  run = i,
  network = network,
  formula = f,
  aic = aic,
  gf_pval = gf_pval,
  edges = edges
)
saveRDS(
  result,
  paste0(
    "data/ergm_results_",
    i,
    "_",
    network,
    "_",
    formula_type,
    ".rds"
  )
)
return(result)
},

```

```

    error = function(e) {
      return(NA)
    }
  )
}

run_and_monitor_processes <- function(bg, timeout = 120) {
  start_times <- Sys.time()

  # Monitor processes
  while (TRUE) {
    Sys.sleep(1) # Check every second

    # Check the status of each process
    for (name in names(bg)) {
      if (bg[[name]]$is_alive()) {
        run_time <- as.numeric(difftime(Sys.time(), start_times, units
↵ = "secs"))

        if (shiny::isTruthy(run_time > timeout)) {
          bg[[name]]$kill() # Kill process if it exceeds timeout
          cat("Process", name, "killed after", run_time, "seconds\n")
        }
      }
    }
  }

  # Exit the loop if all processes are done

```

```

    if (all(!sapply(bg, function(p) p$is_alive()))) {
      break
    }
  }
}

# run_ergm(1, "trading", "edges")
library(callr)

bg <- list()

for (i in 1:10) {
  print(i)

  bg <- list()

  for (network in c("trading", "learning", "visiting", "point",
    ↪ "pot")) {
    print(network)
    bg <- list()

    for (formula_type in c("edges", "triangle", "threetrail",
    ↪ "gwesp")) {
      l <- list(i = i, network = network, formula_type = formula_type)
      bg[[paste0(i, "-", network, "-", formula_type)]] <-
    ↪ r_bg(run_ergm, args = l, supervise = FALSE)
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }
    run_and_monitor_processes(bg, timeout = 120)
  }
}

ls <- list.files("data/", pattern = "ergm_results", full.names = T)
ls <- ls[which(!str_detect(ls, ".csv"))]

results <- lapply(ls, readRDS) %>% bind_rows()

results_summary <- results %>%
  group_by(network, formula) %>%
  summarize(mean_gf_pval = mean(gf_pval, na.rm = T), mean_edges =
    ↪ mean(edges, na.rm = T), mean_aic = mean(aic, na.rm = T), count =
    ↪ n()) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(count > 15)

results_table <- results_summary %>%
  select(network, formula, gof = mean_gf_pval, aic = mean_aic) %>%
  filter(network %in% c("visiting", "point")) %>%
  mutate(formula = case_when(
    str_detect(formula, "gwesp") ~ "edge + gwesp + threetrail + band",
    str_detect(formula, "threetrail") ~ "edge + triangle + threetrail
    ↪ + band",

```

```

    TRUE ~ "edge + band"
  )) %>%
  arrange(network, formula)
results_table
results_table %>% write_csv("tables/ergm_results_table.csv")

results_summary2 <- results %>%
  group_by(formula) %>%
  summarize(mean_gf_pval = mean(gf_pval), mean_edges = mean(edges),
    ↪ mean_aic = mean(aic))
results_summary2
# graphical representation of how an ergm works

library(igraph)
set.seed(1010)
g <- readRDS("data/graphSample.Rds")
i <- 10
network <- "point"
cutoff <- quantile(g[[network]][[i]]$weight, .75)
gdf <- g[[network]][[i]] %>%
  filter(weight > cutoff)
n <- graph_from_data_frame(gdf, directed = F)

# nodeList = g[[network]][[i]] %>% select(id = from, band) %>%
# distinct_all()
nodeList <- structure(

```

```

list(id = c(
  "5", "6", "7", "8", "9", "10", "11", "12",
  "13", "14", "15", "16", "17", "18", "19"
), band = c(
  "0", "0", "0",
  "1", "1", "1", "2", "2", "2", "3", "3", "3", "4", "4", "4"
)),
row.names = c(
  NA,
  -15L
), class = c("tbl_df", "tbl", "data.frame")
)
g_df <- tibble(id = V(n)$name) %>%
  left_join(nodeList)
V(n)$band <- g_df$band
band_colors <- c("0" = "red", "1" = "blue", "2" = "green", "3" =
  ↪ "orange", "4" = "purple")
V(n)$color <- band_colors[V(n)$band]
# png("figures/ergm_example.png", width = 800, height = 800, bg =
  ↪ "black")
# plot(n, main = "", vertex.label.color = "black")
# title(main = "Observed Network", col.main = "white")
# dev.off()
# g_random <- rewire(n, keeping_degseq(niter = vcount(n) * 10))
# png("figures/ergm_example_random.png", width = 800, height = 800,
  ↪ bg = "black")

```

```

# plot(g_random, main = "", vertex.label.color = "black")
# title(main = "Random Network", col.main = "white")
# dev.off()

# g <- make_ring(15) %>%
#   add_edges(c(1,5, 2,6, 3,7, 4,8, 5,9, 6,10, 7,11, 8,12, 9,13,
# ↪ 10,14, 11,15))

# plot(g)

ns <- intergraph::asNetwork(n)

# plot(ns)

formula_type <- "gwest"

formula <- switch(formula_type,
  "edges" = ns ~ edges + nodematch("band"),
  "triangle" = ns ~ edges + triangle + nodematch("band"),
  "threetrail" = ns ~ edges + triangle + threetrail +
  ↪ nodematch("band"),
  "gwest" = ns ~ edges + gwest(0.25, fixed = TRUE) + threetrail +
  ↪ nodematch("band"),
  stop("Unknown formula type")
)

random_ergm <- ergm(formula)
summary(random_ergm)
pgof <- gof(random_ergm)
pdf(glue::glue("figures/gof_{network}_{formula_type}.pdf"))
plot(pgof)
dev.off()

```

```

# test probability that random networks are correlated

g <- readRDS("data/graphSample.Rds")
i <- sample(1:100, 1)
i
network <- "visiting"
cutoff <- quantile(g[[network]][[i]]$weight, .75)
gdf <- g[[network]][[i]] %>%
  filter(weight > cutoff)
n <- graph_from_data_frame(gdf, directed = F)

nodeList <- gdf %>%
  select(id = from, band) %>%
  distinct_all()
ns <- intergraph::asNetwork(n)
ns %v% "band" <- nodeList$band
controlVals <- control.ergm(
  parallel = 14,
  seed = 1010,
  MCMLE.confidence = 0.9,
  MPLE.maxit = 1000
)

ergm_model <- ergm(ns ~ edges + triangle + threerail +
  ↪ nodematch("band"), control = controlVals)
# ns_visiting = ns

```

```

nsim <- simulate(ergm_model, nsim = 10000)
gcor_values <- numeric(length = length(nsim))
# ns_matrix = as.matrix(ns)
ns_matrix <- as.matrix(ns_visiting)

# Loop through each simulated network and calculate gcor
for (i in seq_along(nsim)) {
  nsim_matrix <- as.matrix(nsim[[i]]) # Convert simulated network to
  ↪ matrix
  ns_row_names <- rownames(ns_matrix)
  ns_col_names <- colnames(ns_matrix)
  nsim_row_names <- rownames(nsim_matrix)
  nsim_col_names <- colnames(nsim_matrix)

  # Union of row and column names (all possible nodes in both
  ↪ matrices)
  all_row_names <- union(ns_row_names, nsim_row_names)
  all_col_names <- union(ns_col_names, nsim_col_names)

  # Initialize matrices to the larger set of row and column names,
  ↪ filled with zeros
  new_ns_matrix <- matrix(0,
    nrow = length(all_row_names), ncol = length(all_col_names),
    dimnames = list(all_row_names, all_col_names)
  )

```

```

new_nsim_matrix <- matrix(0,
  nrow = length(all_row_names), ncol = length(all_col_names),
  dimnames = list(all_row_names, all_col_names)
)

# Fill the new matrices with the values from the original matrices
new_ns_matrix[ns_row_names, ns_col_names] <- ns_matrix
new_nsim_matrix[nsim_row_names, nsim_col_names] <- nsim_matrix
gcor_values[i] <- gcor(new_ns_matrix, new_nsim_matrix) # Calculate
↪ gcor
}

hist(gcor_values)
gcor_values %>% summary()

network <- "visiting"
cutoff <- quantile(g[[network]][[i]]$weight, .75)
gdf <- g[[network]][[i]] %>%
  filter(weight > cutoff)
n <- graph_from_data_frame(gdf, directed = F)

nodeList <- gdf %>%
  select(id = from, band) %>%
  distinct_all()

```

```

ns <- intergraph::asNetwork(n)
ns %v% "band" <- nodeList$band
controlVals <- control.ergm(
  parallel = 14,
  seed = 1010,
  MCMLE.confidence = 0.9,
  MPLE.maxit = 1000
)

ergm_model <- ergm(ns ~ edges + triangle + threerail +
  ↪ nodematch("band"), control = controlVals)
nsim <- simulate(ergm_model, nsim = 1000)
gcor_values <- numeric(length = length(nsim))
ns_matrix <- as.matrix(ns)

# Loop through each simulated network and calculate gcor
for (i in seq_along(nsim)) {
  nsim_matrix <- as.matrix(nsim[[i]]) # Convert simulated network to
  ↪ matrix
  gcor_values[i] <- gcor(ns_matrix, nsim_matrix) # Calculate gcor
}

# hist(gcor_values)
# gcor_values %>% summary()

```

```

#### export session info ####

# Get the R version
r_version <- paste0("R version=", paste(R.version$major,
↪ R.version$minor, sep = "."))

# Get the loaded packages and their versions
loaded_packages <- sessionInfo()$otherPkgs
loaded_versions <- sapply(loaded_packages, function(x)
↪ paste(x$Package, x$Version, sep = "="))

# Write the R version and package versions to the file
writeLines(c(r_version, loaded_versions), con =
↪ "analysis/r_environment.qmd")

```

Functions

```

# custom functions
library(tictoc)
library(magrittr)
library(ggnetwork)
library(ggthemes)

#' Load all data by specifying one complete name or the partial date
↪ file name
#'
#' @param fileName

```

```

#'
#' @return
#' @export
#'
#' @examples
loadRun <- function(fileName) {
  if (file.exists(here(stringr::str_glue("results/{fileName}")))) {
    fileName %<>% str_remove_all("run_[A-z]*_")
  }
  map(
    list.files(here("results"),
              pattern = fileName,
              full.names = T
            ) %>% .[str_detect(., fileName)],
    ~
    read_csv(., show_col_types = F)
  ) %>% set_names(c(
    "assemblages",
    "links",
    "nodes",
    "variables"
  ))
}

# x = runResults$assemblages$pointAssemblage[[7]]

```

```

#' Convert NetLogo list format into R list
bracket2list <- function(x) {
  if (str_detect(x, "[0-9]")) {
    x %>%
      str_remove_all("\\\\|\\[") %>%
      str_split_fixed(" ", n = Inf) %>%
      matrix(ncol = 2, byrow = T) %>%
      as_tibble(.name_repair = "minimal") %>%
      setNames(c("tick", "tool"))
  } else {
    NA
  }
}

#' Calculate manhattan similarity
#'
#' @param analysis dataframe formatted through formatAssemblage
↳ function
#' @param type pot or point
#' @param group band or site
#' @param cutoff quantile cutoff to keep links
#' @param similarity either 'BR' for Brainerd-Robinson or 'WJ' for
↳ weighted Jaccard
#'
#' @return dataframe of nodes and dataframe of links

```

```

#' @export
#'
#' @examples
calcDistanceTools <- function(analysis,
                               toolType = "pot",
                               group = "band",
                               cutoff = 0,
                               similarity = "WJ") {

  tmp <- analysis %>%
    filter(type == toolType)
  m <- table(tmp[[group]], tmp$tool) %>%
    prop.table(1) %>%
    {
      . * 100
    }

  # calculate similarity
  if (similarity == "BR") {
    g <- dist(m, "manhattan") %>%
      as.matrix()
    g <- 1 - (g / 200)
    diag(g) <- 0
    # g[] = round(g, 2)
  } else {
    g <- weightedJaccard(m)
    # g[] = round(g, 2)
  }
}

```

```

}

links <- g %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("from") %>%
  pivot_longer(-from,
    names_to = "to",
    values_to = "weight"
  ) %>%
  # remove duplicate links
  dplyr::rowwise() %>%
  mutate(combo = paste(min(from, to), max(from, to))) %>%
  arrange(desc(to)) %>%
  distinct(combo, .keep_all = T) %>%
  select(-combo)

links %<>%
  filter(weight > 0)

cutoff <- quantile(links$weight, cutoff)

links %<>%
  filter(weight >= cutoff) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(weight), round, 2)

if (group != "band" & "band" %in% names(analysis)) {
  nodes <- links %>%
    select(from, to) %>%
    pivot_longer(c(from, to), values_to = "name", names_to = "var")
  ↪ %>%

```

```

select(name) %>%
  arrange(name) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  full_join(
    analysis %>%
      select(name = site, band) %>%
      mutate_at(vars(name), as.character),
    by = "name"
  ) %>%
  mutate(camp = name) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  mutate_at(vars(band), factor)
} else {
  nodes <- analysis %>%
    ungroup() %>%
    select(any_of(group)) %>%
    mutate(name = !!as.name(group)) %>%
    distinct_all()
}

return(list(links = links, nodes = nodes))
}

# function to remove labels from names
rmLabel <- function(x) {
  map_chr(

```

```

x,
~ str_extract_all(.x, "[0-9]") %>%
  unlist() %>%
  paste(collapse = "")
)
}

# links = runResults$links
# nodes = runResults$nodes
calcDistanceLinks <- function(links,
                               nodes,
                               colS = "all",
                               group,
                               cutoff = 0) {
  if (colS == "all") {
    colS <- c("learning", "hunting", "visiting", "trading")
  }
  df <- links %>%
    select(end1, end2, all_of(colS)) %>%
    mutate_at(vars(end1, end2), rmLabel) %>%
    left_join(
      nodes %>%
        select(end1 = who, band, camp) %>%
        mutate(end1 = end1 %>% as.character()),
      by = "end1"
    ) %>%

```

```

left_join(
  nodes %>%
    select(end2 = who, band, camp) %>%
    mutate(end2 = end2 %>% as.character()),
  by = "end2",
  suffix = c("", "2")
)
linksMod <- df %>%
  select(group, any_of(str_glue("{group}2")), all_of(colS)) %>%
  # create unique paths
  mutate(path = map2_chr(
    !!as.name(group),
    !!as.name(str_glue("{group}2")),
    ~ sort(c(.x, .y)) %>% paste(collapse = "_")
  )) %>%
  group_by(path) %>%
  summarize_at(vars(all_of(colS)), sum) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  separate(path, into = c(group, str_glue("{group}2")), sep = "_")
  ↪ %>%
  mutate_at(vars(group, str_glue("{group}2")), as.character) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  mutate_at(vars(group, str_glue("{group}2")), factor) %>%
  filter(!as.name(group) != !!as.name(str_glue("{group}2"))) %>%
  mutate(total = rowSums(select(., .dots = any_of(colS))))

```

```

newLinks <- map(colS %>% c("total"), function(c) {
  x <- quantile(linksMod[[c]], cutoff)
  linksTmp <- linksMod %>%
    select(
      from = all_of(group),
      to = all_of(str_glue("{group}2")),
      weight = !!as.name(c)
    ) %>%
    filter(weight >= x) %>%
    arrange(gtools::mixedsort(from))
}) %>% setNames(colS %>% c("total"))

newNodes <- df %>%
  select(any_of(contains(c("camp", "band")))) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  rowid_to_column() %>%
  pivot_longer(-rowid) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(name), list(~ str_remove_all(.x, "2"))) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  pivot_wider(
    names_from = name,
    values_from = value,
    values_fn = list
  ) %>%
  unchop(c(band, camp)) %>%
  select(-rowid) %>%

```

```

distinct_all() %>%
select(camp, band) %>%
mutate_all(factor) %>%
mutate(name = !!as.name(group))

return(list(links = newLinks, nodes = newNodes))
}

plotGraph <- function(links,
                      nodes,
                      title = "",
                      weighted = T,
                      color = NA,
                      shape = NA,
                      labels = T,
                      nodeSize = 10,
                      save = F,
                      layout = NA,
                      plotDevice = "svg",
                      groupByBand = F) {
  # layout are coordinates for each node in a data frame format

  # old <- .Random.seed
  # on.exit({
  #   .Random.seed <<- old
  # })

```

```

# set.seed(5010)

if (is.data.frame(layout)) {
  if (is.matrix(links)) {
    links <- links %>%
      as.data.frame() %>%
      rownames_to_column("from") %>%
      pivot_longer(-from, names_to = "to", values_to = "weight")
  }
  plotdf <- links %>%
    rename(name = from) %>%
    full_join(layout, by = "name") %>%
    left_join(
      layout %>% rename(
        to = name,
        xend = x,
        yend = y
      ),
      by = "to"
    )
} else if (is.data.frame(links)) {
  n <- igraph::graph_from_data_frame(links, directed = F)
} else if (is.matrix(links)) {
  colnames(links) <- rownames(links) <- nodes$name
  n <- igraph::graph_from_adjacency_matrix(links, mode =
↪ "undirected", weighted = T, diag = F)

```

```

} else {
  stop("check class of links")
}

if (!is.data.frame(layout)) {
  if (groupByBand) {
    V(n)$band <- nodes$band
    nG <- contract(n, as.integer(V(n)$band) + 1, vertex.attr.comb =
↪ "first")
    V(nG)$name <- nodes$band %>% unique()
    nG <- simplify(nG, edge.attr.comb = "sum")
    plotdf <- ggnetwork::ggnetwork(nG) %>%
      as_tibble()
  } else {
    plotdf <- ggnetwork::ggnetwork(n) %>%
      as_tibble()
  }
}

plotdf %<>%
  mutate(weight = weight %>% as.numeric()) %>%
  left_join(nodes %>% mutate_at(vars(name), as.character),
    by = "name"
  )

gg <-

```

```

plotdf %>%
  ggplot(aes(
    x = x,
    y = y,
    xend = xend,
    yend = yend
  ))
if (weighted == T) {
  print("adding weights")
  gg <- gg +
    geom_edges(aes(color = weight), size = .75) +
    scale_color_viridis_c(
      direction = -1,
      breaks = c(
        min(plotdf$weight, na.rm = T),
        max(plotdf$weight, na.rm = T)
      ),
      labels = c("low", "high")
    )
} else {
  gg <- gg +
    geom_edges(
      color = "black",
      size = .5,
      alpha = .5
    )
}

```

```

}
if (!is.na(shape) && shape == "band" & is.na(color)) {
  print("adding shape")
  gg <- gg +
    geom_point(aes(shape = !!as.name(shape)),
              size = nodeSize
            ) +
    scale_shape_manual(values = c(15, 17, 19))
} else if (isTRUE(shape == "band" & !is.na(color))) {
  print("adding shape and color")
  gg <- gg +
    geom_point(
      aes(
        shape = !!as.name(shape),
        fill = !!as.name(color)
      ),
      size = nodeSize
    ) +
    scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set1") +
    scale_shape_manual(values = c(21, 22, 24))
} else if (shape != "band" & !is.na(shape)) {
  stop("too many shapes -- maybe try color?")
} else if (is.na(shape) & !is.na(color)) {
  print("adding color")
  gg <- gg +
    geom_point(aes(fill = !!as.name(color)),

```

```

    size = nodeSize,
    shape = 21
  ) +
  scale_fill_brewer(palette = "Set1")
} else {
  gg <- gg +
  geom_point(
    size = nodeSize,
    color = "black",
    shape = 19
  )
}

if (labels == T) {
  print("adding labels")
  gg <- gg +
  geom_nodetext(aes(label = name),
    # size = 3,
    fontface = "bold",
    color = "white"
  )
}

# determine if legend shape should be overridden
if (!is.na(shape)) {
  f1 <- guide_legend()

```

```

} else if (isTRUE(!is.na(color) && shape != color) | !is.na(color))
↪ {
  f1 <- guide_legend(override.aes = list(shape = 21))
} else {
  f1 <- guide_legend()
}
gg <- gg +
  theme_blank() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "bottom",
    legend.background = element_rect(fill = F),
    plot.margin = margin(0, 0, 0, 0)
  ) +
  coord_cartesian(clip = "off") +
  guides(
    fill = f1,
    shape = guide_legend(direction = "horizontal"),
    color = guide_colorbar(
      direction = "horizontal",
      title.position = "top"
    )
  ) +
  ggtitle(title)
print(gg)
if (save == T) {
  if (plotDevice == tolower("svg")) {

```

```

    ggsave(
      filename = glue::glue("plots/{title}.svg"),
      plot = gg
    )
  } else if (plotDevice == tolower("png")) {
    ggsave(
      filename = glue::glue("plots/{title}.png"),
      plot = gg,
      dpi = 450
    )
  } else {
    stop("how about svg or png instead?")
  }
}
return(gg)
}

#' Calculate weighted Jaccard
weightedJaccard <- function(m) {
  #' weighted jaccard similarity matrix setup
  #' from:
  #' https://rpubs.com/lgadar/weighted-jaccard

  r <- matrix(0, nrow = nrow(m), ncol = nrow(m))
  rownames(r) <- rownames(m)
  colnames(r) <- rownames(m)
}

```

```

# weighted jaccard
pairs <- t(combn(1:nrow(m), 2))
for (i in 1:nrow(pairs)) {
  num <-
    sum(sapply(1:ncol(m), function(x) {
      (min(m[pairs[i, 1], x], m[pairs[i, 2], x]))
    }))
  den <-
    sum(sapply(1:ncol(m), function(x) {
      (max(m[pairs[i, 1], x], m[pairs[i, 2], x]))
    }))
  r[pairs[i, 1], pairs[i, 2]] <- num / den
  r[pairs[i, 2], pairs[i, 1]] <- num / den
}
r[which(is.na(r))] <- 0
diag(r) <- 0
return(r)
}

#' Format netlogo adjacency tables as matrices
#'
#' @param x Netlogo matrix
#'
#' @return
#' @export

```

```

#'
#' @examples
string2MatrixR <- function(x) {
  m <- x %>%
    str_remove_all("\\[[\\[|\\]\\]\\]") %>%
    str_split_1(pattern = fixed("] [")) %>%
    as.matrix() %>%
    apply(1, str_split_1, pattern = " ")
  m[] <- as.double(m[])
  return(m)
}

library(Rcpp)
sourceCpp("analysis/string2matrix.cpp")

#' Format Netlogo Adjacency Tables
#'
#' @param p run number
#' @param nB number of bands
#' @param cutoff cutoff value
#' @param x adjacency table formatted as string
#'
#' @return
#' @export
#'
#' @examples

```

```

formatNLAdjTables <- function(x, p = NULL, standardize = T) {
  result <- purrr::map(x, function(x1) {
    m <- string2matrix(x1)
    nB <- ncol(m) / 3
    nms <- nB:(nB * 3 + nB - 1)
    bands <- data.frame(band = as.character(sort(rep(0:(nB - 1),
↪ 3))), camp = as.character(nms))
    colnames(m) <- rownames(m) <- nms
    df <- as.data.frame(m) %>%
      rownames_to_column("from") %>%
      pivot_longer(all_of(nms %>% as.character()),
        names_to = "to",
        values_to = "weight"
      )
    if (!is.null(p)) {
      df <- df %>%
        mutate(property = p) %>%
        mutate(id = map2_chr(from, to, function(f, t) {
          sort(c(f, t)) %>%
            paste(collapse = "_")
        })) %>%
        distinct(id, .keep_all = T) %>%
        select(-id) %>%
        separate(
          col = property,
          into = c("run_number", "property"),

```

```

      sep = "_",
      extra = "drop"
    )
  }

df <- df %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(id = sort(c(from, to)) %>% paste(collapse = "_")) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  distinct(id, .keep_all = T) %>%
  filter(from != to) %>%
  filter(weight > 0)

if (standardize) {
  df <- df %>%
    mutate(weight = weight / max(weight))
}

df <- df %>%
  # mutate_at(vars(from, to), as.character) %>%
  left_join(bands %>% rename(from = camp), by = "from")
return(df)
})

# nodes = tibble(camp = nms,
#                 band = rep((1:nB - 1), 3) %>% sort) %>%
# mutate_all(as.character) %>%

```

```

# mutate(name = camp)
# return(list(links = links, nodes = nodes))
return(result)
}

#' Format assemblages into a data frame structure
formatAssemblages <- function(assemblages) {
  # tictoc::tic()
  tmp <- assemblages %>%
    # remove the aggregation sites
    filter(!is.na(band)) %>%
    mutate_at(vars(band, site), as.character)
  pot <- tmp %>%
    select(band, site, potAssemblage) %>%
    mutate(potAssemblage = potAssemblage %>%
      map(bracket2list)) %>%
    unnest(potAssemblage) %>%
    mutate(type = "pot") %>%
    select(band, site, tick, type, tool)
  point <- tmp %>%
    select(band, site, pointAssemblage) %>%
    mutate(pointAssemblage = pointAssemblage %>%
      map(bracket2list)) %>%
    unnest(pointAssemblage) %>%
    mutate(type = "point") %>%
    select(band, site, tick, type, tool)
}

```

```

# print(tictoc::toc())$elapsed)
return(bind_rows(pot, point))
}

#' Create attribute network
attrNetworks <- function(runResults,
                          attr = "pointAttributes",
                          group = "who") {
  links <- runResults$nodes %>%
    select(who, band, camp, !!as.name(attr)) %>%
    mutate(attr = !!as.name(attr) %>% str_remove_all("\\[[|\\]")) %>%
    select(-!!as.name(attr)) %>%
    separate_rows(attr, sep = " ")
  # table(links$who, links$attr)
  if (group == "camp") {
    links %<>%
      select(-who) %>%
      distinct_all()
  } else if (group == "band") {
    links %<>%
      select(-who, -camp) %>%
      distinct_all()
  }
  d <-
  table(
    links[[group]],

```

```

    links$attr
  )
n <- nrow(d)
m <- matrix(nrow = n, ncol = n)
rownames(m) <- rownames(d)
colnames(m) <- rownames(d)
for (i in 1:n) {
  for (j in 1:n) {
    r1 <- which(d[i, ] > 0)
    r2 <- which(d[j, ] > 0)
    m[i, j] <- intersect(
      r1,
      r2
    ) %>%
      length()
  }
}
m
diag(m) <- 0
m[which(m < 2)] <- 0
g <- list()
g$links <- as.data.frame(m) %>%
  rownames_to_column("from") %>%
  pivot_longer(2:ncol(.), names_to = "to", values_to = "weight")
  ↪ %>%
  filter(weight > 0) %>%

```

```

mutate(id = map2_chr(
  from, to,
  ~ paste0(min(.x, .y), "_", max(.x, .y))
)) %>%
distinct(id, .keep_all = T) %>%
select(-id)
g$nodes <- links %>%
  mutate(name = !!as.name(group)) %>%
  mutate_all(as.character) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(any_of(c(
    "who", "name", "camp", "band"
  ))), list(function(x) {
    factor(x, levels = unique(x) %>% gtools::mixedsort())
  }))
return(g)
}

#' Select a proportion of the data either randomly or nonrandomly
sampleData <- function(df,
  p, # proportion of each site to keep
  method # c("random", "nonrandom")
) {
  s <- df %>%
    group_by(site) %>%
    count() %>%
    mutate(

```

```

    c = floor(n * p),
    c = case_when(c == 0 ~ 1, TRUE ~ c)
  )
if (method == "random") {
  rs <- df %>%
    group_by(site) %>%
    group_split()
  r <- map2_dfr(rs, s$c, ~ {
    .x %>%
      slice_sample(n = .y)
  })
} else {
  rs <- df %>%
    slice(gtools::mixedorder(site)) %>%
    arrange(site) %>%
    rowid_to_column() %>%
    group_by(site) %>%
    group_split()
  r <- map2_dfr(
    rs,
    s$c, function(rsi, si) {
      print("asdf")
      indx <- rsi %>%
        group_by(site) %>%
        slice_sample(n = 1) %>%
        pull(rowid)
    }
  )
}

```

```

indx2 <- indx + si
if (indx2 > max(rsi$rowid)) {
  tmp1 <- rsi %>%
    filter(
      rowid >= indx,
      rowid <= max(rsi$rowid)
    )
  n <- si - nrow(tmp1)
  indx <- rsi$rowid[which.min(rsi$rowid)]
  indx2 <- indx + n

  tmp2 <- rsi %>%
    filter(
      rowid >= indx,
      rowid < indx2
    )
  rsi <- bind_rows(tmp1, tmp2)
} else {
  rsi %<>%
    filter(
      rowid >= indx,
      rowid < indx2
    )
}
return(rsi)

```

```

    }
  )
}
return(r)
}

compareMissing <- function(df,
                           group,
                           prop, # proportion of each site to keep
                           method # c("random", "nonrandom")){
) {
  df %<>% rename(group = !!as.name(group))
  original <- table(df$site, df$tool) %>%
    prop.table(1) %>%
    {
      . * 100
    } %>%
  weightedJaccard()
  results <- map_dfr(prop, function(p) {
    print(paste("running", method, p))
    reduced <- sampleData(df = df, p = p, method = method)
    sampled <- table(reduced$site, reduced$tool) %>%
      prop.table(1) %>%
      {
        . * 100
      } %>%

```

```

    weightedJaccard()
  l <- list(original, sampled)
  distance <- try(round(nd.dsd(l,
    out.dist = T,
    type = "Lap"
  )$D, 3))
  if (inherits(distance, "try-error")) {
    distance <- NA_real_
  }
  result <- tibble(
    count = nrow(reduced),
    proportion = p,
    method = method,
    distance = unlist(distance)[1]
  )
  return(result)
})
return(results)
}

formatMatrix <- function(net, q = 0, binarize = F, rescale = T,
↪ groupByBand = F) {
  if (inherits(net, "list")) {
    net <- net[[1]]
  }
  if (inherits(net[1, 1], "character")) {

```

```

net <- apply(net, 1, as.numeric)
}
if (groupByBand) {
  nB <- ncol(net) / 3
  bNms <- 0:(nB - 1)
  nms <- (nB):(ncol(net) + (nB - 1))
  colnames(net) <- rownames(net) <- nms
  n <- igraph::graph_from_adjacency_matrix(net, mode =
↪ "undirected", weighted = T, diag = F)
  igraph::V(n)$band <- bNms
  nG <- igraph::contract(n, as.integer(V(n)$band) + 1,
↪ vertex.attr.comb = "first")
  igraph::V(nG)$name <- bNms
  nG <- igraph::simplify(nG, edge.attr.comb = "sum")
  net <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(nG, attr = "weight") %>%
↪ as.matrix()
}
if (q > 0) {
  cutoff <- quantile(net, q)
  net[which(net <= cutoff)] <- 0
  if (binarize) {
    net[which(net > cutoff)] <- 1
  }
}
if (rescale) {
  net <- log(net + 1)
}

```

```

    net <- scales::rescale(net)
  }
  rownames(net) <- colnames(net) <- 1:ncol(net)
  return(net)
}

adjacency_compare <- function(net1, net2, q = 0, binarize = F,
  ↪ rescale = T) {
  net1 <- formatMatrix(net1, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
  ↪ rescale)
  net2 <- formatMatrix(net2, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
  ↪ rescale)
  net_diff <- abs(net1 - net2)
  out <-
    1 - (sum(net_diff) / (nrow(net_diff) * (nrow(net_diff) - 1)))
  return(out)
}

adjacency_compare2 <- function(net1, net2) {
  if (!identical(dim(net1), dim(net2))) {
    warning("matrices must be the same size: returning NA")
    return(NA)
  } else if (any(is.na(net1)) || any(is.na(net2))) {
    warning("matrices must not be NA: returning NA")
    return(NA)
  } else if (any(is.infinite(net1)) || any(is.infinite(net2))) {

```

```

warning("matrices must not be Infinite: returning NA")
return(NA)
} else {
  diag(net1) <- diag(net2) <- 0
  net_diff <- abs(net1 - net2)
  out <- 1 - sum(net_diff) / (nrow(net_diff) * nrow(net_diff))
  return(out)
}
}

adjacency_compare3 <- function(net1, net2) {
  net_diff <- sum(abs(net1 - net2))
  return(net_diff)
}

cor_compare <- function(net1, net2) {
  tryCatch(
    {
      if (!identical(dim(net1), dim(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must be the same size: returning NA")
        return(NA)
      } else if (any(is.na(net1)) || any(is.na(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must not be NA: returning NA")
        return(NA)
      } else if (any(is.infinite(net1)) || any(is.infinite(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must not be Infinite: returning NA")

```

```

    return(NA)
  } else {
    diag(net1) <- diag(net2) <- 0
    out <- sna::gcor(net1, net2)
    return(out)
  }
},
error = function(e) {
  return(NA)
}
)
}

qapTestFun <- function(net1, net2) {
  tryCatch(
    {
      if (!identical(dim(net1), dim(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must be the same size: returning NA")
        return(NA)
      } else if (any(is.na(net1)) || any(is.na(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must not be NA: returning NA")
        return(NA)
      } else if (any(is.infinite(net1)) || any(is.infinite(net2))) {
        warning("matrices must not be Infinite: returning NA")
        return(NA)
      } else {

```

```

    diag(net1) <- diag(net2) <- 0
    out <- sna::qaptest(list(net1, net2), sna::gcor, g1 = 1, g2 =
↪ 2)$pleeq
    return(out)
  }
},
error = function(e) {
  return(NA)
}
)
}

adjacency_correlation <- function(net1, net2, q = 0, binarize = T,
↪ rescale = F) {
  net1 <- formatMatrix(net1, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
↪ rescale)
  net2 <- formatMatrix(net2, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
↪ rescale)
  library(igraph)
  g1 <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(net1, mode = "undirected", diag
↪ = F)
  g2 <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(net2, mode = "undirected", diag
↪ = F)
  library(multinet)
  net <- ml_empty("comparison")
  add_igraph_layer_ml(net, g1, "net1")

```

```

add_igraph_layer_ml(net, g2, "net2")
m <- layer_comparison_ml(net, method = "pearson.degree", mode =
↪ "all")
diag(m) <- NA
return(max(m, na.rm = T))
}

adjacency_laplacian <- function(net1, net2, q = 0, binarize = F,
↪ rescale = T) {
  net1 <- formatMatrix(net1, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
↪ rescale)
  net2 <- formatMatrix(net2, q = q, binarize = binarize, rescale =
↪ rescale)
  library(NetworkDistance)
  l <- list(net1, net2)
  m <- round(nd.dsd(l,
    out.dist = T,
    type = "Lap"
  )$D, 3)
  return(m)
}

adjacency_laplacian2 <- function(net1, net2) {
  if (!identical(dim(net1), dim(net2))) {
    warning("matrices must be the same size: returning NA")
    return(NA)
  }
}

```

```

} else if (any(is.na(net1)) || any(is.na(net2))) {
  warning("matrices must not be NA: returning NA")
  return(NA)
} else if (any(is.infinite(net1)) || any(is.infinite(net2))) {
  warning("matrices must not be Infinite: returning NA")
  return(NA)
} else {
  library(NetworkDistance)
  l <- list(net1, net2)
  m <- round(nd.dsd(l,
    out.dist = T,
    type = "Lap"
  )$D, 3)
  return(m)
}
}

compareAdjacencyResults <- function(runs) {
  results <- runs %>%
  mutate_all(as.character) %>%
  pivot_longer(-run_number,
    names_to = "property",
    values_to = "value"
  ) %>%
  mutate(property = str_remove_all(

```

```

    property,
    "matrix_to_row_list_camp_l_adjacency"
  )) %>%

  pivot_wider(names_from = property, values_from = value) %>%
  pivot_longer(visiting:pot, names_to = "property", values_to =
  ↪ "adj") %>%
  unite("id", run_number, property, remove = F)

nB <- runs %>%
  select(n_of_bands) %>%
  dplyr::pull() %>%
  unique()

formatted <- map2_df(
  results$adj, results$id,
  formatNLAdjTables, nB
)

nms <- nB:(nB * 3 + nB - 1)
nodes <- tibble(
  camp = nms,
  band = rep((1:nB - 1), 3) %>% sort()
) %>%
  mutate_all(as.character) %>%
  mutate(name = camp)

groups <- formatted$property %>%

```

```

unique() %>%
sort()
comparison <- tibble()
for (i in formatted$run_number %>%
unique() %>%
as.integer()) {
print(i)
try({
run <- formatted %>%
filter(run_number == i)
nms <- run$property %>%
unique() %>%
sort()
run %<>%
group_by(property) %>%
group_split() %>%
setNames(nms)

# plotGraph(run$hunting,nodes, "hunting",shape = 'band', color
↪ = 'band')
cutoff <- quantile(run$learning$weight, 0.5)
run$learning %<>% filter(weight > cutoff)
# plotGraph(run$learning,nodes, "learning",shape = 'band',
↪ color = 'band')
cutoff <- quantile(run$trading$weight, 0.5)

```

```

run$trading %<>% filter(weight > cutoff)
# plotGraph(run$trading,nodes, "trading",shape = 'band', color
↪ = 'band')

cutoff <- quantile(run$visiting$weight, 0.5)
run$visiting %<>% filter(weight > cutoff)
# plotGraph(run$visiting,nodes, "visiting",shape = 'band',
↪ color = 'band')

cutoff <- quantile(total$weight, 0.5)
# plotGraph(total,nodes, "total",shape = 'band', color =
↪ 'band')

cutoff <- quantile(run$point$weight, 0.5)
run$point %<>% filter(weight > cutoff)
# plotGraph(run$point,nodes, "point",shape = 'band', color =
↪ 'band')

cutoff <- quantile(run$pot$weight, 0.5)
run$pot %<>% filter(weight > cutoff)
# plotGraph(run$pot,nodes, "pot",shape = 'band', color =
↪ 'band')

# multilayer network
library(igraph)
library(multinet)
net <- ml_empty("comparison")

```

```

    ig1 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$pot, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig1)$weight <- run$pot$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig1, name = "pots")
    ig2 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$point, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig2)$weight <- run$point$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig2, name = "points")
    ig3 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$ hunting, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig3)$weight <- run$hunting$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig3, name = "hunting")
    ig4 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$learning, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig4)$weight <- run$learning$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig4, name = "learning")
    ig5 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$trading, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig5)$weight <- run$trading$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig5, name = "trading")
    ig6 <- graph_from_data_frame(d = run$visiting, directed = F,
↳ vertices = nodes)
    E(ig6)$weight <- run$visiting$weight
    add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = ig6, name = "visiting")
    m2raw <- layer_comparison_ml(net, method = "pearson.degree",
↳ mode = "all")

```

```

m2 <- round(m2raw, 2) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("from") %>%
  pivot_longer(-from, names_to = "to") %>%
  filter(from != to) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(variable = paste0(
    paste(sort(c(from, to)), collapse = "->"),
    "-pearson.degree"
  ), .before = 1) %>%
  select(-from, -to) %>%
  distinct_all()
# m %>% knitr::kable()

ig1m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig1)
ig2m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig2)
ig3m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig3)
ig4m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig4)
ig5m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig5)
ig6m <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(ig6)

result <- bind_rows(
  tibble(
    variable = "pots->points-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig1m, ig2m)
  ),

```

```

tibble(
  variable = "pots->hunting-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig1m, ig3m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "pots->learning-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig1m, ig4m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "pots->trading-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig1m, ig5m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "pots->visiting-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig1m, ig6m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "points->hunting-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig2m, ig3m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "points->learning-AdjComparison",
  value = adjacency_compare(ig2m, ig4m)
),
tibble(
  variable = "points->trading-AdjComparison",

```

```

    value = adjacency_compare(ig2m, ig5m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "points->visiting-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig2m, ig6m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "hunting->learning-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig3m, ig4m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "hunting->trading-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig3m, ig5m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "hunting->visiting-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig3m, ig6m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "learning->trading-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig4m, ig5m)
  ),
  tibble(
    variable = "learning->visiting-AdjComparison",
    value = adjacency_compare(ig4m, ig6m)
  ),

```

```

    tibble(
      variable = "trading->visiting-AdjComparison",
      value = adjacency_compare(ig5m, ig6m)
    ),
    m2
  )
vars <- results %>%
  filter(run_number == i) %>%
  select(-id, -property, -adj) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  pivot_longer(-run_number, names_to = "variable")
result <- vars %>%
  bind_rows(result %>%
    mutate_at(vars(value), round, digits = 2) %>%
    mutate(run_number = i) %>%
    mutate_all(as.character))
comparison <- bind_rows(comparison, result)
})
}
return(comparison)
}

matrix2rank <- function(adj) {
  m <- string2matrix(adj)
  v <- sort(unique(as.vector(m)), decreasing = T)
  vRank <- 1:length(v)
}

```

```

m[] <- match(m, v)
diag(m) <- 0
return(m)
}

# net1 =
↔ matrix2rank(runs$wordMatrixToRowListCampLearningAdjacency[2])
# net2 = matrix2rank(runs$wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency[2])
# adjacency_compare2(net1, net2)

matrix2rank2 <- function(adj) {
  m <- adj
  v <- sort(unique(as.vector(m)), decreasing = T)
  vRank <- 1:length(v)
  m[] <- match(m, v)
  diag(m) <- 0
  return(m)
}

matrix2zscore <- function(adj) {
  m <- string2matrix(adj)
  v <- (m - mean(m)) / sd(m)
  m[] <- v
  diag(m) <- 0
  m[] <- round(m, 3)
  m <- scales::rescale(m)
}

```

```

    return(m)
  }

matrix2zscoreBand <- function(adj) {
  m <- string2matrix(x)
  nc <- ncol(m) / 3
  bands <- rep(0:(nc - 1), 3) %>% sort()
  camps <- 1:length(bands)
  dict <- tibble(bands, camps)
  m <- as.data.frame(m) %>%
    rowid_to_column("from") %>%
    pivot_longer(-from, names_to = "to") %>%
    mutate(to = str_remove_all(to, "V") %>% as.integer()) %>%
    left_join(dict, by = c("from" = "camps")) %>%
    rename(bands1 = bands) %>%
    left_join(dict, by = c("to" = "camps")) %>%
    rename(bands2 = bands) %>%
    group_by(bands1, bands2) %>%
    summarize(value = sum(value)) %>%
    ungroup() %>%
    pivot_wider(names_from = bands2, values_from = value) %>%
    column_to_rownames("bands1") %>%
    as.matrix()
  diag(m) <- 0
  v <- (m - mean(m)) / sd(m)
  m[] <- v
}

```

```

diag(m) <- 0
m[] <- round(m, 3)
m <- scales::rescale(m)
return(m)
}

matrix2one <- function(adj) {
  m <- string2matrix(adj)
  m[] <- m / max(m)
  diag(m) <- 0
  m[] <- round(m, 3)
  return(m)
}

# net1 =
↪ matrix2rank(runs$wordMatrixToRowListCampLearningAdjacency[2])
# net2 = matrix2rank(runs$wordMatrixToRowListCampPotAdjacency[2])
# adjacency_compare2(net1,net2)

formatNLAdjTablesOld <- function(x, p, nB = 3) {
  nms <- nB:(nB * 3 + nB - 1)
  links <- x %>%
    strsplit(" |\\[|\\]") %>%
    unlist() %>%
    as.numeric() %>%
    .[which(!is.na(.))] %>%

```

```

matrix(
  nrow = length(nms),
  ncol = length(nms),
  byrow = T
) %>%
set_colnames(nms) %>%
set_rownames(nms) %>%
as.data.frame() %>%
rownames_to_column("from") %>%
pivot_longer(all_of(nms %>% as.character()),
  names_to = "to",
  values_to = "weight"
) %>%
mutate(
  property = p,
  id = map2_chr(from, to, function(f, t) {
    sort(c(f, t)) %>%
      paste(collapse = "_")
  })
) %>%
distinct(id, .keep_all = T) %>%
select(-id) %>%
separate(
  col = property,
  into = c("run_number", "property"),
  sep = "_",

```

```

    extra = "drop"
  ) %>%
  filter(from != to) %>%
  filter(weight > 0)
return(links)
}
#' Format assemblages into a data frame structure

eigenDiff <- function(adj1, adj2) {
  m1 <- matrix2rank(adj1)
  m2 <- matrix2rank(adj2)
  e1 <- sna::evcent(m1)
  e2 <- sna::evcent(m2)
  return(sum(abs(e1 - e2)))
}

# tmp = runs %>% slice(1:100)

# subset common vertices from 2 networks
network_subset_common <-
  function(net1, net2, namevar = "vertex.names") {
    net1_names <-
      network::get.vertex.attribute(net1, attrname = namevar)
    net2_names <-
      network::get.vertex.attribute(net2, attrname = namevar)
    common_names <- net1_names[which(net1_names %in% net2_names)]
  }

```

```
out1 <- net1 %s% which(net1 %v% namevar %in% common_names)
out2 <- net2 %s% which(net2 %v% namevar %in% common_names)
return(list(out1, out2))
}
```

R Environment

R version=4.4.3 callr=3.7.6 ergm=4.8.1 network=1.19.0 mgcv=1.9-1 nlme=3.1-167 Rcpp=1.0.14 ggthemes=5.1.0 magrittr=2.0.3 BayesFactor=0.9.12-4.7 Matrix=1.7-2 coda=0.19-4.1 magick=2.8.5 tictoc=1.2.1 ggnetwork=0.5.13 igraph=2.1.4 ggpubr=0.6.0 arrow=19.0.1 lubridate=1.9.4 forcats=1.0.0 stringr=1.5.1 purrr=1.0.4 readr=2.1.5 tidyr=1.3.1 tibble=3.2.1 ggplot2=3.5.1 tidyverse=2.0.0 here=1.0.1 flextable=0.9.7 gt=0.11.1 dplyr=1.1.4 rio=1.2.3

ODD

“ArchMatNet: Archaeological Material Networks”

ODD: Overview, Design concepts, and Details

Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias, Claudine Gravel-Miguel, and Robert Bischoff¹

23 December 2022

Purpose

The purpose of the model is to investigate how different factors affect the ability of researchers to reconstruct prehistoric social networks from artifact stylistic similarities, as well as the overall diversity of cultural traits observed in archaeological assemblages. Given that cultural transmission and evolution are affected by multiple interacting phenomena, our model allows to simultaneously explore six sets of factors that may condition how social networks relate to shared culture between individuals and groups:

¹authors listed alphabetically by first name—each contributed equally to the agent based model.

1. Factors relating to the structure of social groups
2. Factors relating to the cultural traits in question
3. Factors relating to individual learning strategies
4. Factors relating to the environment
5. Factors relating to the context in which different types of cultural traits are learned
6. Factors relating to the method used to reconstruct ancient social networks

Process overview and scheduling

At the beginning of each time-step, the model checks what type of environment is set. If it is only one large biome, it rolls the die to see if the environment will change. If it does, the new environment is a random value between 0 and 99. Patches get that new environment.

If the user wants highResolutionData, the model checks if it is time to export data (every 1000 time-steps). If it is the case, it calls procedures that compile data and the procedure that exports it to the correct CSV file.

People remove any superfluous alliances they may have accumulated in previous tick, using the cleanUpAlliances procedure.

People run the possibility to invent new types and new variants and create one pot and point each. A person may create a new pot and/or point each tick. Each new object is created based on a randomly selected trait from the person's trait list. Each object also records the tick when it was created for use in subsequent analyses.

The model then checks if it is time to aggregate (based on the aggregation-freq slider). If it is, it sets aggregation to T, and calls the aggregate procedure, which moves people to their respective aggregation camps.

While aggregating, the model keeps track of the aggregation's length. If it has reached the aggregationDuration limit, people go back to their own camp. When they are aggregating, people "visit" with all the people they are aggregated with, which is recorded in

the interactions' "visiting" counter, as well as the inter-camps campInteractions "visiting" counters. Aggregated people can go hunting with a certain probability.

When an aggregation is not occurring, people can do different activities, with a given probability. They can create a new alliance with someone from another camp. They can go visit an ally. They can go hunting.

When hunting, people gather other people from their band and go to a different location together. When the hunt occurs during an aggregation, the hunting site is within 15 patches of the aggregation site. When the hunt occurs at other times, the hunting site is simply within the band territory. On a hunt, the hunters calculate their pointPrestige, and have different probabilities to drop a point, trade points with one another, and transmit trait knowledge to one another. Hunters keep track of how many times they hunted together. This interaction is also recorded by the campInteractions counter between camps. When the hunt is over, everyone returns to their own camp.

When visiting, one person chooses one ally to go visit at random. They move to that ally's camp and visit with all the allies present there. The people who are involved in the visit keep track of how many times they visited one another, which is also recorded by the campInteractions visiting counter. The people who participate in the visit have different probabilities to drop one pot, drop one point, trade objects with one another, and transmit trait knowledge to one another. When those activities are done, the visitor returns to their own camp.

If recordPrestige is T, camps call the recordCampPrestige procedure. This procedure helps to follow the progression of mean and max prestige of the people of each camp, to see how those values change over time.

All people have a certain probability to call the loseTrait procedure, in which they forget one pot or point trait.

All people call the `transmitCulture` procedure to share knowledge of traits, and `tradeItems` to trade objects from their inventories.

Then, all people call the `dropItem` procedure, in which they have a certain probability to drop one pot or one point.

After the first 1000 ticks, people check if they want to migrate or not at every tick, based on a probability set by the user. When `genderedMigration` is T, only people with gender 1 roll the die and they have twice the probability to migrate as everyone does when `genderedMigration` is F. When migration occurs, the person who is migrating chooses another person to switch place with. When `genderedMigration` is T, only people of gender 1 can be selected. The two people switch home camps.

The model checks to see if it has reached the maximum number of ticks. If it has and the user wants to see the metrics, it computes and prints all the metrics to the Command Center, exports results as a CSV file if `saveResults` is T, and stops.

Design concepts

Basic principles

We built this model to allow testing assumptions that archaeologists have made about the possibility to reconstruct social networks from material culture, as well as improve our methods to reconstruct said networks.

Emergence

We expect styles to emerge over time within well-connected people who share the same traits and innovate on the shared known traits.

Adaptation

The people do not adapt to their environment or their context. Their behavior is constant throughout the run.

Objectives

One objective people have is to learn fitter traits (when learning via Prestige).

Learning

People regularly learn from the people around them. This is the base of the cultural transmission subprocedure. While the learning is not considered adaptation, people will learn the traits that are most popular at any given time, traits which change as innovations gain popularity or are lost.

Prediction

There is no prediction.

Sensing

People sense the environment onto which they hunt, and it affects their prestige. When meeting one another, people can sense which traits the others know. People also know who their allies are, and how often they have visited them. Camps and bands sense the knowledge of their inhabitants. None of the knowledge involve errors. Interaction Interactions make the most important part of the model. People hunt together and visit one another. When interacting, people can trade items or share knowledge of some traits.

Stochasticity

To keep the model general, we use stochasticity often. A lot of the activities are done with a certain probability, controlled by Interface sliders. Traded items are chosen at random amongst traders' inventories. When creating a new variant, the type to innovate upon is chosen randomly amongst the traits known by the innovator. Forgotten traits are also selected at random. This use of stochasticity is also because we do not know how often and how those activities were done in the past. Therefore, it is simpler to use probabilities to get a wider range of behaviors.

Collectives

People are grouped by camps, which are grouped by bands. There are three camps per

band. People aggregate and hunt with the people from their band, therefore, their group affect who they will interact with the most, which in turn affects the similarity of their known traits and created objects.

Observation

The model can produce different types of outputs. It can calculate and print the following metrics (in the following names, X can be point or pot): 1) `AssemblageSizeX`: the sum of pots or points discarded at camps and bands; 2) `interactionFreqY` (where Y can be hunting, visiting, learning, and trading): the sum of all Y interactions between people; 3) `brDistBandX`: mean Brainerd Robinson distance between known traits, grouped by bands; 4) `brDistCampX`: mean Brainerd Robinson distance between known traits, grouped by camps; 5) `meanPeoplePrestige`: mean hunting prestige of all people; 6) `modBandX`: modularity metric which evaluates if there is more between-band links than within-band links, based on the Jaccard similarity of traits known by people; 7) `modCampX`: modularity metric which evaluates if there is more between-camp links than within-camp links, based on the Jaccard similarity of traits known by people; 8) `networkMetricX`: difference between the clustering coefficient of the network created by people who interacted with one another (hunting and learning) and the clustering coefficient of the network created by similarities in objects (point and pot); 9) `PhiSTXBand`: PhiST measure to see if variation in known traits is structured around bands; 10) `PhiSTXCamp`: PhiST measure to see if variation in known traits is structured around camps; 11) `nTraitX`: sum of the known traits at the end of the simulation (includes duplicates); and 12) `elapsedTime`: time elapsed since the start of the run.

In addition, the model can produce CSV outputs recording the parameter values, all the interactions between people, as well as the characteristics of all objects discarded at camp/band sites.

Input data

This model does not import external data.

Submodels

Social activities

People meet one another through hunting and visiting. Hunting is done with bandmates only, but visiting is done between allies, which can be of other bands, as hunter-gatherers in the ethnographic literature tend to travel further distances to visit acquaintances than to carry out subsistence activities (Hewlett et al. 1982; Weissner, 1977; Hill et al. 2014)

When someone initiates a hunt, they select a certain number of bandmates to bring with them. They all move to the hunting spot, which is either within the band territory, or within 15 patches of the aggregation site (when the hunt happens during an aggregation). All people taking part in one hunt update their and their camps' interaction "hunting" counter. Hunting people calculate the fitness of their known traits in the current environment, by calculating how many of their point traits were invented in the current environment. They then have a certain probability of dropping a point, trading items and/or transmit trait knowledge with a fellow hunter. After that, all hunters return to their own camp.

To visit an ally, a person has first to have allies. Allies are formed randomly and with a given probability at each tick. When forming an alliance, a person chooses another person at random. That ally can be of any camp other than ego's. When someone has more than the limit of allies allowed, they remove one. To select which alliance will go, the person uses weighted sampling, with the number of visits serving as the inverted weight (alliances of people who visit one another often will have less chances of being removed).

When visiting an ally, a person moves to the camp of one of their allies, choosing at random. If they have other allies in that camp, they all participate in the visit and they all update their and their camps' interaction "visiting" counter. They then have a certain

probability of dropping a point and a pot, trading items and/or transmit trait knowledge with a fellow ally. After that, the visitor returns to their own camp. Item exchange

The `tradeItems` procedure controls exchange between people. It is only run if the person has a point or pot to give and has found a trading partner on the same patch who also has an object to trade in its inventory. This is done first for points, and then for pots. The trading partners for both objects do not need to be the same, but they can be. Both partners choose one item at random from their inventory, and swap them. The interaction link between the agents and the `campInteraction` links between their camps record that interaction.

Cultural transmission

Cultural transmission happens when the `transmitCulture` is called (in `GO`, `hunt`, and `visit`). This procedure identifies if the transmission will take place (based on probabilities) and the type of transmission. For pots, and then points, people roll the die to see if they will transmit information. When successful, they will call `transmitPrestige` with a probability set by the `learningMethod` slider. Every other time, they will call `transmitConformism`. These procedures return a set of new traits, following the rules detailed below.

After learning the new traits, people craft a new item (calling the `craftItem` procedure) and remove any duplicate traits they might have just learned. The `transmitConformism` [`toolType`] reporter takes as `toolType` either “pot” or “point” and is used to determine which attributes are copied.

1. Ego asks all people on the same patch (including itself) to select their traits of the given `toolType`.
2. If visibility changes how often traits are transmitted, everyone uses the `getMostlyVisibleTraits` reporter to get mostly visible traits from their list. High visibility traits are chosen for transmission 98% of the time. This value is arbitrary but generally fits expectations from a broad reading of the ethnographic literature.

3. Everyone pools their list together and the reporter reports the most common trait. Then, the interaction links between all people update their learning counter (+1).

The `transmitPrestige [toolType]` takes as `toolType` either “pot” or “point” and is used to determine which attributes are copied.

1. Ego identifies who on the same patch they will learn from. For points, they select the person with the highest `pointPrestige`. If `potPrestige` is T, they choose the person with the highest `potPrestige`, but if `potPrestige` is F, they choose someone at random. This person is now the “teacher.”
2. The teacher adds its list of traits to a temporary global list.
3. If visibility affects transmission, the list is filtered through the `getMostlyVisibleTraits` reporter.
4. The reporter chooses and reports one of the traits in the teacher’s list. The interaction links between the teacher and Ego updates its learning counter (+1).

The `getMostlyVisibleTraits [traitList]` reporter selects and reports mostly visible tools from the `traitList` given. There is some error as the visibility of a tool becomes its probability of being chosen.

1. This first separates the `traitList` into two lists. One that focuses on the main types, and one that focuses on types with variants. For the main types, it simply pairs this new list with a list of 2s of the same length, as all main tools have high visibility. For variants, it pairs the list with each variants’ visibility obtained from the `visibilityTable`.
2. It then merges both paired lists and samples traits from that list, using their score as the probability to be chosen. The list of chosen traits is as long as the original list and includes replacements.
3. The reporter then removes any duplicates and reports this list.

Cultural innovation

Innovation can occur through the procedures `luckyLeap` (where a person creates a new main type) and `createVariant` (where a person creates a variant of a main type they know) (see Kolodny et al. 2015; Creanza et al. 2017 for a similar implementation of cultural dynamics in an ABM. This allows creating innovations that are dependent on other innovations, which is a key feature of cultural innovations. For example, the invention of a new snare hunting method may enable new kinds of game hunting and in turn the further invention of specialized tools for processing these novel foods. Such dependence in culture is what makes it cumulative over time. These procedures add the newly invented trait to a person's repertoire and to the master pot and point traits tables. Main types are coded as integers, and their variants are coded as letters.

The `luckyLeap [nextTrait toolType]` procedure is called by a person (ego) in Go if a random value is below the threshold set in `pLuckyLeap (Interface)`. The value is multiplied by 2 for pots so that pots are twice less likely to see random innovations.

The `nextTrait` is the number of the next trait in the list of main tools to invent, calling `getNextNumber` to calculate it. The `getNextNumber` reporter takes the list of pot or point attributes ego has and reports the number following the number ego already knows. That number is converted as a string to be used by `luckyLeap`. The `toolType` can be either "pot" or "point" and is used to determine which traits are innovated.

1. Ego adds the `nextTrait` to its relevant trait list (point or pot).
2. It then removes any duplicates.
3. If this type is not in its relevant master table, it adds an entry for it.
4. If `toolType` is "point" and the `traitEnvironment` table does not have it already, ego adds an entry to that table with the key = trait, and the value = the `environmentZone` of the patch where ego stands.

The createVariant [toolType] procedure is called by a person in Go if a roll die is successful. It takes one main type from the agent's known traits and adds a new variant to it.

1. It first populates a temporary variable with the list of traits the agent knows for the given toolType.
2. It then chooses one trait at random from that list. It uses the getTraitNumber reporter to get the number of the trait (main type). It also identifies the last variant the agent owns of that type, using the getLastVariant reporter.
3. The procedure then checks if ego has reached the limit of possible variants ("o"). If they have not, they identify the next variant in the alphabet. This letter becomes the newVariation.
4. Ego merges the newVariation to the main type to create a new type with variant.
5. If toolType is "point" and the traitEnvironment table does not have it already, ego adds an entry to that table with the key = trait, and the value = the environmentZone of the patch where ego stands.

Creating the archaeological record

The dropItem procedure removes objects from a person's inventory based on the pointsBreakageRate or potsBreakageRate parameters, which are now set to 0.3. If the person dropping an object is hunting, the probability of discard is unchanged. If not hunting, the probability is divided by twenty to represent less likelihood of losing a point while engaged in other activities. This value was chosen to represent the probabilities of a point being discarded at a camp based on Claudine Gravel-Miguel et al. 2021. The potsBreakageRate does not vary. When dropping an item, a person removes the first item in its inventory (the oldest item made). If the person is on a camp or aggregation site, that site records the discarded object in its pot or point assemblage.

Global Extensions Description {-} These are the extensions used in the model. Note that stats is not bundled and must be downloaded and placed in the extensions folder of the Netlogo app or in the same directory as the model. sr is commented out as it requires additional setup, but can be enabled by uncommenting.

```
extensions [  
  profiler  
  rnd  
  nw  
  table  
  matrix  
  stats  
; sr  
]
```

Global Variables Description {-} These are the global variables defined for the model.

```
globals [  
  inventorySizePoints ; size of point inventory allowed per person  
  inventorySizePots ; size of pot inventory allowed per person  
  groupColors ; list of colors possible for each group  
  currentView ; determines whether environmental zones or territories  
↪ are displayed  
  aggregation ; Monitor whether people are currently aggregating or  
↪ not
```

aggregationCounter ; A counter to monitor the aggregation period
hideLinksInteractions ; whether links should start out hidden or
↪ not
randomWho ; random person to record activity for
traitLetters ; for trait variations (new variants on main types)
pointTraitsTable ; table that records all point traits created
potTraitsTable ; table that records all pot traits created
traitEnvironments ; table recording environment in which each point
↪ trait got created (the trait, not the object itself)
visibilityTable ; table that records which letter traits are
↪ visible (2) or not (1)
potBreakageRate; rate that pots break -- do not break while hunting
pointsBreakageRate; rate that points break -- more likely to break
↪ while hunting
campVisitingAdjacency ; record visits between their agent and other
↪ people
campTradingAdjacency ; record trades between their agent and other
↪ people
campHuntingAdjacency ; record hunts between their agent and other
↪ people
campLearningAdjacency ; record learning between their agent and
↪ other people
campPointAdjacency ; record the number of similar points between
↪ camps
campPotAdjacency ; record the number of similar pots between camps
fileHighRes ; file to record the high resolution dataset

```
]
```

Agent Types Description {-} Each agent type forms a nested hierarchy—bands contain camps which contain people.

```
breed [ bands band ] ; bands represent a higher-level grouping of  
↔ people  
breed [ camps camp ] ; camps represent a small group of people  
breed [ people person ] ; people belong to a camp and its band  
  
undirected-link-breed [ interactions interaction ] ; keep track of  
↔ interactions between people  
undirected-link-breed [ campInteractions campInteraction ] ; to  
↔ record interactions between people, compiled by camps  
undirected-link-breed [ tempLinks tempLink ] ; links created  
↔ temporarily between individuals, camps, or bands to calculate  
↔ different metrics
```

Agent Properties Description {-} These are the variables specific to each type of agent.

```
camps-own [  
  potAssemblage ; pots deposited at camp  
  pointAssemblage ; points deposited at camp  
  ownedBy ; which band owns the camp  
  otherCamps ; record camps that are not this one
```

```

otherCampsMyband ; records camps that are in this camp's band
meanPrestige ; record mean prestige per camp
maxPrestige ; record prestige of most prestigious individual in a
↔ camp
  allPoints ; point traits known by the camp's people (with
↔ duplicates)
  allPots ; point traits known by the camp's people (with duplicates)
]

bands-own [
  potAssemblage ; pots deposited at band
  pointAssemblage ; points deposited at band
  allPoints ; point traits known by the band's people (with
↔ duplicates)
  allPots ; pot traits known by the band's people (with duplicates)
]

people-own [
  activity ; variable to hold the activity the agent is engaged in
  originalHome ; location of originalHome camp
  homeBand ; origin band for each person
  homeCamp ; camp the person lives at
  pointTraits ; point traits known (can be used to create a point or
↔ be transfered to someone else)
  potTraits ; pot traits known (can be used to create a pot or be
↔ transfered to someone else)

```

```

pointInventory ; points the person possesses
potInventory ; pots the person possesses
pointPrestige ; value influenced by the traits possessed
potPrestige ; value given at random
huntResults ; list of last 10 hunting trip success rates
myAllies ; people with whom person has an alliance
gender ; 0 or 1 to represent two different genders (for gendered
↔ migration only)
]

```

Patch Variables Description {-} These variables are specific to patches.

```

patches-own [
  environmentZone ; type of environment for patch
  pOwnedBy ; which band owns the patch
]

```

Link Variables Description {-} These variables are specific to links.

```

links-own [
  ally? ; switch to determine whether links will be "ON" or "OFF"
  lastActive ; counter to record the last tick that the link was
↔ active if switched off
  jaccard ; record the Jaccard distance
]

```

```

    ; keep track of every time people interact for the following
↪ categories
    learning
    visiting
    hunting
    trading
]

```

Procedures setup Description {-} Setup the model.

```

to setup

; sr:setup ; setup R extension -- comment out if not using adjcorr
↪ reporter

; reset everything
reset-timer ; track time
stop-inspecting-dead-agents ; remove any open turtle windows for
↪ now dead turtles
clear-all ; reset everything but time
reset-ticks ; reset time

; set a random seed for each run if option is true - this allows
↪ the model to record the seed for reproducibility

```

```

if randomizeSeed [ set randomSeed random 10000 ]
random-seed randomSeed ; set random seed

; track one person's activity
if recordPerson [
  if file-exists? "results/outputActivity.csv" [ file-delete
↪ "results/outputActivity.csv" ] ; overwrites the file if it
↪ already exists
  file-open "results/outputActivity.csv"
  file-print "activity, tick"
  file-close
  set randomWho nofBands * 3 + nofBands + campPopulation
  show ( word "tracked person is " randomWho ) ; prints who is
↪ followed in the command center
]

; create a new file to log into data at every 1000 tick if wanted
if HighResolutionData [
  set fileHighRes (word "results/outputHighRes-" filenamebase
↪ ".csv")
  file-open fileHighRes
]

; set some defaults values or parameter settings
set potBreakageRate 0.3
set pointsBreakageRate 0.3

```

```

    set hideLinksInteractions true ; by default, links are not visible
↪ (for World clarity)

    set aggregation false ; the simulation starts with people in their
↪ respective camps

    set inventorySizePoints 10 ; people can only carry up to 10 points
    set inventorySizePots 10 ; people can only carry up to 10 pots
    set traitLetters ( list "a" "b" "c" "d" "e" "f" "g" "h" "i" "j" "k"
↪ "l" "m" "n" "o" ) ; creates the possible set of new variant
↪ letters

; procedures to create master tables, patches with environments,
↪ bands, camps, and people

    setupMasterTables

    if visibility [ setupVisibility ] ; assign visibility to specific
↪ variants if it affects transmission

    setupPatches

    setupBandsAndTerritories

    setupCampsAndPeople

; create empty matrices (or adjacency tables) that log:

    set campVisitingAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count
↪ camps 0 ; visiting interactions between camps at each wanted
↪ iteration

    set campTradingAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count
↪ camps 0 ; trading interactions between camps at each wanted
↪ iteration

```

```

    set campHuntingAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count
↪ camps 0 ; hunting interactions between camps at each wanted
↪ iteration

    set campLearningAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count
↪ camps 0 ; learning interactions between camps at each wanted
↪ iteration

    set campPointAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count camps
↪ 0 ; similarities in points between camps at each wanted iteration
    set campPotAdjacency matrix:make-constant count camps count camps 0
↪ ; similarities in pots between camps at each wanted iteration

end

```

setupPatches Description {-} Procedure to create patch environments (1 or 3).

```

to setupPatches

    ; define initial viewpoint as environmental zones
    set currentView "zone"

    ; if chooser gradualEnvChange on - homogenous environmentZone that
↪ changes over time
    ifelse gradualEnvChange [
        ask patches [ set environmentZone 67 ] ; all patches get the same
↪ environmentZone
    ]

```

```

][
  let pZones [ 47 67 37 ] ; colors for patches

  ; each pZone finds an unassigned patch, make it their own and
↳ create a buffer around it
  foreach pZones [
    a -> ask one-of patches with [ environmentZone = 0 ][
      set environmentZone a
      set pOwnedBy a ; borrowing this variable to speed up the code
↳ as it is not set yet
    ]
  ]

  ; sample patches to speed up code
  let assignedPatches patches with [ pOwnedBy != 0 ] ; only the 3
↳ patches that have an environment (will be the center of each
↳ environment)

  ; Each patch without an environmentZone takes the environmentZone
↳ of the closest patch with one
  ask patches with [ environmentZone = 0 ][
    set environmentZone [ environmentZone ] of min-one-of
↳ assignedPatches [ distance myself ]
  ]
]

```

```
ask patches [ set pcolor environmentZone ]  
  
end
```

setupBandsAndTerritories Description {-} Procedure to create bands and their territories. Each band is separated by a minimum distance.

```
to setupBandsAndTerritories  
  
    ; create invisible bands that will define the extent of the band's  
    ↪ territory  
    ; important - this code will separate each band by a specific  
    ↪ radius, if the  
    ; radius is too high then the code will print an error  
  
    let radiusBand 15 ; radius for min distance between band centers  
    let nBands ( count bands ) ; number of bands (update through the  
    ↪ while loop)  
    set groupColors [ 14 24 34 44 54 64 74 84 94 104 114 124 134 ] ;  
    ↪ define colors for bands  
    let tmpColor groupColors ; list of colors the bands take from (and  
    ↪ remove the color they took so that each band has a unique color)  
    let counter 0 ; to break the while loop in certain circumstances  
  
    while [( nBands < nOfBands ) and ( counter < 10 )][
```

```

let potentialPatches 0
create-bands 1 [
  set hidden? false
  set shape "circle"
  set size 3
  set label who
  set label-color white
  ; set color from list but make sure it is unique
  set color ( item 0 tmpColor )
  set tmpColor ( remove-item 0 tmpColor )
  move-to one-of patches

  ; if there are other bands too close, the band will move
↪ somewhere else
  if any? other bands in-radius radiusBand [
    set potentialPatches patches with [ not any? bands in-radius
↪ radiusBand ]
    ifelse any? potentialPatches [
      move-to one-of potentialPatches
    ][
      set counter 10; to kill the while loop
      die
    ]
  ]
]
set nBands ( count bands )

```

```

    set counter counter + 1
  ]

  ; warning message if radius is too high and not all bands can be
↪ placed
  if nBands < nOfBands [ print "did not succeed in placing all bands"
↪ ]

  ; define default variable for pOwnedBy
ask patches [ set pOwnedBy 9999 ]

  ; setup bands as aggregation sites (and their inventories)
ask bands [
  set pointAssemblage []
  set potAssemblage []
  set size 10
  set label ""
  set hidden? false
  set shape "campsite"
  ask patches in-radius radiusBand [ set pOwnedBy [ who ] of myself
↪ ] ; set band territory
]

let tmpPatches up-to-n-of 100 patches with [ pOwnedBy != 9999 ]

ask patches with [ pOwnedBy = 9999 ][

```

```

    set pOwnedBy [ pOwnedBy ] of min-one-of tmpPatches [ distance
↪ myself ]
  ]
end

```

setupCampsAndPeople Description {-} Procedure to set up camps and their people.

```

to setupCampsAndPeople

; create camp sites within band territory
; follows the same rules above by not letting camps be too close
; but in this case all the camps are created first and then moved

let nOfCamps 3 ; number of camps per band
let radiusCamp 10 ; radius for camps to be spread out

ask bands [
  hatch-camps nOfCamps [
    ; initialize lists to hold deposited items
    set pointAssemblage []
    set potAssemblage []
    set size 6
    set label ""
    set hidden? false
    set shape "campsite"
  ]
]

```

```

    set ownedBy [ who ] of myself
    set meanPrestige [] ; list of mean prestige of the camp per
↪ tick
        set maxPrestige [] ; list of max prestige of the camp per tick
    ]
]

; set additional variables after all camps are created
ask camps [
    set otherCamps other camps
    set otherCampsMyband other camps with [ ownedBy = [ ownedBy ] of
↪ myself ]
    create-campInteractions-with otherCamps [
        set hidden? true
    ]
]

; move camps to their location
ask bands [
    let tmpPatches patches with [ pOwnedBy = [ who ] of myself ] ;
↪ identifies the band's territory
    ask camps with [ ownedBy = [ who ] of myself ][ move-to one-of
↪ tmpPatches ] ; asks their camp to move to their territory
]

; if the camp is too close to someone else, they try to move

```

```

ask camps [
  if any? other camps in-radius radiusCamp [
    let potentialPatches patches with [ pOwnedBy = [ OwnedBy ] of
↪ myself and not any? camps in-radius radiusCamp ]
    ifelse any? potentialPatches [
      move-to one-of potentialPatches
    ] [
      show ( word [ who ] of one-of other camps in-radius
↪ radiusCamp " is too close" )
    ]
  ]
]

; create user specified number of people per camp
ask camps [
  hatch-people campPopulation [
    set shape "person" ; make it look like a person
    set size 2 ; change size
    set homeBand [ pOwnedBy ] of patch-here ; set home band
    set homeCamp myself ; set home camp
    set originalhome [ who ] of myself; set original home camp
    set pointInventory [] ; create empty list to hold point
↪ inventory
    set potInventory [] ; create empty list to hold pot inventory
    set pointTraits [] ; create empty list to hold point traits
    set potTraits [] ; create empty list to hold pot traits
  ]
]

```

```

    set huntResults [] ; list of hunting results
    set myAllies ( turtle-set ) ; set this as turtle-set that will
↪ be filled later
    set potPrestige precision ( random-normal 10 5 ) 2 ; each
↪ person gets a value from random distribution with mean 10 and
↪ standard deviation 5 (arbitrary)

    ; get its first known trait
    let minTrait 1 ; set the min trait to create objects from (by
↪ default is 1)
    if uniqueTraits [ set minTrait [ who ] of homeCamp * 10 ] ; but
↪ if we want different values per camp, this changes it trait set
↪ for each camp
    luckyLeap ( word minTrait ) "point" ; this also creates one
↪ point at the beginning
    luckyLeap ( word minTrait ) "pot" ; this does NOT create a pot
↪ at the beginning
]
; each camp asks 1/2 of its population to set their gender to 1

```

setupMasterTables Description {-} Observer procedure. Creates 3 tables, one for point traits, one for pot traits, and one for points' environment (in which environment aare they fit?).

```

to setupMasterTables

```

```

    set pointTraitsTable table:make ; Table that will take on the
↳ learned values of main traits

    table:put pointTraitsTable "mainType" "variations" ; For easier
↳ visualization of which values are what

    set potTraitsTable table:make ; Table that will take on the
↳ learned values of main traits

    table:put potTraitsTable "mainType" "variations" ; For easier
↳ visualization of which values are what

    set traitEnvironments table:make ; Table that will take on the
↳ learned values of main traits

    table:put traitEnvironments "trait" "environment" ; For easier
↳ visualization of which values are what

end

```

setupVisibility Description {-} Observer procedure. Creates visibility table.

```

to setupVisibility

    set visibilityTable table:make

end

```

go Description {-} This is the main procedure that calls the others. In this order: the visibility table is updated; the environment is changed (if necessary), the adjacency tables are updated, alliances are cleaned, innovations are made, people craft new object, aggregation occurs (if applicable), people do activities, prestige gets calculated, Traits are lost, traits and items are transmitted, objects are dropped, migration occurs (if applicable). Then, if the run has reached its end, metrics are outputted (if applicable).

```
to go

  ; update visibility table
  if visibility [ updateVisibility ]

  ; change the environmentZone
  if gradualEnvChange and random-float 100 < pEnvChange [ ; if the
↪ environment is set to change over time and the roll die is
↪ successfull...
    print ( word "Climate change at tick: " ticks )
    let newZone random 100 ; random number (integer)
    ask patches [ set environmentZone newZone ]
  ]

  ; Update adjacency tables when in need of high resolution data
↪ (need to figure out timing, right now, it updates every 1000
↪ ticks)
```

```

if HighResolutionData and ticks > 0 and remainder ticks 1000 = 0 [
↳ ; this is active only if we need it
    compileArtifactSimilarities
    compileCampInteractions
    exportFineTunedData
    ; clear camp interaction links and camp assemblages
    ask campInteractions [
        set learning 0
        set visiting 0
        set hunting 0
        set trading 0
    ]
    ask camps [
        set potAssemblage []
        set pointAssemblage []
    ]
]

; people remove alliances if they are over the limit, before doing
↳ anything else
ask people [ cleanUpAlliances ]

; Innovate at very low probability
ask people [
    if random-float 1000 < pNewVariant [ createVariant "point" ] ; if
↳ die is successful, create a new point variant

```

```

    if random-float 1000 < pNewVariant [ createVariant "pot" ] ; if
↪ die is successful, create a new pot variant
    if random-float 1000 < pLuckyLeap [ luckyLeap ( getNextNumber
↪ "point" ) "point" ] ; if die is successful, create a new point
↪ type
    if random-float 1000 < pLuckyLeap * 2 [ luckyLeap ( getNextNumber
↪ "pot" ) "pot" ] ; if die is successful, create a new pot type
↪ (not as often as points)
  ]

; produce new items if needed
ask people [
  craftItem "point" true ; the "true" calls a probability within
↪ the craftItem procedure, so that they create new objects at a
↪ certain rate
  craftItem "pot" true ; the "true" calls a probability within the
↪ craftItem procedure, so that they create new objects at a certain
↪ rate
]

; control aggregation
if ticks > 0 and remainder ticks aggregationFreq = 0 [ ; If it is
↪ time to aggregate then aggregate
  set aggregation true
  aggregate
]

```

```

ifelse aggregation = true [
  ifelse aggregationCounter = aggregationDuration [ ; If the
↪ aggregation duration period has passed then disperse
    set aggregationCounter 0
    disperse
  ] [
    set aggregationCounter ( aggregationCounter + 1 ) ; if they are
↪ still aggregating, update the counter and push people to
↪ participate in some activities (hunting only, as they are already
↪ visiting)
    ask people [
      changeActivity "aggregating"
      if random-float 100 < pHunting [ ; random decision to hunt
↪ based on slider specified odds
        changeActivity "hunting"
        hunt ; procedure to create travel groups and destinations
      ]
    ]
  ] [
    ; trading, hunting and visiting only if not aggregated
    ask people [
      if random-float 100 < pNewAlliance [ createAlliance ] ;
↪ procedure to create alliances who can be outside one's band

```

```

]

; do activities (the same person can both go hunting and go
↔ visiting in the same tick
ask people [
    if random-float 100 < pHunting [ ; random decision to hunt
↔ based on slider specified odds
        changeActivity "hunting"
        hunt ; procedure to create travel groups and destinations
    ]
    if random-float 100 < pVisiting and any? myAllies [ ; you
↔ cannot go visit anyone if you dont have any allies
        changeActivity "visiting"
        visit ; procedure to create travel groups and destinations
    ]
]
]

if recordPrestige [ ; if recordPrestige switch is on
    ask camps [ recordCampPrestige ] ; camps record the prestige
↔ variables from their people (mean and max)
]

; give each person chance to lose a trait (forget what they know) -
↔ equal chance to lose pot or point trait
ask people [

```

```

if random-float 100 < pLoss [
  ifelse random 2 = 0 [ ; roll the dice to see if they will lose
↪ a point or pot trait that time
    set pointTraits ( loseTrait pointTraits )
  ][
    set potTraits ( loseTrait potTraits )
  ]
]

; cultural transmission of known traits and exchange of objects
ask people [
  transmitCulture
  tradeItems
]

; drop object from inventory at random
ask people [
  dropItem "point" true
  dropItem "pot" true
]

if ticks >= 1000 [
  ask people [
    ; Migration (or exogamy) procedure

```

```
    ifelse genderedMigration = TRUE [ ; when genderedMigration  
↪ occurs, only people with gender 1 will move
```

changeActivity Parameters {-} Description needs to be a string identifying the new activity. It can be “hunting”, “learning”, “trading”, or “visiting”.

Description {-} Change the activity of the person and if recordPerson is true then records the activity.

```
to changeActivity [ description ]  
  
  set activity description  
  
  if recordPerson and who = randomWho [ ; if tracking someone, open  
↪ the file, write the new activity with timestamp, and close the  
↪ file  
  file-open "results/outputActivity.csv"  
  file-print ( word ( activity ) "," ( ticks ))  
  file-close  
  
  if debug [ show ( word activity " on tick " ticks )] ; if  
↪ debugging, show the new activity and timestamp  
  ]  
  
end
```

aggregate Description {-} Observer procedure. Tells people to go to their band’s spot,

which serves as the aggregation camp. All people in the same camp add 1 visiting to their counter. People can then create alliance and exchange items with people in the same camp.

```
to aggregate

if debug [ print "aggregate" ] ; for debugging

; people move to their band
ask people [ move-to band homeBand ]

ask interactions with [ link-length = 0 ][ ; this focuses only on
↪ links between people who are in the same aggregation camp.
  set visiting visiting + 1 ; this assumes that everyone
↪ aggregating with one another has some sort of social contact
↪ (counted only once, not every month of aggregation)
  updateCampInteractions "visiting" end1 end2 ; updates the camp
↪ counter
```

disperse Description {-} Observer procedure. Called when the aggregation is over. Tells people to return to their home camp.

```
to disperse

if debug [ print "disperse" ] ; for debugging
```

```

set aggregation false ; reset the variable
set aggregationCounter 0 ; restart the counter
ask people [ returnToCamp ] ; people go back to their camp

end

```

hunt Description {-} People procedure. People go hunting with band mates.

```

to hunt

  let party ( turtle-set self ) ; create turtle-set of hunting or
  ↪ visiting party

  let activityLocation 0
  let availablePeople 0

  ; sets the activity location (when aggregating, it is nearby, when
  ↪ not aggregating, it is simply within the band territory)
  set activityLocation ifelse-value aggregation [ one-of patches
  ↪ in-radius 15 ][ one-of patches with [ pOwnedBy = [ homeBand ] of
  ↪ myself ]]

  move-to activityLocation ; move to the set location

  ; identify the hunting party (always band mates)

```

```

    set availablePeople ( turtle-set other people with [ homeBand = [
↪ homeBand ] of myself ])
    ask up-to-n-of huntingGroupSize availablePeople [ ; tell a specific
↪ number of those people to join the hunt
        changeActivity "hunting"
        set party ( turtle-set party self )
        move-to activityLocation

        ; add to counters for activity (each member of the party does it
↪ once with the person starting the hunt, so everythin counts only
↪ once).
        updateCampInteractions "hunting" self myself ; this updates the
↪ counter of the camps
        ask interaction [ who ] of self [ who ] of myself [ set hunting
↪ hunting + 1 ] ; update the people counter
    ]

    ask party [
        calculatePrestige ; this assumes that the hunt occurred and
↪ everyone evaluated how well their knowledge fit the current
↪ environment
        dropItem "point" true ; this calls the dropItem procedure to see
↪ if the people lose one of their points ("true" means that it will
↪ happen with a certain probability)
        tradeItems ; people hunting together have the opportunity to
↪ trade points with one another

```

```

    transmitCulture ; people hunting together also share knowledge
↪ with one another
]

; when all members of the party have had the chance to do all
↪ activities, they all return home

ask party [ returnToCamp ] ; this needs to be separated so that
↪ people don't leave before others have had the time to share with
↪ them

end

```

createAlliance Description {-} People procedure. People create a new alliance. When aggregating, they choose someone new (who is not already their ally) in the same camp. At other times, they choose someone new from another camp, favoring people from nearest camps.

```

to createAlliance

if debug [ print "createAlliance" ] ; for debugging

let newAlly 0 ; temp

changeActivity "making allies"

```

```

ifelse aggregation = true [
  if any? other people-here [ ; When aggregating, they choose
↪ someone in the same band who is not already their ally, who can
↪ get a new ally, and who is not from the same camp
      set newAlly ( one-of other people-here with [ not member? self
↪ myAllies and count myAllies < maximumAlliesN and homeCamp != [
↪ homeCamp ] of myself ])
  ]
][ ; when not aggregating, they can form an alliance with someone
↪ outside their band (they favor people from nearby camps, though)
  let allOtherCamps []
  let distAllOtherCamps []
  ask [ otherCamps ] of homeCamp [ ; this fills in the two
↪ temporary lists above (the camps are in the same order)
      set allOtherCamps lput self allOtherCamps ; list of camps other
↪ than homeCamp
      set distAllOtherCamps lput precision ( distance [ homeCamp ] of
↪ myself ) 0 distAllOtherCamps ; list of their distance from
↪ homeCamp (without decimals)
  ]

  let maxDist max distAllOtherCamps ; the furthest camp
  set distAllOtherCamps ( map [ x -> abs( x - maxDist )]
↪ distAllOtherCamps ) ; inverts the distance so that the closest
↪ camp has the highest probability

```

```

let pairs ( map list allOtherCamps distAllOtherCamps ) ; Pairs
↳ the camps with their probabilities

let selectedCamp first rnd:weighted-one-of-list pairs [[ p ] ->
↳ last p ] ; chooses one camp at random, but favoring closest ones
set newAlly one-of people with [ homeCamp = selectedCamp and not
↳ member? self myAllies and count myAllies < maximumAlliesN ] ;
↳ select one person from that camp who is not yet its ally
]

if is-turtle? newAlly [ ; in case no newAlly was found
ask interaction [ who ] of self [ who ] of newAlly [ set ally?
↳ true ] ; activate the alliance

; reset the agentset to only allies from active links and tell
↳ the new ally to reset theirs as well
set myAllies ( turtle-set [ other-end ] of my-interactions with [
↳ ally? ])

```

cleanUpAlliances Description {-} People procedure. People count the number of allies they have and drop one or more if they have more than the limit. Allies with strong ties have less chance to get dropped than allies with weak ties.

```

to cleanUpAlliances ; to make sure no one ever has more allies than
↳ allowed

```

```

if debug [ print "cleanUpAlliances" ] ; for debugging

; remove alliances with probability inversely proportional to the
↪ number of times you've visited that ally
if count myAllies > maximumAlliesN [ ; if you have more allies than
↪ maximum
let allyVisitsList ([ visiting ] of my-interactions with [ ally?
↪ ]) ; create a temporary variable with the list of all links'
↪ visiting counters
set allyVisitsList ( map [ x -> x + 1 ] allyVisitsList ) ; add
↪ one to avoid dividing by zero when no visit have yet occurred
let sumVisits sum allyVisitsList ; calculate the sum of the
↪ number of visits to other people
let allyProbList allyVisitsList ; create a copy list that will
↪ take in the calculated probabilities of each visit value

foreach range length allyProbList [ itemN -> ; itemN takes the
↪ value of each item in the allyProbList list
let currentVisitN item itemN allyProbList ; Reports the value
↪ of each link (number if visits)
set allyProbList replace-item itemN allyProbList ( 1 / (
↪ currentVisitN / sumVisits )) ; the probability that the link will
↪ be lost will be inversely related to network counter
]

```

```

let pairs ( map list allyVisitsList allyProbList ) ; Pairs the
↔ link counters with their 0-1 probabilities

let chosenVisitN rnd:weighted-one-of-list pairs [[ p ] -> last p
↔ ] ; rnd:weighted-one-of-list reports a random agent from the
↔ 'pairs' list, taking their probability (p) into account

let chosenLink one-of interactions with [ visiting = ( first
↔ chosenVisitN ) - 1 ] ; The link with the chosen cost (see above)
↔ is used as an alliance.

ask chosenLink [
    set ally? false ; link becomes inactive (alliance lost)
    set lastActive ticks
]

set myAllies ( turtle-set [ other-end ] of my-interactions with [
↔ ally? ] ) ; reset agentset to only active links after making some
↔ inactive

```

visit Description {-} People procedure. People go visit one of their allies.

```

to visit

let party ( turtle-set self ) ; will take on all people
↔ participating in the activity

move-to one-of myAllies ; moving to the ally should be the same as
↔ moving to its camp.

```

```

; as we are choosing amongst allies, a camp
↪ with multiple allies will have more chances to be chosen (same as
↪ when choosing amongst camps)

let alliesHere people-here with [ member? myself myAllies ] ;
↪ identifies all the allies within one camp

ask alliesHere [ ; visit only allies in destination camp
changeActivity "visiting"
set party ( turtle-set party self ) ; add themselves to the party
↪ (to do activities later on)

; add to counters for activity (each person visited does it once
↪ with the person visiting, so everythin counts only once).

updateCampInteractions "visiting" self myself ; this updates the
↪ counter of the camps

ask interaction [ who ] of self [ who ] of myself [ set visiting
↪ visiting + 1 ] ; this is done only by the allies, so it counts
↪ only once.

]

ask party [ ; then everyone does a few activities

dropItem "point" true ; they will drop a point with a certain
↪ probability

dropItem "pot" true ; they will drop a pot with a certain
↪ probability

tradeItems ; they will drop a pot with a certain probability

```

```

    transmitCulture
  ]

  returnToCamp ; this is separate from the "ask alliesHere" because
↪ allies stay in their camp. Only ego goes home.

end

```

calculatePrestige Description {-} People procedure. People take their inventory of points and calculate how many of them are fit in the current environment. This gets added to their huntResults variable. They take the average of the last 10 of those values as their prestige.

```

to calculatePrestige

  if debug [ print "calculatePrestige" ] ; for debugging

  if length pointInventory > 0 [ ; prestige is only calculated on the
↪ points in the inventory
    let onlyPoints ( map [ x -> last x ] pointInventory ) ; points in
↪ pointInventory have the tick and then the object. This filters
↪ out the tick to keep only the point
    let toolList ( map [ x -> table:get traitEnvironments x ]
↪ onlyPoints ) ; this extracts the environment in which the trait
↪ of each object in inventory was invented

```

```

let myZone [ environmentZone ] of patch-here ; variable to
↔ determine environmental zone of location

let usefulToolList filter [ i -> i = myZone ] toolList ; keeps
↔ only the points' environments that fit the current environment

let fitness length usefulToolList / length toolList ; the ratio
↔ of points the person has that is good for the current environment

set huntResults lput fitness huntResults ; add the latest fitness
↔ to the list of huntResults

if length huntResults > 10 [ set huntResults remove-item 0
↔ huntResults ] ; this list can only have the latest 10 hunts, so
↔ the oldest 11st gets dropped, when appropriate

set pointPrestige mean huntResults ; pointPrestige is the average
↔ of the last 10 hunts' fitness

]

end

```

tradeItems Description {-} People procedure. Two people in the same place exchange one of their point and/or pot with one another. When they do so, they add 1 to their “trading” counter.

```

to tradeItems

if debug [ print "tradeItems" ] ; for debugging

```

```

    let egoCurrentActivity activity ; so they can go back to their
↪ activity after the exchange

    let partnerCurrentActivity 0 ; for the partners to remember what
↪ they were doing too

    let theirGift 0 ; hold their present

;; POT ;;

    if random-float 100 < pTrading and activity != "hunting" and length
↪ potInventory > 0 [ ; pot trading cannot occur during a hunt or if
↪ you have nothing to trade

        let tradingPartners other people-here with [ length potInventory
↪ > 0 ] ; find other people who also have pots to trade

        if any? tradingPartners [ ; the trade occurs only if they found
↪ someone who had something to trade

            changeActivity "trading pots"

            let myGift one-of potInventory ; choose gift

            let posGift position myGift potInventory ; identify the
↪ position of the item to be given

            set potInventory remove-item posGift potInventory ; remove that
↪ specific object from the inventory

            ask one-of tradingPartners [ ; exchange with one person

                set partnerCurrentActivity activity ; identify the activity
↪ the partner was doing

```

```

        changeActivity "trading pots" ; change activity (for
↪ debugging, mostly)
        set theirGift one-of potInventory ; they choose one pot to
↪ trade
        set posGift position theirGift potInventory ; identify the
↪ position of the item to be given
        set potInventory remove-item posGift potInventory ; remove
↪ that specific object from the inventory
        set potInventory lput myGift potInventory ; then add the new
↪ item
        changeActivity partnerCurrentActivity ; reset to previous
↪ activity

        ; update the interaction counters for camps and people links
        updateCampInteractions "trading" self myself ; update the
↪ counter of the camps
        ask interaction [ who ] of self [ who ] of myself [ set
↪ trading trading + 1 ] ; update the people counter
    ]
        set potInventory lput theirGift potInventory ; add the
↪ partner's gift to inventory
        changeActivity egoCurrentActivity ; resets to previous activity
    ]
]

;; POINT ;;

```

```

if random-float 100 < pTrading and length pointInventory > 0 [ ;
↪ point trading can only happen if there are points to trade (which
↪ should always be the case)
    let tradingPartners other people-here with [ length
↪ pointInventory > 0 ] ; find other people who also have points to
↪ trade
    if any? tradingPartners [ ; the trade occurs only if they found
↪ someone on the same spot who had something to trade
        changeActivity "trading points"
        let myGift one-of pointInventory ; choose gift
        let posGift position myGift pointInventory ; identify the
↪ position of the item to give
        set pointInventory remove-item posGift pointInventory ; remove
↪ that specific object from the inventory
        ask one-of tradingPartners [ ; exchange with one person
            set partnerCurrentActivity activity ; identify the activity
↪ the partner was doing
            changeActivity "trading points" ; change activity (for
↪ debugging, mostly)
            set theirGift one-of pointInventory ; they choose one point
↪ to trade
            set posGift position theirGift pointInventory ; identify the
↪ position of the item to give
            set pointInventory remove-item posGift pointInventory ;
↪ remove that specific object from the inventory

```

```

        set pointInventory lput myGift pointInventory ; then add the
↪ new item
        changeActivity partnerCurrentActivity ; reset to previous
↪ activity

        ; update the interaction counters for camps and people links
        updateCampInteractions "trading" self myself ; update the
↪ counter of the camps
        ask interaction [ who ] of self [ who ] of myself [ set
↪ trading trading + 1 ] ; update the people counter
    ]
    set pointInventory lput theirGift pointInventory
    changeActivity egoCurrentActivity ; resets to previous activity
]
]
end

```

dropItem Parameters {-} itemType can be “point” or “pot” so it can be called individually. prob? is a boolean used to increase flexibility of the procedure (so it can be called by breaking the object as well as if they are over their inventory limit).

Description {-} People procedure. People drop one itemType with a probability set by the object’s breakageRate (if prob? is FALSE) or automatically if they are over their hand limit (prob? TRUE). Hunters are much more likely to drop a point when hunting. If it was the last point they had, they create a new one. If the drop occurs at a camp, that camp records the object’s characteristics.

```

to dropItem [ itemType prob? ]

if debug [ print "drop-item" ] ; for debugging

ifelse itemType = "point" [

    ;; POINT;;

    ; the threshold for breakage is lower if the agent is hunting
    let threshold ifelse-value activity = "hunting" [
↪ pointsBreakageRate ][ pointsBreakageRate / 20 ]

    ; the first part of the line below is if dropItem is called
↪ during a hunt or GO, the second is if it is called because the
↪ person has reached its hand limit
    if ( prob? and random-float 100 < threshold ) or ( not prob? ) [
        if ( length pointInventory > 0 ) [ ; only drop if an item exists
            changeActivity "dropping point"
            let site ( turtle-set camps-here bands-here ) ; identifies if
↪ the person is at a camp or band

            ; if there is a site here, it records the dropped point (the
↪ oldest of the inventory)
            ask up-to-n-of 1 site [ set pointAssemblage lput ( item 0 [
↪ pointInventory ] of myself ) pointAssemblage ]

```

```

        set pointInventory remove-item 0 pointInventory ; remove the
↪ dropped item from inventory

        ; if the inventory is empty, create a new point (hunters
↪ always need to have one point in their inventory)
        if ( length pointInventory = 0 )[ set pointInventory lput (
↪ list ticks one-of pointTraits ) pointInventory ]
    ]
]

;;POT ;;

; same procedure as for points, except activity does not affect
↪ breakage rate
if ( prob? and random-float 100 < potBreakageRate ) or ( not
↪ prob? )[
    if ( length potInventory > 0 )[ ; only drop if an item exists
        changeActivity "dropping pot"
        let site ( turtle-set camps-here bands-here ) ; identifies if
↪ the person is at a camp or band

        ; if there is a site here, it records the dropped pot (the
↪ oldest of the inventory)
        ask up-to-n-of 1 site [ set potAssemblage lput ( item 0 [
↪ potInventory ] of myself ) potAssemblage ]

```

```

        set potInventory remove-item 0 potInventory ; remove that pot
↪ from the inventory
    ]
]
]
end

```

returnToCamp Description {-} People procedure. Agents move back to home camp or to the aggregation location (can be called by disperse or doActivity at the end of a hunt).

```

to returnToCamp

    if debug [ print "returnToCamp" ] ; for debugging

    ; choose where to move to depending on what's happening right now

```

updateCampInteractions Parameters {-} interactionType is a string that can be “learning”, “hunting”, “trading”, or “visiting”. agentA and agentB are two different people doing the interaction.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Update the camp interaction link every time agents interact

```

to updateCampInteractions [ interactionType agentA agentB ]

```

```

    let campA [ who ] of [ homeCamp ] of agentA ; gets the number of
↪ agentA's camp

    let campB [ who ] of [ homeCamp ] of agentB ; gets the number of
↪ agentB's camp

    if campA != campB [ ; Because people interacting within one camp
↪ will not be counted here

        ask campInteraction campA campB [ ; the remaining lines update
↪ the appropriate counter

            ifelse interactionType = "learning" [
                set learning learning + 1
            ]
            ifelse interactionType = "hunting" [
                set hunting hunting + 1
            ]
            ifelse interactionType = "trading" [
                set trading trading + 1
            ]
            set visiting visiting + 1
        ]
    ]
]
]

```

```
end
```

craftItem Parameters {-} itemType can be “point” or “pot” so it can be called individually. prob? is a boolean used to increase flexibility of the procedure (T: it happens with a certain probability, F: it happens automatically).

Description {-} People procedure. People have a certain probability to create an object (pot or point). When created, the object records the current tick as well as its type (one of the types its maker knows).

```
to craftItem [ itemType prob? ]

  if debug [ print "craftItem" ] ; for debugging

  ; Every tick, each individual has a small chance to produce a new
  ↪ object (when prob? = true).

  ; Every time people acquire a new knowledge (when prob? = false),
  ↪ the create a new object

  let diceRoll random-float 100 ; for easier testing and
  ↪ troubleshooting

  ;; POINTS ;;

  ifelse itemType = "point" [
    if ( prob? and diceRoll < pNewObject ) or ( not prob? ) [
      changeActivity "making a point"
```

```

    let fitTrait getFitTrait ; chooses the trait among the fitter
↪ ones (based on environment)
    set pointInventory lput ( list ticks fitTrait ) pointInventory
↪ ; add the point to its inventory (includes the tick number it was
↪ made)
    ]
    ; if that new creation pushed them above their toolkit limit,
↪ they drop the oldest point
    if length pointInventory > inventorySizePoints [ dropItem "point"
↪ false ]
  ][
    ;; POTS ;;
    if ( prob? and diceRoll < pNewObject ) or ( not prob? ) [
      changeActivity "making a pot"
      set potInventory lput ( list ticks one-of potTraits )
↪ potInventory ; add the pot to its inventory (includes the tick
↪ number it was made)
    ]
    ; if that new creation pushed them above their toolkit limit,
↪ they drop the oldest pot
    if length potInventory > inventorySizePots [ dropItem "pot" false
↪ ]
  ]
end

```

migrate Description {-} People procedure. One person chooses another camp and trade

place with someone from that camp. Migration can be gendered, in which case, only people with gender 1 trade places.

```
to migrate

if debug [ print "migrate" ] ; for debugging

changeActivity "migrating"

let oldCamp homeCamp ; store old camp for swapping
let possibleCamps 0 ; will take on the ID of possible camps
ask homeCamp [ set possibleCamps other camps ]
set homeCamp one-of possibleCamps ; choose one of the other camps
↳ at random as its new home

set homeBand [ ownedBy ] of homeCamp

if aggregation = false [ move-to homeCamp ] ; when not aggregating,
↳ move to the new home (when aggregating, stay within the
↳ aggregation camp for now)

; find someone who can take its old place

let myID homeCamp ; the new camp

let myNewCampmates people with [ homeCamp = myID ] ; all the people
↳ in the new home

; select the
↳ migration partner (if gendered, only gender 1 can be selected)
```

recordCampPrestige Description {-} Camp procedure. Camps calculate the mean and max prestige of their people.

```

to recordCampPrestige

  let myPeople people with [ homeCamp = myself ] ; identify the
  ↪ people who belong to this camp

  let meanPrestigeHere precision (( sum [ pointPrestige ] of myPeople
  ↪ ) / campPopulation ) 2 ; Mean prestige of its people (rounded to
  ↪ 2 decimals)

  set meanPrestige lput meanPrestigeHere meanPrestige ; adds that
  ↪ value to a list

  let maxPrestigeHere ( max [ pointPrestige ] of myPeople ) ; Max
  ↪ prestige of its people

  set maxPrestige lput maxPrestigeHere maxPrestige ; add that value
  ↪ to a list

end

```

luckyLeap Parameters {-} objectType can be “point” or “pot”. nextTrait is the trait that will be innovated (added to the list).

Description {-} People procedure. People create a new object (point or pot) with the trait set to the given nextTrait. They then create a new object.

```

to luckyLeap [ nextTrait objectType ]

  if debug [ print "luckyLeap" ] ; for debugging

```

```

ifelse objectType = "point" [
  changeActivity "inventing point"
  ; create a new main POINT type
  set pointTraits lput nextTrait pointTraits ; add the next number
↪ to the list
  set pointTraits remove-duplicates pointTraits ; make sure there
↪ are no duplicates
  if not table:has-key? pointTraitsTable nextTrait [
    table:put pointTraitsTable nextTrait [] ; if this is a brand
↪ new type, create a new entry in the table
  ]
  ; assign the new type to its environment if not already invented
  ; but only for points as pots' fitness does not change with
↪ environment
  if not table:has-key? traitEnvironments nextTrait [
    let numberHere [ environmentZone ] of patch-here ; record the
↪ environment where the type is created
    table:put traitEnvironments nextTrait numberHere ; list
↪ recording environment in which each main axis type was created
  ]
  craftItem "point" false ; then create a new point
][
  changeActivity "inventing pot"
  ; create a new main POT type

```

```

    set potTraits lput nextTrait potTraits ; add the next number to
↪ the list

    set potTraits remove-duplicates potTraits ; make sure there are
↪ no duplicates

    if not table:has-key? potTraitsTable nextTrait [
        table:put potTraitsTable nextTrait [] ; if this is a brand new
↪ type, create a new entry in the table
    ]

    craftItem "pot" false ; then create a new pot
]

end

```

createVariant Parameters {-} objectType can be “point” or “pot”.

Description {-} People procedure. Add a variant to a mainType already known by ego.

Then create an object.

```

to createVariant [ objectType ]

    if debug [ print "addVariant" ]

    changeActivity word "inventing variant" objectType

    ; set up temporary variables

```

```

let reachedLimit? false ; will help stop the addition of variation
↪ when it reached the limit ("o" for sequential, and all letters
↪ used for non-sequential

let newTypeVariation "" ; temp variable that will be filled later
let newVariation "a" ; by default, the newVariation will be "a" so
↪ that it can be used if there is not already a variant

; select one known trait of the correct type
let traitKit ifelse-value objectType = "point" [ pointTraits ][
↪ potTraits ] ; define a temporary set of the relevant traits based
↪ on objectType

let traitA one-of traitKit ; choose one known trait at random.
let traitNumber getTraitNumber traitA ; focus only on the main
↪ number (the main type)

let lastVariant getLastVariant traitA objectType ; gets the last
↪ variant that person has of the main type

if lastVariant != "" [ ; if ego knew some variants...
  ifelse lastVariant != "o" [ ; ... and that variant is not the
↪ last possible one (there can only be 15 variations on each
↪ type)...
    set newVariation nextLetter lastVariant ; ...get the next
↪ possible letter alphabetically
  ][
    set reachedLimit? true ; if the type has reached its variation
↪ limit ("o"), the following block of code will not get called

```

```

]
]

; After the new type variant has been chosen (if not passed the
↔ limit), this updates the traitkit and the tables.
  if reachedLimit? = false [ ; only if the type has variations
↔ remaining (including "a") does it create a new one
    set newTypeVariation ( word traitNumber "-" newVariation ) ; add
↔ a letter to the type's variation
                                                                    ; add
↔ the new trait to the relevant trait list
  ifelse objectType = "point" [
    ; POINT ;
    set pointTraits lput newTypeVariation pointTraits ; add the new
↔ trait to the person's known traits list

    ; determine if the point type already has an environment
↔ attached to it, and adds it if not
    if not table:has-key? traitEnvironments newTypeVariation [
      let numberHere [ environmentZone ] of patch-here ; record the
↔ environment number
      table:put traitEnvironments newTypeVariation numberHere ;
↔ list recording environment in which each type was created
    ]

; Add this new variant to the master table

```

```

    let listTraitKits table:get pointTraitsTable ( word traitNumber
↪ ) ; focus on all variations already done for this type
    let newTraitKit remove-duplicates ( sentence listTraitKits
↪ newVariation ) ; add the new type variation to that type's list
↪ only if it's not already there
    table:put pointTraitsTable ( word traitNumber ) newTraitKit ;
↪ replace the list in the table by that updated one

    craftItem "point" false ; then create a new point

  ] [ ; POT ;
    set potTraits lput newTypeVariation potTraits ; ads the new
↪ trait to the person's trait list

    ; Add this new type variant to the master table
    let listTraitKits table:get potTraitsTable ( word traitNumber )
↪ ; focus on all variations already done for this type
    let newTraitKit remove-duplicates ( sentence listTraitKits
↪ newVariation ) ; add the new type variation to that type's list
↪ only if it's not already there
    table:put potTraitsTable ( word traitNumber ) newTraitKit ;
↪ replace the list in the table by that updated one
  ]
]
end

```

loseTrait Parameters {-} traitsList represents the list of known trait by ego (either pot-Traits or pointTraits).

Return {-} Returns the trait or traits that ego remembers after forgetting one trait (and its variant if it was a main type).

Description {-} People procedure. People forget one of the traits they know, at random. If a main trait is forgotten, ego forgets its variants as well.

```
to-report loseTrait [ traitsList ]

  let lossTrait 0
  let rememberedTraitsList traitsList ; by default, if they do have
  ↪ enough traits to lose, they keep what they had

  if length traitsList > 1 [ ; do not remove trait if only one trait
  ↪ exists
    changeActivity "losing trait"
    set lossTrait one-of traitsList ; choose one of the known traits
  ↪ at random

  let listToFilter map [ i -> ifelse-value member? lossTrait i [
  ↪ "loss" ][ i ]] traitsList ; creates a list with "loss" if the
  ↪ trait needs to be lost, and the trait if it is kept
  set rememberedTraitsList filter [ i -> i != "loss" ] listToFilter
  ↪ ; filters the list to keep only the traits remembered (remove all
  ↪ "loss")
```

```

; if they forgot the only main type they had and its variants
↪ (would happen a lot at first), they do not forget anything
    if length rememberedTraitsList = 0 [ set rememberedTraitsList
↪ traitsList ]
    ]

report rememberedTraitsList

end

```

getNextNumber Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the max number already known + 1.

Description {-} People procedure. Called with LuckyLeap only. It finds the next number (type) to innovate.

```

to-report getNextNumber [ objectType ] ; People reporter, reports the
↪ next number for the objectType (can be "pot" or "point")(for
↪ luckyLeap)

let tempListTraits [] ; temp variable to allow using this reporter
↪ for both points and pots
ifelse objectType = "point" [
    set tempListTraits pointTraits ; populate it with point traits
][

```

```

    set tempListTraits potTraits ; populate it with point traits
  ]

  let listOfNumbers ( map [ trait -> getTraitNumber trait ]
↳ tempListTraits ) ; transform the traits into their main trait
↳ number

  let nextNumber ( max listOfNumbers ) + 1

  report ( word nextNumber ) ; get the max number already known and
↳ add 1 for the next (as a string)

end

```

`getFitTrait` Return {-} Returns one point type with a relatively high fitness, given the current environment.

Description {-} People procedure. Looks at the person's pointTraits's fitnesses in the current environment, and then chooses one of the traits from that list (fit traits have more chance to be selected than non-fit traits).

```

to-report getFitTrait

  if debug [ print "getFitTrait" ] ; for debugging

  let myZone [ environmentZone ] of patch-here ; environmental zone
↳ of the current location

```

```

let traitFitnessList ( map [ x -> table:get traitEnvironments x ]
↳ pointTraits ) ; this extracts the environment of each point trait
↳ known

; for each point trait known, it replaces the trait with its
↳ fitness (5 if the trait was invented in the same environment as
↳ myZone, 2 if not)

set traitFitnessList map [ x -> ifelse-value ( x = myZone ) [ 5 ] [
↳ 2 ]] traitFitnessList

let pairs ( map list pointTraits traitFitnessList ) ; Pairs the
↳ pointTraits counters with their current fitness

let fitTrait first rnd:weighted-one-of-list pairs [[ p ] -> last p
↳ ] ; chooses one trait, favoring the fitter ones (based on
↳ environment)

report fitTrait ; report the chosen trait

end

```

deconstructingTrait Parameters {-} trait is a trait known by the person calling this reporter. It can be either a point or a pot trait (not the object made with it).

Return {-} Returns the last part of the trait in its correct format (either a letter as a string or a number as a number).

Description {-} People procedure. Used to define if a trait is a main type or a type with a variant, so the person innovating onto it can add the correct variant (called in createVariant).

```

to-report deconstructingTrait [ trait ] ; people procedure called in
↳ createVariant to set the last item to its type (string or number)
↳ without erroring-out

  let traitWithType 0 ; temporary variable

  carefully [ ; this allows separating the trait without creating
↳ errors (if the trait is a main type, it should not be
↳ read-from-string).

    set traitWithType read-from-string last trait ; that's when the
↳ trait is a main type, which is transformed into a number (was a
↳ string of the number)

  ][

    set traitWithType last trait ; that's when the trait has a
↳ variant, which is a string

  ]

  if traitWithType = e [ set traitWithType "e" ] ; e is read as a
↳ number, so this fixes the error it would cause.

  report traitWithType

end

```

getTraitNumber Parameters {-} trait is a trait known by the person calling this reporter.

It can be either a point or a pot trait (not the object made with it).

Return {-} Returns the number of the trait as a number (main type).

Description {-} People procedure. Gets the main type of the object (without variants).

```
to-report getTraitNumber [ trait ]

  ; first identify the position of the "-" (when there is a variant)
  ↪ or the length of the trait (when it is a main type)
  let p position "-" trait
  if p = false [ set p length trait ] ; if there was no "-", p became
  ↪ "false," so this gives it the length of the whole trait

  ; then extract the part of the trait up to p (a.k.a., up to the "-"
  ↪ or the whole trait)
  let traitN substring trait 0 p ; removes the variation letter and
  ↪ keeps only the number
  set traitN read-from-string traitN ; transform the string into its
  ↪ number form

  report traitN

end
```

nextLetter Parameters {-} currentLetter is the letter of the variant upon which the person will innovate.

Return {-} returns the next letter alphabetically.

Description {-} People procedure. Helps find the next letter when innovating on a trait with variant.

```
to-report nextLetter [ currentLetter ]

  let thisPosition position currentLetter traitLetters ; finds the
  ↪ position of the currentLetter in the alphabetical list set
  ↪ earlier

  let nextPosition thisPosition + 1 ; get the next position

  report item nextPosition traitLetters ; returns the letter
  ↪ following currentLetter alphabetically

end
```

traitVisibility Parameters {-} trait is one trait known by ego (can be for points or pots).

The trait needs to be one with variant.

Return {-} Returns the visibility assigned to the trait provided.

Description {-} People procedure. Identifies the visibility of a certain trait. Called by checkVisibility only for traits with variants.

```
to-report traitVisibility [ trait ]

  let result 0

  carefully [set result table:get visibilityTable trait] ; get the
  ↪ assigned visibility of that variant
```

```

    set result 0
  ]
  report result
end

```

getMostlyVisibleTraits Parameters {-} traitList can be a pointTraits list or the potTraits list.

Return {-} Returns a list of some of the most visible traits from the traitList provided.

Description {-} People procedure. Samples traits from the traitList with repeat. Visible traits have higher chances to get selected.

```

to-report getMostlyVisibleTraits [ traitList ]

  ; ; all main types are highly visible, so we can automatically
  ↪ separate them to assign visibility
  ; let mainTypes filter [ x -> is-number? deconstructingTrait x ]
  ↪ traitList

  ;
  ; let variantTraits filter [ x -> is-string? deconstructingTrait x
  ↪ ] traitList ; filters only the traits with variants

  ; for variants

```

```

    let traitsVisibility ( map [ x -> traitVisibility x ] traitList ) ;
↪ computes each variants' visibility

    let traitsPairedVisibility ( map list traitList traitsVisibility )
↪ ; pairs each variant with its visibility

; filter out low visibility traits
let traitsVisibile []

foreach traitsPairedVisibility [
  x -> if item 1 x = 3 [
    set traitsVisibile insert-item 0 traitsVisibile item 0 x
  ]
]

; combine mainTypes and high-visibility variants
; let visibleTraits sentence mainTypes traitsVisibile
report traitsVisibile

end

```

getVariantsOfMainType Parameters {-} trait is the trait considered, objectType can be “point” or “pot”.

Return {-} Returns a list of all the variants of the trait’s mainType already known by ego (NOT all variants created in the simulation).

Description {-} People procedure. Identifies all the variants of trait's mainType known by ego.

```
to-report getVariantsOfMainType [ trait objectType ]

; first get the mainType number
let mainTypeNumber getTraitNumber trait

; create a temp variable that takes on the traits considered here,
↪ based on what the objectType is
let traits ifelse-value objectType = "point" [ pointTraits ] [
↪ potTraits ]

; then produce a list of that type's variants (from the relevant
↪ list)
let mainTypeVariants map [ i -> ifelse-value getTraitNumber i =
↪ mainTypeNumber [ deconstructingTrait i ] [ "" ] ] traits

; This list now has the variants of the main tool or the main tool
↪ itself, and "" for all other tools
report mainTypeVariants

end
```

getLastVariant Parameters {-} trait is the trait considered, objectType can be “point” or “pot”.

Return {-} Returns the last variant ego knows of the type of the trait provided (variant based on alphabetical order).

Description {-} People procedure. Identifies the last variants ego knows of the type of the given trait.

```
to-report getLastVariant [ trait objectType ]

  let variants getVariantsOfMainType trait objectType ; call the
  ↪ reporter to get a list of ego's traits that contains the
  ↪ mainType, its variants, and "" for anything else
  let positionVariants map [ i -> position i traitLetters ] variants
  ↪ ; get the position of each variant in the alphabet (returns false
  ↪ if the variant is not part of the alphabet)
  let maxVariant ""
  carefully [ ; if the type of the trait did not have a variant, this
  ↪ prevents an error and goes to get any other variants that would
  ↪ be for that type
  let maxVariantPos max positionVariants ; get the max position
  ↪ (furthest along the alphabet)
  set maxVariant item maxVariantPos traitLetters ; get the variant
  ↪ associated with that position in the alphabet
  ][ ] ; there is nothing in the second bracket, because if there is
  ↪ an error in the first, nothing changes (maxVariant remains "")

  report maxVariant
```

```
end
```

updateVisibility Description {-} Observer procedure. Assigns visibility of 1 (low visibility) or 2 (high visibility) to a trait or variant.

```
to updateVisibility

  let a remove-duplicates reduce sentence [potTraits] of people
  let b remove-duplicates reduce sentence [pointTraits] of people
  let allTraits remove-duplicates sentence a b

  foreach allTraits [
    k ->
    if not table:has-key? visibilityTable k [
      table:put visibilityTable k (random 2) + 1 ; if this is a brand
↔ new type, create a new entry in the table
    ]
  ]

end
```

transmitCulture Description {-} People procedure. Calls the appropriate procedure to transmit traits based on the transmissionRate, learning method, and object selected.

```

to transmitCulture

  if debug [ print "transmitCulture" ] ; for debugging
  let newTrait 0
  ;; POT ;;

  if random-float 100 < transmissionRate [ ; If they are learning
↪ from someone
    changeActivity "learning pots"

    ; add one learned trait (the source varies based on the
↪ learningMethod)
    set newTrait ifelse-value random-float 100 < learningMethod [
↪ transmitPrestige "pot" ][ transmitConformism "pot" ]
    if newTrait != 0 [
      set potTraits lput newTrait potTraits

      craftItem "pot" false ; then create a new pot
      set potTraits remove-duplicates potTraits ; make sure that no
↪ duplicates are added through transmission
    ]
  ]

  ;; POINT ;;

```

```

    if random-float 100 < transmissionRate [ ; If they are learning
↳   from someone
        changeActivity "learning points"
        ; add one learned trait (the source varies based on the
↳   learningMethod)
        set newTrait ifelse-value random-float 100 < learningMethod [
↳   transmitPrestige "point" ][ transmitConformism "point" ]
        if newTrait != 0 [
            set pointTraits lput newTrait pointTraits
            craftItem "point" false ; then create a new point
            set pointTraits remove-duplicates pointTraits ; make sure that
↳   no duplicates are added through transmission
        ]
    ]
end

```

transmitConformism Parameters {-} objectType can be “point” or “pot”

Return {-} Returns the most common trait

Description {-} People procedure. Ego identifies the most common trait known by most people at the same spot. All people who contributed add 1 to their learning counter with ego.

```

to-report transmitConformism [ objectType ]

```

```

if debug [ print "transmitConformism" ] ; for debugging

let learnedTrait 0

let traitList []

let currentTraits []

ask people-here [
    ; everyone (including the agent asking) adds their traits to the
↪ list (if visibility is taken into consideration, the list has
↪ more visible traits

    set currentTraits ifelse-value objectType = "point" [
        ifelse-value visibility and random-float 100 < 98 [
↪ getMostlyVisibleTraits pointTraits ][ pointTraits ]
        ][
            ifelse-value visibility and random-float 100 < 98 [
↪ getMostlyVisibleTraits potTraits ][ potTraits ]
            ]

    set traitList sentence traitList currentTraits ; adds the traits
↪ to the list
]

if not empty? currentTraits [
    set learnedTrait one-of modes traitList ; choose the trait known
↪ the most (mode) by everyone

    ; update the interaction links counter

    ask other people-here [

```

```

        updateCampInteractions "learning" self myself ; update the
↪ counter of the camps
        ask interaction-with myself [ set learning learning + 1 ] ;
↪ identify all links from the people here to the person asking
    ]
]

report learnedTrait ; reports that trait

end

```

transmitPrestige Parameters {-} objectType can be “point” or “pot”.

Return {-} Returns the trait chosen from the person with higher prestige.

Description {-} People procedure. Ego identifies the person with highest prestige around and takes one of its traits. Ego adds 1 to its learning counter with the person with prestige.

```

to-report transmitPrestige [ objectType ]

    if debug [ print "transmitPrestige" ] ; for debugging

    let learnedTrait 0 ; variable for the new trait
    let currentTraits []
    let teacher 0

```

```

ifelse objectType = "point" [
    set teacher one-of people-here with-max [ pointPrestige ] ;
↪ prestige is updated at each hunt
    set currentTraits [ pointTraits ] of teacher
][
    ; set the teacher based on if potteryPrestige is ON or not
    set teacher ifelse-value potteryPrestige [ one-of people-here
↪ with-max [ potPrestige ]][ one-of people-here ]
    set currentTraits [ potTraits ] of teacher
]

if visibility and random-float 100 < 98 [ set currentTraits
↪ getMostlyVisibleTraits currentTraits ] ; if visibility is in
↪ play, this reduces the traits to the most visible
if not empty? currentTraits [

    ; choose amongst the teacher's traits one that has higher fitness
↪ based on the current environment (points) or at random (pots)
    set learnedTrait ifelse-value objectType = "point" [ getFitTrait
↪ ][ one-of currentTraits ]

    ; update the interaction link counter
if teacher != self [
    ask teacher [
        updateCampInteractions "learning" self myself ; update the
↪ counter of the camps

```

```

        ask interaction-with myself [ set learning learning + 1 ] ;
↪ identify the link from the teacher to the person asking
    ]
]
report learnedTrait

end

```

totalTraits Parameters {-} trait can be “potTraits” or “pointTraits”.

Return {-} Returns the number of traits currently known by the population.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Called by the Trait counts plot.

```

to-report totalTraits [ trait ]

    let traits length remove-duplicates reduce sentence trait ;
↪ calculates the number of DIFFERENT traits known by the population

    report traits

end

```

printMetrics Description {-} Observer procedure. Print multiple metrics in the Command Center.

```

to printMetrics

  print word "assemblageSizePoints: " assemblageSize "point"
  print word "assemblageSizePots: " assemblageSize "pot"
  print word "elapsedTime: " timer
  print word "interactionFreqHunting: " interactionFreq "hunting"
  print word "interactionFreqLearning: " interactionFreq "learning"
  print word "interactionFreqTrading: " interactionFreq "trading"
  print word "interactionFreqVisiting: " interactionFreq "visiting"
  print word "brDistBandPoints: " getBRBands "point"
  print word "brDistBandPots: " getBRBands "pot"
  print word "brDistCampPoints: " getBRCamps "point"
  print word "brDistCampPots: " getBRCamps "pot"
  print word "meanPeoplePrestige: " precision (mean [ pointPrestige ]
↪ of people) 3
  print word "modBandPoint: " modularityBand "point"
  print word "modBandPot: " modularityBand "pot"
  print word "modCampPoint: " modularityCamp "point"
  print word "modCampPot: " modularityCamp "pot"
  print word "networkMetricPoint: " networkMetric "point"
  print word "networkMetricPot: " networkMetric "pot"
  print word "PhiPointCamp: " PhiSTCamps "point"
  print word "PhiPotCamp: " PhiSTCamps "pot"
  print word "PhiPointBand: " PhiSTBands "point"
  print word "PhiPotBand: " PhiSTBands "pot"

```

```

print word "nTraitsPoints: " nTraits "point"
print word "nTraitsPots: " nTraits "pot"

end

```

assemblageSize Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the number of objects discarded at camps and bands.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the number of objects (pot or point) discarded at camps and bands.

```

to-report assemblageSize [ objectType ] ; objectType can be "pot" or
↪ "point"

  let assemblageLength 0 ; will take on all the camps and bands'
  ↪ assemblage lengths

  ask camps [ ; camps add their assemblage length first
    set assemblageLength ifelse-value objectType = "pot" [
  ↪ assemblageLength + length potAssemblage ][ assemblageLength +
  ↪ length pointAssemblage ]
  ]

  ask bands [ ; then bands

```

```

    set assemblageLength ifelse-value objectType = "pot" [
↪ assemblageLength + length potAssemblage ][ assemblageLength +
↪ length pointAssemblage ]
    ]

    report assemblageLength

end

```

interactionFreq Parameters {-} activityName is a string describing the activity for which we want the interactions (hunting, learning, trading, or visiting).

Return {-} Returns the rounded sum of all interactions of the given activity.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the sum of the interactions of the given activity.

```

to-report interactionFreq [ activityName ]

    let sumInteractions (ifelse-value
        activityName = "hunting" [ sum [ hunting ] of interactions ] ;
↪ take on the sum of all interactions of the given activity, based
↪ on the name given
        activityName = "learning" [ sum [ learning ] of interactions ]
        activityName = "trading" [ sum [ trading ] of interactions ]
        activityName = "visiting" [ sum [ visiting ] of interactions ])

```

```

report precision sumInteractions 3 ; return that value, rounded to
↪ the nearest 3 decimals.

end

```

getBRBands Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the mean of all inter-band distances (Brainerd-Robinson). Scaled where 1 is most similar, and 0 is no similarity.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Computes the Brainerd-Robinson similarity between bands.

```

to-report getBRBands [ objectType ]

; temporary variable
let allDist []

; create links between bands and calculate distances between each
↪ linked band
ask bands [
  create-tempLinks-with other bands [ set hidden? false ] ; this
↪ makes sure distances are not calculated twice
  set allDist lput calculateBR objectType allDist ; call the
↪ procedure that actually calculates the distance and add it to the
↪ master list
]

```

```

    set allDist ( reduce sentence allDist ) ; remove all square
↪ brackets in the master list (that were added as each band reports
↪ 2 distances as one list)

    report precision mean allDist 3 ; report the mean of all inter-band
↪ distances

end

```

getBRCamps Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the mean of all inter-CAMP distances (Brainerd-Robinson). Scaled where 1 is most similar, and 0 is no similarity.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Computes the Brainerd-Robinson similarity between camps of the same band.

```

to-report getBRCamps [ objectType ]

    ; temporary variable
    let allDist []

    ; calculate distances between each camp within the same band and
↪ calculate distances between each linked camp

    ask camps [

```

```

    create-tempLinks-with other camps with [ ownedBy = [ ownedBy ] of
↳ myself ] [ set hidden? false ] ; this makes sure distances are
↳ not calculated twice

    set allDist lput calculateBR objectType allDist ; call the
↳ procedure that actually calculates the distance and add it to the
↳ master list
]

set allDist ( reduce sentence allDist ) ; remove all square
↳ brackets in the master list (that were added as each camp reports
↳ multiple distances as one list)

report precision mean allDist 3 ; report the mean of all inter-band
↳ distances

end

```

calculateBR Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns a list of distances (Brainerd-Robinson) between the agent asking and its linked agents. Scaled where 1 is most similar, and 0 is no similarity.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Computes the Brainerd-Robinson similarity of the objectType between linked agents.

```
to-report calculateBR [ objectType ]
```

```

; populate variables with all distinct types of traits from people
↪ in that camp or band

listTraits

; temporary variables used below
let allTraitsA 0
let allTraitsB 0
let allDist []
let dist 0

; calculate Brainerd-Robinson distances between linked bands or
↪ camps
set allTraitsA ifelse-value objectType = "point" [ allPoints ] [
↪ allPots ] ; take on the traits of the band/camp's people
set allTraitsA getTraitFreqTable allTraitsA ; get the frequency of
↪ each trait in the list
ask tempLink-neighbors [ ; asks the linked agents (bands or camps)
set allTraitsB ifelse-value objectType = "point" [ allPoints ] [
↪ allPots ] ; take on the traits of the band/camp's people
set allTraitsB getTraitFreqTable allTraitsB ; get the frequency
↪ of each trait in the list
set dist getFreqDistList allTraitsA allTraitsB ; get a list of
↪ the differences in frequency for each trait in both lists
set dist ifelse-value ( sum dist = 0 ) [ 0 ] [ 1 - ( sum dist / 200
↪ ) ] ; compute the Brainerd-Robinson dist with the list provided

```

```

    set allDist lput dist allDist ; add the dist calculated to the
↪ allDist list
]

ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used them
report allDist

end

```

listTraits Description {-} Observer procedure. Tells bands and camps to create a list with all the traits known by their people (one list for point and one list for pot). Then collate this list into a table that has the frequency of each trait type.

```

to listTraits

let traitList []

ask bands [
    set traitList [ pointTraits ] of people with [ homeBand = [ who ]
↪ of myself ] ; compile all the pointTraits of people from this
↪ band
    set allPoints reduce sentence traitList ; remove all the square
↪ brackets around individual traitlists
    set allPoints table:counts allPoints ; count the number of each
↪ trait and enter it as a table

```

```

    set traitList [ potTraits ] of people with [ homeBand = [ who ]
↪ of myself ] ; compile all the potTraits of people from this band
    set allPots reduce sentence traitList ; remove all the square
↪ brackets around individual traitlists
    set allPots table:counts allPots ; count the number of each trait
↪ and enter it as a table
  ]

ask camps [ ; comments are the same as above, but for camps
    set traitList [ pointTraits ] of people with [ homeCamp = myself
↪ ]
    set allPoints reduce sentence traitList
    set allPoints table:counts allPoints
    set traitList [ potTraits ] of people with [ homeCamp = myself ]
    set allPots reduce sentence traitList
    set allPots table:counts allPots
  ]

end

```

getTraitFreqTable Parameters {-} allTraits is a table of all traits collected by either the camp or band. That table has the traits known by their people (key) and the count of those traits (value).

Return {-} Returns a table with the frequency of each trait given as a percentage rather than a count.

Description {-} Camp AND Band procedure. Transforms the count of each trait into a percentage of known traits (frequency).

```
to-report getTraitFreqTable [ allTraits ]

  let sumCountTraits sum table:values allTraits ; the sum count of
  ↪ all traits

  foreach table:keys allTraits [ key -> ; for each key in the table
    let valCount table:get allTraits key ; get the count associated
    ↪ with the key
    table:put allTraits key (( valCount / sumCountTraits ) * 100 ) ;
    ↪ replace the count associated with each key with its frequency
    ↪ (percentage of all known traits)
  ]

  report allTraits

end
```

getFreqDistList Parameters {-} traitsTableA and traitsTableB are two tables of traits with key = traits, and values = frequency of that trait known by the people of the band/camp asking.

Return {-} Returns a list of the frequency differences for all traits found in the two tables.

Description {-} Band AND Camp procedure. Calculate the difference in popularity between all items in two tables.

```

to-report getFreqDistList [ traitsTableA traitsTableB ]

  ; temporary variables
  let dist []
  let tmpA 0
  let tmpB 0

  let allKeys remove-duplicates sentence table:keys traitsTableA
  ↪ table:keys traitsTableB ; get all keys in both tables of
  ↪ proportions

  foreach allKeys [ key -> ; for each key, this calculates the
  ↪ difference between tables A and B
    set tmpA ifelse-value table:has-key? traitsTableA key [ table:get
  ↪ traitsTableA key ][ 0 ] ; take the value associated with the key
  ↪ in table A, if present
    set tmpB ifelse-value table:has-key? traitsTableB key [ table:get
  ↪ traitsTableB key ][ 0 ] ; take the value associated with the key
  ↪ in table B, if present
    set dist lput abs ( tmpA - tmpB ) dist ; calculate their
  ↪ difference and add to the list
  ]

  report dist

```

```
end
```

modularityBand Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the modularity of bands. Modularity is “defined based on the number of in-community links versus the number of between-community links” (manual).

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the modularity of bands, based on the traits known. Creates links between people based on the similarity of their known traits and uses those links to calculate modularity.

```
to-report modularityBand [ objectType ] ; objectType can be "pot" or
↳ "point"

  let modul -999 ; because 0 is an actual possible modularity
↳ measure, this is used to troubleshooting (if this returns -999,
↳ there is a problem)

  ; reset the tempLinks, which only keeps the links with 25th
↳ percentile Jaccard distance (the most similar)
  resetTempLinksForModularity objectType
  nw:set-context people tempLinks ; set the context to compute
↳ network metrics on
  let peoplePerBands []
  ask Bands [ set peoplePerBands lput people with [ homeband = [ who
↳ ] of myself ] peoplePerBands ] ; group people per band
```

```

    set modul nw:modularity peoplePerBands ; calculate modularity by
↪ considering the number of WITHIN-BAND links versus the number of
↪ BETWEEN-BAND links

    ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used them

    report modul

end

```

modularityCamp Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the modularity of camps. Modularity is “defined based on the number of in-community links versus the number of between-community links” (manual).

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the modularity of camps, based on the traits known. Creates links between people based on the similarity of their known traits and uses those links to calculate modularity.

```

to-report modularityCamp [ objectType ]

    let modul -999 ; because 0 is an actual possible modularity
↪ measure, this is used to troubleshooting (if this returns -999,
↪ there is a problem)

    ; reset the tempLinks, which only keeps the links with 25th
↪ percentile Jaccard distance (the most similar)

```

```

resetTempLinksForModularity objectType

nw:set-context people tempLinks ; set the context to compute
↔ network metrics on
let peoplePerCamps []
ask camps [ set peoplePerCamps lput people with [ homecamp = myself
↔ ] peoplePerCamps ] ; groups people per camp
set modul nw:modularity peoplePerCamps ; calculate modularity by
↔ considering the number of WITHIN-CAMP links versus the number of
↔ BETWEEN-CAMP links

ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used them

report modul

end

```

resetTempLinksForModularity Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the Jaccard distance between traits of people. The most similar create a new set of links used to compute modularity.

```

to resetTempLinksForModularity [ objectType ] ; objectType can be
↔ "pot" or "point"

ask interactions [

```

```

    setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits objectType
  ]

  let interactionsJaccardList [( list jaccard )] of interactions ;
  ↪ get a list of all interaction Jaccards

  let tbl stats:newtable-from-row-list interactionsJaccardList ;
  ↪ transform the list into a stat table, necessary for the next step
  ↪ (quantile)

  let threshold stats:quantile tbl 0 25 ; compute the Jaccard
  ↪ threshold (the 25th quantile)

  ask interactions with [ jaccard <= threshold ][ ask end1 [
  ↪ create-tempLink-with [ end2 ] of myself ]] ; create tempLinks
  ↪ between people with jaccard distance below threshold

```

networkMetric Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns a value between -1 and 1. If it is close to 0, it means the network from artifacts represents relatively well the network from interactions, if it is positive, the network from interactions is more clustered than the network from artifacts, if it is negative, the network from artifacts is more clustered than the network from interactions.

Description {-} Observer reporter. Calculates the difference between the clustering coefficient of the network of people and the clustering-coefficient of the network reconstructed from similar objects.

```

to-report networkMetric [ objectType ]

```

```

; if it is close to 0, it means the network from artifacts
↪ represents relatively well the network from interactions
; if it is positive, the network from interactions is more
↪ clustered than the network from artifacts
; if it is negative, the network from artifacts is more clustered
↪ than the network from interactions

ifelse objectType = "point" [
  nw:set-context people ( interactions with [ hunting > 0 ]) ; sets
↪ the context through which the metrics will be computed (hunting
↪ interactions when looking at points)
][
  nw:set-context people ( interactions with [ learning > 0 ]) ;
↪ sets the context through which the metrics will be computed
↪ (learning interactions when looking at pots)
]

let globalClustering mean [ nw:clustering-coefficient ] of people ;
↪ calculate the clustering-coefficient of the whole network

; compute the clustering coefficient between camps on the basis on
↪ their shared items
ask campInteractions [
  let A ifelse-value objectType = "point" [[ pointAssemblage ] of
↪ end1 ] [[ potAssemblage ] of end1 ]

```

setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Description {-} Link procedure. Calculates the Jaccard distance between traits of agents linked by the link asking.

```
to setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits [ objectType ] ; objectType can be  
↪ "pot" or "point"  
  
let A ifelse-value objectType = "point" [[ pointTraits ] of end1 ]  
↪ [[ potTraits ] of end1 ] ; get the correct traits to compare
```

setupJaccardDistBetweenObjects Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Description {-} Link procedure. Calculates the Jaccard distance between assemblages (objects) of agents linked by the link asking.

```
to setupJaccardDistBetweenObjects [ objectType ] ; objectType can be  
↪ "pot" or "point"  
  
let A ifelse-value objectType = "point" [[ pointAssemblage ] of  
↪ end1 ] [[ potAssemblage ] of end1 ]
```

jaccardDist Parameters {-} A and B are two lists (of traits or objects discarded) to be compared.

Return {-} Returns the Jaccard distance between the two lists.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This calculates the Jaccard distance between two lists (A and B).

```

to-report jaccardDist [ A B ] ; A and B represent two lists

; The Jaccard distance is 1- Jaccard Index
; The Jaccard index for two sets of numbers is: (the Union of both
↪ sets - the Intersection of both sets)/The Union of both sets

let AIB [] ; this will be the intersection of both sets
let AUB 0 ; this will be the union of both sets

foreach A [ x ->
  if member? x B [ set AIB lput x AIB ] ; if the item is shared, it
↪ is added to the list
]

set AIB length AIB ; the number of shared items
set AUB length ( remove-duplicates ( sentence A B )) ; the total
↪ number of items

; calculate the Jaccard index if there are traits already
let JDist ifelse-value AUB = 0 [ 2 ] [ ( AUB - AIB ) / AUB ] ; to
↪ avoid errors if there are no traits (e.g., at beginning of a
↪ simulation)

report JDist

```

```
end
```

jaccardDistWeighted Parameters {-} A and B are two lists (of traits or objects discarded) to be compared.

Return {-} Returns the weighted Jaccard distance between the two lists.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This calculates the weighted Jaccard distance between two lists (A and B).

```
;; SHOULD NOT BE USED FOR PEOPLE INTERACTIONS AS IT IS VERY SLOW
to-report jaccardDistWeighted [ A B ] ; A and B represent two lists

  ; The weighted Jaccard index is the sum of the minimum of each set
  ↪ divided by the sum of the max of each set
  ; 1 - Jaccard index is the similarity value

  ; faster?

  let tblA getTraitFreqTable table:counts A ; get a table of
  ↪ proportions of each trait in list
  let tblB getTraitFreqTable table:counts B ; get a table of
  ↪ proportions of each trait in list
  let allKeys remove-duplicates ( sentence table:keys tblA table:keys
  ↪ tblB ) ; get all keys in both tables of proportions

  ; will be used to calculate min and max of each set
  let minVals 0
```

```

let maxVals 0

foreach allKeys [ key -> ; for each key, this calculates the min
↪ and max value between tables A and B
    let tmpA ifelse-value table:has-key? tblA key [ table:get tblA
↪ key ][ 0 ] ; take the value associated with the key in table A,
↪ if present
        let tmpB ifelse-value table:has-key? tblB key [ table:get tblB
↪ key ][ 0 ] ; take the value associated with the key in table B,
↪ if present
            set minVals minVals + ( min ( list tmpA tmpB )) ; calculate the
↪ min of the two values and add to the previous value (cumulative
↪ sum)
            set maxVals maxVals + ( max ( list tmpA tmpB )) ; calculate the
↪ max of the two values and add to the previous value (cumulative
↪ sum)
        ]

    let JDist minVals / maxVals ; calculate the weighted Jaccard
↪ distance

report precision JDist 3

end

```

PhiSTCamps Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the PhiST statistic. If it is close to 0, variation is not significantly structured around camps.

Description {-} Observer reporter. Calculate PhiST statistic between people's inventories according to the camp they belong to.

```
to-report PhiSTCamps [ objectType ]

  let phi -999 ; for troubleshooting to see errors

  carefully [
    ; first compute jaccard among people between camps
    ask people [ ; create tempLinks between people who are NOT from
↪ the same camp
      let peopleOtherCamps other people with [ homeCamp != [
↪ homeCamp ] of myself ]
      create-tempLinks-with peopleOtherCamps
    ]

    ; calculate jaccard between traits of those linked people
    ask tempLinks [ setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits objectType ]

    ; calculate variance in jaccard distances
    let j [ jaccard ] of tempLinks
    let varBetween variance j
    ask tempLinks [ die ] ; reset the tempLinks
```

```

; now variance within camps
ask people [ ; create tempLinks between people who ARE from the
↪ same camp
    let peopleMyCamp other people with [ homeCamp = [ homeCamp ]
↪ of myself ]
    create-tempLinks-with peopleMyCamp
]

; calculate jaccard between traits of those linked people
ask tempLinks [ setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits objectType ]

; calculate variance in jaccard distances
let k [ jaccard ] of tempLinks
let varWithin variance k
ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used
↪ them

; calculate PhiST
set phi ( varBetween - varWithin ) / ( varBetween )

][ show "error in PhiST" ]

report phi

end

```

PhiSTBands Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the PhiST statistic between bands. If it is close to 0, variation is not significantly structured around camps.

Description {-} Observer reporter. Calculate PhiST statistic between people’s inventories according to the camp they belong to.

```
to-report PhiSTBands [ objectType ] ; if it is close to 0, variation
↳ not significantly structured around camps

let phi -999 ; for troubleshooting to see errors

carefully [
  ; first compute jaccard among people between bands
  ask people [ ; create tempLinks between people who are NOT from
↳ the same band
    let peopleOtherBands other people with [ homeBand != [
↳ homeBand ] of myself ]
    create-tempLinks-with peopleOtherBands
  ]

  ; calculate jaccard between traits of those linked people
  ask tempLinks [ setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits objectType ]

  ; calculate variance in jaccard distances
  let j [ jaccard ] of tempLinks
```

```

let varBetween variance j
ask tempLinks [ die ] ; reset the tempLinks

; now variance within bands
ask people [ ; create tempLinks between people who ARE from the
↪ same band
    let peopleMyBand other people with [ homeBand = [ homeBand ]
↪ of myself ]
    create-tempLinks-with peopleMyBand
]

; calculate jaccard between traits of those linked people
ask tempLinks [ setupJaccardDistBetweenTraits objectType ]

; calculate variance in jaccard distances
let k [ jaccard ] of tempLinks
let varWithin variance k
ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used
↪ them

; calculate PhiST
set phi ( varBetween - varWithin ) / ( varBetween )

][ show "error in PhiST" ]

report phi

```

```
end
```

nTraits Parameters {-} objectType can be “pot” or “point”.

Return {-} Returns the number of traits known of the given objectType. It considers repetitions (e.g., if 15 agents all know trait “1” only, the result will be 15).

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the number of traits known by the whole population (with repetitions).

```
to-report nTraits [ objectType ] ; objectType can be "pot" or "point"

  let nList []

  ask people [ ; each person adds their known trait to the list
    set nList ifelse-value objectType = "pot" [ sentence nList
↪ potTraits ] [ sentence nList pointTraits ]
  ]

  report length nList

end
```

compileArtifactSimilarities Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculate the similarity of objects between camps, keep only the most similar and update the relevant adjacency tables with the similarity data.

```

to compileArtifactSimilarities

; For points
ask campInteractions [
  setupJaccardDistBetweenObjects "point" ; compute the similar
↪ objects
  updateAdjacencyTables campPointAdjacency jaccard ; and that that
↪ value to the table
]

; For pots
ask campInteractions [
  setupJaccardDistBetweenObjects "pot" ; compute the similar
↪ objects
  updateAdjacencyTables campPotAdjacency jaccard ; and that that
↪ value to the table
]

end

```

compileCampInteractions Description {-} Observer procedure. Asks the links between camps to update the adjacency tables with their counters.

```

to compileCampInteractions

```

```

ask campInteractions [ ; each link between camps add their counter
↪ value to the adjacency table

updateAdjacencyTables campVisitingAdjacency visiting
updateAdjacencyTables campTradingAdjacency trading
updateAdjacencyTables campHuntingAdjacency hunting
updateAdjacencyTables campLearningAdjacency learning

]

end

```

`updateAdjacencyTables` Parameters {-} `matrixName` is the name of the adjacency table getting updated, and `addedValue` is the value that will be added to the table.

Description {-} Link procedure. Updates the values in the adjacency table given (`matrixName`) by adding `addedValue` to the values already there.

```

to updateAdjacencyTables [ matrixName addedValue ]

let rowN [ who ] of end1 - nOfBands ; get the row number associated
↪ with the camp at one end (as camps are created after bands, their
↪ numbers follow the band count)

```

`fileNameBase` Return {-} Returns a filename with the following structure: “day-month-year-time”.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Takes the current time and produces a name with it.

```

to-report fileNameBase

  let dt (remove ":" remove " " date-and-time)
  let t substring dt 0 12
  let d substring dt 12 length dt
  report (word d "-" t)

end

```

exportResults Description {-} Observer procedure. Exports variable and values to a CSV file with filename set by fileNameBase.

```

to exportResults

  let fileName fileNameBase ; create a new file name based on date
  ↪ and time
  print ( word "file name is " fileName )
  let fileNameCSV ( word "results/run_outputAssemblages_" fileName
  ↪ ".csv" ) ; the complete CSV file name
  if not file-exists? fileNameCSV [ ; so it does not overwrite it, if
  ↪ it already exists.

  ; save assemblages
  file-open fileNameCSV

```

```

file-print (
↪ "band,site,pointAssemblage,potAssemblage,MeanPrestige,MaxPrestige"
↪ )

ask camps [ file-print ( word ownedBy "," who "," pointAssemblage
↪ "," potAssemblage "," MeanPrestige "," MaxPrestige) ]

ask bands [ file-print ( word "" "," who "," pointAssemblage ","
↪ potAssemblage )]

file-close

; save variables to a different file

set fileNameCSV ( word "results/run_outputVariables_" fileName
↪ ".csv" )

file-open fileNameCSV

file-print ( "variable,value" )

file-print ( word "nOfBands," nOfBands )

file-print ( word "campPopulation," campPopulation )

file-print ( word "pVisiting," pVisiting )

file-print ( word "pHunting," pHunting )

file-print ( word "huntingGroupSize," huntingGroupSize )

file-print ( word "potBreakageRate," potBreakageRate )

file-print ( word "pointsBreakageRate," pointsBreakageRate )

file-print ( word "pNewObject," pNewObject )

file-print ( word "aggregationFreq," aggregationFreq )

file-print ( word "aggregationDuration," aggregationDuration )

file-print ( word "pMigration," pMigration )

file-print ( word "pNewAlliance," pNewAlliance )

```

```

file-print ( word "maximumAlliesN," maximumAlliesN )
file-print ( word "learningMethod," learningMethod )
file-print ( word "transmissionRate," transmissionRate )
file-print ( word "gradualEnvChange," gradualEnvChange )
file-print ( word "pEnvChange," pEnvChange )
file-print ( word "nTicks," nTicks )
file-print ( word "randomSeed," randomSeed )
file-print ( word "uniqueTraits," uniqueTraits )
file-close

; save network links to a different file
set fileNameCSV ( word "results/run_outputLinks_" fileName ".csv"
↪ )
file-open fileNameCSV
file-print ( "end1,end2,learning,hunting,visiting,trading" )

```

exportFineTunedData Description {-} Observer procedure. Writes adjacency tables data to a separate file at 1000 ticks interval if wanted.

```

to exportFineTunedData

file-open fileHighRes ; open the file already created and write the
↪ adjacency tables info with ticks (one per row)
file-print ( word ticks ",campVisiting," matrix:to-row-list
↪ campVisitingAdjacency )

```

```

    file-print ( word ticks ",campTrading," matrix:to-row-list
↪  campTradingAdjacency )
    file-print ( word ticks ",campHunting," matrix:to-row-list
↪  campHuntingAdjacency )
    file-print ( word ticks ",campLearning," matrix:to-row-list
↪  campLearningAdjacency )
    file-print ( word ticks ",campPots," matrix:to-row-list
↪  campPotAdjacency )
    file-print ( word ticks ",campPoints," matrix:to-row-list
↪  campPointAdjacency )
    file-close
end

```

getJaccardBand Parameters {-} objectType is either “points” or “pots”.

Description {-} Observer procedure. Calculates the Jaccard distance between the traits found in the camps belonging to each band. Essentially this is a measure where 0 is most similar and 1 is most distant for sharing the same types and variants between bands.

```

to-report getJaccardBand [ objectType ]

; temporary variable
let allDist []

```

```

; create links between bands and calculate distances between each
↳ linked band
ask bands [
  create-tempLinks-with other bands [ set hidden? true] ; this
↳ makes sure distances are not calculated twice
  set allDist lput calculateJaccard objectType allDist ; call the
↳ procedure that actually calculates the distance and add it to the
↳ master list
]
ifelse not empty? allDist [
  set allDist ( reduce sentence allDist ) ; remove all square
↳ brackets in the master list (that were added as each band reports
↳ 2 distances as one list)
] [
  set allDist [0]
]
report precision mean allDist 3 ; report the mean of all inter-band
↳ distances

end

```

getJaccardCamp Parameters {-} objectType is either “points” or “pots”.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This is the same as the getJaccardBand procedure except the values are calculated between camps.

```

to-report getJaccardCamp [ objectType ]

  ; temporary variable
  let allDist []

  ; create links between bands and calculate distances between each
  ↪ linked band
  ask camps [
    create-tempLinks-with other camps [ set hidden? true] ; this
    ↪ makes sure distances are not calculated twice
    set allDist lput calculateJaccard objectType allDist ; call the
    ↪ procedure that actually calculates the distance and add it to the
    ↪ master list
  ]
  ifelse not empty? allDist [
    set allDist ( reduce sentence allDist ) ; remove all square
    ↪ brackets in the master list (that were added as each band reports
    ↪ 2 distances as one list)
  ] [
    set allDist [0]
  ]
  report precision mean allDist 3 ; report the mean of all inter-band
  ↪ distances

end

```

calculateJaccard Parameters {-} objectType is either “points” or “pots”.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This function calculates the Jaccard distance between two lists.

```
to-report calculateJaccard [ objectType ]

  ; populate variables with all distinct types of traits from people
  ↪ in that camp or band
  listTraits

  ; temporary variables used below
  let allTraitsA table:make
  let allTraitsB table:make
  let allDist []
  let dist 0

  ; calculate Jaccard distances between linked bands or camps
  set allTraitsA ifelse-value objectType = "points" [ allPoints ] [
  ↪ allPots ] ; take on the traits of the band/camp's people
  set allTraitsA remove-duplicates (table:keys allTraitsA)
  ask tempLink-neighbors [ ; asks the linked agents (bands or camps)
    set allTraitsB ifelse-value objectType = "points" [ allPoints ] [
  ↪ allPots ] ; take on the traits of the band/camp's people
    set allTraitsB remove-duplicates table:keys allTraitsB
    set dist jaccardDist allTraitsA allTraitsB
```

```

    set allDist lput dist allDist ; add the dist calculated to the
↪ allDist list
]

ask tempLinks [ die ] ; always remove the links after we used them
report allDist

end

```

adjCompare Parameters {-} m1 and m2 are matrices.

Return {-} Returns a number between zero and one where one represents identical matrices and zero is no similarity.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This function calculates the absolute differences between two matrices. It is a method to compare networks.

```

to-report adjCompare [m1 m2]
  let result 0
  carefully[
    let nr item 0 matrix:dimensions m1
    let md median reduce sentence reduce sentence matrix:to-row-list
↪ m1
    set m1 matrix:map [x -> ifelse-value (x > md) [1][0]] m1
    set md median reduce sentence reduce sentence matrix:to-row-list
↪ m2
    set m2 matrix:map [x -> ifelse-value (x > md) [1][0]] m2

```

```

let netDiff matrix:minus m1 m2

set netDiff matrix:map abs netDiff

let out 1 - (sum reduce sentence reduce sentence
↔ matrix:to-row-list netDiff) / (nr * (nr - 1))

set result precision out 3

][set result "NA"]

report result

end

```

adjCorr Parameters {-} m1 and m2 are matrices

Return {-} Returns a number between -1 and 1 representing the Pearson's R correlation.

Description {-} Observer procedure. This procedure uses the sr extension which is disabled by default and this code is commented out. To enable. Uncomment the sr extension, follow the sr setup instructions, install R on your computer with the igraph and multinet packages, and uncomment this code. This procedure takes two matrices and converts them to networks. It then calculates the Pearson's R correlation between the network edges. It is a method to compare networks.

```

;to-report adjCorr [m1 m2]

; let result 0

; carefully[

; let md median reduce sentence reduce sentence matrix:to-row-list
↔ m1

; set m1 matrix:map [x -> ifelse-value (x > md) [1][0]] m1

```

```

;   set md median reduce sentence reduce sentence matrix:to-row-list
↪ m2
;   set m2 matrix:map [x -> ifelse-value (x > md) [1][0]] m2
;   sr:set "m1" matrix:to-row-list m1
;   sr:set "m2" matrix:to-row-list m2
;   (sr:run
;     "m1 = as.matrix(do.call(rbind,m1))"
;     "m2 = as.matrix(do.call(rbind,m2))"
;     "rownames(m1) = colnames(m1) = 1:nrow(m1)"
;     "rownames(m2) = colnames(m2) = 1:nrow(m2)"
;     "print(m1)"
;     "g1 = igraph::graph_from_adjacency_matrix(m1, mode =
↪ 'undirected', diag = F)"
;     "g2 = igraph::graph_from_adjacency_matrix(m2, mode =
↪ 'undirected', diag = F)"
;     "net = multinet::ml_empty('comparison')"
;     "multinet::add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = g1,name = 'm1')"
;     "multinet::add_igraph_layer_ml(n = net, g = g2,name = 'm2')"
;     "comp = multinet::layer_comparison_ml(net, method =
↪ 'pearson.degree', mode = 'all')"
;   )
;   set result precision sr:runresult "comp[1,2]" 3
; ][set result "NA"]
; report result
;end

```

GUI elements | Name | Type | Value | Properties | | — | — | — | ——— | | nTicks |

INPUTBOX | 2000.0 | entrytype: Number || randomSeed | INPUTBOX | 9433.0 | entrytype: Number || randomizeSeed | SWITCH | TRUE ||| saveResults | SWITCH | TRUE ||| pLoss | SLIDER | 33 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || aggregationFreq | SLIDER | 12 | min: 6; max: 36; incr: 1 || pNewObject | SLIDER | 10 | min: 0.05; max: 100; incr: 0.05 || aggregationDuration | SLIDER | 1 | min: 0; max: 12; incr: 1 || pMigration | SLIDER | 0.05 | min: 0; max: 10; incr: 0.1 || transmissionRate | SLIDER | 5 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || nOfBands | SLIDER | 3 | min: 3; max: 6; incr: 1 || campPopulation | SLIDER | 15 | min: 1; max: 100; incr: 1 || pHunting | SLIDER | 1 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || pVisiting | SLIDER | 5 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || huntingGroupSize | SLIDER | 5 | min: 1; max: 100; incr: 1 || pNewAlliance | SLIDER | 0.5 | min: 0; max: 10; incr: 0.05 || maximumAlliesN | SLIDER | 50 | min: 10; max: 150; incr: 1 || pLuckyLeap | SLIDER | 1 | min: 0; max: 10; incr: 0.1 || learningMethod | SLIDER | 50 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || recordPrestige | SWITCH | TRUE ||| gradualEnvChange | SWITCH | TRUE ||| pEnvChange | SLIDER | 0.1 | min: 0; max: 20; incr: 0.1 || uniqueTraits | SWITCH | TRUE ||| visibility | SWITCH | TRUE ||| genderedMigration | SWITCH | TRUE ||| pNewVariant | SLIDER | 6 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || potteryPrestige | SWITCH | TRUE ||| pTrading | SLIDER | 5 | min: 0; max: 100; incr: 1 || recordPerson | SWITCH | TRUE ||| debug | SWITCH | TRUE ||| showMetrics | SWITCH | TRUE ||| HighResolutionData | SWITCH | TRUE ||

References cited

Creanza, N., Kolodny, O., Feldman, M.W., 2017. Greater than the sum of its parts? Modelling population contact and interaction of cultural repertoires. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*. 14, 20170171.

Derex, M., Mesoudi, A., 2020. Cumulative Cultural Evolution within Evolving Population Structures. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. 24, 654–667.

Hamilton, M.J., 2021. Collective computation and the emergence of hunter-gatherer small-worlds (preprint). *Ecology*.

Kolodny, O., Creanza, N., Feldman, M.W., 2015. Evolution in leaps: The punctuated accumulation and loss of cultural innovations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 112, E6762–E6769.

Mesoudi, A., 2011. *Cultural Evolution: How Darwinian Theory Can Explain Human Culture and Synthesize the Social Sciences*. University of Chicago Press.

Migliano, A.B., Battiston, F., Viguier, S., Page, A.E., Dyble, M., Schlaepfer, R., Smith, D., Astete, L., Ngales, M., Gomez-Gardenes, J., Latora, V., Vinicius, L., 2020. Hunter-gatherer multilevel sociality accelerates cumulative cultural evolution. *Science Advances*. 6, eaax5913.

Powell, A., Shennan, S., Thomas, M.G., 2009. Late Pleistocene Demography and the Appearance of Modern Human Behavior. *Science*. 324, 1298–1301.

Premo, L.S., Tostevin, G.B., 2016. Cultural Transmission on the Taskscape: Exploring the Effects of Taskscape Visibility on Cultural Diversity. *PLOS ONE*. 11, e0161766.

Rorabaugh, A., 2015. Modeling Pre-European Contact Coast Salish Seasonal Social Networks and Their Impacts on Unbiased Cultural Transmission. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*. 18.

Salali, G.D., Chaudhary, N., Bouer, J., Thompson, J., Vinicius, L., Migliano, A.B., 2019. Development of social learning and play in BaYaka hunter-gatherers of Congo. *Scientific Reports*. 9.

Salali, G.D., Chaudhary, N., Thompson, J., Grace, O.M., van der Burgt, X.M., Dyble, M., Page, A.E., Smith, D., Lewis, J., Mace, R., Vinicius, L., Migliano, A.B., 2016. Knowledge-Sharing Networks in Hunter-Gatherers and the Evolution of Cumulative Culture. *Current Biology*. 26, 2516–2521.

Yasuoka, H., 2006. Long-Term Foraging Expeditions (Molongo) among the Baka Hunter-Gatherers in the Northwestern Congo Basin, with Special Reference to the “Wild Yam Question.” *Human Ecology*. 34, 275–296.

APPENDIX B

CODE AND ENVIRONMENTS FOR CHAPTER 3

This chapter contains the code used for the analysis in chapter 3. The code is organized into six sections: **R**, **R Environment**, **Python Training Code**, **Python Evaluation Code**, and **Python Environment**. The **R** section contains the code for the analysis, the **R Environment** section contains the R environment used to run the analysis, the **Python Training Code** section contains the code used to train the model, the **Python Evaluation Code** section contains the code to evaluate the model, and the **Python Environment** section contains the Python environment used to run the analysis.

R Code

```
library(tidyverse)
library(here)
library(magick)
library(sf)
library(Momocs)
library(umap)
library(randomForest)
library(SpatialKDE)
library(terra)
library(ggrepel)
library(ggnewscale)
library(ggfx)
library(colorspace)
library(viridis)
library(rnaturalearth)

run_hotellings <- function(groups, category, data) {
```

```

# Load necessary library
library(Hotelling)

vars <- names(data)
vars <- vars[!vars %in% c(category)]

# Initialize the results dataframe
results <- data.frame(
  group1 = character(),
  group2 = character(),
  n_group1 = integer(),
  n_group2 = integer(),
  T_squared = numeric(),
  p_value = numeric(),
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)

# Loop over each pair of groups
for (i in 1:(length(groups) - 1)) {
  for (j in (i + 1):length(groups)) {
    group1 <- groups[i]
    group2 <- groups[j]
    if (group1 == group2) next

    # Subset the data for the two groups
    subset_data <- data[data[[category]] %in% c(group1, group2), ]
  }
}

```

```

# Split the data into the two groups for Hotelling's T2 test
group1_data <- subset_data[subset_data[[category]] == group1,
↪ vars]
group2_data <- subset_data[subset_data[[category]] == group2,
↪ vars]

# Calculate the sample size for each group
n_group1 <- nrow(group1_data)
n_group2 <- nrow(group2_data)

# Debugging: print the group names and sizes to verify
cat(
  "Comparing", group1, "vs", group2, "- n_group1:",
  n_group1, "n_group2:", n_group2, "\n"
)

# Check if there are enough samples for Hotelling's T2
if (n_group1 < 5 || n_group2 < 5) {
  warning(paste(
    "Skipping comparison for", group1, "vs", group2,
    "due to insufficient data"
  ))
  next
}

```

```

# Perform Hotelling's  $T^2$  test
result <- tryCatch(
  {
    hotelling_result <- hotelling.test(group1_data,
↪ group2_data)
    hotelling_result
  },
  error = function(e) {
    warning(paste(
      "Error in Hotelling's  $T^2$  test for", group1, "vs",
      group2, ":", e$message
    ))
    return(NULL)
  }
)

if (!is.null(result)) {
  # Append results to the dataframe
  results <- rbind(
    results,
    data.frame(
      group1 = group1,
      group2 = group2,
      n_group1 = n_group1,
      n_group2 = n_group2,
      T_squared = result$stats$statistic,

```

```

        p_value = result$pval
      )
    )
  } else {
    # Debugging: indicate that the result is NULL for this
    ↪ comparison
    cat("No result for", group1, "vs", group2, "\n")
  }
}
}

# Ensure p_value is numeric and round to 3 decimal places
results <- results %>%
  mutate(p_value = as.numeric(p_value) %>%
    round(3)) %>%
  tibble::as_tibble()

# Check if results dataframe is empty and return a message if so
if (nrow(results) == 0) {
  warning("No valid comparisons were made. Check your input data.")
}

return(results)
}

i_am("analysis/Chap3Analysis.R")

```

```

points <- rio::import("data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv") %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()
points %>% glimpse()

#### Type Collection ####

type_collection <- points %>%
  filter(map_lgl(
    project_name_title,
    ~ any(.x %in% c("Justice", "MNA Type Collection"))
  )) %>%
  unchop(project_name_title) %>%
  mutate(original_point_type = as.character(original_point_type)) %>%
  filter(!is.na(x1))

types <- table(type_collection$original_point_type) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  filter(Freq > 5) %>%
  pull(Var1) %>%
  as.character()

landmarks <- points %>%
  select(x1:y8) %>%
  names()

```

```

plotdf <- type_collection %>%
  rowid_to_column() %>%
  filter(original_point_type %in% types) %>%
  select(rowid, all_of(landmarks)) %>%
  pivot_longer(any_of(starts_with("x")), names_to = "x1", values_to =
    ↪ "x") %>%
  select(-any_of(landmarks)) %>%
  bind_cols(type_collection %>%
    rowid_to_column() %>%
    filter(original_point_type %in% types) %>%
    select(rowid, all_of(landmarks)) %>%
    pivot_longer(any_of(starts_with("y")),
      names_to = "y1", values_to = "y"
    ) %>%
    select(-any_of(landmarks), -rowid)) %>%
  left_join(type_collection %>% select(-any_of(landmarks)) %>%
    rowid_to_column() %>% select(rowid, original_point_type,
    ↪ point_form))

plotside <- plotdf %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  filter(original_point_type != "Cottonwood Triangular")
mean_df <- plotside %>%
  filter(original_point_type != "Cottonwood Triangular") %>%
  select(-rowid) %>%

```

```

group_by(original_point_type, x1, y1) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(x, y), mean, na.rm = T) %>%
  mutate(original_point_type = str_remove_all(
    original_point_type,
    "Side-notched|Side Notched"
  ) %>% str_replace_all(" ", " ") %>%
  as.character())

plotside %>%
  mutate(original_point_type = str_remove_all(
    original_point_type,
    "Side-notched|Side Notched"
  ) %>% str_replace_all(" ", " ") %>%
  as.character()) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x, y, fill = original_point_type)) +
  geom_point(size = 1, shape = 21, color = "white", alpha = .5) +
  geom_point(
    data = mean_df, aes(
      x = x, y = y,
      fill = original_point_type
    ),
    shape = 21, size = 4, alpha = .8, color = "black"
  ) +
  scale_fill_viridis_d() +
  theme_bw() +
  coord_fixed() +

```

```

guides(fill = "none") +
facet_wrap(~original_point_type) +
theme(
  strip.background = element_rect(fill = "white"),
  strip.text = element_text(size = 6)
)

nm <- "mean_landmarks_side"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")),
# dpi = 900, width = 170, units = "mm")

# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>% image_read() %>%
# image_trim() %>% image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white")
↪ %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

plotmeanall <- plotside %>%
  group_by(x1, y1) %>%
  summarize_all(mean) %>%
  janitor::remove_constant() %>%
  mutate(label = str_remove_all(x1, "x"))

# magick::image_read(fn) %>% magick::image_trim() %>%
# magick::image_write(fn, density = 900)

```

```

# Landmark example #

point <- read_csv("data/meanpointexample.csv", show_col_types = F)

ggplot() +
  geom_polygon(data = point, aes(x, y), color = "black", size = 1) +
  geom_point(
    data = plotmeanall, aes(x, y), shape = 16, color = "red",
    alpha = .75, size = 8
  ) +
  geom_text(
    data = plotmeanall, aes(x, y, label = label), color = "white",
    size = 4
  ) +
  theme_void() +
  coord_equal()

# fn = "figures/landmarks_example.png"
# ggsave(fn, dpi = 900, width = 4, height = 5)

# triangular

plottri <- plotdf %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%
  mutate(original_point_type = str_remove_all(
    original_point_type, "Triangular"
  )

```

```

) %>%
  str_replace_all(" ", " ") %>% as.character()
mean_df <- plottri %>%
  select(-rowid) %>%
  group_by(original_point_type, x1, y1) %>%
  summarise_at(vars(x, y), mean, na.rm = T)

plottri %>%
  ggplot(aes(x, y, fill = original_point_type)) +
  geom_point(size = 1, shape = 21, color = "white", alpha = .5) +
  geom_point(
    data = mean_df, aes(x = x, y = y, fill = original_point_type),
    shape = 23, size = 4, alpha = .8, color = "black"
  ) +
  scale_fill_viridis_d() +
  theme_bw() +
  coord_equal() +
  guides(fill = "none") +
  facet_wrap(~original_point_type) +
  theme(
    strip.background = element_rect(fill = "white"),
    strip.text = element_text(size = 7.5)
  )

nm <- "mean_landmarks_tri"

```

```

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")),
# dpi = 900, width = 170, units = "mm")

# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
#   image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

# Examine side-notched types

type_side <- type_collection %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  filter(original_point_type != "Cottonwood Triangular")
types <- table(type_side$original_point_type) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  filter(Freq > 5) %>%
  pull(Var1) %>%
  as.character()
type_side <- type_side %>%
  filter(original_point_type %in% types)
u <- umap(type_side %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
u_df <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(type_side %>%
    select(original_point_type)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%

```

```

mutate(original_point_type = original_point_type %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(`point type` = original_point_type, x = V1, y = V2)

u_df_sub <- u_df %>%
  filter(`point type` %in% c("Awatovi", "Bonito", "Buck Taylor"))

# Create a custom legend for both color and shape by combining the
↪ aesthetics
ggplot(u_df, aes(y, x, color = `point type`, shape = `point type`)) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  scale_color_viridis_d() +
  scale_shape_manual(values = c(15, 17, 18, 19, 19, 19, 19, 19, 19,
↪ 19)) +
  stat_ellipse(
    data = u_df_sub, aes(fill = `point type`),
    geom = "polygon", level = 0.68, alpha = .1
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  coord_equal() +
  guides(
    fill = guide_none(),
    color = guide_legend(ncol = 3)
  ) +
  theme(
    legend.position = "bottom",
    legend.title = element_blank(),

```

```

    legend.text = element_text(size = 8),
    legend.key.size = unit(0.4, "cm"),
    legend.margin = ggplot2::margin(t = -20, 0, 0, 0)
  ) +
  xlab("") +
  ylab("")

nm <- "umap_side_original"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")),
# dpi = 900, width = 170, units = "mm")
#
# file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")))
#
# browseURL(file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")))

groups <- levels(u_df$`point type`)
category <- "point type"
results_hot_side_notch_original_types <- run_hotellings(groups,
  ↪ category, u_df)
print(results_hot_side_notch_original_types %>% select(group1,
  ↪ group2, p_value))

```

```

tbl1 <- results_hot_side_notch_original_types %>%
  filter(p_value > 0.1) %>%
  mutate(form = "side-notched")
names(tbl1) <- c(
  "Type 1", "Type 2", "Type 1 Total",
  "Type 2 Total", "T-squared", "P-value", "Form"
)

# Examine triangular types
type_tri <- type_collection %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular")
types <- table(type_tri$original_point_type) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  filter(Freq > 5) %>%
  pull(Var1) %>%
  as.character()
type_tri <- type_tri %>%
  filter(original_point_type %in% types)
landmarks <- type_tri %>%
  select(x1:y5) %>%
  names()
u <- umap(type_tri %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
u_df <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(type_tri %>%
    select(original_point_type)) %>%

```

```

as_tibble() %>%
mutate(original_point_type = original_point_type %>% factor()) %>%
rename(`point type` = original_point_type, x = V1, y = V2)

ggplot(u_df, aes(x, y, color = `point type`, shape = `point type`)) +
  geom_point(size = 3) +
  scale_shape_manual(values = c(19, 17, 19, 15, 15, 18)) +
  stat_ellipse(aes(fill = `point type`),
    geom = "polygon",
    level = 0.68, alpha = .1
  ) +
  theme_bw() +
  scale_color_viridis_d() +
  coord_equal() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "bottom",
    legend.title = element_blank(),
    legend.margin = ggplot2::margin(-20, 0, 0, 0, unit = "pt")
  ) +
  guides(color = guide_legend(ncol = 3)) +
  xlab("") +
  ylab("")

nm <- "umap_tri_original"

# ggsave(file.path("figures", paste0(nm, ".png")),

```

```

# dpi = 900, width = 170, units = "mm")
#
# file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")))
#
# browseURL(file.path("figures",paste0(nm, ".png")))

groups <- levels(u_df$`point type`)
category <- "point type"
results_triangular_original_types <- run_hotellings(groups, category,
↪ u_df)
print(results_triangular_original_types %>% select(group1, group2,
↪ p_value))

tbl2 <- results_triangular_original_types %>%
  filter(p_value > 0.1) %>%
  mutate(form = "triangular")
names(tbl2) <- c(
  "Type 1", "Type 2",
  "Type 1 Total",
  "Type 2 Total",
  "T-squared",
  "P-value",
  "Form"

```

```

)
# write_csv(bind_rows(tbl1, tbl2),
# "tables/hotelling_test_results_original_types.csv")

#### Cluster Analysis of All Landmarks ####

# landmark shape clusters
points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(point_form %in% c("side-notched", "triangular")) %>%
  select(object_id, point_form, x1:y5) %>%
  filter(!is.na(y5))

points_out <- lapply(1:nrow(points_sub), function(i) {
  # Extract the relevant x, y columns for row i
  row <- points_sub[i, c(
    "x1", "y1", "x2", "y2", "x3", "y3", "x4", "y4",
    "x5", "y5"
  )]

  # Convert to numeric and reshape into an 8x2 matrix (x, y pairs)
  matrix(as.numeric(unlist(row)), ncol = 2, byrow = TRUE)
})

# project triangular and side-notched points into the same
↪ morphospace
points_out <- Out(points_out) %>%

```

```

Ldk() %>%
  fgProcrustes()

points_out_df <- as_df(points_out)

u <- umap(points_out_df)
u_df <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>% select(object_id, point_form)) %>%
  as_tibble()

ggplot(u_df, aes(V1, V2, color = point_form)) +
  geom_point()

hc <- hclust(dist(u$layout, method = "minkowski"), method =
  ↪ "ward.D2")

plot(hc)

clusters <- cutree(hc, k = 3)
clusters <- kmeans(u$layout, centers = 3, nstart = 3)$cluster
u_df$cluster <- factor(clusters)

ggplot(u_df, aes(V1, V2, color = cluster)) +
  geom_point() +
  scale_color_viridis_d() +
  coord_equal() +
  theme_bw() +
  xlab("") +

```

```

ylab("") +
theme(
  legend.position = "bottom",
  legend.margin = ggplot2::margin(-20, 0, 0, 0, unit = "pt")
)

nm <- "umap_landmark_cluster"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")),
# dpi = 900, width = 150, units = "mm")
#
# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>%
# image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

#### EFA Cluster analysis ####

k <- 3

rect_hclust_filled <- function(tree, k = NULL, which = NULL, x =
↪ NULL, h = NULL,
                                border = 2, cluster = NULL, alpha = 1)
↪ {
  if (length(h) > 1L || length(k) > 1L) {

```

```

    stop("'k' and 'h' must be a scalar")
  }
  if (!is.null(h)) {
    if (!is.null(k)) {
      stop("specify exactly one of 'k' and 'h'")
    }
    k <- min(which(rev(tree$height) < h))
    k <- max(k, 2)
  } else if (is.null(k)) {
    stop("specify exactly one of 'k' and 'h'")
  }
  if (k < 2 || k > length(tree$height)) {
    stop(gettextf("k must be between 2 and %d", length(tree$height)),
         ↪ domain = NA)
  }

  if (is.null(cluster)) {
    cluster <- cutree(tree, k = k)
  }

  clustab <- table(cluster)[unique(cluster[tree$order])]
  m <- c(0, cumsum(clustab))

  if (!is.null(x)) {
    if (!is.null(which)) {
      stop("specify exactly one of 'which' and 'x'")
    }
  }

```

```

}

which <- x

for (n in seq_along(x)) which[n] <- max(which(m < x[n]))
} else if (is.null(which)) {
  which <- 1L:k
}

if (any(which > k)) {
  stop(gettextf("all elements of 'which' must be between 1 and %d",
  ↪ k), domain = NA)
}

border <- rep_len(border, length(which))
retval <- list()

for (n in seq_along(which)) {
  fill_col <- adjustcolor(border[n], alpha.f = alpha)
  rect(
    m[which[n]] + 0.66,
    par("usr")[3L],
    m[which[n] + 1] + 0.33,
    mean(rev(tree$height)[(k - 1):k]),
    border = border[n],
    col = fill_col
  )
}

```

```

    retval[[n]] <- which(cluster ==
↪ as.integer(names(clustab)[which[n]]))
  }

  invisible(retval)
}

out <- readRDS(here("data/point_outlines.Rds"))

efa_out <- out %>%
  fgProcrustes(tol = 0.1) %>%
  Momocs::efourier()
pca_out <- efa_out %>% Momocs::PCA()

u <- umap(efa_out$coe)
u_df <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rownames_to_column("object_id") %>%
  as_tibble()

hc <- hclust(dist(u$layout, method = "minkowski"), method =
↪ "ward.D2")

# fn = file.path("figures", "hclust.png")
# png(fn, width = 200, height = 100, res = 900, units = "mm")

```

```

# plot(
#   hc,
#   labels = FALSE,
#   hang = -1,
#   xlab = "",
#   ylab = "",
#   main = "",
#   sub = "",
#   yaxt = "n",
#   cex.main = 1.5,
#   cex.axis = 1.2
# )
# rect_hclust_filled(hc, k = k, border = c("#1b9e77", "#d95f02",
↪ "#7570b3"), alpha = .2)
# dev.off()
# image_read(fn) %>%
#   image_trim() %>%
#   image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
#   image_write(fn)
# browseURL(fn)

clusters <- cutree(hc, k = k)
u_df$cluster <- factor(clusters)
out$fac$cluster <- factor(clusters)
# mean shapes of clusters
out_split <- chop(out, fac = "cluster")

```

```

# Compute mean shapes for each category
mean_shapes_list <- lapply(out_split, function(coo_object) {
  MSHAPES(coo_object$coo)
})
mean_shapes_list <- Momocs::combine(mean_shapes_list %>% Out())
mean_shapes_list$fac <- tibble(cluster = names(mean_shapes_list))

a <- coo_length(mean_shapes_list) / min(coo_length(mean_shapes_list))
mean_shapes_list <- coo_scale(mean_shapes_list, a)
stack(mean_shapes_list)

mean_shapes_df <- as_df(mean_shapes_list) %>%
  mutate(coo = map(coo, as_tibble)) %>%
  unnest(coo) %>%
  group_split(cluster)

getbbox <- function(x, y, q = .75) {
  q1 <- quantile(x, 1 - q)
  q2 <- quantile(x, q)
  q3 <- quantile(y, 1 - q)
  q4 <- quantile(y, q)
  xt <- x[x > q1 & x < q2]
  yt <- y[y > q3 & y < q4]
  return(c(mean(xt), mean(yt)))
}

```

```

u_df_group <- u_df %>%
  group_split(cluster)

coords <- lapply(1:length(u_df_group), function(i) {
  tmp <- u_df_group[[i]]
  getbbox(tmp$V1, tmp$V2)
})

p <- list()

for (i in 1:length(mean_shapes_df)) {
  tmp <- mean_shapes_df[[i]] %>%
    ggplot(aes(x = V1, y = V2, group = cluster)) +
    geom_polygon(fill = "#404040") +
    theme_void() +
    coord_equal()
  tmp <- ggplotGrob(tmp)
  p[[i]] <- tmp
}

library(grid)
library(cowplot)

u_df %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2) %>%

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = y, y = x, color = cluster)) +
  annotation_custom(
    grob = p[[1]],
    ymin = coords[[1]][1] - .75,
    ymax = coords[[1]][1] + .75,
    xmin = coords[[1]][2] - 1.5,
    xmax = coords[[1]][2] + 1.5
  ) +
  annotation_custom(
    grob = p[[2]],
    ymin = coords[[2]][1] - .75,
    ymax = coords[[2]][1] + .75,
    xmin = coords[[2]][2] - 1.5,
    xmax = coords[[2]][2] + 1.5
  ) +
  annotation_custom(
    grob = p[[3]],
    ymin = coords[[3]][1] - .75,
    ymax = coords[[3]][1] + .75,
    xmin = coords[[3]][2] - 1.5,
    xmax = coords[[3]][2] + 1.5
  ) +
  geom_point(size = .75, alpha = 0.66) +
  stat_ellipse(aes(fill = cluster), geom = "polygon", level = 0.68,
    ↪ alpha = .1) +
  theme_bw() +

```

```

scale_color_viridis_d() +
coord_equal() +
# remove x and y labels

theme(
  axis.title.x = element_blank(),
  axis.title.y = element_blank(),
  axis.ticks = element_blank(),
  legend.margin = ggplot2::margin(-10, 0, 0, 0, unit = "pt"),
) +
theme(legend.position = "bottom")

nm <- "cluster_shapes_all"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")),
# dpi = 900, width = 170, height = 100, units = "mm")
# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))
# browseURL(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

# check cluster assignments
tst <- manova(cbind(u_df$V1, u_df$V2) ~ cluster, data = u_df)
summary(tst, test = "Wilks")

```

```

run_hotellings(levels(u_df$cluster), "cluster", u_df[, c("cluster",
↪  "V1", "V2"]])

points_update <- points %>%
  select(`H-ID` = projectile_point_h_id, object_id) %>%
  inner_join(u_df %>% select(object_id, cluster)) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(cluster = paste0("shape-", cluster))

#### examine base shapes using landmarks ####

# calculate the angle between the base points y3 and y5
points <- points %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(base_slope = atan((y5 - y3) / (x5 - x3)) * 180 / pi)

points %>%
  pull(base_slope) %>%
  summary()

points %>%
  pull(base_slope) %>%
  hist()

points %>%
  filter(!is.na(base_slope)) %>%

```

```

filter(!base_type %in% c("", "unknown")) %>%
mutate(base_type = factor(base_type,
  levels = c("deeply concave", "concave", "straight", "convex")
)) %>%
ggplot(aes(x = base_slope, fill = base_type)) +
geom_boxplot()

points %>%
  filter(!is.na(base_slope)) %>%
  filter(!base_type %in% c("", "unknown")) %>%
  group_by(base_type) %>%
  summarize(
    mean_slope = mean(base_slope, na.rm = T),
    quantile1 = quantile(base_slope, .25, na.rm = T),
    quantile3 = quantile(base_slope, .75, na.rm = T)
  )

points <- points %>%
  filter(basal_notch == "") %>%
  mutate(base_type_updated = case_when(
    base_slope < -18 ~ "deeply concave",
    base_slope < -5 ~ "concave",
    base_slope > 5 ~ "convex",
    TRUE ~ "straight"
  ))

```

```

points %>%
  filter(!is.na(base_slope)) %>%
  filter(!base_type %in% c("", "unknown")) %>%
  mutate(base_type_updated = factor(base_type_updated,
    levels = c("deeply concave", "concave", "straight", "convex")
  )) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = base_slope, fill = base_type_updated)) +
  geom_boxplot()

diff <- points %>%
  filter(!is.na(base_slope)) %>%
  filter(!base_type %in% c("", "unknown")) %>%
  filter(base_type != base_type_updated) %>%
  select(object_id, base_type, base_type_updated, base_slope,
    ↪ basal_notch)

diff <- diff %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  slice(175:728) %>%
  filter(base_type_updated == "deeply concave")

# write_tsv(diff, "C://users/rjbischo/Downloads/base_type_diff.tsv",
  ↪ na = "")

#### Notch Heights ####

```

```

points_side <- points %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  select(object_id, point_type, x1:y8) %>%
  filter(!is.na(x6)) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(
    notch_height_bottom =
      dist(matrix(c(x3, y3, x8, y8), ncol = 2, byrow = T)) %>%
        ↪ as.numeric(),
    length = dist(matrix(c(x1, y1, x3, y3), ncol = 2, byrow = T)) %>%
      as.numeric(),
    notch_ratio = length / notch_height_bottom
  ) %>%
  ungroup()

fn <- file.path("figures", "notch_ratio.png")

# png(fn, width = 150, height = 100, res = 900, units = "mm")
hist(points_side$notch_ratio, breaks = 100, xlab = "", main = "")

low <- quantile(points_side$notch_ratio, .025)
high <- quantile(points_side$notch_ratio, .67)

abline(v = low, col = "red", lwd = 2, lty = 2)
abline(v = high, col = "red", lwd = 2, lty = 2)

# dev.off()

```

```

# image_read(fn) %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(fn)

points_side <- points_side %>%
  mutate(
    notch_height = case_when(
      notch_ratio < low ~ "high",
      notch_ratio > high ~ "low",
      TRUE ~ "mid"
    ),
    point_type = paste0(point_type, "-", notch_height)
  ) %>%
  mutate(point_type = case_when(
    str_detect(point_type, "-high") ~ "side-notched-high", TRUE ~
    ↪ point_type
  ))

table(points_side$notch_height)

#### Assigning Point Types ####

points <- points %>%
  rowwise() %>%

```

```

mutate(
  b = ifelse(basal_notch == "Yes", "basal_notch", ""),
  s = ifelse(point_form == "side-notched", "", serrated),
  s = ifelse(point_form == "triangular" & s == "Yes", "serrated",
  ↪  ""),
  point_type_old = point_type
) %>%
mutate(point_type = paste(
  c(point_cluster, base_type, point_form, b, notch_height, s),
  collapse = "_")
)) %>%
ungroup() %>%
# select(-b,-s) %>%
mutate(
  point_type = str_remove_all(point_type, "_NA"),
  point_type = str_remove_all(point_type, "^_|_$$"),
  point_type = str_remove_all(point_type, "^_|_$$"),
  point_type = str_replace_all(point_type, "__", "_"),
  point_type = str_remove_all(point_type, "^_|_$$")
) %>%
mutate(
  point_type = ifelse(!point_form %in% c("side-notched",
  ↪  "triangular"),
  "undetermined", point_type
),

```

```

point_type = ifelse(point_cluster == "", "undetermined",
  ↪ point_type),
point_type = ifelse(str_detect(point_type,
  ↪ "undetermined|unknown|archaic"),
  "undetermined", point_type
)
)

table(points$point_type)
length(points$point_type %>% unique())
points %>%
  filter(point_type_old != point_type) %>%
  select(`H-ID` = projectile_point_h_id, object_id, point_type) %>%
  write_tsv(file.path("data/point_types.tsv"), na = "")

valid_types <- points %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  group_by(point_form, point_type) %>%
  count()

table(valid_types$point_form)

valid_types %>%
  filter(n == 1) %>%
  pull(point_type) %>%
  paste(collapse = "\n") %>%

```

```

cat()

valid_types %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  pull(n) %>%
  summary()

valid_types %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%
  pull(n) %>%
  summary()

tmp <- points %>%
  filter(
    original_point_type %in% c(
      "Awatovi",
      "Bonito",
      "Citrus Side-notched",
      "Cohonino Triangular",
      "Cottonwood Triangular",
      "Desert Side Notched",
      "Snaketown Triangular Concave Base",
      "Snaketown Triangular Straight-base",
      "Sobaipuri",

```

```

    "Temporal"
  )
)
m <- table(tmp$point_type, tmp$original_point_type) %>% as.matrix()
m[m < 3] <- 0
m <- m[rowSums(m != 0) > 0, ]
m <- m %>% t()
m <- m[rowSums(m != 0) > 0, ]
fn <- "figures/original_point_type_matrix.png"
# png(fn, width = 6, height = 6, res = 900, units = "in")
# pheatmap::pheatmap(m, display_numbers = T,
# number_format = "%.0f", legend = F, angle_col = 315)
# dev.off()

# # trim white space
# image_read(fn) %>% image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
# image_write(fn)

#### Hotellings tests to discriminate between types ####

points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  select(object_id, point_type, x1:y8) %>%
  filter(!is.na(y8))

```

```

landmarks <- points_sub %>% # nolint
  dplyr::select(x1:y8) %>%
  names()

groups <- points_sub$point_type %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

u <- umap(points_sub %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
udf <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>%
    select(object_id, point_type)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(point_type = point_type %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2)

results_hot_side <- run_hotellings(groups, "point_type", udf %>%
  select(-object_id))
results_hot_side

results_hot_side %>%
  filter(p_value < .1) %>%
  nrow() / nrow(results_hot_side)

points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%

```

```

filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
select(object_id, point_type, x1:y5) %>%
filter(!is.na(y5))
landmarks <- points_sub %>%
  select(x1:y5) %>%
  names()
groups <- points_sub$point_type %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
u <- umap(points_sub %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
udf <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>%
    select(object_id, point_type)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(point_type = point_type %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2)
results_hot_tri <- run_hotellings(groups, "point_type", udf %>%
  select(-object_id))
results_hot_tri

results_hot_tri %>%
  filter(p_value < .1) %>%
  nrow() / nrow(results_hot_tri)

points_sub <- points %>%

```

```

select(object_id, point_cluster, x1:y5) %>%
  filter(!is.na(y5)) %>%
  filter(!point_cluster %in% c(""))
landmarks <- points_sub %>%
  select(x1:y5) %>%
  names()
groups <- points_sub$point_cluster %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
u <- umap(points_sub %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
udf <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>%
    select(object_id, point_cluster)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(point_cluster = point_cluster %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2)
results_hot_shape <- run_hotellings(groups, "point_cluster", udf %>%
  select(-object_id))
results_hot_shape

points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(notch_height != "") %>%
  select(object_id, notch_height, x1:y8) %>%
  filter(!is.na(y8))
landmarks <- points_sub %>%

```

```

select(x1:y8) %>%
  names()
groups <- points_sub$notch_height %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
u <- umap(points_sub %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
udf <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>%
    select(object_id, notch_height)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(notch_height = notch_height %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2)
results_hot_notch <- run_hotellings(groups, "notch_height", udf %>%
  select(-object_id))
results_hot_notch

# easily distinguishes between notch heights

points_sub <- points %>%
  select(object_id, base_type, x1:y5) %>%
  filter(!is.na(y5)) %>%
  filter(!base_type %in% c("", "unknown"))
landmarks <- points_sub %>%
  select(x1:y5) %>%
  names()

```

```

groups <- points_sub$base_type %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

u <- umap(points_sub %>% select(any_of(landmarks)))
udf <- u$layout %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  cbind(points_sub %>%
    select(object_id, base_type)) %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  mutate(base_type = base_type %>% factor()) %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2)

results_hot_base <- run_hotellings(groups, "base_type", udf %>%
  select(-object_id))

results_hot_base

table <- bind_rows(
  results_hot_side,
  results_hot_tri, results_hot_shape,
  results_hot_notch, results_hot_base
) %>%
  rename(
    `Group 1` = group1, `Group 2` = group2,
    `Group 1 Total` = n_group1, `Group 2 Total` = n_group2,
    `T-squared` = T_squared, `P-value` = p_value
  ) %>%
  distinct_all() %>%

```

```

filter(`P-value` > .1) %>%
filter(`Group 1 Total` > 9) %>%
filter(`Group 2 Total` > 9)
table
# write_csv(table, "tables/hotelling_test_results_all.csv")

table %>%
  separate(`Group 1`, c("a1", "b1", "c1", "d1", "e1"), sep = "_",
    ↪ remove = F) %>%
  separate(`Group 2`, c("a2", "b2", "c2", "d2", "e2"), sep = "_",
    ↪ remove = F) %>%
  mutate(rowid = 1:n()) %>%
  select(
    all_of(c("rowid", "Group 1", "Group 2")),
    a1, b1, c1, d1, e1, a2, b2, c2, d2, e2
  ) %>%
  mutate_all(replace_na, "") %>%
  mutate(matches = rowSums(
    across(c(a1, b1, c1, d1, e1)) == across(c(a2, b2, c2, d2, e2))
  ))

#### compute mean shapes ####

types1 <- table(points %>% filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  pull(point_type)) %>%

```

```

as.data.frame() %>%
  arrange(desc(Freq)) %>%

  head(9) %>%

  pull(Var1)

types2 <- table(points %>% filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%
  pull(point_type)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  arrange(desc(Freq)) %>%
  head(9) %>%
  pull(Var1)

types <- c(types1, types2)

points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined")

ntotal <- points_sub %>% nrow()

nsub <- points_sub %>%
  filter(point_type %in% types) %>%
  nrow()

nsub / ntotal

out <- readRDS(here("data/point_outlines.Rds"))

out$fac <- out$fac %>%
  select(object_id) %>%
  left_join(points) %>%
  distinct(object_id, .keep_all = T)

out_sub <- out %>%

```

```

filter(point_type %in% types) %>%
mutate(point_type = factor(point_type))

x <- coo_length(out_sub)

f <- x / max(x)

out_sub <- coo_scale(out_sub, f)

# Split the object by 'point_type' using chop
out_split <- chop(out_sub, fac = "point_type")

# Compute mean shapes for each category
mean_shapes_list <- lapply(out_split, function(coo_object) {
  MSHAPES(coo_object$coo)
})

# Combine the mean shapes into a new 'Out' object
mean_shapes <- Momocs::combine(mean_shapes_list %>% Out())

# Check the resulting object
mean_shapes$fac <- tibble(type = names(mean_shapes) %>% factor()) %>%
  mutate(form = ifelse(str_detect(type, "side-notched"), "SN",
    ↪ "Tri"))

mean_shapes_df <- mean_shapes %>%

```

```

as_df() %>%
mutate(coo = map(coo, as_tibble)) %>%
unnest(coo)

mean_shapes_df <- mean_shapes_df %>%
  group_by(type) %>%
  mutate(row_number = row_number()) %>%
  filter(row_number == 1) %>%
  bind_rows(mean_shapes_df, .) %>%
  arrange(type, row_number) %>%
  select(-row_number)

generate_letter_combinations <- function(n) {
  if (n <= 26) {
    return(letters[1:n])
  } else {
    # Single letters (a-z)
    single_letters <- letters

    # Double letters (aa, ab, ac, ..., zz) in the correct order
    double_letters <- expand_grid(first = letters, second = letters)
    ↪ %>%
    mutate(combination = paste0(first, second)) %>%
    pull(combination)

    # Combine single and double letters and take the first 'n'

```

```

    return(c(single_letters, double_letters)[1:n])
  }
}

unique_types <- mean_shapes_df %>%
  filter(form == "SN") %>%
  pull(type) %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

letters_combined1 <-
  ↪ generate_letter_combinations(length(unique_types))

# Create the tibble
dict1 <- tibble(form = "SN", type = unique_types, letter1 =
  ↪ letters_combined1)

unique_types <- mean_shapes_df %>%
  filter(form == "Tri") %>%
  pull(type) %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

letters_combined2 <-
  ↪ generate_letter_combinations(length(unique_types))

# Create the tibble

```

```

dict2 <- tibble(form = "Tri", type = unique_types, letter2 =
  ↪ letters_combined2)

mean_shapes_df <- mean_shapes_df %>%
  left_join(dict1) %>%
  left_join(dict2) %>%
  mutate(letter = ifelse(is.na(letter1), letter2, letter1)) %>%
  mutate(letter = factor(letter,
    levels =
      unique(sort(c(letters_combined1, letters_combined2)))
  ))

hex_colors <- hcl.colors(length(letters_combined1), palette =
  ↪ "Spectral")
hcl_colors <- coords(as(hex2RGB(hex_colors), "polarLUV"))
hcl_colors[, "C"] <- hcl_colors[, "C"] * 1.25
saturated_colors <- hcl(hcl_colors[, "H"], hcl_colors[, "C"],
  ↪ hcl_colors[, "L"])

df_grps <- mean_shapes_df %>%
  group_split(form)

g1 <- ggplot(data = df_grps[[1]]) +
  geom_polygon(aes(x = x, y = y, group = type, fill = letter),
    alpha = .85, linewidth = 1, color = "black"
  ) +

```

```

# scale_fill_viridis_d() +
scale_fill_manual(values = saturated_colors) +
theme_void() +
coord_fixed(clip = "off") +
guides(fill = "none") +
theme(
  strip.text = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"),
  element_rect(fill = "white")
) +
facet_wrap(~letter, ncol = 3) +
ggtitle("Side-Notched Points")

g2 <- ggplot(data = df_grps[[2]]) +
  geom_polygon(aes(x = x, y = y, group = type, fill = letter),
    alpha = .85, linewidth = 1, color = "black"
  ) +
  # scale_fill_viridis_d() +
  scale_fill_manual(values = saturated_colors) +
  theme_void() +
  coord_fixed(clip = "off") +
  guides(fill = "none") +
  theme(
    strip.text = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"),
    element_rect(fill = "white")
  ) +
  facet_wrap(~letter, ncol = 3) +

```

```

ggtitle("Triangular Points")

g <- cowplot::plot_grid(g1, g2, ncol = 2)
g
nm <- "mean_types"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")), dpi = 900,
# width = 170, units = "mm")

# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>% image_read() %>%
# image_trim() %>% image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white")
↪ %>%
# image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

dict <- df_grps[[1]] %>%
  distinct(form, type, letter) %>%
  arrange(form)

paste(
  "For side-notched types:",
  map2_chr(dict$type, dict$letter, function(x, y) paste0(x, "(", y,
  ↪ ")")) %>%
  paste(collapse = ", ")
) %>% cat()

dict <- df_grps[[2]] %>%

```

```

distinct(form, type, letter) %>%
  arrange(form)

paste(
  "For triangular types:",
  map2_chr(dict$type, dict$letter, function(x, y) paste0(x, "(", y,
    ↪ ")) %>%
    paste(collapse = ", "))
) %>% cat()

#### Stack Points ####

types1 <- table(points %>% filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  pull(point_type)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  arrange(desc(Freq)) %>%
  head(9) %>%
  pull(Var1)

types2 <- table(points %>% filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%
  pull(point_type)) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  arrange(desc(Freq)) %>%
  head(9) %>%
  pull(Var1)

```

```

types <- c(types1, types2)
points_sub <- points %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined")
ntotal <- points_sub %>% nrow()
nsub <- points_sub %>%
  filter(point_type %in% types) %>%
  nrow()
nsub / ntotal
out <- readRDS(here("data/point_outlines.Rds"))

# x = out_sub %>%
# filter(object_id == "NA680.R3.9-1")

# out = out %>%
# filter(object_id != "NA3673T.174-1")

# stack(x)

out$fac <- out$fac %>%
  select(object_id) %>%
  left_join(points) %>%
  distinct(object_id, .keep_all = T)

out_sub <- out %>%
  filter(point_type %in% types) %>%
  mutate(point_type = factor(point_type))

```

```

out_aligned <- out_sub %>% fgProcrustes()

x <- coo_length(out_sub)

f <- x / max(x)

out_sub <- coo_scale(out_sub, f)

out_df <- out_aligned %>%
  as_df() %>%
  mutate(coo = map(coo, as_tibble)) %>%
  unnest(coo)

out_df <- out_df %>%
  group_by(point_type) %>%
  rowid_to_column("row_number") %>%
  filter(row_number == 1) %>%
  bind_rows(out_df, .) %>%
  arrange(point_type, row_number) %>%
  mutate(row_number = row_number())

generate_letter_combinations <- function(n) {
  if (n <= 26) {
    return(letters[1:n])
  } else {

```

```

    # Single letters (a-z)
    single_letters <- letters

    # Double letters (aa, ab, ac, ..., zz) in the correct order
    double_letters <- expand_grid(first = letters, second = letters)
  ↪ %>%
    mutate(combination = paste0(first, second)) %>%
    pull(combination)

    # Combine single and double letters and take the first 'n'
    return(c(single_letters, double_letters)[1:n])
  }
}

unique_types <- out_df %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  pull(point_type) %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

letters_combined1 <-
  ↪ generate_letter_combinations(length(unique_types))

# Create the tibble
dict1 <- tibble(
  point_form = "side-notched", point_type = unique_types,
  letter1 = letters_combined1

```

```

)

unique_types <- out_df %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%
  pull(point_type) %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()

letters_combined2 <-
  ↪ generate_letter_combinations(length(unique_types))

# Create the tibble
dict2 <- tibble(
  point_form = "triangular", point_type = unique_types,
  letter2 = letters_combined2
)

out_df <- out_df %>%
  left_join(dict1) %>%
  left_join(dict2) %>%
  mutate(letter = ifelse(is.na(letter1), letter2, letter1)) %>%
  mutate(letter = factor(letter,
    levels =
      unique(sort(c(letters_combined1, letters_combined2)))
  ))

```

```

hex_colors <- hcl.colors(length(letters_combined1), palette =
  ↪ "Spectral")
hcl_colors <- coords(as(hex2RGB(hex_colors), "polarLUV"))
hcl_colors[, "C"] <- hcl_colors[, "C"] * 1.25
saturated_colors <- hcl(hcl_colors[, "H"], hcl_colors[, "C"],
  ↪ hcl_colors[, "L"])

df_grps <- out_df %>%
  rename(x = V1, y = V2) %>%
  arrange(point_type, row_number) %>%
  group_split(point_form)

g1 <- ggplot(data = df_grps[[1]]) +
  geom_path(aes(x = x, y = y, group = object_id, color = letter),
    alpha = .85
  ) +
  scale_color_manual(values = saturated_colors) +
  theme_void() +
  coord_fixed(clip = "off") +
  guides(color = "none") +
  theme(
    strip.text = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"),
    plot.background = element_rect(
      fill = "#e8eaed", color = "black", linewidth = 1.5
    ),
    plot.title = element_text(hjust = .1)
  )

```

```

) +
facet_wrap(~letter, ncol = 3) +
ggtitle("Side-Notched Points")
g2 <- ggplot(data = df_grps[[2]]) +
  geom_path(aes(x = x, y = y, group = object_id, color = letter),
    alpha = .85
  ) +
  scale_color_manual(values = saturated_colors) +
  theme_void() +
  coord_fixed(clip = "off") +
  guides(color = "none") +
  theme(
    strip.text = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"),
    plot.background = element_rect(
      fill = "#e8eaed", color = "black", linewidth = 1.5
    ),
    plot.title = element_text(hjust = .1)
  ) +
  facet_wrap(~letter, ncol = 3) +
  ggtitle("Triangular Points")

g <- cowplot::plot_grid(g1, g2, ncol = 2, align = "hv")
g
nm <- "types_stacked"

# ggsave(file.path("figures", paste0(nm, ".png")),

```

```

# dpi = 900, width = 170, units = "mm")
#
# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>%
# image_read() %>%
# image_trim() %>%
# image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
#   image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

dict <- df_grps[[1]] %>%
  distinct(point_form, point_type, letter) %>%
  arrange(point_form)

paste(
  "For side-notched types:",
  map2_chr(dict$point_type, dict$letter, function(x, y) paste0(x, "
  ↪  ", y, ")) %>%
  paste(collapse = ", ")
) %>% cat()

dict <- df_grps[[2]] %>%
  distinct(point_form, point_type, letter) %>%
  arrange(point_form)

paste(
  "For triangular types:",

```

```

map2_chr(dict$point_type, dict$letter, function(x, y) paste0(x, "
  ↪  (" , y, ")")) %>%
  paste(collapse = ", ")
) %>% cat()

#### Point Distributions ####

points <- rio::import(file.path("data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv"))
↪ %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

points <- points %>%
  filter(!point_type %in% c("undetermined"))

table(points$point_type) %>%
  t() %>%
  t()

# create hexagonal grids

site_data <- rio::import(file.path("data/heurist_sites.csv")) %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

states <- rnaturalearth::ne_states() %>%

```

```

  filter(name %in% c("Arizona", "New Mexico")) %>%
  st_transform(26912)
sites <- site_data %>%

  select(site_name, long, lat, start_date, end_date) %>%
  filter(site_name != "") %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  mutate_at(vars(long, lat), as.numeric) %>%
  filter(!is.na(long)) %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326, remove = F) %>%
  st_transform(26912)

point_freq <- points %>%
  filter(site_name != "") %>%
  select(site_name, point_type) %>%
  group_by(site_name, point_type) %>%
  count(name = "count") %>%
  group_by(site_name) %>%
  mutate(total = sum(count)) %>%
  mutate(freq = count / total) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(total > 4)

point_freq <- inner_join(sites %>% select(site_name), point_freq)

sites <- sites %>%
  filter(site_name %in% point_freq$site_name)

```

```

grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
types <- point_freq$point_type %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
p <- list()
for (type in types) {
  print(type)
  plotdf <- point_freq %>%
    filter(point_type == type)
  total_type <- sum(plotdf$count)
  if (total_type < 10) next # skip if less than 10 points
  grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
  plotdf <- plotdf %>%
    select(-site_name) %>%
    st_join(grid %>% mutate(id = 1:n())) %>%
    group_by(id) %>%
    summarize(
      count = sum(count),
      total = sum(total), freq = count / total
    ) %>%
    st_centroid()
  r <- kde(plotdf %>% select(freq), 72000, grid = grid)
  p[[type]] <- ggplot() +
    geom_sf(data = states, fill = "white") +
    # geom_sf(data = grid_data, aes(fill = freq)) +

```

```

geom_sf(data = r, aes(fill = kde_value)) +
geom_sf(
  data = sites,
  color = "white", alpha = 0.75, shape = 17, size = 1
) +
scale_fill_viridis_c() +
theme_minimal() +
theme(plot.margin = unit(c(2, 2, 2, 2), "mm")) + # Set margins to
↪ zero
labs(title = type, subtitle = paste(total_type, "total points"))
↪ +
coord_sf(xlim = c(150000, 850000), ylim = c(3600000, 4124890))
ggsave(file.path(paste0(
  "figures/points_kde/",
  type, "-kde_hex_binned.png"
)), width = 8, height = 4.5, dpi = 600)
}

point_freq <- points %>%
  filter(site_name != "") %>%
  filter(point_form %in% c("side-notched", "triangular")) %>%
  select(site_name, point_form) %>%
  group_by(site_name, point_form) %>%
  count(name = "count") %>%
  group_by(site_name) %>%
  mutate(total = sum(count)) %>%

```

```

mutate(freq = count / total) %>%
ungroup() %>%
filter(total > 4)

point_freq <- inner_join(sites %>% select(site_name), point_freq)

sites <- sites %>%
  filter(site_name %in% point_freq$site_name)

grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
types <- point_freq$point_form %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
p <- list()
for (type in types) {
  print(type)
  plotdf <- point_freq %>%
    filter(point_form == type)
  total_type <- sum(plotdf$count)
  if (total_type < 10) next # skip if less than 10 points
  grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
  plotdf <- plotdf %>%
    select(-site_name) %>%
    st_join(grid %>% mutate(id = 1:n())) %>%
    group_by(id) %>%
    summarize(

```

```

    count = sum(count),
    total = sum(total), freq = count / total
  ) %>%
  st_centroid()
r <- kde(plotdf %>% select(freq), 72000, grid = grid)
p[[type]] <- ggplot() +
  geom_sf(data = states, fill = "white") +
  geom_sf(data = r, aes(fill = kde_value)) +
  geom_sf(
    data = sites,
    color = "white", alpha = 0.75, shape = 17, size = 1
  ) +
  scale_fill_viridis_c() +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(plot.margin = unit(c(2, 2, 2, 2), "mm")) + # Set margins to
  ↪ zero
  labs(title = type, subtitle = paste(total_type, "total points"))
  ↪ +
  coord_sf(xlim = c(150000, 850000), ylim = c(3600000, 4124890))
ggsave(file.path(paste0(
  "figures/points_kde/",
  type, "-kde_hex_binned.png"
)), width = 8, height = 4.5, dpi = 600)
}

point_freq <- points %>%

```

```

filter(site_name != "") %>%
filter(point_form %in% c("side-notched", "triangular")) %>%
select(site_name, point_cluster) %>%
group_by(site_name, point_cluster) %>%
count(name = "count") %>%
group_by(site_name) %>%
mutate(total = sum(count)) %>%
mutate(freq = count / total) %>%
ungroup() %>%
filter(total > 4)

point_freq <- inner_join(sites %>% select(site_name), point_freq)

sites <- sites %>%
  filter(site_name %in% point_freq$site_name)
grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
types <- point_freq$point_cluster %>%
  unique() %>%
  sort()
p <- list()
for (type in types) {
  print(type)
  plotdf <- point_freq %>%
    filter(point_cluster == type)
  total_type <- sum(plotdf$count)
  if (total_type < 10) next # skip if less than 10 points

```

```

grid <- create_grid_hexagonal(sites, cell_size = 36000)
plotdf <- plotdf %>%
  select(-site_name) %>%
  st_join(grid %>% mutate(id = 1:n())) %>%
  group_by(id) %>%
  summarize(
    count = sum(count),
    total = sum(total), freq = count / total
  ) %>%
  st_centroid()
r <- kde(plotdf %>% select(freq), 72000, grid = grid)
p[[type]] <- ggplot() +
  geom_sf(data = states, fill = "white") +
  geom_sf(data = r, aes(fill = kde_value)) +
  geom_sf(data = sites, color = "white", alpha = 0.75, shape = 17,
    ↪ size = 1) +
  scale_fill_viridis_c() +
  theme_minimal() +
  guides(fill = "none") +
  theme(plot.margin = unit(c(2, 2, 2, 2), "mm")) + # Set margins to
    ↪ zero
  labs(title = type, subtitle = paste(total_type, "total points"))
    ↪ +
  coord_sf(xlim = c(150000, 850000), ylim = c(3600000, 4124890))
ggsave(
  file.path(

```

```

    paste0("figures/points_kde/", type,
          ↪ "-kde_hex_binned_nolegend.png")
  ),
  width = 8, height = 4.5, dpi = 600, bg = "white"
)
}

combine_imgs <- function(imgs, nrow, file_name) {
  imgs <- lapply(imgs, function(x) {
    image_trim(x) %>%
      image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
      image_scale("1500x")
  })
  if (length(imgs) %% 2 != 0) {
    print("adding extra image to make even number of images")
    info <- image_info(imgs[[1]])
    width <- info$width
    height <- info$height
    imgs <- c(imgs, image_blank(
      width = width, height = height, color = "white"
    ))
  }
  ncol <- length(imgs) / nrow
  sq <- seq(1, length(imgs), ncol)
  rows <- list()
  for (i in 1:nrow) {

```

```

    indx <- sq[i]:(sq[i] + ncol - 1)
    print(indx)
    rows[[i]] <- image_append(do.call(c, imgs[indx]))
  }
  final_image <- image_append(do.call(c, rows), stack = TRUE)
  final_image <- image_scale(final_image, "4500x")
  image_write(final_image, path = file_name, density = 900)
  print(paste("saved to", file_name))
}

imgs <- lapply(types, function(x) {
  image_read(
    file.path(paste0(
      "figures/points_kde/",
      x, "-kde_hex_binned_nolegend.png"
    ))
  )
})

# combine_imgs(imgs, nrow = 2,
# file_name = file.path("figures/combined_hexbins.png"))

# combine top 4 types for side-notch and triangular

types_tri <- points %>%
  filter(point_form == "triangular") %>%

```

```

select(point_type) %>%
group_by(point_type) %>%
count() %>%
ungroup() %>%
slice_max(n = 6, order_by = n) %>%
pull(point_type)

types_side <- points %>%
  filter(point_form == "side-notched") %>%
  select(point_type) %>%
  group_by(point_type) %>%
  count() %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  slice_max(n = 6, order_by = n) %>%
  pull(point_type)

# imgs_tri = lapply(types_tri, function(x)
# image_read(file.path(paste0(
#   "figures/points_kde/", x, "-kde_hex_binned.png"
#   )))
# combine_imgs(imgs = imgs_tri, nrow = 3,
# file_name = file.path(
#   "figures/combined_hexbins_triangular.png"
#   ))
# imgs_side = lapply(types_side, function(x)
# image_read(file.path(paste0(

```

```

# "figures/points_kde/",x,"-kde_hex_binned.png"
# )))
# combine_imgs(imgs = imgs_side, nrow = 3,
# file_name = file.path(
# "figures/combined_hexbins_side.png"
# ))

#### Community Detection ####

base <- readRDS(file.path("data/backgroundmap.Rds"))
base_tonto <- readRDS(file.path("data/backgroundmap_tonto.Rds"))

site_data <- rio::import(file.path("data/heurist_sites.csv")) %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

states <- rnaturalearth::ne_states() %>%
  filter(name %in% c("Arizona", "New Mexico")) %>%
  st_transform(26912)

sites <- site_data %>%
  select(site_name, long, lat, start_date, end_date) %>%
  filter(site_name != "") %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  mutate_at(vars(long, lat), as.numeric) %>%
  filter(!is.na(long)) %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326, remove = F) %>%
  st_transform(26912)

```

```

points_sub <- points %>%
  left_join(sites %>% select(site_name, start_date, end_date)) %>%
  filter(!point_type %in% c("undetermined")) %>%
  filter(!site_name %in% c("", "Wupatki National Monument"))

d <- table(points_sub$site_name, points_sub$point_type) %>%
  prop.table(margin = 1) %>%
  as.matrix() %>%
  {
    . * 100
  }
m <- dist(d, method = "manhattan") %>% as.matrix()
m <- 1 - (m / 200)
diag(m) <- 0
colnames(m)
hist(m)
edges <- m %>%
  as.table() %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  setNames(c("from", "to", "weight")) %>%
  filter(from != "to") %>%
  filter(weight > quantile(weight, 0.75))

library(igraph)
g <- graph_from_data_frame(d = edges, directed = F)
g <- simplify(g)

```

```

plot(g)
communities <- cluster_louvain(g, weights = E(g)$weight, resolution =
↪ 1)
membership_df <- data.frame(
  community = membership(communities)
) %>%
  rownames_to_column("site_name")

sites_communities <- sites %>%
  inner_join(membership_df) %>%
  mutate(community = factor(community))

# mapview::mapview(sites_communities, zcol = "community")

coords <- st_coordinates(st_transform(sites_communities, 26912))

sites_communities_df <- sites_communities %>%
  st_drop_geometry() %>%
  mutate(x = coords[, 1], y = coords[, 2]) %>%
  distinct(lat, long, .keep_all = T) %>%
  mutate(community = factor(community))

tonto_boundary <- st_as_sfc(st_bbox(
  c(
    xmin = -111.04,
    ymin = 33.62, xmax = -110.92, ymax = 33.68
  )
))

```

```

),
  crs = 4326
)) %>%
  st_transform(26912) %>%
  st_cast("POLYGON") %>%
  st_sfc() %>%
  st_sf() %>%
  mutate(id = "tonto boundary")

tonto_sites <- sites_communities_df %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("x", "y"), crs = 26912, remove = F) %>%
  st_crop(tonto_boundary)

table(tonto_sites$site_name, tonto_sites$community)

# Define shape and color mappings
shape_mapping <- c("1" = 16, "2" = 17, "3" = 18, "4" = 15) # Shape
↪ codes
color_mapping <- c(
  "1" = "#440154FF", "2" = "#FDE725FF",
  "3" = "#31688EFF", "4" = "#35B779FF"
) # Colors

insert <- base_tonto +
  geom_sf(data = tonto_sites, aes(
    color = community,

```

```

    shape = community
  ), alpha = 0.8, size = 3) +
  scale_shape_manual(values = shape_mapping) +
  scale_color_manual(values = color_mapping) +
  coord_sf(
    xlim = c(496289.7, 507420.6),
    ylim = c(3720024.3, 3726678.8)
  ) +
  guides(color = "none", shape = "none") +
  theme(plot.background = element_rect(
    fill = "white",
    color = "red", linewidth = 2
  )) +
  ggtitle("Roosevelt")
insert
insert <- ggplotGrob(insert)

xmin_inset <- 600000
xmax_inset <- 900000
ymin_inset <- 3660000
ymax_inset <- 3770000

g <- base +
  # ggplot() +
  geom_point(data = sites_communities_df, aes(
    x = x, y = y,

```

```

    color = community, shape = community
  ), alpha = 0.7, size = 3) +
  scale_shape_manual(values = shape_mapping) +
  scale_color_manual(values = color_mapping) +
  geom_sf(data = tonto_boundary, color = "white", fill = "red", alpha
↪ = 0.6) +
  annotation_custom(
    grob = insert,
    xmin = 600000, xmax = 900000, ymin = 3660000, ymax = 3770000
  ) +
  theme(legend.position = "top")

nm <- "point_type_boundaries"

# ggsave(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")), dpi = 900, width =
↪ 170, units = "mm")

# file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")) %>% image_read() %>%
# image_trim() %>% image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white")
↪ %>%
#   image_write(file.path("figures",paste0(nm,".png")))

#### Machine Learning Confusion Matrices ####

# Load libraries

```

```

library(tidyverse)
library(janitor)
library(readxl)
library(cowplot)
library(ggtext)

# Define model categories and corresponding metadata columns
models <- list(
  bases = "base_type",
  notches = "notch_height",
  shape = "point_cluster",
  serrated = "serrated"
)

notches <- rio::import("data/predicted_types_notches.xlsx") %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

serrated <- rio::import("data/predicted_types_serrated.xlsx") %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

shape <- rio::import("data/predicted_types_shape.xlsx") %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

bases <- rio::import("data/predicted_types_bases.xlsx") %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%

```

```

as_tibble() %>%
  filter(base_type != "unknown")

dfs <- list(
  bases = bases,
  notches = notches,
  shape = shape,
  serrated = serrated
)

# Helper function to generate ggplot confusion matrix
plot_conf_mat <- function(df, model) {
  print(model)
  df <- tibble(truth = factor(df[[model]]), prediction =
↪ factor(df$predicted_type)) %>%
  filter(!is.na(truth), !is.na(prediction))

  tab <- table(df$truth, df$prediction)
  acc <- round(sum(diag(tab)) / sum(tab), 3)
  title <- str_replace_all(model, "_", " ") %>%
    str_to_title()

  as.data.frame(tab) %>%
    rename(Truth = Var1, Predicted = Var2, n = Freq) %>%
    ggplot(aes(x = Predicted, y = Truth, fill = n)) +
    geom_tile(color = "white") +

```

```

geom_text(aes(label = n), color = "black", size = 4) +
scale_fill_gradient(low = "white", high = "#2c7fb8") +
theme_minimal(base_size = 10) +
theme(
  axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1),
  legend.position = "none",
  plot.title = element_markdown(size = 11, face = "bold"),
  plot.background = element_rect(fill = "white", color = "black",
  ↪ linewidth = 1.5)
) +
labs(
  title = glue::glue("{title}<br><span
  ↪ style='font-size:10pt;'>Accuracy = {acc}</span>"),
  x = "Predicted",
  y = "True"
)
}

# Generate plots
plots <- map2(
  dfs,
  models,
  plot_conf_mat
)

# Combine into single figure

```

```

final_plot <- plot_grid(plotlist = plots, ncol = 2, labels = "AUTO")

# Save to file
fn <- "figures/confusion_matrices_combined.png"
ggsave(fn, final_plot, width = 6.5, height = 8, dpi = 600)

image_read(fn) %>%
  image_trim() %>%
  image_border(geometry = "50x50", color = "white") %>%
  image_write(fn)

#### export session info ####
# Get the R version
r_version <- paste0("R version=", R.version$major, R.version$minor,
  ↪ sep = ".")

# Get the loaded packages and their versions
loaded_packages <- sessionInfo()$otherPkgs
loaded_versions <- sapply(
  loaded_packages,
  function(x) paste(x$Package, x$Version, sep = "=")
)

# Write the R version and package versions to the file

```

```
writeLines(c(r_version, loaded_versions), con =  
↪ "analysis/r_environment2.qmd")
```

R Environment

R version=44.3. cowplot=1.1.3 Hotelling=1.0-8 corpcor=1.6.10 rnaturalearth=1.0.1
viridis=0.6.5 viridisLite=0.4.2 colorspace=2.1-1 ggfx=1.0.1 ggnewscale=0.5.1 ggrepel=0.9.6 terra=1.8-29 SpatialKDE=0.8.2 randomForest=4.7-1.2 umap=0.2.10.0 sf=1.0-19
magick=2.8.5 gt=0.11.1 flextable=0.9.7 NetworkDistance=0.3.4 vegan=2.6-10 lattice=0.22-6
permute=0.9-7 ggnetwork=0.5.13 igraph=2.1.4 rio=1.2.3 here=1.0.1 ggthemes=5.1.0
huxtable=5.5.7 kableExtra=1.4.0 Momocs=1.4.1 magrittr=2.0.3 lubridate=1.9.4 forcats=1.0.0 stringr=1.5.1 dplyr=1.1.4 purrr=1.0.4 readr=2.1.5 tidyr=1.3.1 tibble=3.2.1
ggplot2=3.5.1 tidyverse=2.0.0

Python Training Code

```
import os  
import pandas as pd  
import torch  
import torch.nn as nn  
import torch.optim as optim  
from torch.utils.data import Dataset, DataLoader  
from torchvision import transforms  
from PIL import Image  
from torchvision.models import efficientnet_v2_s  
import contextlib  
import time  
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

```

def test_model(model, test_loader, device, criterion):
    model.eval()
    correct = 0
    total = 0
    test_loss = 0.0

    with torch.no_grad():
        for images, labels in test_loader:
            images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device)
            outputs = model(images)
            loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
            test_loss += loss.item()

            _, predicted = outputs.max(1)
            total += labels.size(0)
            correct += predicted.eq(labels).sum().item()

    avg_test_loss = test_loss / len(test_loader)
    test_accuracy = 100 * correct / total
    print(
        f"Test Loss: {avg_test_loss:.4f}, Test Accuracy:
        ↪ {test_accuracy:.2f}%"
    )
    return avg_test_loss, test_accuracy

```

```

def train_and_save_model(class_type, form, include_types, version):
    # Load the Excel file
    data_path = "data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv"
    df = pd.read_csv(data_path)

    if isinstance(form, str):
        form = [form]

    df = df[df['Point Form'].isin(form)].copy()
    df = df[df[class_type].isin(include_types)].copy()
    df['Media file Name'] = df['objectID'].astype(str) + ".png"

    img_dir = "data/pointImages/ml"
    image_filenames = set(os.listdir(img_dir))
    df_exists = df[df['Media file
↪ Name'].isin(image_filenames)].copy()

    counts = df_exists[class_type].value_counts().reset_index()
    counts[f'{class_type}_new'] = counts.apply(
        lambda row: row[class_type] if row['count'] > 9 else 'other',
        ↪ axis=1
    )
    counts = counts[[class_type, f'{class_type}_new']]
    df_merged = pd.merge(df_exists, counts, on=class_type,
↪ how='left')

```

```

df_merged = df_merged.drop(columns=[class_type])
df_merged = df_merged.rename(columns={f'{class_type}_new':
↪ class_type})
df_merged = df_merged[~df_merged[class_type].isin(
    ['Unknown', 'other', 'Unclassified']
)].copy()
df_merged = df_merged.dropna(subset=[class_type]).copy()
train_df, test_df = train_test_split(
    df_merged, test_size=0.15,
    stratify=df_merged[class_type], random_state=42
)

# Define the number of rotations for each image to expand the
↪ dataset
ROTATION_ANGLES = [0] # You can adjust rotation angles if needed

# Create a custom dataset for images and labels with
↪ augmentations
class AugmentedPointClusterDataset(Dataset):
    def __init__(self, df, img_dir, transform=None,
                 rotation_angles=ROTATION_ANGLES):
        self.df = df
        self.img_dir = img_dir
        self.transform = transform
        self.rotation_angles = rotation_angles
        self.label_to_idx = {

```

```

        label: idx for idx, label in
↪ enumerate(include_types)}

        self.idx_to_label = {
            idx: label for label, idx in
↪ self.label_to_idx.items()}

    def __len__(self):
        return len(self.df) * len(self.rotation_angles)

    def __getitem__(self, idx):
        original_idx = idx // len(self.rotation_angles)
        rotation_angle = self.rotation_angles[idx % len(
            self.rotation_angles
        )]

        img_name = self.df.iloc[original_idx]["Media file Name"]
        img_path = os.path.join(self.img_dir, img_name)
        image = Image.open(img_path).convert("RGB")
        image = image.rotate(rotation_angle)

        if self.transform:
            image = self.transform(image)

        label = self.df.iloc[original_idx][class_type]
        label_idx = self.label_to_idx[label]

```

```

        return image, label_idx

# Define transformations
transform = transforms.Compose([
    transforms.Resize((224, 224)),
    transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip(),
    transforms.ToTensor(),
    transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[
        0.229, 0.224, 0.225]),
])

# Create Dataset and DataLoader with augmentations
train_dataset = AugmentedPointClusterDataset(
    train_df, img_dir, transform=transform)
test_dataset = AugmentedPointClusterDataset(
    test_df, img_dir, transform=transform)
train_loader = DataLoader(
    train_dataset, batch_size=4, shuffle=True)
test_loader = DataLoader(
    test_dataset, batch_size=4, shuffle=False)

# Load the EfficientNetV2 model and adjust the classification
↪ head
model = efficientnet_v2_s(pretrained=True)
num_classes = len(include_types)

# print(model.classifier)

```

```

model.classifier[1] = nn.Linear(
    model.classifier[1].in_features, num_classes) # type: ignore

# Set up loss function and optimizer
criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
optimizer = optim.Adam(model.parameters(), lr=1e-4) # type:
↪ ignore

# Training loop
device = torch.device("cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else
↪ "cpu")
model.to(device)
print(device)

epochs = 12
form_string = "_".join(form)
log_file_path =
↪ f"models/class_{class_type}_{form_string}_{version}.txt"

for epoch in range(epochs):
    start_time = time.time()

    with contextlib.redirect_stdout(open(os.devnull, 'w')):
        model.train()

    running_loss = 0.0

```

```

correct = 0
total = 0
for images, labels in train_loader:
    images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device)

    optimizer.zero_grad()
    outputs = model(images)
    loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
    loss.backward()
    optimizer.step()

    running_loss += loss.item()
    _, predicted = outputs.max(1)
    total += labels.size(0)
    correct += predicted.eq(labels).sum().item()

epoch_loss = running_loss / len(train_loader)
epoch_accuracy = 100 * correct / total
elapsed_time = time.time() - start_time

print(f"""
    Epoch {epoch + 1}/{epochs},
    Loss: {epoch_loss:.4f},
    Accuracy: {epoch_accuracy:.2f}%,
    Time: {elapsed_time:.2f}
    seconds
""")

```

```

        """)

        # Save the model for the current epoch
        model_save_path = f"""
models/class_{class_type}_{form_string}_epoch_{epoch +
↪ 1}_{version}.pth
        """
        torch.save(model.state_dict(), model_save_path)
        print(f"Model saved to {model_save_path}")

        # Log training metrics to file
        with open(
            log_file_path, 'a'
        ) as log_file:
            log_file.write(
                f"""
                Epoch {epoch + 1}/{epochs},
                Loss: {epoch_loss:.4f},
                Accuracy: {epoch_accuracy:.2f}%\n
                """
            )

        # Evaluate on the test set and log test metrics
        test_loss, test_accuracy = test_model(
            model, test_loader, device, criterion)
        with open(log_file_path, 'a') as log_file:

```

```

        log_file.write(
            f"""
            Test Loss: {test_loss:.4f},
            Test Accuracy: {test_accuracy:.2f}%\n
            """
        )

# usage
data_path = "data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv"
df = pd.read_csv(data_path)
df.columns

# df['Point Form'].unique()

# df['Notch Height'].unique()
# class_type = 'Notch Height'
# form = ['side-notched']
# include_types = ["low", "mid", "high"]
# train_and_save_model(class_type=class_type, form=form,
# include_types=include_types, version="v1")
# models\class_Notch Height_side-notched_epoch_12_v1.pth

df['Base Type'].unique()
class_type = 'Base Type'
form = ['side-notched', 'triangular']

```

```

include_types = ['straight', 'concave', 'deeply concave', 'convex']
train_and_save_model(class_type=class_type, form=form,
                      include_types=include_types, version="v2")
# models\class_Base Type_side-notched_triangular_epoch_12_v12.pth

# class_type = 'Point Cluster'
# df[class_type].unique()
# form = ['side-notched', 'triangular']
# include_types = ['shape-2', 'shape-3', 'shape-1']
# train_and_save_model(class_type=class_type, form=form,
#                       include_types=include_types, version="v1")
# class_Point Cluster_side-notched_triangular_epoch_9_v1.pth

# class_type = 'Serrated'
# df[class_type].unique()
# form = ['side-notched', 'triangular']
# include_types = ['No', 'Yes']
# train_and_save_model(class_type=class_type, form=form,
#                       include_types=include_types, version="v1")
# models\class_Serrated_side-notched_triangular_epoch_12_v1.pth

```

Python Evaluation Code

```

import os

import pandas as pd

import torch

import torch.nn as nn

```

```

import torch.optim as optim
from torch.utils.data import Dataset, DataLoader
from torchvision import transforms
from PIL import Image
from torchvision.models import efficientnet_v2_s
import torch.nn.functional as F
from tqdm import tqdm

def predict(image_path, model, transform, labels, top_k=5,
↳ verbose=False):
    # Automatically adjust top_k based on the number of classes
    num_classes = len(labels)
    top_k = min(top_k, num_classes)

    model.eval() # Set the model to evaluation mode
    image = Image.open(image_path).convert("RGB")
    image = transform(image).unsqueeze(0).to(device)

    with torch.no_grad(): # Disable gradient computation for
↳ inference
        outputs = model(image) # Get the raw logits from the model

        # Apply softmax to get the probabilities
        probabilities = F.softmax(outputs, dim=1)

```

```

# Get the top k probabilities and their corresponding indices
top_probs, top_idxes = probabilities.topk(top_k, dim=1)

# Convert the top probabilities and indices to lists
top_probs = top_probs.cpu().numpy().flatten()
top_idxes = top_idxes.cpu().numpy().flatten()

# Print the top k predictions with probabilities
if verbose:
    print("Top predictions:")
    for i in range(top_k):
        label = labels[top_idxes[i]] # Get the label based on
↪ the index
        prob = top_probs[i]
        print(f"{i+1}: {label} ({prob:.4f})")

predicted_idx = top_idxes[0]
# Get the label from the labels list
predicted_label = labels[predicted_idx]
predicted_prob = top_probs[0]

return predicted_label, predicted_prob

# Define class_type, form, and include_types for evaluation
class_type = 'Point Cluster'

```

```

form = ['side-notched', 'triangular']
include_types = ['shape-2', 'shape-3', 'shape-1']

# Define transformations
transform = transforms.Compose([
    transforms.Resize((224, 224)), # Resize to 224x224 for
↳ EfficientNet
    transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip(), # Randomly flip the image
↳ horizontally
    transforms.ToTensor(),
    transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406],
                          std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]),
])

labels = include_types

# Load the EfficientNetV2 model and adjust the classification head
model = efficientnet_v2_s(pretrained=True)
model.classifier[1] = nn.Linear(
    model.classifier[1].in_features, len(labels)
) # type: ignore

# Load the saved model weights
model_save_path = """
models/class_Base Type_side-notched_triangular_epoch_12_v2.pth
"""
model.load_state_dict(torch.load(model_save_path))

```

```

device = torch.device("cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu")
model.to(device)
print(device)

# Define image directory and data path
img_dir = "data/pointImages/ml"

# Get a set of all image filenames in img_dir
image_filenames = set(os.listdir(img_dir))

if isinstance(form, str):
    form = [form]
data_path = "data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv"
df = pd.read_csv(data_path)
df['Media file Name'] = df['objectID'].astype(str) + ".png"
df_exists = df[df['Media file Name'].isin(image_filenames)].copy()
len(df_exists)
df_exists[class_type].unique()
df_unknown = df_exists

# df_unknown = df_exists[pd.isna(df_exists[class_type])]
# df_unknown = df_unknown[df_unknown['Point Form'].isin(form)].copy()
# df_unknown = df_unknown[['Projectile point H-ID',
# 'objectID', class_type, 'Media file Name', 'Point Form']]
# df_unknown['Predicted Type'] = None
# df_unknown['Prediction Probability'] = None
len(df_unknown)

```

```

# Predict and update df_unknown DataFrame
for image_name in tqdm(df_unknown['Media file Name'],
                       desc="Processing images"):
    if image_name.lower().endswith(".png"):
        image_path = os.path.join(img_dir, image_name)

        # Use the predict function to get
        # the predicted class and probability
        predicted_cluster, predicted_prob = predict(
            image_path, model, transform, labels, top_k=5,
↪ verbose=False
        )

        # Set predicted_cluster to
        # "Unclassified" if predicted_prob is below 0.5
        # predicted_cluster =
        # "Unclassified" if predicted_prob < 0.5 else
        ↪ predicted_cluster

        # Update the df_unknown DataFrame with the predicted type and
        ↪ probability
        df_unknown.loc[df_unknown['Media file Name'] == image_name,
                       'Predicted Type'] = predicted_cluster
        df_unknown.loc[df_unknown['Media file Name'] == image_name,
                       'Prediction Probability'] = predicted_prob

```

```
# Save the updated df_unknown DataFrame to an Excel file
output_tsv_path = "data/predicted_types.tsv"
df_unknown.to_csv(output_tsv_path, sep='\t', index=False)

print(f"Results saved to {output_tsv_path}")
```

Python Environment

Note: this python environment was also used for all python code used in this dissertation.

```
python==3.8.19
aiofiles==23.2.1
aiohappyeyeballs==2.4.3
aiohttp==3.10.11
aiosignal==1.3.1
annotated-types==0.7.0
anyio==4.4.0
asgiref==3.8.1
asttokens==3.0.0
async-timeout==5.0.1
asynccer==0.0.8
attrs==24.2.0
backcall==0.2.0
backports.zoneinfo==0.2.1
Bottleneck
Brotli
build==1.2.2
```

```
cachetools==5.5.0
certifi
cffi==1.17.1
charset-normalizer
click==8.1.7
colorama==0.4.6
coloredlogs==15.0.1
comm==0.2.2
contourpy==1.1.1
cryptography==43.0.1
cyclers==0.12.1
debugpy==1.8.13
decorator==5.2.1
distro==1.9.0
Django==4.2.16
efficientnet_pytorch==0.7.1
et-xmlfile==1.1.0
exceptiongroup==1.2.2
executing==2.2.0
fancycompleter==0.9.1
fastapi==0.115.5
ffmpy==0.4.0
filelock
filetype==1.2.0
flatbuffers==24.3.25
fonttools==4.53.1
```

```
frozenlist==1.5.0
fsspec==2024.9.0
gmpy2
google-ai-generativelanguage==0.1.0
google-api-core==2.19.2
google-auth==2.34.0
google-generativeai==0.1.0rc1
googleapis-common-protos==1.65.0
gradio==4.44.1
gradio_client==1.3.0
grpcio==1.66.1
grpcio-status==1.62.3
h11==0.14.0
httpcore==1.0.5
httpx==0.27.2
huggingface-hub==0.25.0
humanfriendly==10.0
idna
imageio==2.35.1
importlib_metadata==8.5.0
importlib_resources==6.4.4
ipykernel==6.29.5
ipython==8.12.3
jedi==0.19.2
Jinja2
jiter==0.5.0
```

```
joblib==1.4.2
jsonschema==4.23.0
jsonschema-specifications==2023.12.1
jupyter_client==8.6.3
jupyter_core==5.7.2
kiwisolver==1.4.5
lazy_loader==0.4
llvmlite==0.41.1
Markdown==3.7
markdown-it-py==3.0.0
MarkupSafe
matplotlib==3.7.5
matplotlib-inline==0.1.7
mdurl==0.1.2
mkl-fft
mkl-random
mkl-service==2.4.0
mpmath
multidict==6.1.0
munch==4.0.0
nest-asyncio==1.6.0
networkx
numba==0.58.1
numexpr
numpy
onnxruntime==1.19.2
```

```
onnxruntime-gpu==1.19.2
openai==1.45.1
opencv-python-headless==4.10.0.84
openpyxl==3.1.5
orjson==3.10.11
packaging==24.2
pandas
parso==0.8.4
pdbpp==0.10.3
pdf2image==1.17.0
pdfminer.six==20231228
pdfplumber==0.11.4
pickleshare==0.7.5
pillow
pip-tools==7.4.1
pkgutil_resolve_name==1.3.10
platformdirs==4.3.6
pooch==1.8.2
pretrainedmodels==0.7.4
prompt_toolkit==3.0.50
propcache==0.2.0
proto-plus==1.24.0
protobuf==4.25.4
psutil==7.0.0
pure_eval==0.2.3
pyarrow==17.0.0
```

```
pyasn1==0.6.1
pyasn1_modules==0.4.1
pyparser==2.22
pydantic==2.9.1
pydantic_core==2.23.3
pydub==0.25.1
Pygments==2.19.1
PyMatting==1.1.13
pynndescent==0.5.13
pypandoc==1.13
pyparsing==3.1.2
PyPDF2==3.0.1
pypdfium2==4.30.0
pyproject_hooks==1.2.0
pyreadline==2.1
pyreadline3==3.5.4
pyrepl==0.9.0
PySocks
python-dateutil==2.9.0.post0
python-dotenv==1.0.1
python-multipart==0.0.17
pyTRS
pytz
PyWavelets==1.4.1
pywin32==310
PyYAML
```

```
pyzmq==26.3.0
referencing==0.35.1
regex==2024.9.11
rembg==2.0.59
requests
rpds-py==0.20.1
rsa==4.9
ruff==0.7.4
safetensors==0.4.5
scikit-image==0.21.0
scikit-learn==1.3.2
scipy==1.10.1
segmentation-models-pytorch==0.3.3
semantic-version==2.10.0
shapely==2.0.6
shellingham==1.5.4
six==1.17.0
sniffio==1.3.1
sqlparse==0.5.1
stack-data==0.6.3
starlette==0.41.2
sympy
threadpoolctl==3.5.0
tifffile==2023.7.10
tiktoken==0.7.0
timm==0.9.2
```

```
tomli==2.0.1
tomlkit==0.12.0
torch==2.4.0
torchaudio==2.4.0
torchvision==0.19.0
tornado==6.4.2
tqdm==4.66.5
traitlets==5.14.3
typer==0.13.0
typing_extensions==4.12.2
tzdata
umap-learn==0.5.6
urllib3
uunet==2.2.1
uvicorn==0.32.0
watchdog==4.0.2
wcwidth==0.2.13
websockets==12.0
win-inet-pton
wmctrl==0.5
yarl==1.15.2
zipp==3.20.2
```

APPENDIX C

CODE FOR CHAPTER 4

This chapter contains the code used for the analysis in chapter 4. The code is organized into two sections: **R** and **R Environment**. The **R** section contains the code for the analysis and the **R Environment** section contains the R environment used to run the analysis.

R

```
library(tidyverse)
library(magrittr)
library(Momocs)
library(ggthemes)
library(here)
library(rio)
library(igraph)
library(ggnetwork)
library(vegan)

set.seed(1010)

# library(ggimage)

# load data and remove sites with only one projectile point

sites <- import(here("data/TontoBasinNetworkSites.xlsx"), setclass =
↳ "tibble") %>%
  dplyr::ungroup() %>%
  filter(!Site %in% c("AZ V:5:130 (ASM)", "AZ U:4:009 (ASM)", "AZ
↳ U:8:318 (ASM)", "AZ V:5:121 (ASM)", "AZ U:3:128 (ASM)"))
```

```

# data frame for network nodes
nodes <- sites %>%
  select(Site, Area, Architecture) %>%
  mutate(Architecture = case_when(str_detect(Architecture, "compound,
  ↪ platform mound") ~ "platform mound", str_detect(Architecture,
  ↪ "compound, roomblock") ~ "roomblock", TRUE ~ Architecture)) %>%
  rowid_to_column("id") %>%
  dplyr::ungroup()

coords <- import(here("data/siteCoords.xlsx")) %>%
  inner_join(nodes) %>%
  arrange(id)
CeramicData <- rio::import(here("data/CeramicData.xlsx"),
  setclass = "tibble"
)

ceramicDF <- import("data/ceramicDF.xlsx")

outTonto <- readRDS(here("data/outTontoGila.Rds")) %>%
  rename(Site = ArchaMapName)

outTonto$fac <- outTonto$fac %>%
  left_join(points)

table(outTonto$pointCluster)

```

```

cTotal <- ceramicDF %>%
  group_by(Site) %>%
  summarize(Ceramics = as.integer(sum(Roosevelt, na.rm = T)))

pTotal <- table(outTonto$fac$Site) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  setNames(c("Site", "Projectile Points"))

sites %<>%
  select(-any_of(c("Projectile Points", "Ceramics"))) %>%
  left_join(cTotal) %>%
  left_join(pTotal) %>%
  mutate(id = 1:n(), .before = 1)

outTonto$fac <- outTonto$fac %>%
  select(-any_of("id")) %>%
  left_join(sites %>% select(Site, id))

# rio::export(sites, here("tables/TontoBasinSites.xlsx"))

# network functions
scale_to_1 <- function(mat) {
  rng <- range(mat, na.rm = TRUE)
  (mat - rng[1]) / (rng[2] - rng[1])
}

```

```

makeGraph <- function(d, nLinks = NULL) {
  # igraph
  m <- scale_to_1(d)
  g <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(as.matrix(d), mode = "undirected",
  ↪ diag = F, weighted = T)
  n_df <- tibble(id = V(g)$name) %>%
    mutate_all(as.integer) %>%
    left_join(nodes, by = "id")
  V(g)$name <- n_df$id %>% as.character()
  V(g)$Site <- n_df$Site
  V(g)$Area <- n_df$Area
  V(g)$Architecture <- n_df$Architecture
  V(g)$centrality <- eigen_centrality(g, weights =
  ↪ E(g)$weight)$vector

  if (!is.null(nLinks)) {
    # calculate top n (with ties) edges and convert to igraph object
    # convert to dataframe
    n <- igraph::as_data_frame(g)
    n <- bind_rows(n, n %>% dplyr::rename(from = to, to = from))
    n %<>% # sort data frame
      arrange(from, desc(weight)) %>%
      # rank by site
      group_by(from) %>%
      mutate(rank = rank(-weight)) %>%
      ungroup()
  }
}

```

```

nSub <- n %>%
  group_by(from) %>%
  slice_max(n = nLinks, order_by = desc(rank)) %>%
  ungroup()

gRanks <- graph_from_data_frame(nSub, directed = F, vertices =
↪ n_df)
gRanks %<>% igraph::simplify()
V(gRanks)$centrality <- eigen_centrality(gRanks, weights =
↪ E(gRanks)$weight)$vector
return(gRanks)
} else {
  return(g)
}
}

values2graphicsMod <- function(values, output = "color", palette =
↪ "Paired") {
  if (!output %in% c("color", "shape")) {
    stop("wrong parameter: output")
  }
  if (is.data.frame(values)) {
    values <- values[[1]]
  }
  types <- as.factor(values)
  num_types <- length(levels(types))

```

```

color_map <- brewer.pal(num_types, palette)
color_map[types]

if ((output == "shape") & num_types > 5) {
  warning("only 5 distinct shapes available: some shapes have been
  ↪ repeated")
}

l <- vector("list")
l[["legend.text"]] <- levels(types)
l[["legend.pch"]] <- 21
if (output == "color") {
  l[["legend.col"]] <- color_map[1:num_types]
  l[["color"]] <- color_map[types]
}
if (output == "shape") {
  l[["legend.pch"]] <- ((1:num_types) - 1) %% 5 + 21
  l[["shape"]] <- (as.numeric(types) - 1) %% 5 + 21
}
l
}

dists <- list()

d <- dist(coords[, c("UTMEAST", "UTMNORTH")]) %>% as.matrix()
colnames(d) <- rownames(d) <- coords$id
# convert to scaled similarity (1 highest)
d <- 1 - (d / max(d))

```

```

dists$spatial <- d

# architecture network
# convert to adjacency matrix
tmp <- sites %>%
  separate_rows(Architecture, sep = ", ") %>%
  left_join(nodes %>% select(Site, id))
m <- table(tmp$id, tmp$Architecture) %>% as.matrix()
# calculate jaccard distance
d <- vegdist(m, method = "jaccard", na.rm = T) %>% as.matrix()
# convert to jaccard similarity
d <- 1 - d
dists$architecture <- d

# ceramic network
# convert to adjacency matrix
m <- ceramicDF %>%
  select(Type, id, Roosevelt) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(Roosevelt), as.numeric) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = Type, values_from = Roosevelt) %>%
  column_to_rownames("id") %>%
  as.matrix()
# calculate jaccard distance
d <- vegdist(m, method = "jaccard", na.rm = T) %>% as.matrix()
# convert to jaccard similarity
d <- 1 - d

```

```

dists$ceramics <- d

# projectile point network
# convert to adjacency matrix
m <- table(outTonto$fac$id, outTonto$fac$pointCluster) %>%
  ↪ as.matrix()

# calculate jaccard distance
d <- vegdist(m, method = "jaccard") %>% as.matrix()

# convert to jaccard similarity
d <- 1 - d

dists$points <- d

g2List <- list()
nms <- names(dists)
for (n in nms) {
  print(n)
  g <- makeGraph(dists[[n]], nLinks = 3)
  eigen[[paste0(nLinks, "-", n)]] <- V(g)$centrality
  g2List[[n]] <- g
}

netDF <- map2_df(g2List, names(g2List), function(g, n) {
  ggnetwork(g) %>% mutate(layer = n)
})

```

```

ggplot(netDF, aes(x = x, y = y, xend = xend, yend = yend, shape =
↪ Architecture, color = Area, label = name, size = centrality)) +
  geom_edges(color = "gray", linewidth = .75) +
  geom_nodes() +
  geom_nodetext_repel(color = "black", size = 3) +
  scale_shape_manual(values = 15:18) +
  scale_color_brewer(palette = "Set2") +
  scale_size_continuous(range = c(3, 4.5)) +
  facet_wrap(~layer) +
  theme_blank() +
  theme(
    panel.border = element_rect(fill = NA),
    strip.background = element_rect(fill = "white"),
    legend.position = "bottom"
  ) +
  guides(size = "none", shape = guide_legend(ncol = 2, title = NULL),
↪ color = guide_legend(ncol = 2, title = NULL))
ggsave(here("figures/TontoNetworksMultiNet.png"), dpi = 450, width =
↪ 6.5, height = 8)
browseURL(here("figures/TontoNetworksMultiNet.png"))
paste0(nodes$id, ": ", nodes$Site) %>% paste(collapse = "; ")

eigenDF <- map2_df(g2List, names(g2List), function(g, n) {
  tibble(id = V(g)$name, centrality = V(g)$centrality, name = n)
})

```

```

meanEigenVals <- eigenDF %>%
  mutate_at(vars(id), as.integer) %>%
  left_join(nodes, by = "id") %>%
  group_by(id, name, Area, Architecture) %>%
  summarize(centrality = round(mean(centrality), 2)) %>%
  arrange(name) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = name, values_from = centrality) %>%
  mutate(mean = rowMeans(across(c(ceramics, points), ~.))) %>%
  mutate(mean = round(mean, 2)) %>%
  ungroup()

meanEigenVals_architecture <- meanEigenVals %>%
  select(-Area, -architecture, -spatial) %>%
  group_by(Architecture) %>%
  summarize(across(c(ceramics, points, mean), ~ mean(.x, na.rm = T)))
  ↪ %>%
  rename(architecture = Architecture) %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round, 2)

rio::export(meanEigenVals_architecture,
  ↪ here("tables/TontoEigenCentrality_architecture.xlsx"))

# run all links from 3:10
# using gcor from SNA for demonstration as
# multinet package is currently unavailable as
# of the writing of this dissertation

```

```

library(sna)
allGraphs <- list()
gcor_all <- list()
for (nlink in 3:10) {
  for (n in nms) {
    print(n)
    g <- makeGraph(dists[[n]], nLinks = nlink)
    allGraphs[[paste0(nlink, "-", n)]] <- g
  }
  gcor_vars <- matrix(NA, nrow = length(dists), ncol = length(dists))
  for (i in 1:length(dists)) {
    for (j in 1:length(dists)) {
      if (i != j) {
        n1 <- allGraphs[[paste0(nlink, "-", nms[i])]]
        n2 <- allGraphs[[paste0(nlink, "-", nms[j])]]
        n1 <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(n1, attr = "weight") %>%
↪ as.matrix()
        n2 <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(n2, attr = "weight") %>%
↪ as.matrix()
        n1 <- scale_to_1(n1)
        n2 <- scale_to_1(n2)
        gcor_vars[i, j] <- gcor(n1, n2, mode = "graph")
      }
    }
  }
  colnames(gcor_vars) <- rownames(gcor_vars) <- nms
}

```

```

gcor_all[[paste0(nlink, "-gcor")]] <- gcor_vars
}

gcor_all_df <- map2_df(gcor_all, names(gcor_all), function(x, y) {
  nLinks <- str_extract(y, "\\d+")[1]
  x %>%
    as.data.frame() %>%
    rownames_to_column("network") %>%
    pivot_longer(-network, names_to = "network2", values_to = "gcor")
    ↪ %>%
    mutate(network = str_remove_all(network, "[0-9]|\\-")) %>%
    mutate(network2 = str_remove_all(network2, "[0-9]|\\-")) %>%
    mutate(nLinks = nLinks)
}) %>%
  filter(!is.na(gcor)) %>%
  rowwise() %>%
  mutate(network = paste(sort(c(network, network2)), collapse = " ->
    ↪ ")) %>%
  ungroup()

ggplot(gcor_all_df, aes(x = gcor, y = network, color = network)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = "#D3D3D3", alpha = 0.66) +
  scale_color_viridis_d() +
  theme_gdocs() +
  theme(
    legend.position = "bottom",

```

```

    legend.title = element_blank(),
    panel.spacing.x = unit(0.5, "cm")
  ) +
  labs(x = "Pearson Correlation", y = "") +
  guides(color = "none")

eigenDF_all <- map2_df(allGraphs, names(allGraphs), function(g, n) {
  tibble(id = V(g)$name, centrality = V(g)$centrality, name = n)
})

meanEigenVals_all <- eigenDF_all %>%
  mutate_at(vars(id), as.integer) %>%
  left_join(nodes, by = "id") %>%
  group_by(id, name, Area, Architecture) %>%
  summarize(centrality = round(mean(centrality), 2)) %>%
  arrange(name) %>%
  mutate(name = str_remove_all(name, "[0-9]|\\-")) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  mutate(id = factor(id)) %>%
  filter(name %in% c("ceramics", "points"))

ggplot(meanEigenVals_all, aes(x = id, y = centrality, color =
↵ Architecture)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = "#D3D3D3", alpha = .5, linewidth = 0.6) +
  facet_wrap(~name) +

```

```

scale_color_viridis_d() +
coord_flip() +
theme_gdocs() +
theme(
  strip.background = element_rect(fill = "transparent"),
  strip.text = element_text(size = 20),
  legend.position = "bottom",
  legend.direction = "horizontal",
  legend.title = element_blank(),
  panel.spacing.x = unit(0.5, "cm")
) +
labs(x = "Site", y = "Eigenvector Centrality")

# ggsave("figures/TontoEigenCentrality_boxplot.png", dpi = 450, width
↪ = 6.5, height = 4.5)
# browseURL(her("figures/TontoEigenCentrality_boxplot.png"))

#### export session info ####
# Get the R version
r_version <- paste0("R version=", R.version$major, R.version$minor,
↪ sep = ".")

# Get the loaded packages and their versions
loaded_packages <- sessionInfo()$otherPkgs
loaded_versions <- sapply(

```

```

loaded_packages,
function(x) paste(x$Package, x$Version, sep = "=")
)

# Write the R version and package versions to the file
writeLines(c(r_version, loaded_versions), con =
↪ "analysis/r_environment3.qmd")

```

R Environment

R version=4.4.3. gt=0.11.1 flextable=0.9.7 NetworkDistance=0.3.4 vegan=2.6-10
lattice=0.22-6 permute=0.9-7 ggnetwork=0.5.13 igraph=2.1.4 rio=1.2.3 here=1.0.1
ggthemes=5.1.0 huxtable=5.5.7 kableExtra=1.4.0 Momocs=1.4.1 magrittr=2.0.3 lubri-
date=1.9.4 forcats=1.0.0 stringr=1.5.1 dplyr=1.1.4 purrr=1.0.4 readr=2.1.5 tidyr=1.3.1
tibble=3.2.1 ggplot2=3.5.1 tidyverse=2.0.0

APPENDIX D

CODE FOR CHAPTER 5

This chapter contains the code used for the analysis in chapter 5. The code is organized into three sections: **R**, **Functions**, and **R Environment**. The **R** section contains the code for the analysis, the **Functions** section contains the functions used in the analysis, and the **R Environment** section contains the R environment used to run the analysis.

R

```
library(tidyverse)
library(ggthemes)
library(here)
library(rio)
library(igraph)
library(ggnetwork)
library(vegan)
library(magick)
library(sf)

set.seed(1010)

source("analysis/Chap5functions.R")

sites <- rio::import(here("data/heurist_sites.csv")) %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble() %>%
  rename(region = place_name)

points <- rio::import(here("data/heurist_projectilePoints.csv")) %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
```

```

as_tibble()

ceramics <- rio::import(here("data/heurist_ceramics.csv")) %>%
  janitor::clean_names() %>%
  as_tibble()

table_sites <- points %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(site_link_h_id != "") %>%
  group_by(site_link_h_id) %>%
  count(name = "points") %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(points > 4) %>%
  rename(site_h_id = site_link_h_id) %>%
  mutate(site_h_id = as.integer(site_h_id))

table_ceramics <- ceramics %>%
  filter(!decoration %in% c("Unpainted", "Unknown",
  ↪ "Undifferentiated")) %>%
  filter(site_link_h_id != "") %>%
  group_by(site_link_h_id) %>%
  summarize(ceramics = sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  filter(ceramics > 10) %>%
  rename(site_h_id = site_link_h_id) %>%
  mutate(site_h_id = as.integer(site_h_id))

```

```

data <- sites %>%
  select(site_h_id, site_name, long, lat, start_date, end_date,
  ↪ region) %>%
  filter(!is.na(long)) %>%
  inner_join(table_sites, by = "site_h_id") %>%
  inner_join(table_ceramics, by = "site_h_id") %>%
  filter(end_date > 1100) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(-site_name, -region), as.numeric) %>%
  mutate(site_name = reorder(factor(site_name), end_date))

library(ggnetwork)

ggplot(data) +
  geom_edges(aes(x = start_date, y = site_name, xend = end_date, yend
  ↪ = site_name, color = region, group = site_name),
  linewidth = 1.5,
  arrow = arrow(length = unit(0.75, "lines"), ends = "both", type =
  ↪ "open")
) +
  theme_gdocs() +
  xlab("Date AD") +
  ylab("")

data <- data %>%
  filter(end_date > 1200) %>%

```

```

filter(start_date < 1250)

ggplot(data) +
  geom_edges(aes(x = start_date, y = site_name, xend = end_date, yend
↵ = site_name, color = region, group = site_name),
  linewidth = 1.5,
  arrow = arrow(length = unit(0.75, "lines"), ends = "both", type =
↵ "open")
) +
  theme_gdocs() +
  xlab("Date AD") +
  ylab("") +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(1125, 1375), breaks = seq(1150, 1350,
↵ 50), oob = scales::oob_keep)

fn <- "figures/siteOccupations.png"
# ggsave(fn, dpi = 450, width = 6.5, height = 4.5)
# image_read(fn) %>%
# image_trim() %>%
# image_write(fn)

north <- data %>%
  filter(lat > 34)

south <- data %>%
  filter(lat < 34)

```

```

analyze(data)
analyze(north, "north")
analyze(south, "south")

library(cowplot)
library(magick) # Optional: for better image scaling/format handling

# Load the images
img_A <- cowplot::ggdraw() +
  ↪ draw_image("figures/Chap5NetworkCorrelations_all.png")
img_B <- cowplot::ggdraw() +
  ↪ draw_image("figures/Chap5NetworkCorrelations_north.png")
img_C <- cowplot::ggdraw() +
  ↪ draw_image("figures/Chap5NetworkCorrelations_south.png")

# Combine with labels
combined_plot <- plot_grid(
  img_A, img_B, img_C,
  labels = c("A", "B", "C"),
  label_size = 16,
  ncol = 1, # vertical stacking
  align = "v"
)

# Display or save

```

```

print(combined_plot)

# To save
ggsave("figures/combined_network_correlations.png", combined_plot,
↪ height = 8, dpi = 450)

#### export session info ####
# Get the R version
r_version <- paste0("R version=", R.version$major, R.version$minor,
↪ sep = ".")

# Get the loaded packages and their versions
loaded_packages <- sessionInfo()$otherPkgs
loaded_versions <- sapply(
  loaded_packages,
  function(x) paste(x$Package, x$Version, sep = "=")
)

# Write the R version and package versions to the file
writeLines(c(r_version, loaded_versions), con =
↪ "analysis/r_environment5.qmd")

```

Functions

```

# network functions
scale_to_1 <- function(mat) {

```

```

rng <- range(mat, na.rm = TRUE)
(mat - rng[1]) / (rng[2] - rng[1])
}

makeGraph <- function(d, nLinks = NULL, sf = FALSE) {
  # igraph
  m <- scale_to_1(d)
  g <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(as.matrix(d),
    mode = "undirected",
    diag = F,
    weighted = T
  )
  n_df <- tibble(site_name = V(g)$name) %>%
    left_join(data, by = "site_name")
  V(g)$centrality <- eigen_centrality(g, weights =
    ↪ E(g)$weight)$vector
  V(g)$region <- n_df$region

  if (!is.null(nLinks)) {
    # calculate top n (with ties) edges and convert to igraph object
    # convert to dataframe
    n <- igraph::as_data_frame(g)
    n <- bind_rows(n, n %>% dplyr::rename(from = to, to = from)) %>%
      mutate_if(is.numeric, replace_na, 0)
    q <- quantile(n$weight, 0.5)
    n <- n %>% # sort data frame

```

```

filter(weight > q) %>%
arrange(from, desc(weight)) %>%
# rank by site
group_by(from) %>%
mutate(rank = rank(-weight)) %>%
ungroup()
nSub <- n %>%
  group_by(from) %>%
  slice_max(n = nLinks, order_by = desc(rank)) %>%
  ungroup()

if (sf) {
  nSub <- nSub %>%
    left_join(data %>% select(site_name, region, long, lat),
              by = c("from" = "site_name")
            ) %>%
    left_join(
      data %>% select(
        site_name,
        region,
        longend = long,
        latend = lat
      ),
      by = c("to" = "site_name")
    ) %>%
    return(nSub)
}

```

```

} else {
  gRanks <- graph_from_data_frame(nSub, directed = F, vertices =
↪ n_df)
  gRanks <- gRanks %>% igraph::simplify()
  V(gRanks)$centrality <- eigen_centrality(gRanks, weights =
↪ E(gRanks)$weight)$vector
  return(gRanks)
}
} else {
  return(g)
}
}

```

```

analyze <- function(data, label = "all") {
  ceramics <- ceramics %>%
  filter(!decoration %in% c("Unknown", "Undifferentiated")) %>%
  filter(site_link_h_id %in% data$site_h_id) %>%
  group_by(site_link_h_id) %>%
  filter(end_age > 1200) %>%
  filter(begin_age < 1300) %>%
  select(site_name, ceramic_type, count)

  points <- points %>%
  filter(point_type != "undetermined") %>%
  filter(site_link_h_id %in% data$site_h_id) %>%

```

```

select(site_name, point_type)

dists <- list()
coords_sf <- data %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326) %>%
  st_transform(26912)

coords <- st_coordinates(coords_sf) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  rename(UTMEAST = X, UTMNORTH = Y)

d <- dist(coords[, c("UTMEAST", "UTMNORTH")]) %>% as.matrix()
colnames(d) <- rownames(d) <- data$site_name
# convert to scaled similarity (1 highest)
d <- 1 - (d / max(d))
dists$spatial <- d

# ceramic network
# convert to adjacency matrix
m <- ceramics %>%
  select(ceramic_type, site_name, count) %>%
  mutate_at(vars(count), as.numeric) %>%
  group_by(site_name, ceramic_type) %>%
  summarize(count = sum(count)) %>%
  ungroup() %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = ceramic_type, values_from = count) %>%

```

```

column_to_rownames("site_name") %>%
mutate_all(as.integer) %>%
as.matrix()
m <- m / rowSums(m, na.rm = T)
# m[1,] %>% sum(na.rm = T)
d <- vegdist(m, method = "manhattan", na.rm = T) %>% as.matrix()
d <- 1 - (d / 2)
dists$ceramics <- d

# projectile point network
# convert to adjacency matrix
m <- points %>%
select(point_type, site_name) %>%
mutate(count = 1) %>%
group_by(site_name, point_type) %>%
summarize(count = sum(count)) %>%
ungroup() %>%
pivot_wider(names_from = point_type, values_from = count) %>%
column_to_rownames("site_name") %>%
mutate_all(as.integer) %>%
as.matrix()
m <- m / rowSums(m, na.rm = T)
# m[1,] %>% sum(na.rm = T)
d <- vegdist(m, method = "manhattan", na.rm = T) %>% as.matrix()
d <- 1 - (d / 2)
dists$points <- d

```

```

g2List <- list()
nms <- names(dists)
for (n in nms) {
  print(n)
  g <- makeGraph(dists[[n]], nLinks = 3)
  g2List[[n]] <- g
}

netDF <- map2_df(g2List, names(g2List), function(g, n) {
  ggnetwork(g) %>% mutate(layer = n)
}) %>%
  mutate(weight = weight / 2)

ggplot(
  netDF,
  aes(
    x = x,
    y = y,
    xend = xend,
    yend = yend,
    color = region,
    label = name
  )
) +

```

```

geom_edges(aes(linewidth = weight),
  color = "#404040",
  alpha = .75
) +
scale_linewidth(range = c(.5, 2)) +
geom_nodes(size = 5) +
geom_nodetext_repel(color = "black", size = 2.5) +
facet_wrap(~layer, ncol = 1) +
theme_blank() +
theme(
  panel.border = element_rect(fill = NA),
  strip.background = element_rect(fill = "#404040"),
  strip.text = element_text(size = 20, color = "white"),
  legend.position = "bottom",
  legend.text = element_text(size = 8)
) +
guides(size = "none", color = guide_legend(ncol = 4, title =
↪ NULL))

fn <- glue::glue("figures/Chap5MultilayerNetworks_{label}.png")
ggsave(fn,
  dpi = 450,
  width = 6.5,
  height = 9
)
# browseURL(fn)

```

```

g2List_sf <- list()
nms <- names(dists)
for (n in nms) {
  print(n)
  g <- makeGraph(dists[[n]], nLinks = 3, sf = T)
  g2List_sf[[n]] <- g
}

for (i in 1:length(g2List_sf)) {
  g2List_sf[[i]] <- g2List_sf[[i]] %>%
    mutate(
      layer = names(g2List_sf[i]),
      geometry = st_as_sfc(
        paste0("LINESTRING(", long, " ", lat, ",", longend, " ",
              ↪ latend, ")"),
        crs = 4326
      )
    ) %>%
    st_as_sf()
}

g2List_sf <- bind_rows(g2List_sf)

# mapview::mapview(g2List_sf)

```

```

try(st_write(g2List_sf,
  here(glue::glue("data/Chap5MultilayerNetworks_{label}.geojson")),
  delete_dsn = T
))

nodes_sf <- data %>%
  select(site_name, region, long, lat) %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326)

try(st_write(nodes_sf,
  here(glue::glue("data/Chap5MultilayerNodes_{label}.geojson")),
  delete_dsn = T
))

eigenDF <- map2_df(g2List, names(g2List), function(g, n) {
  tibble(
    id = V(g)$name,
    centrality = V(g)$centrality,
    name = n
  )
}) %>%
  left_join(data %>% select(site_name, region), by = c("id" =
  ↪ "site_name"))

eigenDF_plot <- eigenDF %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = name, values_from = centrality) %>%

```

```

mutate(id = reorder(
  factor(id),
  desc(ceramics)
))

ggplot(eigenDF_plot, aes(
  x = ceramics,
  y = id,
  xend = points,
  yend = id
)) +
  geom_nodes(
    data = eigenDF_plot,
    aes(x = points, y = id),
    color = "black",
    size = 7,
    alpha = .75
  ) +
  geom_nodes(
    data = eigenDF_plot,
    aes(x = ceramics, y = id),
    color = "tan",
    size = 7,
    alpha = .75
  ) +
  geom_edges(aes(color = region), linewidth = 2) +

```

```

theme_gdocs() +
theme(
  axis.text.x = element_text(size = 10),
  axis.text.y = element_text(size = 8),
  plot.margin = margin(
    t = 0.1,
    r = 0.1,
    b = 0.01,
    l = 0.1,
    unit = "cm"
  ),
  legend.margin = margin(t = -30)
) +
guides(color = guide_legend(
  title = element_blank(),
  position = "bottom",
  ncol = 4
)) +
xlab("") +
ylab("")

fn <- glue::glue("figures/Chap5Centrality_{label}.png")
ggsave(fn,
  dpi = 450,
  width = 8.5,
  height = 5.5

```

```

)

image_read(fn) %>%
  image_trim() %>%
  image_write(fn)

# browseURL(fn)

library(sna)

corr_result <- matrix(NA, nrow = length(g2List), ncol =
↪ length(g2List))
for (i in 1:length(g2List)) {
  for (j in 1:length(g2List)) {
    if (i != j) {
      g1 <- g2List[[i]]
      g2 <- g2List[[j]]
      n1 <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(g1, attr = "weight") %>%
↪ as.matrix()
      n2 <- igraph::as_adjacency_matrix(g2, attr = "weight") %>%
↪ as.matrix()
      corr_result[i, j] <- sna::gcor(n1, n2, mode = "graph")
    }
  }
}

```

```

colnames(corr_result) <- rownames(corr_result) <- names(g2List)

library(pheatmap)

fn <-
↪ here(glue::glue("figures/Chap5NetworkCorrelations_{label}.png"))

pheatmap(
  corr_result,
  cluster_rows = F,
  cluster_cols = F,
  fontsize_row = 10,
  fontsize_col = 10,
  cellwidth = 20,
  cellheight = 20,
  color = colorRampPalette(c("white", "orange"))(50),
  filename = fn,
  width = 6.5,
  height = 6.5,
  show_rownames = T,
  show_colnames = T,
  display_numbers = T,
  legend = F,
  angle_col = 45
)

```

```

image_read(fn) %>%
  image_trim() %>%
  image_write(fn)

# multilayer communities

combined <- make_empty_graph(directed = F)

for (i in c("ceramics", "points")) {
  g <- g2List[[i]]
  combined <- union(combined, g)
  simplify(combined, remove_multiple = T, remove_loops = T)
}

comm <- cluster_louvain(combined, weights = E(combined)$weight)

comm_df <- data.frame(
  site_name = V(combined)$name,
  comm = comm$membership
) %>%
  left_join(data %>% select(site_name, region, long, lat), by =
  ↪ "site_name") %>%
  distinct_all() %>%
  arrange(site_name) %>%
  st_as_sf(coords = c("long", "lat"), crs = 4326)

```

```
try(st_write(comm_df,  
  ↪ glue::glue("data/Chap5MultilayerCommunities_{label}.geojson"),  
    delete_dsn = T  
  ))  
print("completed")  
}
```

R Environment

R version=44.3. sna=2.8 network=1.19.0 statnet.common=4.11.0 sf=1.0-19 mag-
ick=2.8.5 vegan=2.6-10 lattice=0.22-6 permute=0.9-7 ggnetwork=0.5.13 igraph=2.1.4
rio=1.2.3 here=1.0.1 ggthemes=5.1.0 lubridate=1.9.4 forcats=1.0.0 stringr=1.5.1
dplyr=1.1.4 purrr=1.0.4 readr=2.1.5 tidyr=1.3.1 tibble=3.2.1 ggplot2=3.5.1 tidyverse=2.0.0

APPENDIX E

NOTICE OF COPYRIGHT PERMISSIONS

This Appendix contains the permissions granted for this dissertation. These include permissions from the co-authors of the ArchMatNet agent-based model, the co-author of Chapter 2, and from the publisher of the journal Kiva–Taylor and Francis Ltd.

ArchMatNet and Chapter 2

Cecilia Padilla-Iglesias (cecilia.padillaiglesias@iea.uzh.ch), co-author of Chapter 2, has granted permission to produce this chapter in this dissertation. Claudine Gravel-Miguel (cgravelm@asu.edu) has given permission to use the ArchMatNet model in any publication.

Chapter 4

Chapter 4 was originally published in the journal KIVA:

Bischoff, Robert J. 2023 Investigating Material Culture Through Multi-layer Network Analysis in Tonto Basin. KIVA 89(3): 247–273. DOI: 10.1080/00231940.2023.2235137.

The publication of this article included permission for the reuse of this article in this dissertation.

Copyright in subscription articles

For an article published in a subscription journal, as with an open access article, Taylor & Francis will validate, produce, disseminate, and act as steward in the long-term curation of the article. Taylor & Francis may also handle re-use requests. In the subscription model, the author receives these services for free, and instead Taylor & Francis recoups its investment in the above services by selling access to the content. In order to achieve this, the owner of the applicable journal (e.g. a learned society or Taylor & Francis) typically requires a transfer or "assignment" of the copyright in the article.

As is the case for open access publishing, when publishing in a subscription journal, the author (or copyright owner of the article, if different) signs an author publishing agreement. The agreement incorporates the necessary transfer of copyright.

After assigning copyright, you will still retain the right to:

- ✓ Be credited as the author of the article.
- ✓ Own and exercise any trademark or patent rights held by you and addressed in the article.
- ✓ Make printed copies of the article to use for a lecture or class that you are leading on a non-commercial basis.
- ✓ Share the article using your [free eprints](#) with friends, colleagues and influential people you would like to read the work.
- ✓ Include the article in your thesis or dissertation.
- ✓ Present the article at a meeting or conference and distribute printed copies of the article on a non-commercial basis.
- ✓ Post the [Author's Original Manuscript \(AOM\)](#) or [Accepted Manuscript \(AM\)](#) on a departmental, personal website or institutional repositories depending on embargo period. To find the embargo period for any Taylor & Francis journal, please use the [Open Access Options Finder](#).

